

**Support Uptake Integrated
Pest Management and Low-
Risk Pesticide Use**

Deliverable: 4.5
Title: IPM strategies of 25 NCC's

**Horizon Europe Research and Innovation
Programme**

Grant agreement: 101084527
Project duration: 48 months

Published by the SUPPORT consortium
Dissemination level: public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement No. 101084527

Document Control Information

Project Title:	Support Uptake Integrated Pest Management and Low-Risk Pesticide Use
Acronym:	SUPPORT
Project Manager:	Florien Bos
Scientific Coordinator:	Johan Bremmer

Deliverable	Number	4.5	Title	IPM strategies of 25 NCCs
Work Package	Number	4	Title	National Crop Clusters and Community of Practices

Document Authors:	Name and organization	Clara Sciffer, EV ILVO Kaat Peeters, EV ILVO	Contact first author:	Clara Sciffer clara.sciffer@ilvo.vlaanderen.be
Contributors:	Name and organization	Cordelia Kreft - Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich Lars Ole Hingst - Julius Kühn-Institut Maria Toader - University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest Dorota Labanowska-Bury - Spółdzielnia Ogrodnicza w Grojcu Joanna Golian - The National Institute of Horticultural Research Dominika Boguszewska-Mańkowska - Polish Plant Breeding and Acclimatization Institute Jens Erik Jensen - SEGES Innovation Kalliopi Kounani - Agricultural University of Athens Vicky Inglezou - Synetairismos Pistopoiimenon Agrotikon Proionton Dimou Nestoros Messinias Simona Fabroni - Council for Agricultural Research and Economics Alberto Sturla - Council for Agricultural Research and Economics Maria Grazia Tommasini - RiNova Carolina Gattorno - Zuidelijke Landbouw en Tuinbouworganisatie Juan Sagarna - Cooperative Agro-Alimentarias Celeste Oliveira - Cooperative Agro-Alimentarias Clara Sciffer - Eigen Vermogen Instituut voor Landbouw-, Visserij- en Veedingsonderzoek		

Deliverable type:	R – Document, report
Dissemination level:	PU – Public
Due date of deliverable:	
Actual submission date:	

This report only reflects the views of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s)

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All Reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as Optional.

Name	Role	Action	Date
Alberto Sturla	Reviewer	First review	3 Sep 2024
Per Kudsk	Reviewer	First review	13 Sep 2024
Johan Bremmer	Reviewer	Second review	22 Oct 2024

Document history

The Document Author is authorized to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner.

Changes to this document are summarized in the following table in reverse chronological order (latest version first).

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes
First draft submitted	23/08/2024	Clara Sciffer	First draft submitted, not all NCC reports are included.
Final draft submitted	1/10/2024	Clara Sciffer	Final draft submitted for review.
Final version	28/10/2024	Clara Sciffer	Small adjustments made based on the second review.

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in [insert relevant link to the sharepoint]

Executive summary of the deliverable

This deliverable contains 25 reports which describe exemplary IPM strategies for every case study within the SUPPORT project, by relying on the IPM inventory that was already provided in Deliverable 1.1 of this project. The crops that are being studied within SUPPORT are: wheat, maize, onion, potato, strawberry, apple, wine grape and olive.

The aim is to combine the IPM tools from Deliverable 1.1 into complete crop protection strategies for the most important cropping systems of each NCC (National Crop Cluster). For each cropping system, two scenarios were drafted, one that is representative for the majority of the farmers (state-of-the-art scenario) and one that is being used by a minority of farmers who are more sustainability oriented (IPM improved scenario). Each NCC leader within the project was tasked with the selection and the description of the strategies and scenarios using the provided templates (Annex 6.9).

The crop protection strategies presented in this deliverable can be used as a guide for bilateral talks with farmers or during meetings with a larger group of farmers on IPM tools and strategies. It can inspire farmers and advisors to consider additional or different IPM tools that can lower their pesticide use and the associated pressure on health and the environment. They can moreover use the information gathered in this deliverable to combine the IPM tools into crop protection strategies that can deal with climate change and regulatory restrictions. The 25 IPM strategies reports will be further used in task 1.3 of the SUPPORT project, in which the IPM monitoring system that is being developed in task 1.2 will be applied to the current and future IPM crop protection scenarios. This will provide an impact assessment of the crop protection strategies regarding pest control efficacy, economic performance of farms and the environmental and social impact.

Contents

Executive summary of the deliverable	3
Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	6
1. Introduction.....	7
1.1 Background.....	7
1.2 The SUPPORT project	7
1.3 Objective	9
2. Approach.....	10
3. Results.....	11
3.1 General results.....	11
3.2 Wine Grape.....	13
3.3 Olive	15
3.4 Apple	17
3.5 Strawberry.....	19
3.6 Wheat	22
3.7 Maize	24
3.8 Potato	26
3.9 Onion	29
4. Reflections.....	31
5. References.....	33
6. ANNEXES	34
6.1 Wine Grape.....	34
6.1.1 Greece.....	34
6.1.2 Spain.....	60
6.2 Olive	70
6.2.1 Greece.....	70
6.2.2 Italy	81
6.2.3 Spain.....	93
6.3 Apple	103
6.3.1 Italy	103
6.3.2 Netherlands.....	117
6.3.3 Poland	126
6.4 Strawberry.....	146
6.4.1 Belgium	146
6.4.2 Netherlands.....	180
6.4.3 Spain.....	195
6.5 Wheat	201
6.5.1 Denmark.....	201
6.5.2 Germany.....	215
6.5.3 Romania	229
6.5.4 Switzerland	246

6.6	Maize	
		256
6.6.1	Denmark.....		256
6.6.2	Romania		264
6.6.3	Switzerland		284
6.7	Potato		294
6.7.1	Belgium		294
6.7.2	Germany.....		324
6.7.3	Denmark.....		341
6.7.4	Netherlands.....		351
6.7.5	Poland		360
6.8	Onion		386
6.8.1	Italy		386
6.8.2	Poland		411
6.9	Template reports		421

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CA	Consortium Agreement
CoP	Community of Practices
DoA	Description of the action
EB	Executive Board (Core Team)
GA	The General Assembly
IPM	Integrated Pest Management
NCC	National Crop Cluster
NoP	Network of Practices
PAB	Project Advisory Board
PM	Project Manager
PMO	Project Management Officer
PMT	The Project Management Team
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SCT	Scientific Coordination Team
TL	Task leader
WP	The Work Package
WPL	The Work Package Leader

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Integrated Pest Management (IPM) has been an important cornerstone of the EU-politics since 2009 (Sustainable Use Directive (Directive 2009/128/EC). The importance of IPM implementation is also highlighted in EU's Farm to Fork strategy as it can play a role in becoming less dependent on chemical pesticides. However, according to the evaluation report of the EU Commission on the progress of the implementation of Directive 2009/128/EC and the implementation of national targets, the uptake of IPM practices by farmers and the reduction of pesticide use remains low.

Within the SUPPORT project, deliverable 3.1 Policy analysis (K. Kounani & A. Kannavou, 2024) gives an overview of the differences in IPM implementation in the individual EU member states and deliverable 1.1 Inventory of IPM tools (M.D. Thorsted, S. Appel & J.E. Jensen, 2024) assembles the most important IPM tools that are currently used by farmers or tools that are expected to be available within the next 3-5 years for the eight crops that have been selected within SUPPORT.

Because of the current gap between potential and realized uptake of IPM measures, more insight is needed in the current IPM practices, the decision-making process of farmers and other stakeholders regarding crop protection strategies and the drivers and barriers for IPM adoption. This knowledge will create the basis for the development or adjustment of strategies and policies at member state and EU level to stimulate the adoption of IPM practices, in order to meet previously mentioned political goals.

1.2 The SUPPORT project

The SUPPORT project started in January 2023 and will run until the end of 2026. It involves 20 different partners, including universities, higher education, SME's, cooperatives and public bodies, from 10 countries; the Netherlands, Germany, Italy, France, Belgium, Switzerland, Poland, Romania, Greece, Spain and Denmark.

The overall objective of SUPPORT is to stimulate the adoption of IPM tools and technologies by developing relevant and actionable scientific knowledge, that will be used to co-create, together with different actors, public policies and private sector strategies. Some more detailed goals within the project are:

- 1) Create a SUPPORT stakeholder ecosystem to co-create strategies and policies with actors.
- 2) Develop and inventory of current and future IPM tools and assess their impact on pest control efficacy, economic performance of farms and the environment.
- 3) Identify barriers and drivers in the entire agri-food system for the adoption of IPM and analyse their role in farmer decision-making.
- 4) Propose public policies and private sector strategies for enhancing the adoption of IPM tools and technologies in a co-creation process with the engagement of relevant stakeholders.

The SUPPORT stakeholder ecosystem, where the co-creation processes with different actors will take place, is shaped as a multi-level system. Figure 1.2.1 displays the multi-actor approach in which 25 National Crop Clusters (NCCs) will be used for data collection (focus groups, interviews, surveys, choice experiments). Additional data will also be derived from the FADN (Farm Accountancy Data Network). Around eight of these NCCs, Community of Practices (CoPs) will be gathered as a place for co-creation. The Network of Practice (NoP) is the over-arching level of all CoP- and consortium members where project results will be discussed further in order to foster wider change.

Figure 1.2.1: SUPPORT stakeholder ecosystem: implementation of the multi-actor approach.

Figure 1.2.2 shows the eight crops (wheat, maize, onion, potato, strawberry, apple, wine grape and olive) that are studied within SUPPORT and which countries of the consortium that are focusing on them, resulting in 25 NCC's. As shown in figure 1.2.3, there is a balance between perennial vs. annual cropping systems, crops for the fresh market vs. processing industry, specialty products vs. commodities and there is a broad coverage of different bio-geographical regions.

Figure 1.2.2: The European coverage of SUPPORT crop areas in the member states of the SUPPORT consortium.

Country	Bio-geographical region	Perennial				Annual cropping system			
		Processing industry		Fresh		Processing industry		Fresh	
Denmark	Atlantic					X	X	X	
France	Atlantic								
Germany	Atlantic					X		X	
Italy	Mediterranean		X	X					X
Netherlands	Atlantic			X	X			X	
Belgium	Atlantic				X			X	
Poland	Continental			X				X	X
Romania	Continental					X	X		
Spain	Mediterranean	X	X		X				
Switzerland	Alpine					X	X		
Greece	Mediterranean	X	X						

■ Mediterranean
 ■ Atlantic
 ■ Continental
 ■ Alpine
 X T4.3 Community of Practices 9
 X T4.2 National Crop Clusters 25

Figure 1.2.3: The 25 NCC's and 9 CoP's, highlighting the high variety in cropping systems in different bio-geographical regions.

1.3 Objective

The objective of subtask 4.2.1 (ii) is to develop 25 NCC reports which describe exemplary IPM strategies for each of the NCC's covered within the SUPPORT project by relying on the IPM inventory that is already provided in Deliverable 1.1 (M.D. Thorsted, S. Appel & J.E. Jensen, 2024).

A typical IPM strategy represents a crop protection strategy applied on a farm of average size during an average year concerning biotic stress (pest and disease pressure and damage), abiotic stress (weather conditions) and market situation (Mathis et al., 2022). For some NCCs, it was not possible to describe one typical IPM strategy, because of the use of different cultivation systems or big regional differences due to climatic or environmental features. Therefore, each NCC leader was asked to select, in consultation with local crop specialists, at minimum 1 and at maximum 5 production systems/geographic regions for which an IPM strategy should be defined and analysed.

The 25 IPM strategies reports will be further used in task 1.3 of the SUPPORT project, in which the IPM monitoring system that is being developed in task 1.2 will be applied to the current and future IPM crop protection scenarios.

For each of the targeted crops the IPM strategies contain the most important crop protection measures that are applied in a certain cropping system/region. For each strategy, 3 different scenarios are defined and will be analysed by the monitoring tool in task 1.3.

1. State-of-the-art scenario: This is the reference scenario (the baseline) against which the results of the holistic impact assessment of the monitoring tool will be evaluated. This scenario describes 'an average crop protection strategy' applied by the majority of the conventional farmers in the NCC. In this scenario, farmers apply IPM according to the prescriptions provided in the National Action Plans which were developed according to the Sustainable Use Directive (SUD).
2. IPM-improved scenario: This scenario represents a crop protection management that intensely applies IPM and is only used by a minority of sustainability oriented farmers. Yet, the scenario should be realistic and economically viable. The aim of this IPM strategy is minimising the use of synthetic pesticides, and making intensive use of alternative crop protection measures (Mathis et al., 2022).

3. Future IPM scenario: These scenarios will be developed in a later stage of the project and represent a realistic scenario of crop protection used within 5 years. This scenario describes the state-of-the-art scenario in which IPM tools that are currently under development, but expected to be implemented in practice within 5 years, are being applied in addition to, or as replacement of current IPM tools. The future IPM scenarios will be added to the previous scenarios as Deliverable 4.6 of the SUPPORT project.

2. Approach

Every NCC leader was tasked with the selection of minimum 1 and maximum 5 relevant production systems/geographic regions for which an IPM strategy should be defined and analysed. If necessary, this happened in consultation with local crop specialists. Every strategy had to be briefly described, as well as the choice of the reference year. In case 2023 was a representative year, this was chosen as the reference year. If this was not the case, because of atypical (a)biotic stress or an atypical market situation, another year had to be selected with a brief motivation on why that year was selected.

In addition, every strategy (cropping system/geographical region) had to be described including the following data:

- Number of growers using this strategy
- Acreage (ha)
- Share of the acreage (%) of this strategy compared to the total acreage
- Production (tonnes/year)
- Share (%) of the total crop production

As explained in the previous section (1.3), every strategy consists of a state-of-the-art and an IPM improved scenario. Each scenario was described by the following variables (Mathis et al., 2022; Strassemeyer et al., 2017), if needed supplemented with additional information to fully describe and distinct the scenarios:

- 10-20 of the most used (and combined) IPM tools (these can be tools listed in the IPM inventory (task 1.1), but in case relevant tools are missing, these can be added). For each tool the following information was asked:
 - o Application frequency (in case this is relevant)
 - o Application date
 - o Stage of development of the crop
 - o Target pest/disease
- Used cultivar
- Use of resistant cultivars (yes/no)
- Use of seed coating (yes/no)
- Cropping density (plants/ha)
- Cropping cycle (start/end date)
- Estimated annual yield (t/ha)
- Price per kg product (€/kg)
- Subsidies for adopting the specific IPM tools
- Storage loss (kg/ha or %)
- PPP-use: Number fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (product)
- % drift reduction
- Minimum buffer zone to surface water (m)
- Use of crop rotation (yes/no) and with which crops
- Use of intercropping (yes/no)

All data were collected using desktop research and expert consultation. NCC leaders bundled all information in a Word document and a PowerPoint document, with the latter being a visualisation of the crop protection strategy, depicting the cropping cycle and the used IPM tools (Annex 6). Templates of the report (both the Word and the PowerPoint document) can be found in Annex 6.9.

3. Results

3.1 General results

Table 3.1.1 gives an overview of the different strategies selected for each crop and country (NCC).

Table 3.1.1: Overview of the different strategies selected for each NCC and the chosen reference year.

Crop	Country	Reference year	Strategy
Wine Grape	Greece	2023-2024	1) Pest monitoring and biological control 2) Integrated crop rotation and cover cropping 3) Sustainable soil management and conservation 4) Pest and disease monitoring and warning systems 5) Agroecological practices and habitat management
	Spain	2021	1) Rainfed 2) Irrigated
Olive	Greece	2022-2023	1) Organic, low density, irrigated
	Italy	2022	1) Low density, not irrigated 2) High density, irrigated
	Spain	2021	1) Low density, not irrigated 2) High density, irrigated
Apple	Italy	2022	1) High density 2) Low density
	the Netherlands	2023	1) High density
	Poland	2023	1) High density 2) Low density
Strawberry	Belgium	2020	1) Full soil, open and sheltered 2) Substrate, sheltered 3) Substrate, sheltered, heated 4) Propagation
	the Netherlands	2023	1) Substrate, sheltered 2) Propagation
	Spain	2023	1) Full soil, sheltered
Wheat	Denmark	2023	1) Conventional
	Germany	2021	1) Conventional
	Romania	2023	1) Conventional 2) Organic
	Switzerland	2023	1) Conventional
Maize	Denmark	2023	1) Conventional
	Romania	2023	1) Conventional 2) Organic
	Switzerland	2023	1) Conventional
Potato	Belgium	2021	1) Warehouse 2) Early 3) Starch
	Denmark	2023	1) Starch

	Germany	2021	1) Warehouse 2) Early 3) Starch
	the Netherlands	2022	1) Warehouse, seed, starch
	Poland	2023	1) Warehouse 2) Early 3) Seed
Onion	Italy	2023	1) Summer sowing 2) Spring sowing
	Poland	2023	1) Spring sowing

3.2 Wine Grape

The production of wine grapes is covered by the NCC's in **Greece** and **Spain**. The detailed IPM strategies for these NCC's can be found in Annex 6.1.1 and 6.1.2.

Kiato, located in the northeastern part of the Peloponnese, is a significant area for wine grape production in **Greece**. The predominant grape cultivation method in this region is done in biological open vineyard systems. Five strategies with a varying degree of IPM implementation for this cropping system are presented in Annex 6.1.1: enhanced pest monitoring and biological control, integrated crop rotation and cover cropping, sustainable soil management and conservation agriculture, pest and disease monitoring and early warning systems and lastly, agroecological farming practices and habitat management. These strategies include both irrigated and rainfed systems. The adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies among grape growers in Kiato is gradually increasing, driven by regional characteristics, farming practices, economic incentives, and access to education and resources. Agricultural extension services, cooperatives, and government initiatives play a crucial role in promoting IPM and supporting sustainable grape production in the region, but broadening IPM adoption stays challenging.

For the **Spanish** grapevine production, a clear distinction can be made between the crop protection strategies of rainfed and irrigated grape production. Approximately 69% of the total area used for wine grapes is rainfed. It is not very profitable compared to the irrigated system (4,659 tonnes/year on 628,037 ha versus 11,676 tonnes/year on 284,396 ha), but limited water resources make that rainfed farming is still viable. Vineyards are particularly sensitive to climatic conditions, and in recent years this crop has been severely affected, as the lack of water and high temperatures can significantly reduce grape quality. In addition, water stress affects the plants' ability to absorb nutrients from the soil, which can lead to loss of leaves and grape bunches, reducing vineyard yields.

Table 3.2.1 gives an overview of the number of tools included in the IPM strategies for Greece and Spain, both in the state-of-the-art scenarios and the IPM improved scenarios.

Table 3.2.1: Overview of the number of tools included in the five strategies in Greece and the two strategies in Spain, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. Tools are divided over the 3 IPM principles: prevention, monitoring and intervention.

Wine Grape	IPM principle	Greece 1:	Greece 2:	Greece 3:	Greece 4:	Greece 5:
		Pest monitoring & boil. control	Integrated crop rotation & cover cropping	Sustainable soil management & conservation agriculture	Pest/disease monitoring & warning systems	Agroecological practices & habitat management
State-of-the-art scenario	Prevention	3	5	7	0	8
	Monitoring	2	1	1	10	1
	Intervention	5	4	2	0	1
IPM improved scenario	Prevention	7	10	13	0	18
	Monitoring	4	2	3	20	1
	Intervention	9	8	4	0	1
	IPM principle	Spain 1: Rainfed	Spain 2: Irrigated			
State-of-the-art scenario	Prevention	3	3			
	Monitoring	2	2			
	Intervention	1	4			
IPM improved scenario	Prevention	6	6			
	Monitoring	4	4			
	Intervention	2	5			

The main pest in the Greek and Spanish vineyards is the European grapevine moth (*Lobesia botrana*). Powdery mildew (*Uncinula necator*) and downy mildew (*Plasmopara viticola*) are the most important diseases that require intervention.

The five Greek strategies all have a different focus, however the most common measures are biological control, monitoring of the European grapevine moth with pheromone traps, crop rotation/diversification, the integration of cover crops, precision agriculture techniques and soil moisture/structure management. The IPM improved scenarios all focus on enhanced monitoring systems (against *Lobesia botrana*, but also soil health) and a better integration of the different measures.

The Spanish rainfed strategy focuses on hygiene of machinery and treatment equipment, healthy planting material, phytosanitary networks for the abovementioned main pest and diseases and a sulphur treatment against powdery mildew (*Uncinula necator*). The IPM improved scenario for rainfed vineyards also includes biological pest control and protection of natural enemies, the monitoring of *Lobesia botrana* with traps and the use of pest prediction methods. The irrigated strategy is the same as the rainfed strategy, however also includes herbicides treatments with glyphosate and insecticide treatment with abamectin against *Lobesia botrana*.

Table 3.2.2 displays the number of crop protection products (not applications) used in all strategies and scenarios.

Table 3.2.2: Overview of the number of pesticide products (not applications) included in the five strategies in Greece and the two strategies in Spain, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario.

Wine Grape	Pesticides	Greece 1:	Greece 2:	Greece 3:	Greece 4:	Greece 5:
		Pest monitoring & boil. control	Integrated crop rotation & cover cropping	Sustainable soil management & conservation agriculture	Pest/disease monitoring & warning systems	Agroecological practices & habitat management
State-of-the-art scenario	Fungicides	3	2	2	3	1
	Insecticides	2	1	1	2	0
	Herbicides	2	2	2	1	0
IPM improved scenario	Fungicides	2	2	1	2	1
	Insecticides	1	1	1	1	0
	Herbicides	2	2	1	0	0
	IPM principle	Spain 1: Rainfed	Spain 2: Irrigated			
State-of-the-art scenario	Fungicides	1	1			
	Insecticides	0	1			
	Herbicides	0	1			
IPM improved scenario	Fungicides	1	1			
	Insecticides	0	1			
	Herbicides	0	1			

The Spanish rainfed vineyards are grown organically, as only sulphur treatments against powdery mildew (*Uncinula necator*) are included in this strategy. The irrigated vineyards are additionally also treated with glyphosate against weeds and abamectin against the grapevine moth (*Lobesia botrana*), hence they are not organic. There is no difference in the number of crop protection products used between the Spanish state-of-the-art scenarios and the IPM improved scenarios. This is the case however for the first, third and fourth Greek strategy, with a slight decrease in the number of used pesticides.

3.3 Olive

Olive production is covered by the NCC's in **Greece, Italy** and **Spain**. The detailed IPM strategies for all three NCC's can be found in Annex 6.2.1, 6.2.2 and 6.2.3.

In **Greece**, organic low density open field growing is the most important strategy. If necessary, the olive groves will be irrigated. Messinia, in the southwestern part of the Peloponnese region, is the region that produces the largest amount of olives. The majority of farmers in Messinia are organic olive cultivators or are transitioning to organic olive cultivation. In the season of 2022-2023, 250,000 tonnes of olives were produced on 83,000 ha.

In the **Italian** case, two strategies are based on cropping system and geographical specifications: the extensively grown low density open field olives without irrigation and the intensively grown high density open field olives with irrigation. The extensive strategy is distinct for the northern regions of Italy along the Tyrrhenian coast, where the production is typically done on terraced land. The intensive strategy is situated in the southern regions (Puglia, Campania, Calabria and Sicilia) and requires high inputs and high maintenance. According to national statistics, in 2022, the extensive strategy produced 463.736 tonnes of olives on 293.315 ha (1.58 t/ha) and the intensive strategy produced 2.318.402 tonnes on 773.238 ha (3,00 t/ha). The intensively managed olive groves' yield is therefore double the yield of the extensively managed groves.

Spain has, similar to Italy, a rainfed low density open field strategy and an irrigated high density open field strategy. In 2021, the extensive production yielded 2,249 kg/ha on 1,777,498 ha and the intensive production yielded 4,867 kg/ha on 795,897 ha, so similar to the Italian case the intensive strategy yielded more than double compared to the extensive strategy.

Table 3.3.1 gives an overview of the number of tools included in the IPM strategies for Greece, Italy and Spain, both in the state-of-the-art scenarios and the IPM improved scenarios.

Table 3.3.1: Overview of the number of tools included in the one strategy in Greece, the two strategies in Italy and the two strategies in Spain, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. Tools are divided over the three IPM principles: prevention, monitoring and intervention. Irr. and no irr. indicates whether the olive orchards are irrigated (irr.) or not (no irr.).

Olive	IPM principle	Greece 1: Organic low density, irr.	Italy 1: Low density, no irr.	Italy 2: High density, irr.	Spain 1: Low density, no irr.	Spain 2: High density, irr.
State-of-the-art scenario	Prevention	9	6	7	1	1
	Monitoring	3	2	1	1	1
	Intervention	3	3	4	5	7
IPM improved scenario	Prevention	10	7	8	4	4
	Monitoring	5	2	1	1	1
	Intervention	3	6	9	5	7

The organic strategy of Greece includes most crop protection tools, whereas the Spanish strategies contain the lowest number of tools. Both Greek and Italian farmers use resistant varieties: the Greek variety "Mavrolia" demonstrates resistance against esca-associated fungi (*Fomitiporia mediterranea*), olive leaf spot disease (*Spilotea oleaginea* or *Cycloconium oleaginum cast.*), verticillium (*Verticillium dahlia*), and olive knot disease (*Pseudomonas savastanoi*). The Greek "Koroneiki" variety is also resistant against *Verticillium dahlia*. The Italian variety "Leccino", used in the low density strategy, is resistant to *Xylella fastidiosa* and the variety "Arbequina", used in the high density strategy, is resistant to olive knot disease (*Pseudomonas savastanoi*) and olive leaf spot disease (*Cycloconium oleaginum cast.*). Spanish farmers do not use resistant varieties, however they do use certified planting material, just like the Italian farmers in the intensively managed olive groves.

The Greek state-of-the-art organic scenario focuses a lot on soil health (using cover crops, incorporation of the pruning waste into the soil) and orchard hygiene (e.g. pruning). A well-structured orchard is also important in the extensively managed Italian strategy, as it promotes circulation of light and air which reduces the risk of diseases.

The olive fruit fly (*Bactrocera Oleae*) seemed to be the most important pest in all NCC's. Greek farmers control this pest by regular monitoring and scouting, using pheromone traps (for monitoring) and bait sprays, biological control and bioinsecticides. In the Italian orchards, olive fruit flies are controlled by most farmers by using mass trapping (only extensive strategy) and insecticides (both extensive and intensive strategies). A minority of the farmers (IPM improved scenario) also uses kaolin foliar treatments, pheromone traps and additional monitoring. Spanish farmers mostly rely on phytosanitary warning networks (extensive rainfed and intensive irrigated strategy) and pesticides (intensive irrigated strategy) for this pest.

Italy was the only NCC that reported on specific attention to drift reduction when using pesticides, as it is recommended by regional specifications for integrated productions. The majority of farmers strive for 35-40% drift reduction (extensive strategy) or 50% drift reduction (intensive strategy), with a minority (IPM improved scenario) that strives for 60% (both strategies).

Additional monitoring or scouting was part of all IPM improved scenarios. The Greek IPM improved scenario is the only one mentioning the use of high-tech tools and AI, which can increase efficiency, reduce costs and improve yield, quality and crop health.

Table 3.3.2 displays the number of crop protection products (not applications) used in all strategies and scenarios. In case of the organic Greek strategy, the data in the table reflect the use of biopesticides.

Table 3.3.2: Overview of the number of pesticide products (not applications) included in the one strategy in Greece (biopesticides), the two strategies in Italy and the two strategies in Spain for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario.

Olive	IPM principle	Greece 1: Organic low density, irr.	Italy 1: Low density, no irr.	Italy 2: High density, irr.	Spain 1: Low density, no irr.	Spain 2: High density, irr.
State-of-the-art scenario	Fungicides	4	3	3	1	1
	Insecticides	2	3	3	0	1
	Herbicides	0	1	1	1	2
IPM improved scenario	Fungicides	4	2	2	1	1
	Insecticides	2	2	2	0	1
	Herbicides	0	1	1	1	2

As shown in table 3.3.2, the organic production in Greece is the only strategy in which no herbicides are used. Greek farmers only use mowing as an intervention tool against weeds. The extensive, low density rainfed strategy in Spain is the only strategy that does not include insecticides. This strategy also uses overall the least amount of pesticide products compared to the other strategies, despite being the strategy with the least amount of crop protection measures (see table 3.3.1). Only in the Italian case, there is a slight drop in the number of products used in the IPM improved scenario compared to the state-of-the-art scenario.

3.4 Apple

The production of apple is covered by three NCC's: **Italy, the Netherlands** and **Poland**. The detailed IPM strategies for all three NCC's can be found in Annex 6.3.1, 6.3.2 and 6.3.3.

Italy and Poland both cover 2 strategies: high density and low density open field apple growing. The cropping density in the high-density orchards in Poland is 3125-6666 plants/ha, in Italy this is 1500-4000 plants/ha. The cropping density for low-density orchards in Poland is 1250-1666 plants/ha and for Italy this is 800-1200 plants/ha. With a cropping density of 2400-3200 plants/ha, the apple orchards in the Netherlands can be considered high density.

High density apple production in Italy is mostly done in the Northern Italian regions (Trentino and Emilia Romagna), while low density production is widespread all over Italy, mostly devoted to local varieties and targeted to local markets. The high density orchards in Italy produced 2,122,099 tonnes of apples in 2022 on 48,132 ha (44 t/ha), which is 93% of the production. Low density apple production yielded 159,998 tonnes in the same year on 8,146 ha (20 t/ha).

In 2023, 198,000 tonnes of apple were produced in the Netherlands on 5,502 ha (35 t/ha). In general, apple farming is already using a very integrated approach. Only a limited number of chemicals are still allowed. Many methods are aimed at preventing the spread of diseases, since apple trees are grown for at least 15 years before being replaced. Therefore, no risks can be taken regarding the health of the trees.

High density apple growing in Poland yielded 1.9 million tonnes in 2023 on 50,000 ha (38 t/ha). Low density growing yielded 2 million tonnes on 100,000 ha (20 t/ha).

Table 3.4.1 gives an overview of the number of tools included in the IPM strategies for Italy, the Netherlands and Poland, both in the state-of-the-art scenarios and the IPM improved scenarios.

Table 3.4.1: Overview of the number of tools included in the two strategies in Italy, the one strategy in the Netherlands and the two strategies in Poland, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. Tools are divided over the three IPM principles: prevention, monitoring and intervention.

Apple	IPM principle	Italy 1: High density	Italy 2: Low density	the Netherlands 1: High density	Poland 1: High density	Poland 2: Low density
State-of-the-art scenario	Prevention	9	8	9	10	9
	Monitoring	1	1	2	2	1
	Intervention	3	3	4	3	2
IPM improved scenario	Prevention	14	12	11	19	13
	Monitoring	2	2	2	2	2
	Intervention	5	4	5	7	6

The main pests and diseases in all three NCC's are: apple scab disease (*Venturia inaequalis*), powdery mildew (*Podosphaera leucotricha*), fireblight (*Erwinia amylovora*), the codling moth (*Cydia pomonella*) and aphids like *Dysaphis plantaginea* (rosy apple aphid) and *Erisoma lanigerum* (woolly apple aphid). The main intervention technique to control these pests and diseases in the orchards are pesticides.

The high density orchards of all three NCC's are all irrigated and include quite similar crop protection measures. Common measures in the state-of-the-art scenarios are: attention to orchard hygiene (pruning, removal of infected material), the use of bio stimulants to improve tree resilience and nutrient uptake, biological control using natural enemies (e.g. the use of predatory mites against spider mites), grassing to create a natural habitat for beneficial organisms, beehives to improve pollination and pest monitoring with pheromone traps. In Poland, resistant apple varieties are rarely used, as there is no added market value. In Italy and the Netherlands, resistant varieties against apple scab disease, powdery mildew or fireblight are sometimes used. The state-of-the-art scenarios of the low density strategies include the same measures as the abovementioned tools in the state-of-the-art scenarios of the high density strategies. Only in the Polish case, there is no biological control and no herbicides are being used, only mechanical weeding.

The IPM improved scenarios of the high density strategies in Italy and Poland are also almost identical: use of mycorrhizal colonization (to control plant pathogens through the production of siderophores and antibiotics), mulch against weeds, physical methods for weeding (e.g. hot water, burning), improved monitoring of pests and an earlier detection of diseases, the use of anti-hail nets (to prevent damaged fruits that can be an easy target for pests/diseases) and lastly the rationalized use of pesticides. In the Netherlands, farmers use mechanical weeding, flower strips for pollinators and delayed mowing to stimulate the creation of natural habitats for beneficials.

The IPM improved scenarios of the low density strategies in Italy and Poland are slightly different than the high density ones: besides the use of mulch against weeds, and improved monitoring and a rationalized use of pesticides, farmers also use calcium hydroxide against apple canker (*Neonectria galligena*) and kaolin against *Halyomorpha halys* (brown marmorated stink bug), *Cacopsylla melanoneura*, *Dysaphys plantaginea* (rosy apple aphid), *Erwinia amylovora* (fireblight) and *Venturia inaequalis* (apple scab disease).

Table 3.4.2 displays the number of crop protection products (not applications) used in all strategies and scenarios.

Table 3.4.2: Overview of the number of pesticide products (not applications) included in two strategies in Italy, the one strategy in the Netherlands and the two strategies in Poland, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario.

Olive	IPM principle	Italy 1: High density	Italy 2: Low density	the Netherlands 1: High density	Poland 1: High density	Poland 2: Low density
State-of-the-art scenario	Fungicides	5-7	5-7	10-15	8-13	4-9
	Insecticides	3-5	3-5	2-5	4-6	2-4
	Herbicides	2-3	1-2	2	0-2	0-1
IPM improved scenario	Fungicides	3-5	3-5	10-15	8-13	4-9
	Insecticides	1-3	1-3	2-5	5-7	2-4
	Herbicides	0	0	2	0	0

In all IPM improved scenarios, except for the Netherlands, no herbicides are used. A slight drop in the use of pesticides between the state-of-the-art and the IPM improved scenarios can be noticed in the Italian and Polish strategies, due to the more rationalized use of pesticides and the use of alternatives to herbicides.

3.5 Strawberry

Strawberry production is covered by three NCC's: **Belgium (Flanders), the Netherlands and Spain**. The detailed IPM strategies for all three NCC's can be found in Annex 6.4.1, 6.4.2 and 6.4.3.

In 2020, 48,433 tonnes strawberries were produced on 1,140 ha in **Flanders**, with a ratio of open versus sheltered production of 40/60. In general, sheltered production systems on substrate result in higher yield and better quality, with a higher price per kg product. For the Flemish case, four strategies for strawberry production are selected: open or sheltered full soil production with mainly June bearing cultivars, heated and unheated sheltered production on substrate with both June bearing and everbearing cultivars and lastly strawberry propagation and cultivation on trayfields.

In **the Netherlands**, 75% of the strawberries or 59,700 tonnes/year, are produced sheltered, in tunnels (90 ha) or greenhouses on substrate (480 ha), despite the fact that 60% of the acreage used for strawberry production consists of open field cropping systems. Because of the higher production in sheltered systems, this is considered the most important strategy. Besides that, plant propagation and cultivation on tray fields (900 ha) is also a highly specialized and significant sector within the Dutch strawberry industry. Like in Belgium, June bearing cultivars are still used more than everbearing cultivars, however a shift is happening.

The majority of the strawberry production in **Spain** is done in a sheltered full soil production system on raised beds with June bearing cultivars. In 2023, 346,484 tonnes strawberries were produced on 7,328 ha.

Table 3.5.1 gives an overview of the number of tools included in the IPM strategies for Belgium, the Netherlands and Spain, both in the state-of-the-art scenarios and the IPM improved scenarios.

Table 3.5.1: Overview of the number of tools included in the four strategies in Belgium, the two strategies in the Netherlands and the one strategy in Spain, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. Tools are divided over the 3 IPM principles: prevention, monitoring and intervention.

Strawberry	IPM principle	Belgium strategy 1: full soil, open and sheltered	Belgium strategy 2: substrate, sheltered	Belgium strategy 3: substrate, sheltered, heated	Belgium strategy 4: propagation
State-of-the-art scenario	Prevention	7	8	8	6
	Monitoring	1	2	2	1
	Intervention	8	5	6	8
IPM improved scenario	Prevention	7	8	8	6
	Monitoring	1	2	2	1
	Intervention	8	5	6	8
Strawberry	IPM principle	the Netherlands strategy 1: substrate, sheltered	the Netherlands strategy 2: propagation	Spain strategy 1: full soil, sheltered	
State-of-the-art scenario	Prevention	7	7	5	
	Monitoring	2	2	1	
	Intervention	11	1	6	
IPM improved scenario	Prevention	10	8	5	
	Monitoring	3	2	1	
	Intervention	12	4	9	

The Dutch and Flemish strategies for sheltered production on substrate include similar measures with slightly different focus points. Whereas the Dutch state-of-the-art scenario focuses more on preventive climatic measures, the Flemish scenario includes more preventive measures that focus on hygiene during and after a cropping cycle. The same pests require intervention in both countries: powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*), Botrytis fruit rot (*Botrytis cinerea*), aphids, spider mites (*Tetranychus* spp.), thrips, Suzukii fly (*Drosophila suzukii*), whitefly and caterpillars. The intervention measures in the Flemish state-of-the-art scenario include mostly pesticides and natural enemies, whereas the Dutch scenario has a greater focus on natural enemies and also includes biological insecticides and biological products like fatty acids and potassium salts to control pests.

The IPM improved scenarios for the different Flemish strategies are all the same: they all include extra attention to optimal fertilization (to make the crop more resilient and to minimise the risk of powdery mildew, botrytis fruit rot and aphids by avoiding too much nitrogen fertilizer), the use of (additional) biological fungicides against powdery mildew and in the sheltered systems on substrate the use of UV-C light robots against powdery mildew.

The Dutch farmers also use UV-C light in the IPM improved scenario. They also add plant enhancers that increase resilience and neem based insecticides (against aphids, spider mites and thrips). To minimise the use of pesticides, spot spraying and PATS-C monitoring, which is the automatic, real time scouting of insects, are also included in the Dutch IPM improved scenario.

The Spanish strategy uses the lowest number of crop protection tools, with a focus on the use of healthy plant material, appropriate fertilisation and good ventilation and drainage to avoid fungal diseases. In the sheltered full soil strategy in Spain, the majority of the farmers use intervention measures to control spider mites (*Tetranychus* spp.), Botrytis fruit rot (*Botrytis cinerea*) and soilborne diseases. Only in the IPM improved scenario, there are additional measures against aphids (use of ladybirds and lacewings), spider mites (*Tetranychus* spp.) and thrips (use of predatory mites and bugs) as well. Unlike the open/sheltered full soil strategy in Flanders, intervention measures against powdery mildew (*Podosphaera aphanis*) are not common in Spain. This is not surprising, as the fungus is generally harder to control in sheltered systems and on substrate. Another difference between the Flemish and Spanish full soil strategies is that in Spain, no herbicides are used, as the raised beds are covered with a plastic mulch to control weeds. In Belgium, both physical barriers and herbicides are used to control weeds.

The heated and non-heated sheltered strategies on substrate in Belgium contain the same crop protection measures, with the only difference that there are usually more (three) cropping cycles for the June bearing cultivars in the heated strategy, repeating some hygiene and crop protection measures several times.

The propagation and cultivation of new strawberry plants are 2 separate crop protection strategies that are often done by separate growers on separate locations. In Belgium, most farmers only do the cultivation on trayfields themselves, as the first part of plant propagation is for certain cultivars only allowed for certified growers and it requires a lot of labour. The propagation and cultivation of strawberry plants are both outdoor activities in Belgium, unlike the Netherlands, where greenhouse propagation/cultivation is also done. Botrytis fruit rot and the Suzukii fruit fly (*Drosophila suzukii*) require no attention in these cropping systems, as there is no fruit that could get affected by this disease or pest. The plant propagation and cultivation in trayfields strategy in Belgium includes, compared to the full soil strategy, also mechanical weed control and an insecticide against strawberry mites (*Tarsonemus pallidus*). The intervention measures in both countries consist mostly of the use of chemical pesticides. In the Netherlands, hygienic measures (like the sanitation of trays and gutters, the removal of affected plants, disinfecting recirculating water, clean soil material), and controlling climatic conditions (with the use of Controlled Atmosphere Temperature Treatment and proper ventilation) are also focus points. Both countries focus in their IPM improved scenarios on stimulating plant resilience through optimal fertilization and biological control. Dutch farmers also include mechanical weeding in outdoor cropping systems and UV light to disinfect circulating water.

Table 3.5.2 displays the number of crop protection products (not applications) used in all strategies and scenarios, except for Belgium.

The use of herbicides is not necessary in cropping systems using substrate. However, unlike the full soil strategy in Belgium, herbicides are also not used in the full soil strategy in Spain., highlighting the difference in weed pressure.

The propagation strategy in the Netherlands requires more chemical inputs than the production strategy, which can be explained by the fact that it is from utmost importance to create clean and healthy starting material, as it serves as the basis for the strawberry production in the next season.

Table 3.5.2: Overview of the number of pesticide products (not applications) included in the two strategies in the Netherlands and the one strategy in Spain for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. There is no exact data available for Belgium.

Strawberry	IPM principle	the Netherlands strategy 1: substrate, sheltered	the Netherlands strategy 2: propagation	Spain strategy 1: full soil, sheltered
State-of-the-art scenario	Fungicides	7-9	15	5
	Insecticides	3-5	8	5
	Herbicides	0	8-15 (outdoor trayfields); 0 (glasshouse)	0
IPM improved scenario	Fungicides	7-9	15	5
	Insecticides	3-5	8	5
	Herbicides	0	8-15 (outdoor trayfields); 0 (glasshouse)	0

3.6 Wheat

There are four NCC's that cover wheat production: **Denmark, Germany, Romania and Switzerland**. The detailed IPM strategies for all four NCC's can be found in respectively Annex 6.5.1, 6.5.2, 6.5.3 and 6.5.4.

Winter wheat is the most commonly grown winter cereal crop in **Denmark**, and only one crop protection strategy for winter wheat production should be considered. In 2023, 470,000 hectares were used to produce winter wheat, with a mean yield of 7.5 t/ha. In **Germany**, there is also one strategy for winter wheat production that is followed by the majority of the farmers. In 2021, 21.1 million tonnes of winter wheat were produced on 2.84 million ha. In **Romania** conventional winter wheat production yielded 9.6 million tonnes on 2.2 million ha last year, while organic winter wheat production was a second strategy that yielded 96,000 tonnes on 78,327 ha. Similar to Denmark and Germany, there is only one strategy for winter wheat production in **Switzerland**, with 450,000 tonnes of production last year on 80,000 ha.

Table 3.6.1 gives an overview of the number of tools included in the IPM strategies for Denmark, Germany, Romania and Switzerland, both in the state-of-the-art scenarios and the IPM improved scenarios.

Table 3.6.1: Overview of the number of tools included in the one strategy in Denmark, the one strategy in Germany, the two strategies in Romania and the one strategy in Switzerland, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. Tools are divided over the three IPM principles: prevention, monitoring and intervention.

Wheat	IPM principle	Germany strategy 1: conventional	Romania strategy 1: conventional	Romania strategy 2: organic	Switzerland strategy 1: conventional	Denmark Strategy 1: conventional
State-of-the-art scenario	Prevention	7	4	4	8	15
	Monitoring	1	1	1	1	11
	Intervention	6	3	3	13	9
IPM improved scenario	Prevention	11	10	10	10	15
	Monitoring	3	3	3	2	11
	Intervention	9	5	5	10	8
IPM improved scenario 2 (only Germany)	Prevention	9				
	Monitoring	1				
	Intervention	6				

As shown in table 3.6.1, Denmark and Switzerland have more crop protection tools included in their state-of-the-art scenario compared to the German and Romanian baseline scenarios. Germany, Romania and Switzerland include more tools in their IPM improved scenarios compared to their state-of-the-art scenarios.

When comparing the conventional and organic strategies of the Romanian case, the preventive and monitoring crop protection practices and tools are the same for both scenarios. The only major differences are the intervention tools (biological pesticides are used instead of synthetic pesticides), the length of the time interval between wheat crops (wheat is grown every fourth year instead of every third/fourth year) and the use of natural enemies as biological control measures in the organic IPM improved scenario. In all NCC's, resistant cultivars and seed treatments are part of all of the different crop protection strategies/scenarios, mostly against fungi, but sometimes also against pests like wireworms (*Agriotes sp.*), the black coloured ground beetle (*Zabrus tenebrioides*), the Hessian fly (*Mayetiola destructor*) or the cereal leaf beetle (*Oulema melanopa*).

In all state-of-the-art scenarios, herbicides, fungicides and insecticides are used. The most common diseases in wheat are: Septoria (*Septoria tritici*), powdery mildew (*Blumeria graminis*), brown and yellow rust (*Puccinia recondite* and *Puccinia striiformis*), *Fusarium sp.*, *Tilletia sp.*, and *Ustilago sp.* The most common pests that are treated include the orange wheat blossom midge (*Sitodiplosis mosellana*) and aphids.

Farmers in Switzerland use the narrowest crop rotation: wheat is grown every second year. As shown in table 6.3.1, Switzerland has the highest number of intervention tools. The very narrow crop rotation could be one of the reasons why more intervention measures are needed compared to the other countries. In Germany, farmers who apply the state-of-the-art scenario grow wheat every third year, whereas farmers applying the IPM improved scenarios use a broader crop rotation for wheat of 5 years. In Romania wheat is grown every third or fourth year in the conventional production and every fourth year in the organic production. In Denmark, most farmers grow wheat every third year. A minority of Danish farmers applies a longer crop rotation (wheat grown every fourth year).

In all state-of-the-art scenarios of these NCC's, tillage was applied. In Denmark, Germany and Switzerland, there is already quite some attention to the optimal sowing conditions (sowing time, seed density) in the state-of-the-art scenarios. In Romania, this is considered in the IPM improved scenarios. Mechanical weeding and physical weed control measures are already applied in the state-of-the-art scenario of Switzerland. In the other NCC's, this was part of their IPM improved scenarios.

Switzerland is also the only country to promote ecological habitats like flowering strips or hedges to promote beneficials or to apply precision agriculture in their state-of-the-art scenario. Beneficial insects or microbes were also part of the IPM improved scenarios of Germany and Romania. In all IPM improved scenarios, except for Denmark, additional monitoring measures were included, so farmers can apply pesticides more precisely and more effectively. The reason no additional monitoring measures are included in the Danish IPM improved scenario, can be explained by the fact that the majority of the Danish farmers already implement a lot of monitoring measures (11 measures versus 1 monitoring measure in all the other NCC's).

In Germany, two IPM improved scenarios were considered, one where no tillage was applied and one in case of the occurrence of herbicide resistance weeds. Both IPM improved scenarios included a wider crop rotation (every fifth year) instead of every third year, however for the no tillage scenario, the focus was on a more site-specific application of pesticides (in terms of pesticide placement and dosage), based on more extensive monitoring, and for the herbicide resistance scenario, there were some tools that were added to replace herbicide treatments, like ploughing, undersown crops/intercropping, a stale seedbed and mechanical weeding. This scenario is applied when certain weeds like *Alopecurus myosuroides* or *Polygonum concolvolus* have become resistant to herbicides.

Table 3.6.2 displays the number of crop protection products (not applications) used in the Romanian and Danish strategies and scenarios. There are no differences in the number of used pesticide products between the state-of-the-art and the IPM improved scenarios. For Denmark, the improved IPM scenario for winter wheat looks very much like the baseline scenario. The reason is that pesticide inputs have been optimized during many years in the form of reduced dosages and optimized mixtures, as Denmark has had governmental pesticide action plans since 1986. This does not mean that no improvements can be made, but it implies more risk/more costs for the farmers, which could result in bigger (financial) losses in challenging years. Despite the fact that the Danish strategy includes more tools than the Romanian strategy, no real differences in the number of used pesticide products can be noticed.

Table 3.7.2: Overview of the number of pesticide products (not applications) included in the two strategies in Romania and the one strategy in Denmark, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. There is no exact data available for Germany and Switzerland.

Maize	IPM principle	Romania strategy 1: Conventional	Romania strategy 2: Organic	Denmark strategy 1: Conventional
State-of-the-art scenario	Fungicides	2-3	0-1	3-4
	Insecticides	2-3	0-2	1-3
	Herbicides	2-3	0	3-4
IPM improved scenario	Fungicides	2-3	0-1	3-4
	Insecticides	2-3	0-2	1-3
	Herbicides	2-3	0	3-4

3.7 Maize

Maize production is covered by the NCC's in **Denmark, Romania and Switzerland**. The detailed IPM strategies for all three NCC's can be found in Annex 6.6.1, 6.6.2 and 6.6.3.

90% of the maize production in **Denmark** is silage maize, used for feeding dairy cattle. It is mainly located in Jutland, the main peninsula, where the dairy farming is also concentrated. To lesser extent, maize is grown for grain (to feed pigs) or as input for biogas plants. However, the described scenario is considered representative of at least 90 % of the maize production in Denmark. In 2023, 180,000 ha was used for maize production, with a yield of 14-19.5 tonnes of dry matter/ha/year, however there are no official statistics on yield available.

In **Romania**, a total of 8.5 million tonnes of maize were produced in 2023, on 2.3 million hectares, which ranks Romania first among EU nations in terms of cultivated area for maize. Two strategies were selected for the Romanian case; a strategy for the conventional cropping system, which is 98.9% of the maize production, primarily grain maize, and a strategy for the organic production of maize, which is 1.1% of the Romanian production. There are no relevant regional differences for any of the cultivation methods. In 2023, 8.4 million tonnes of conventional maize was grown on 2,332,684 ha, versus 96,000 tonnes of organic maize on 40,316 ha.

Similar to Romania, the most important strategy for maize production in **Switzerland** is maize grown in a conventional cropping system, with no relevant region-specific differences. In 2023, Switzerland produced 993,000 tonnes of maize on 62,794 ha (silage maize: 47,140 ha; grain maize: 15,654 ha).

Table 3.7.1 gives an overview of the number of tools included in the IPM strategies for Denmark, Romania and Switzerland, both in the state-of-the-art scenarios and the IPM improved scenarios.

Table 3.7.1: Overview of the number of tools included in the one strategy in Denmark, the two strategies in Romania and the one strategy in Switzerland, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. Tools are divided over the three IPM principles: prevention, monitoring and intervention.

Maize	IPM principle	Romania strategy 1: Conventional	Romania strategy 2: Organic	Switzerland strategy 1: Conventional	Denmark strategy 1: Conventional
State-of-the-art scenario	Prevention	4	4	8	5
	Monitoring	1	1	1	4
	Intervention	4	3	11	4
IPM improved scenario	Prevention	10	9	10	5
	Monitoring	3	3	2	4
	Intervention	6	5	11	4

When comparing the conventional and organic strategies in Romania, the preventive and monitoring crop protection practices and tools are the same. The only major differences are the intervention tools, where biological pesticides are used instead of non-biological pesticides, the time interval between maize crops is longer (organic maize is grown every fourth year instead of every third year) and in the organic IPM improved scenario light traps are included against *Agrotis segetum*.

When comparing the state-of-the-art scenarios and the IPM improved scenarios of Denmark, Switzerland and Romania for conventional maize, the Swiss scenarios include more tools than the Romanian and Danish cases, while the Danish strategy includes the lowest number of measures.

In both Switzerland and Romania, resistant cultivars, field monitoring, mechanical weed control, herbicides (against dicotyledonous weeds) and biological pest control (*Trichogramma spp.* against caterpillars) are used by the majority of conventional farmers. However, the Swiss state-of-the-art scenario focuses even more on biological pest control by using *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* against grubs and *Bacillus thuringiensis* against caterpillars as well and by providing ecological habitats like flower strips or hedges. Compared to the Romanian case, there are also more physical weed control measures included in the Swiss state-of-the-art scenario, and there is also specific attention to field and machine hygiene, precision agriculture, reduced frequency of pesticide applications and the use of bio-stimulants that promote the crop's resilience. However, crop rotations with maize are broader in Romania (maize is grown every third or fourth year) than in Switzerland (maize is grown every second year). In Romania, it is also common to use seeds that had a seed treatment against various pests (*Tanymecus dilaticollis* and *Agriotes spp.*).

The Danish state-of-the-art scenario is quite different from the Swiss and Romanian case: it includes no mechanical or physical weed control, no resistant maize cultivars, no obligatory crop rotation and no biological control. In Denmark, the biggest challenges regarding crop protection in maize is weeds, in particular cockspur grass (*Echinochloa crus-galli*), which has spread enormously during the last 10-15 years, and is now present in almost every maize field. Perennial weeds and certain annual weeds like *Veronica* species are also troublesome. Diseases are less of a problem in Denmark. Regarding pests, bird damage during the emergence and early growth phases of the crop can be a big problem in some areas. In areas vulnerable to bird attacks, a seed coating with products less palatable to birds is used. Some insect pests are present, but there is normally no need for insecticide spraying in Denmark. Because of the high weed pressure, most measures are focused on this: glyphosate spraying before sowing, herbicide applications, interrow cultivation, hygiene of machinery to prevent the spread of *Echinochloa crus-galli* and evaluation of weed resistance and weeds control measures after harvest. The Danish IPM improved scenario focuses on the practice of crop rotation, band application of herbicides and more interrow cultivation (2-3 times instead of 1). Band spraying and more mechanical weed control (interrow cultivation) could reduce herbicide use already by 60-80%.

In Switzerland and Romania, a closer monitoring of diseases, pests and weeds and more attention to the ideal sowing conditions are included in the IPM improved scenarios. For both cases, the majority of the added tools are preventive measures. In Switzerland, this also means the use of a stale seedbed and no herbicides. In Romania, a balanced fertilization, better soil conditions through soil drainage and liming when necessary, field hygiene and only using insecticides and fungicides when necessary are also part of the IPM improved scenario.

Table 3.7.2 displays the number of crop protection products (not applications) used in all strategies and scenarios, except for the Swiss strategy, as no exact data was available. This data also shows a focus on weed control. In all cases, there are usually no fungicides used.

Table 3.7.2: Overview of the number of pesticide products (not applications) included in the two strategies in Romania and the one strategy in Denmark, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. There is no exact data available for Switzerland.

Maize	IPM principle	Romania strategy 1: Conventional	Romania strategy 2: Organic	Denmark strategy 1: Conventional
State-of-the-art scenario	Fungicides	0-1	0-1	0-1
	Insecticides	1-3	0-2	0
	Herbicides	1-3	0	2-5
IPM improved scenario	Fungicides	0-1	0-1	0-1
	Insecticides	1-3	0-2	0
	Herbicides	1-3	0	2-5

3.8 Potato

There are five NCC's that cover potato production within SUPPORT: **Belgium, Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands and Poland**. The detailed IPM strategies for all NCC's can be found in Annex 6.7.1 to Annex 6.7.5.

In **Belgium (Flanders region)**, three strategies were selected, representing the three most important cropping systems for potato; warehouse potatoes, early potatoes and seed potatoes. No relevant regio-specific differences within Flanders were mentioned. The first strategy is the most important one in terms of production an acreage: in 2021 1,867,240 tonnes of storage potatoes were produced on 43,540 ha. In that same year, 239,353 tonnes of early potatoes were grown on 6,093 ha and 38,022 tonnes of seed potatoes were grown on 1,393 ha. Overall, storage potatoes yield 45-55 tonnes/ha, early potatoes yield 40-45 tonnes/ha and seed potatoes yield 25-30 tonnes/ha.

In **Denmark**, the production of starch potatoes for processing is the most important strategy, representing 75-80% of the production (2 million tonnes/year) and 70% of the agricultural are used for potato production (41,300 ha).

The **German** NCC reported on three strategies for potato production: the production of early potatoes, warehouse potatoes and starch potatoes. The biggest differences between these strategies are the varieties grown and the length of the growing phase. Varieties are usually selected based on their desired characteristics. Popular varieties that are in high demand usually don't have good tolerance to harmful organisms. The longer the growing period, the greater the pressure from harmful organisms and diseases, which results in a higher treatment index of pesticides.

The Netherlands presented one strategy for open field potato production, however a distinction was made in the report between warehouse, starch and seed potatoes in terms of chemical pesticide applications (Annex 6.7.4). In 2022, the total Dutch potato production was 6,915,875 tonnes which is an average of 42,6 tonnes per hectare. In that year, 163,058 hectares were used for potato production, of which 76,595 ha were used for warehouse potatoes, 43,157 ha for seed potatoes and 43,306 for starch potatoes.

In **Poland**, the same strategies were selected as in Belgium (warehouse, early and seed potatoes). Similar to the Flemish case, the production of warehouse potatoes is the most important cropping system for potato in Poland, with a production of 2,000,000 tonnes in 2023 on 50,000 ha (which is a mean yield of 40 tonnes/ha). Early potato production accounts for 375,000 tonnes of potatoes grown on 15,000 ha (mean yield: 25t/ha) and seed potatoes for 170,000 tonnes grown on 6,000 ha (mean yield: 28t/ha).

Table 3.8.1 gives an overview of the number of tools included in the IPM strategies for Belgium, Germany, Denmark, the Netherlands and Poland, both in the state-of-the-art scenarios and the IPM improved scenarios.

Table 3.8.1: Overview of the number of tools included in the three strategies in Belgium, the one strategy in Denmark, the three strategies in Germany, the one strategy in the Netherlands and the three strategies in Poland, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. Tools are divided over the 3 IPM principles: prevention, monitoring and intervention.

Potato	IPM principle	Belgium 1: warehouse	Belgium 2: early	Belgium 3: seed	Germany 2: warehouse	Germany 1: early	Germany 3: starch
State-of-the-art scenario	Prevention	7	7	8	4	4	4
	Monitoring	1	1	1	1	1	1
	Intervention	9	6	8	6	5	6
IPM improved scenario	Prevention	8	8	8	6	6	6
	Monitoring	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Intervention	8	5	8	8	8	8
	IPM principle	the Netherlands: warehouse, seed and starch	Poland 1: warehouse	Poland 2: early	Poland 3: seed	Denmark 1: starch	
State-of-the-art scenario	Prevention	6	5	7	6	8	
	Monitoring	2	1	1	1	4	
	Intervention	4	7	5	8	10	
IPM improved scenario	Prevention	6	7	8	8	8	
	Monitoring	3	1	1	1	4	
	Intervention	7	8	6	9	10	

Table 3.8.1 shows that early potato strategies require less intervention tools than storage or late potato strategies. This can be explained by their shorter/earlier growing season, resulting in less pest and disease pressure. For example, in Belgium, no *Alternaria* or Colorado beetle (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata*) treatment is necessary in early potatoes production and less sprayings against late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) are possible.

Even though seed potatoes are also harvested earlier, similar to the early potatoes, they do require more intervention tools than the early potatoes because of the stricter pest and disease tolerance as a result of the certification process. Starting with healthy plant material is essential for a good harvest, therefore the quality of the seed potatoes is the foundation of the potato production for the next season. In general, all strategies highlight the importance of starting with healthy planting material (seed potatoes) and using resistant varieties (e.g. against *Phytophthora infestans*) when possible.

In all NCC's most intervention tools are targeting the same important diseases and pests for potato production: *Phytophthora infestans*, *Alternaria* spp, Colorado bug (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata*) and weeds. Aphids also need to be tackled in seed potatoes. These pests/diseases/weeds are in all state-of-the-art scenarios controlled by using chemical pesticides.

Poland implements the smallest crop rotation in the state-of-the-art scenarios for warehouse and early potatoes (potatoes are grown every second year). Seed potatoes had a slightly broader rotation (grown every third year). The broadest crop rotation is found in the IPM improved scenario of the Netherlands, where the rotation time of potatoes is improved from 4 years to 6 years compared to the state-of-the-art scenario. Flemish farmers apply the same rotation time for potatoes as their Dutch neighbours in all of their strategies (4 years), which improves to a rotation time of 5 years in the IPM improved version of the different strategies. In Germany and Denmark potatoes are grown every third year, which improves to every fifth year in the IPM improved scenarios of all German strategies and every fourth/fifth year in the Danish IPM improved scenario.

Sprout inhibition is a measure that is only included in warehouse potato strategies of Belgium and Germany, to prevent post-harvest sprouting. Pre-sprouted seed potatoes on the other hand, are commonly used by Polish farmers for the production of early potatoes. A tuber treatment is also included in all of the Polish and Danish production strategies in order to protect the plants against fungal diseases. This is also used by most Flemish farmers for the production of early and warehouse potatoes.

Only in Denmark mechanical weed control is used by most potato farmers (state-of-the-art scenario). For all other NCCs, this measure is part of the IPM improved scenarios except for the IPM improved scenario for warehouse potatoes in Germany.

Nematode identification is only in Denmark and in the Belgian seed potato strategy included in the state-of-the-art scenario. By identifying the type of nematodes present on the field, farmers are able to select specific resistant cultivars. This is currently also applied by a minority of farmers in Belgium, Germany and the Netherlands (IPM improved scenarios).

Besides enhanced crop rotation, mechanical weed control and nematode identification, extra monitoring and scouting tools and more attention to field and machinery hygiene are also part of most IPM improved scenarios.

Table 3.8.2 displays the amount of crop protection products (not applications) used in all strategies and scenarios of the different NCC's, except for Denmark and Germany.

Table 3.8.2: Overview of the number of pesticide products (not applications) included in the three strategies in Belgium, the one strategy in the Netherlands and the three strategies in Poland, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. There is no data available for Denmark and Germany.

Potato	Pesticides	Belgium 1: warehouse	Belgium 2: early	Belgium 3: seed	the Netherlands 1	the Netherlands: warehouse	the Netherlands: starch	the Netherlands: seed
State-of-the-art scenario	Fungicides	7-12	6-10	6-10	5-8	8	5	8
	Insecticides	0-2	0-1	4-6	1-3	1	3	3
	Herbicides	5-7	3-5	3-5	4-5	5	4	4
IPM improved scenario	Fungicides	7-11	6-10	5-8	5-8	8	5	8
	Insecticides	0-1	4-6	5	1-3	1	3	3
	Herbicides	5-7	3-5	3-9	4-5	5	4	4
	IPM principle	Poland 1: warehouse	Poland 2: early	Poland 3: seed				
State-of-the-art scenario	Fungicides	5-7	4-6	5-7				
	Insecticides	2-3	2-3	5-7				
	Herbicides	2	2	2				
IPM improved scenario	Fungicides	5-7	4-6	4-7				
	Insecticides	2-3	2-3	4-6				
	Herbicides	2	1-2	1-2				

Table 3.8.2 shows that not all IPM improved scenarios resulted in the use of less pesticide products. However, this table gives no indication of the number of applications, hence no conclusions on the difference in pesticide use between the state-of-the-art and IPM improved scenarios can be drawn.

The Belgian strategies contain the highest number of fungicide and herbicide products used, however the use of insecticide products in the early and warehouse potatoes was the lowest of all NCC's. This can give an indication of difference in the pest and disease pressure between the countries.

3.9 Onion

There are two NCC's that cover onion production; **Italy** and **Poland**. The detailed IPM strategies for both NCC's can be found in Annex 6.8.1 and 6.8.2.

For the **Italian** case, two strategies were selected based on differences in cultivars, as there are no relevant regional differences in cultivation methods for the different varieties. The first strategy covers onion production using "short-day" varieties (summer sowing) intended for the fresh market, the second strategy covers onion production using "long-day" varieties (spring sowing) which produce onions that can easily be stored. The short- and long-day varieties cover respectively 25% and 75% of the total acreage and onion production in Italy.

In **Poland**, the most important production method is, similar to the Italian case, spring sowing. It is estimated that 90-95% of the Polish onion production using spring sowing. In Poland there are also no regional differences that effect the cultivation method.

Table 3.9.1 gives an overview of the number of tools included in the IPM strategies for Italy in Poland, both in the state-of-the-art scenarios and the IPM improved scenarios.

Table 3.9.1: Overview of the number of tools included in the two strategies in Italy and one strategy in Poland, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario. Tools are divided over the three IPM principles: prevention, monitoring and intervention.

Onion	IPM principle	Italy strategy 1: summer sowing	Italy strategy 2: spring sowing	Poland strategy 1: spring sowing
State-of-the-art scenario	Prevention	10	10	6
	Monitoring	2	2	1
	Intervention	8	8	9
IPM improved scenario	Prevention	15	16	7
	Monitoring	4	4	1
	Intervention	8	10	12

When comparing the state-of-the-art scenarios for spring sowing in Italy and Poland, the Italian case includes more tools and focuses more than in Poland on the correct sowing time and location, field hygiene measures, the use of forecasting models as a monitoring tool, splitting herbicide doses and the use of extensions services/experts for advice. In both cases, no tolerant/resistant cultivars and no mechanical weed control are used by the majority of conventional farmers.

In the IPM improved scenarios, both in Italy and in Poland, resistant/tolerant cultivars and mechanical weed control are included compared to the respective state-of-the-art scenarios.

In Italy, other additional tools like the alternation of long- and short-day varieties, a longer crop rotation, reduction of tillage depth, the use of a stale seedbed, the use of more and new forecasting models, monitoring in an earlier stage, monitoring with traps, using less pesticides and optimizing fertilization are included in the IPM improved scenarios.

In Poland, additional tools like biological pest control, the use of flaming for weed control and using less pesticides are included in the IPM improved scenario compared to the state-of-the-art scenario.

Table 3.9.2 displays the number of crop protection products (not applications) used in all strategies and scenarios. When comparing the Italian and Polish spring sowing scenarios, the larger number of insecticides used in the Polish case is notable. This could be because of the lower amount of preventive tools in the Polish strategy compared to the Italian strategy or because of differences in pest pressure in both countries. Similar numbers of used fungicide and herbicide products can be noticed. There are no notable differences between the Italian spring and summer sowing strategy regarding the amount of crop protection products used.

Table 3.9.2: Overview of the amount of pesticide products (not applications) included in the two strategies in Italy and the one strategy in Poland, for both the state-of-the-art scenario and the IPM improved scenario.

Onion	IPM principle	Italy strategy 1: summer sowing	Italy strategy 2: spring sowing	Poland strategy 1: spring sowing
State-of-the-art scenario	Fungicides	12-15	12-15	10-12
	Insecticides	5-6	5-8	10-12
	Herbicides	4-5	4-7	4-5-6
IPM improved scenario	Fungicides	<12-15	<12-15	8-10
	Insecticides	5-6	4-6	10-14
	Herbicides	<4	<4	4-5-6

4. Reflections

Deliverable 1.1 of the SUPPORT project created an IPM inventory (M.D. Thorsted, S. Appel & J.E. Jensen, 2024), providing an overview of the different IPM tools that can be used in the cultivation of the eight crops that are being investigated within the project. This deliverable aimed at combining these IPM tools into complete crop protection strategies for the most important cropping systems of each NCC. In all NCC's, no region-specific differences were noticed, therefore only the different cropping systems were taken into account when constructing the crop protection strategies. For each cropping system, two scenarios were drafted, one that is representative for the majority of the farmers (state-of-the-art scenario) and one that is being used by a minority of farmers who are more sustainability oriented (IPM improved scenario).

A comparison of these two types of strategies revealed that, in general, a wider variety of IPM tools is being applied in the IPM improved scenarios compared to the state-of-the-art scenarios. Consequently, the additional actions that are being implemented by farmers in order to reduce the use of synthetic pesticides require extra efforts from them, such as more labour time and extra know-how on the additional measures. The most common tools that are included in the IPM improved scenarios are: additional monitoring and scouting of pests and diseases, longer crop rotations, optimizing sowing/planting conditions, field/crop hygiene, the use of beneficials or natural enemies and mechanical weed control. Longer crop rotations were mentioned in the IPM improved strategies of potato, onion, maize (only Denmark, not Romania and Switzerland) and wheat (only Denmark and Germany, not Romania and Switzerland).

Also at the level of the crops, interesting similarities and differences could be noticed;

The **perennial crops winegrape and olive** require overall the lowest number of used pesticides, especially the low density orchards. Because of the perennial nature of these crops, the main focus is on healthy plant material and hygiene of the crop/on the field. Also noticeable is the fact that in **apple** production, bio stimulants are already commonly used to increase plant resilience and stimulate nutrient uptake.

Cereal crops strongly differ regarding disease pressure: in **maize**, no fungicides are used since weeds are the main problem in maize and thus the focus of the intervention measures. **Wheat** production on the other hand has to deal with fungal diseases. Because of the high weed pressure in maize, mechanical weed control is already part of the state-of-the-art scenarios in Romania and Switzerland (not yet in Denmark). In wheat, this is also the case for Switzerland, however mechanical weed control is not mentioned in the state-of-the-art/IPM improved scenarios of Denmark, Germany and Romania.

For **potatoes**, some important differences were noticed between the different cropping systems. The production of early potatoes requires less intervention tools than the production of warehouse potatoes. This can be explained by their shorter/earlier growing season, resulting in less pest and disease pressure. For example, in Belgium, no *Alternaria* or Colorado beetle (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata*) treatment is necessary in early potatoes production and less sprayings against late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) are possible. Even though seed potatoes are also harvested earlier, similar to the early potatoes, they do require more intervention tools than the early potatoes because of the stricter pest and disease tolerance as a result of the certification process. This is also why a longer crop rotation is done with seed potatoes. Denmark was the only country where most potato farmers already use mechanical weed control and nematode identification.

In **strawberry** production, the propagation strategy also requires more chemical inputs than the production strategy. This can also be explained by the fact that it is of utmost importance to create clean and healthy starting material, as it serves as the basis for the strawberry production in the next season. In strawberry production on substrate, no herbicides are needed. However, in the full soil production strategy in Spain herbicides are also not used, as the raised beds that are covered with a plastic mulch are sufficient to control weeds. In Belgium, both physical barriers and herbicides are necessary to control weeds in full soil systems, highlighting the difference in weed pressure between both countries.

The crop protection strategies presented in this deliverable can be used as a guide for bilateral talks with farmers or during meetings with a larger group of farmers on IPM tools and strategies. It can inspire farmers and advisors to consider additional or different IPM tools that can lower their pesticide use and the associated pressure on health and the environment. They can moreover use the information gathered in this deliverable to combine the IPM tools into crop protection strategies that can deal with climate change and regulatory restrictions.

During the project period other tasks of the SUPPORT project will provide data from surveys and interviews that should give insight in the barriers and levers for IPM adoption and address how the adoption can be improved. The 25 IPM strategies reports will be the basis for task 1.3 of the SUPPORT project, in which the IPM monitoring system being developed in task 1.2 will be applied to the current and future IPM crop protection scenarios. This will provide an impact assessment of the crop protection strategies regarding pest control efficacy, economic performance of farms and the environmental impact.

5. References

- Kounani, K., Kannavou, A. (2024). Deliverable 3.1 Policy analysis. *Deliverable 3.1 from the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme SUPPORT*
- Mathis, M., Blom, J. F., Nemecek, T., Bravin, E., Jeanneret, P., Daniel, O., & de Baan, L. (2022). Comparison of exemplary crop protection strategies in Swiss apple production: Multi-criteria assessment of pesticide use, ecotoxicological risks, environmental and economic impacts. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 31, 512–528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.03.008>
- Strassemeyer, J., Daehmlow, D., Dominic, A. R., Lorenz, S., & Golla, B. (2017). SYNOPS-WEB, an online tool for environmental risk assessment to evaluate pesticide strategies on field level. *Crop Protection*, 97, 28–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2016.11.036>
- Thorsted, M.D., Appel, S., Jensen, J.E. (2024). Deliverable 1.1 Inventory of IPM tools. *Deliverable 1.1 from the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme SUPPORT*

6. ANNEXES

6.1 Wine Grape

6.1.1 Greece

Contact person: Kalliopi Kounani (kalliopi.kounani@aua.gr)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: Enhanced Pest Monitoring and Biological Control

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: Enhanced Pest Monitoring and Biological Control

Strategy 2 – state of the art scenario: Integrated Crop Rotation and Cover Cropping

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario: Integrated Crop Rotation and Cover Cropping

Strategy 3 – state of the art scenario: Sustainable Soil Management and Conservation Agriculture

Strategy 3 – IPM improved scenario: Sustainable Soil Management and Conservation Agriculture

Strategy 4 – state of the art scenario: Pest and Disease Monitoring and Early Warning Systems

Strategy 4 – IPM improved scenario: Pest and Disease Monitoring and Early Warning Systems

Strategy 5 – state of the art scenario: Agroecological Farming Practices and Habitat Management

Strategy 5 – state of the art scenario: Agroecological Farming Practices and Habitat Management

IPM strategies for Greece

Strategy selection

The predominant grape cultivation method in the Kiato region of Peloponnese is open vineyard systems. The traditional Greek vineyard in this area is deeply rooted in the local climate and topography. The adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies among grape growers in Kiato is gradually increasing, driven by regional characteristics, farming practices, economic incentives, and access to education and resources. Despite challenges to broader adoption, the efforts of agricultural extension services, cooperatives, and government initiatives play a crucial role in promoting IPM and supporting sustainable grape production in the region.

Kiato, located in the northeastern part of the Peloponnese, is a significant area for table grape production in Greece. Known for its fertile plains and favorable microclimate, Kiato contributes substantially to the nation's table grape output. The region's landscape, characterized by a mix of vineyards and other agricultural lands, supports traditional grape-growing practices.

The data provided comes from a selected biological producer in the region, reflecting the practices and challenges faced in organic table grape cultivation.

Description reference year:

2023-2024

The 2023-2024 season was particularly challenging, with climate variations impacting grape production. Despite these difficulties, the organic vineyard maintained a relatively stable output, though there were notable issues with pest management and a slight decrease in overall yield compared to previous years.

Strategy 1: Enhanced Pest Monitoring and Biological Control

Description

Number of growers	50
Acreage (ha)	5000 ha
% of total acreage	10%
Production (tonnes/year)	9000 tonnes tonnes/year
% of the total production	15 %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	45 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	May to September
Estimated annual yield	1.8 t/ha
Price per kg product	€2.50/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	€5000/ha

Storage loss	100 kg/ha or 5%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 3 Insecticides: 2 Herbicides: 2
% drift reduction	65 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	4 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops?
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Traps for pest monitoring
Application frequency	Weekly
Application date	April to September
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout growth stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Various pests

Tool	Biological control agents
Application frequency	2-3 times per season
Application date	Based on pest thresholds
Stage of development of the crop	Early to mid-growth stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Specific pests targeted by agents

Tool	Habitat manipulation
Application frequency	Once per season
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	General pest reduction

Tool	Cultural practices (e.g., sanitation)
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Year-round
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Preventive measures

Tool	Pheromone traps
Application frequency	Throughout the season
Application date	Start from early season
Stage of development of the crop	Early to late stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pheromone-sensitive pests

Tool	Predatory insects release
Application frequency	2-3 times per season
Application date	According to pest population
Stage of development of the crop	Mid to late growth stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Specific pests

Tool	Biopesticides
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	Based on pest pressure
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Various pests

Tool	Cover crops
Application frequency	Seasonally
Application date	Rotational planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre and post main crop
Target pest/disease/weed	General pest management

Tool	Trap crops
Application frequency	Periodically
Application date	Before main crop
Stage of development of the crop	Early stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Specific pest diversion

Tool	Physical barriers (e.g., nets)
Application frequency	Throughout the season
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	General pest exclusion
Target pest/disease/weed	X

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	50 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	April to August
Estimated annual yield	2.0 t/ha
Price per kg product	€2.70/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	€6000/ha
Storage loss	80 kg/ha or 4%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 2 Insecticides: 1

	Herbicides: 2
% drift reduction	70%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	5 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops?
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Improved resistant cultivar
Application frequency	One-time planting
Application date	At planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	General resistance

Tool	Enhanced biological control agents
Application frequency	Regularly scheduled
Application date	According to pest cycles
Stage of development of the crop	Early to mid-growth stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Specific pests

Tool	Advanced pheromone traps
Application frequency	Throughout the season
Application date	Early season deployment
Stage of development of the crop	Early to late stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pheromone-sensitive pests

Tool	Integrated habitat management
Application frequency	Seasonally
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	General pest reduction

Tool	Enhanced cultural practices
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Year-round
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Preventive measures

Tool	Biocontrol with native species
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	According to pest outbreaks
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Various pests

Tool	Precision application technology
Application frequency	Based on need
Application date	According to monitoring
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Specific applications

Tool	Innovative trap designs
Application frequency	Throughout the season
Application date	Before main crop
Stage of development of the crop	Early to late stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Various pest traps

Tool	Sustainable cover cropping
Application frequency	Seasonal rotations
Application date	Before and after main crop
Stage of development of the crop	Pre and post main crop
Target pest/disease/weed	General pest management

Tool	Automated monitoring systems
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	General monitoring

Strategy 2: Integrated Crop Rotation and Cover Cropping

Description

Number of growers	30
Acreage (ha)	3000 ha
% of total acreage	6 %
Production (tonnes/year)	6000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	10 %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? no
Cropping density	40 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	April to October
Estimated annual yield	1.5 t/ha
Price per kg product	€2.30/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	€4500/ha
Storage loss	110 kg/ha or 5.5%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>):

	Fungicides: 2 Insecticides: 1 Herbicides: 2
% drift reduction	60%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	5 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops?
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Crop rotation planning
Application frequency	Seasonal rotation
Application date	Annually
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	General pest management

Tool	Cover crop selection
Application frequency	Seasonal rotation
Application date	Pre and post main crop
Stage of development of the crop	Pre and post main crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil health improvement

Tool	Beneficial insect habitats
Application frequency	Seasonal establishment
Application date	Before main crop
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest predator attraction

Tool	Non-host crop buffer zones
Application frequency	Yearly setup
Application date	Pre-planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest control

Tool	Weed suppression covers
Application frequency	Seasonal rotation
Application date	Pre-planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control

Tool	Disease-suppressive rotations
Application frequency	Yearly rotation
Application date	Pre-planting

Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease management

Tool	Precision tillage systems
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	According to soil conditions
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil health improvement

Tool	Water-efficient irrigation methods
Application frequency	Based on need
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Water management

Tool	Integrated nutrient management
Application frequency	Seasonally adjusted
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Nutrient balance

Tool	Soil health monitoring
Application frequency	Continuous assessment
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil quality improvement

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? no
Cropping density	45 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	March to September
Estimated annual yield	1.8 t/ha
Price per kg product	€2.50/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	€5000/ha
Storage loss	100 kg/ha or 5%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 2 Insecticides: 1 Herbicides: 2
% drift reduction	65%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	4 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops?

Intercropping	no
---------------	----

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Enhanced resistant crop varieties
Application frequency	Once at planting
Application date	At planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Resistance enhancement

Tool	Integrated cover cropping
Application frequency	Seasonal rotation
Application date	Before and after main crop
Stage of development of the crop	Pre and post main crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil health improvement

Tool	Advanced biological pest control
Application frequency	According to pest cycles
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest-specific control

Tool	Precision planting techniques
Application frequency	Based on planting schedule
Application date	Pre-planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Plant spacing control

Tool	Enhanced soil fertility management
Application frequency	Seasonal adjustment
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil nutrient balance

Tool	Eco-friendly pesticide alternatives
Application frequency	As needed basis
Application date	According to pest outbreaks
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest management

Tool	Water-saving irrigation systems
Application frequency	Seasonal adjustments
Application date	Throughout the season

Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Water management

Tool	Soil health improvement covers
Application frequency	Seasonal rotation
Application date	Pre and post main crop
Stage of development of the crop	Pre and post main crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil quality enhancement

Tool	Advanced nutrient cycling techniques
Application frequency	Throughout the season
Application date	Seasonal adjustments
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Nutrient recycling

Tool	Enhanced monitoring and scouting
Application frequency	Continuous monitoring
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Early pest detection

Strategy 3: Sustainable Soil Management and Conservation Agriculture

Description

Number of growers	40
Acreage (ha)	4000 ha
% of total acreage	8 %
Production (tonnes/year)	8000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	13 %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	55 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	March to November
Estimated annual yield	2.2 t/ha
Price per kg product	€2.80/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	€6000/ha
Storage loss	90 kg/ha or 4.5%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 2 Insecticides: 1 Herbicides: 2
% drift reduction	70%

Minimum buffer zone to surface water	6 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops?
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	No-till farming
Application frequency	Seasonal rotation
Application date	Pre-planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil health improvement

Tool	Cover crop integration
Application frequency	Seasonal rotation
Application date	Before and after main crop
Stage of development of the crop	Pre and post main crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil nutrient management

Tool	Integrated pest and disease-resistant crops
Application frequency	Throughout the season
Application date	At planting and growth stages
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest and disease control

Tool	Advanced soil moisture management
Application frequency	Throughout the season
Application date	Based on soil moisture levels
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Water management

Tool	Precision nutrient application
Application frequency	Seasonal adjustments
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Nutrient management

Tool	Bio-intensive integrated farming systems
Application frequency	Seasonal adjustments
Application date	Pre and post main crop
Stage of development of the crop	Pre and post main crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Integrated pest management

Tool	Conservation tillage techniques
------	---------------------------------

Application frequency	As needed basis
Application date	Pre-planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil conservation

Tool	Enhanced soil structure management
Application frequency	Yearly adjustments
Application date	According to soil analysis
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil health enhancement

Tool	Ecological pest suppression
Application frequency	Throughout the season
Application date	As needed basis
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest management

Tool	Automated climate monitoring
Application frequency	Continuous monitoring
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Climate-based pest prediction

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	60 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	February to December
Estimated annual yield	2.5 t/ha
Price per kg product	€3.00/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	€7000/ha
Storage loss	80 kg/ha or 4%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 1 Insecticides: 1 Herbicides: 1
% drift reduction	75%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	7 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops?
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	High-resistance seed varieties
Application frequency	Seasonal planting
Application date	At planting
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Resistance enhancement

Tool	Integrated soil fertility management
Application frequency	Seasonal adjustments
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil health improvement

Tool	Precision irrigation systems
Application frequency	Seasonal adjustments
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Water management

Tool	Enhanced nutrient cycling techniques
Application frequency	Seasonal adjustments
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Nutrient recycling

Tool	Advanced pest and disease forecasting
Application frequency	Continuous monitoring
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Early detection

Tool	Eco-friendly pest control methods
Application frequency	As needed basis
Application date	According to pest outbreaks
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest management

Tool	Soil moisture retention covers
Application frequency	Seasonal rotations
Application date	Pre and post main crop
Stage of development of the crop	Pre and post main crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil health enhancement

Tool	Habitat manipulation for beneficial insects
Application frequency	Seasonal adjustments
Application date	Before and after main crop
Stage of development of the crop	Pre and post main crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest predator attraction

Tool	Climate-adaptive pest management
Application frequency	Continuous monitoring
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Climate-based management

Tool	Advanced soil health monitoring
Application frequency	Continuous monitoring
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil quality enhancement

Strategy 4: Pest and Disease Monitoring and Early Warning Systems

Description

Number of growers	70
Acreage (ha)	1200 ha
% of total acreage	15%
Production (tonnes/year)	3000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	12%

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? no
	Seed coating? no
Cropping density	45 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	April to September
Estimated annual yield	2.5 t/ha
Price per kg product	€2.20/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	€4800/ha
Storage loss	80 kg/ha or 3.2%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 3 Insecticides: 2 Herbicides: 1
% drift reduction	55%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	6 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops?

Intercropping	no
---------------	----

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Pheromone traps
Application frequency	Monthly
Application date	April to September
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Insect pests

Tool	Field scouting
Application frequency	Weekly
Application date	April to September
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	Weather monitoring
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Throughout the year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease prediction

Tool	Disease forecasting models
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Throughout the year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease management

Tool	Soil moisture monitoring
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Throughout the year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Irrigation management

Tool	Pest alert systems
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Throughout the year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest outbreaks

Tool	Mobile apps for pest identification
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	Throughout the year

Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest management

Tool	Remote sensing for pest detection
Application frequency	Monthly
Application date	April to September
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest monitoring

Tool	Drone surveillance
Application frequency	Monthly
Application date	April to September
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Crop health

Tool	Data analytics for trend analysis
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Throughout the year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Informed decision-making

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	50 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	March to October
Estimated annual yield	2.8 t/ha
Price per kg product	€2.40/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	€5200/ha
Storage loss	60 kg/ha or 2%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 2 Insecticides: 1 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	65%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	8 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops?
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Advanced pheromone traps
------	--------------------------

Application frequency	Bi-monthly
Application date	March to October
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Insect pests

Tool	Enhanced field scouting
Application frequency	Bi-weekly
Application date	March to October
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	Integrated weather monitoring
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Throughout the year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease prediction

Tool	Advanced disease forecasting models
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Throughout the year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease management

Tool	Precision soil moisture monitoring
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Throughout the year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Irrigation management

Tool	Real-time pest alert systems
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Throughout the year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest outbreaks

Tool	Advanced mobile apps for pest identification
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	Throughout the year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest management

Tool	High-resolution remote sensing
Application frequency	Bi-monthly

Application date	March to October
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest monitoring

Tool	Enhanced drone surveillance
Application frequency	Bi-monthly
Application date	March to October
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Crop health

Tool	Advanced data analytics for trend analysis
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	Throughout the year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Informed decision-making

Strategy 5: Agroecological Farming Practices and Habitat Management

Description

Number of growers	30
Acreage (ha)	1200 ha
% of total acreage	15 %
Production (tonnes/year)	2400 tonnes/year
% of the total production	20%

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	50 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	March to October
Estimated annual yield	2.0 t/ha
Price per kg product	€2.50/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	€5000/ha
Storage loss	80 kg/ha or 4%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 1 Insecticides: 0 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	70 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	10 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops?
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Polyculture planting
Application frequency	Once per season
Application date	March
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Biodiversity enhancement

Tool	Integrated pest and disease-resistant crops
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	March to October
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest and disease management

Tool	Agroforestry systems
Application frequency	Annual
Application date	March and November
Stage of development of the crop	Pre and post main crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Habitat enhancement

Tool	Biological control agents
Application frequency	Bi-monthly
Application date	April to September
Stage of development of the crop	Growth and flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Specific pests

Tool	Trap cropping techniques
Application frequency	Twice per season
Application date	April and August
Stage of development of the crop	Early and late growth
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest diversion

Tool	Habitat manipulation for beneficial insects
Application frequency	Once per season
Application date	March
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Natural pest control

Tool	Soil conservation practices
Application frequency	Twice per year
Application date	March and November
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting and post-harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil erosion prevention

Tool	Organic soil amendments
------	-------------------------

Application frequency	Quarterly
Application date	March, June, September, December
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil fertility improvement

Tool	Beneficial microorganism applications
Application frequency	Monthly
Application date	March to October
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil health enhancement

Tool	Crop rotation and diversification
Application frequency	Annual
Application date	March
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Crop health and diversity

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	40 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	April to November
Estimated annual yield	2.2 t/ha
Price per kg product	€2.70/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	€5500/ha
Storage loss	70 kg/ha or 3%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 1 Insecticides: 0 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	75 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	12 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops?
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	High-resistance crop varieties
Application frequency	Once per season
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Resistance enhancement

Tool	Integrated agroforestry systems
Application frequency	Annual
Application date	April and November
Stage of development of the crop	Pre and post main crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Habitat enhancement

Tool	Biological pest control agents
Application frequency	Monthly
Application date	April to October
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Specific pests

Tool	Trap cropping techniques
Application frequency	Twice per season
Application date	April and September
Stage of development of the crop	Early and late growth
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest diversion

Tool	Habitat management for beneficial insects
Application frequency	Once per season
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Natural pest control

Tool	Soil conservation practices
Application frequency	Twice per year
Application date	April and November
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting and post-harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil erosion prevention

Tool	Organic soil amendments
Application frequency	Quarterly
Application date	April, July, October, January
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil fertility improvement

Tool	Beneficial microorganism applications
Application frequency	Monthly
Application date	April to November
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil health enhancement

Tool	Crop rotation and diversification
------	-----------------------------------

Application frequency	Annual
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Crop health and diversity

Tool	Precision irrigation techniques
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	Throughout the season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Water management

6.1.2 Spain

Contact person: Celeste Oliveira (oliveira@agro-alimentarias.coop)

Juan Sagarna (Sagarna@agro-alimentarias.coop)

Strategy 1 - current situation : [Dryland vineyard].

Strategy 1 - Integrated Pest Management Enhanced Scenario : [Dryland Vineyard].

Integrated pest management strategies for vineyards

Strategy selection

In 2021, the area for wine grapes in dry farming was 628,037 ha, while in irrigated farming it was 284,396 ha.

- 1) Rainfed: in Spain, approximately 69% of the total area used for wine grapes is rainfed. It is not very profitable but the limited water resources mean that dry farming is still viable.
- 2) Irrigated: the irrigated area in Spain for wine grapes is approximately 31%.

The year 2021 has been chosen as the representative year, as in 2022 and 2023 production was reduced due to the drought. Vineyards are particularly sensitive to climatic conditions, and in recent years this crop has been severely affected, as the lack of water and high temperatures can significantly reduce grape quality. In addition, water stress caused by lack of water affects the plants' ability to absorb nutrients from the soil, which can lead to loss of leaves and bunches, reducing vineyard yields.

Strategy 1: Current situation

DRY FARM VINEYARD

Number of producers	57505,29 holdings
Area (ha)	628,037 ha wine grapes
of total area	68.83% grapes for wine-making
Production (tonnes/year)	4,659 t/year grapes for wine making
of total production	28,38%

Current situation

Resistant cultivar	Yes
	Seed coating? NA
Crop density	2000-3000plants/ha
Growing cycle	Start date March-April / end of January-February
Estimated annual yield	6,589 kg/ha
Price per kg of product	0,30 €/kg - 2 €/kg depending on area, variety and quality of wine grapes
Amount of direct payments for the scenario-specific tools	0
Loss of storage	NA
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 2 (sulphur) Insecticides: 0 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface waters	5 m
Crop rotation	no

	With which crops? none
Intercropping	no

Top 10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Farmers' access to expert advice
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	March-October
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Inspection and cleaning of treatment equipment before each application
Frequency of application	Whenever the equipment is used
Date of application	March-October
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew, downy mildew and grape moth mainly

Tool	Correct and regular maintenance of machinery
Frequency of application	Whenever machinery is used
Date of application	March-October
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew, downy mildew and grape moth mainly

Tool	Phytosanitary alert networks
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	March-October
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew, downy mildew and grape moth mainly

Tool	Use of healthy planting material
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	March-May
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew, downy mildew and grape moth mainly

Tool	Treatment with fungicide (sulphur)
------	------------------------------------

Frequency of application	yearly
Date of application	April-august
Crop stage of development	Veraison
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew

IPM enhanced scenario

Resistant cultivar	Yes
	Seed coating? NA
Crop density	2000-3000 plants/ha
Growing cycle	Start date March-April / end of January-February
Estimated annual yield	6,589 kg/ha
Price per kg of product	0,30 €/kg - 2 €/kg depending on area, variety and quality of wine grapes
Amount of direct payments for the scenario-specific tools	0
Loss of storage	NA
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 2 (sulphur) Insecticides: 0 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface waters	5 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? none
Intercropping	No

Top 10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Anti-drift nozzles on machinery
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	X
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Installation of traps for the monitoring of the control of lobesia
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	x
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Lobesia

Tool	Pest prediction to reduce the use of fungal treatments
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	x
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew and downy mildew

Tool	Avoid the abusive use of phytosanitary treatments that may eliminate the pest's natural enemies.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	X
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Biological pest control in wine grapes
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	X
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Lobesia

Tool	Auxiliary fauna
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	X
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Treatment with fungicide (sulphur)
Frequency of application	yearly
Date of application	April-august
Crop stage of development	Veraison
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew

Strategy 2: Current situation

IRRIGATED VINEYARD

Number of producers	25835,71 holdings
Area (ha)	284,396 ha wine grapes
of total area	31.16% wine grapes
Production (tonnes/year)	11,676 t/year grapes for wine making
of total production	71,62%

Current situation

Cultivate	Resilient? Yes
-----------	----------------

	Seed coating? NA
Crop density	3000-4000plants/ha
Growing cycle	Start date March-April/end January-February
Estimated annual yield	11,465 kg/ha
Price per kg of product	0,30 €/kg - 2 €/kg depending on area, variety and quality of wine grapes
Amount of direct payments for the scenario-specific tools	0
Loss of storage	NA
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 3 (sulphur) Insecticides: 1 (abamectin) Herbicides: 1 (glyphosate)
% drift reduction	X %
Minimum buffer zone to surface waters	5 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? No
Intercropping	no

Top 10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Farmers' access to expert advice
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	March-October
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pests/diseases/weeds

Tool	Inspection and cleaning of treatment equipment before each application
Frequency of application	Whenever the equipment is used
Date of application	March-October
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew, downy mildew and grape moth mainly

Tool	Correct and regular maintenance of machinery
Frequency of application	Whenever machinery is used
Date of application	March-October
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew, downy mildew and grape moth mainly

Tool	Phyosanitary alert networks
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	March-October
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew, downy mildew and grape moth mainly

Tool	Use of healthy planting material
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	March-May
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew, downy mildew and grape moth mainly

Tool	Treatment with herbicide (glyphosate)
Frequency of application	Yearly
Date of application	February-march and june-september
Crop stage of development	Foliation and maturation
Pest/disease/target weed	weeds

Tool	Treatment with insecticide (abamectin)
Frequency of application	yearly
Date of application	March-june
Crop stage of development	Foliation
Pest/disease/target weed	Lobesia

Tool	Treatment with fungicide (sulphur)
Frequency of application	yearly
Date of application	September-December
Crop stage of development	rest
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew

IPM enhanced scenario

Cultivate	Resilient? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes/No/NA
Crop density	3000-4000plants/ha
Growing cycle	Start date March-April / end of January-February
Estimated annual yield	11,465 kg/ha
Price per kg of product	0,30 €/kg - 2 €/kg depending on area, variety and quality of wine grapes

Amount of direct payments for the scenario-specific tools	0
Loss of storage	NA
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 3 (sulphur) Insecticides: 1 (abamectin) Herbicides: 1 (glyphosate)
% drift reduction	X %
Minimum buffer zone to surface waters	5 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? No
Intercropping	no

Top 10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Anti-drift nozzles on machinery
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	x
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Installation of traps for the monitoring of the control of lobesia
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	x
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Lobesia

Tool	Pest prediction to reduce the use of fungal treatments
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	x
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew and downy mildew

Tool	Avoid the abusive use of phytosanitary treatments that may eliminate the pest's natural enemies.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	X
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Biological pest control in wine grapes
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	X
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Lobesia

Tool	Auxiliary fauna
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	X
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Treatment with herbicide (glyphosate)
Frequency of application	Yearly
Date of application	February-march and june-september
Crop stage of development	Foliation and maturation
Pest/disease/target weed	weeds

Tool	Treatment with insecticide (abamectin)
Frequency of application	yearly
Date of application	March-june
Crop stage of development	Foliation
Pest/disease/target weed	Lobesia

Tool	Treatment with fungicide (sulphur)
Frequency of application	yearly
Date of application	September-December
Crop stage of development	rest
Pest/disease/target weed	Powdery mildew

6.2 Olive

6.2.1 Greece

Contact person: Vicky Inglezou (v.inglezou@outlook.com.gr)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: Low-density Open Field Olive Growing

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: Low-density Open Field Olive Growing

IPM strategies for olive, Messinia

Strategy selection

The only growing strategy of olives in Greece is open olive orchards. The traditional Greek olive orchard responds to the country's unique climate and topography. The adoption of IPM strategies among Greek olive growers is on the rise, influenced by regional factors, type of farming, economic incentives, and access to education and resources. While there are challenges to widespread adoption, ongoing efforts by agricultural extension services, cooperatives, and government programs are crucial in promoting IPM and supporting sustainable olive production in Greece. Messinia is the Regional Unit that produces the largest amount of olives, located in the southwestern part of the Peloponnese peninsula. Messinia is renowned for its extensive olive groves and high-quality olive oil production, contributing significantly to Greece's overall olive oil output. The region's favourable climate, fertile soil, and traditional olive-growing practices make it a prime area for olive cultivation. The intense terrain of the land on the one hand, and the mutual succession of forest areas and olive tree groves on the other, are typical characteristics of the region, that locals are calling it "olive- forest". The adoption of IPM strategies among olive growers is on the rise, influenced by regional factors, type of farming, economic incentives, and access to education and resources. While there are challenges to widespread adoption, ongoing efforts by agricultural extension services, cooperatives, and government programs are crucial in promoting IPM and supporting sustainable olive production in Greece. The majority of the farmers in Messinia are organic olive cultivators, a minority is transitioning from conventional to organic olive cultivation and just a small minority uses conventional farming (usually elders).

Source: Directorate of Agricultural Economy and Veterinary of Trifylia

Description reference year:00

2023-2024 was a relatively poor year in terms of olive production. Although 2022-2023 was a difficult year for olive cultivators, given the fact that it was characterized by climate crisis impacts (high temperatures with humidity during winter, increased drought, limited but heavy rainfalls and hailstorms), the olive production was good. Intense damage was observed in the 2nd fortnight of December from olive fruit fly, and gloeosporium olivarum. In addition, due to the lack of workers, 3% of NILEAS' olive orchards were not harvested. Because of the above, we choose this year.

Strategy 1: Low-density Open Field Olive Growing

Description

Number of growers	40.000
Acreage (ha)	83.000 ha
% of total acreage	7,545 %
Production (tonnes/year)	250.000 tonnes/year (olives) 55.000 tonnes/year (olive oil)
% of the total production	16,6% olives 4,9% olive oil

Source: Directorate of Agricultural Economy and Veterinary of Trifylia

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes, until now
	Seed coating? Yes, only for 15-20% of the farms
Cropping density	180 trees/ha
Cropping cycle	Start: January/end date: December (Note: Depending on the year, there are growers who in January of the following year have not completed the previous season's harvest.)
Estimated annual yield	1,5 t olive oil/ha
Price per kg product	5 €/kg (VAT excluded)
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	350 €/ha
Storage loss	0 kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 4 Insecticides: 2 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	15-20 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	15 m
Crop rotation	No
Intercropping	No

Source: Directorate of Agricultural Economy and Veterinary of Trifylia - Communication with advisors and experts

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	<u>Cover Crops</u> : Important tool for protecting the soil against erosion. It constitutes a physical barrier for the flow of surface water when there is a slope, which causes gullies where there is no grass cover on the surface of the crops. Cover crops can also enhance soil biodiversity and create habitats for natural enemies of some pests.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	January
Stage of development of the crop	Start of crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Replacement of native vegetation with the desired species (leguminous plants). Adds organic matter and nitrogen.

Tool	<u>Monitoring and Scouting</u> : It is important because the mere presence of particular pests and diseases does not provide enough information for decision-making. The pest or disease may not be sufficiently widespread, or
------	---

	<p>the population levels may not cause enough damage, to warrant undertaking management strategies. Regularly monitoring of olive orchards, with an effective recording of the results, helps identify pest populations and disease outbreaks early on. This involves visually inspecting trees, leaves, fruits, and the surrounding environment for signs of pests or damage. Thus, olive tree cultivators have important information at their disposal that helps in making decisions on whether and when action should be taken, and how effective actions have been. The first step is to concentrate on the most serious pests and diseases and keep records about the times and locations where problems are most likely to occur. Since natural enemies play an integral role in the system, they must also be recorded.</p>
Application frequency	Continuously, with an emphasis on critical stages in the crop cycle
Application date	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) 20 February-mid April for lygus bug (Closterotomus or Calocoris trivialis) 2) April for olive moth second generation (Prays oleae) 3) From April until the harvest for Gloeosporium olivarum 4) Mid-May until the end of June for olive fruit weevil (Rhynchites cribripennis) 5) Mid-May until the end of June for olive moth third generation (Prays oleae) 6) At the beginning of summer and after harvest for olive knot disease (Pseudomonas savastanoi) 7) June-July for olive leaf moth (Margaronia unionalis) 8) At the beginning of June until harvest for olive fruit fly (Bactrocera oleae)
Stage of development of the crop	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) During the flowering and early fruit development stages 2) Flowering stage 3) Flowering stage until harvest 4) During the fruit development stage of the olive cropping cycle 5) Early fruit development stage 6) Post-pruning stage, post-harvest stage & wet and humid periods 7) Foliage growth stage, flowering and fruit development stage & post-harvest stage 8) Fruit development stage, ripening stage & harvest stage

Target pest/disease/weed	1)Pest 2)Pest 3)Disease 4)Pest 5)Pest 6)Disease 7)Pest 8)Pest
--------------------------	--

Tool	<p>Cultural Management: Keeping olive trees healthy and preventing plant stress helps trees to withstand better and repair the damage caused by pests, diseases, weeds, etc. Evidence indicates that healthy olive orchards resist infestation by pests better than olive orchards with low vigour. The most effective and important of all practices is observing what is happening on the farm. Many serious disease or pest problems can be halted or slowed by regularly visiting the olive orchard, knowing what to look for, recognizing potential problems, and intervening early. Cultural/traditional methods play a crucial role in managing pests and diseases. Techniques such as proper orchard sanitation, pruning, and maintaining optimal tree nutrition and irrigation help promote tree health and vigour, making them less susceptible to pests and diseases.</p>
Application frequency	Throughout the whole year
Application date	Throughout the whole year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	<p>Biological Control: Biological management is the process of reducing a pest population by using predators, parasites and beneficial insects that ordinarily occur in nature. For example, certain predatory mites, ladybugs, lacewings and parasitic wasps can effectively control pests like olive fruit flies and scale insects. The greatest factor in keeping plant-feeding insects from overwhelming the rest of the world is that they are food for the insects. There are more than one hundred olive pathogens, although only a few causes serious economic losses on olive groves.</p>
Application frequency	Throughout the whole year
Application date	Throughout the whole year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	<p><u>Pheromone Traps:</u> They are used to monitor and manage specific pests in olive orchards in Greece, primarily the olive fruit fly. The traps utilize synthetic versions of the female olive fruit fly's sex pheromones to attract and capture male insects, disrupting their mating patterns and reducing pest populations. Traps are strategically placed throughout the olive orchard. Their number and placement density depend on various factors (size of the orchard, pest pressure and regional recommendations). Traps are regularly monitored to assess pest populations and activity levels. The captured insects are counted and identified to determine the population dynamics and timing of pest emergence. The timing of trap deployment is crucial to coincide with the peak activity of the targeted pest. By capturing male olive fruit flies, the traps indicate the presence and intensity of the pest population, allowing growers to implement control measures when necessary.</p>
Application frequency	Every week from the beginning of June until the end of harvest
Application date	Every week from the beginning of June until the end of harvest
Stage of development of the crop	Fruit development stage, ripening stage & harvest stage
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests

Tool	<p><u>Spraying and Targeted Treatments:</u> They are primarily aimed at controlling pests and diseases that commonly affect olive trees (i.e., olive fruit fly, olive moth, fungal diseases like olive knot and olive anthracnose, and bacterial diseases). When pest populations exceed the established threshold, targeted pesticide applications may be necessary. However, the emphasis is on judicious and selective use of pesticides, adhering to strict guidelines and regulations, and choosing products with the least impact on non-target organisms and the environment. The timing of spraying and targeted treatments depends on the specific pest or disease being targeted. Monitoring and regular field observations help determine the optimal timing for treatments. Targeted treatments involve applications to specific areas of the tree or specific pest hotspots. Spraying and targeted treatments are often employed as part of an IPM approach in olive orchards that combines various strategies, including cultural practices, biological control, and the judicious use of pesticides.</p>
------	---

	Indicatively: 1) Spray with Kaolin 2) Spray with fungicide for <i>Gloeosporium olivarum</i> when there are is history 3) Spray for olive knot disease (<i>Pseudomonas savastanoi</i>)
Application frequency	When necessary 1)1 2)1 -6 3)2 max
Application date	Timely applications of pesticides, fungicides, or biological treatments to minimize damage and ensure healthy crop production. 1)June 2)From April to November 3)From the end of harvest until the end of April
Stage of development of the crop	When necessary 1)From Fruit set until Harvest 2) Before Flowering, after high temperature and humidity & after Autumns' rains 3) Bud Break & Flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases 1)Olive fruit fly 2) <i>Gloeosporium olivarum</i> 3)Olive knot disease (<i>Pseudomonas savastanoi</i>)

Tool	<u>Bait Sprays</u> : They are a highly effective and environmentally friendly method for controlling the olive fruit fly in olive orchards. By combining attractants with targeted insecticides, growers can manage fly populations efficiently while minimizing harm to beneficial insects and the environment. Regular monitoring and timely application are key to successful pest management using bait sprays.
Application frequency	Depends on the population. Usually, 3-7 times
Application date	From mid-June until November. The application must stop 1 month before the harvest.
Stage of development of the crop	Fruit set until Harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Olive fruit fly

Tool	<u>Disease-resistant olive cultivars</u> : It is the best long-term and economically efficient control measure for controlling many diseases and some pests of olives and should be at the core of IPM strategies. The experts indicate that although there are many olive tree varieties around the world, the main criteria taken into account when choosing a variety for planting is the previous knowledge of the variety in
------	---

	the region, farmers prefer to continue planting what they know. Normally, the main factor in selecting a variety is the productivity and environmental adaptation. In areas where the olive oil produced locally has a “certified” or “protected” designation of origin, farmers may be required to use a specific local variety or a combination of varieties. The choice of a tolerant cultivar makes IPM easier and can reduce production costs by reducing a)chemical inputs and b)costs of other control measures.
Application frequency	
Application date	Throughout the year, except in summer
Stage of development of the crop	
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	<u>Rejuvenation Pruning</u> : It is a technique used in olive cultivation to revitalize old or overgrown olive trees, restoring their vigour, productivity, and overall health. This pruning method involves selectively removing old, unproductive wood and stimulating new growth to rejuvenate the tree.
Application frequency	1
Application date	From February to April (after the harvest)
Stage of development of the crop	During the dormant season (late winter to early spring) when the tree is not actively growing
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	<u>Pruning for Fruiting</u> : Pruning olive trees for fruiting is a crucial practice that ensures healthy tree growth, maximizes fruit production, and extends the productive lifespan of the orchard. By following proper pruning techniques and performing regular maintenance, olive growers can achieve a well-structured, productive orchard that supports high-quality fruit yields.
Application frequency	1
Application date	From May to July
Stage of development of the crop	Fruit set stage
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	<u>Crushing Pruning Remains</u> : Crushing and incorporation into the soil as quilting of olive tree pruning waste promotes nutrient retention and provides habitats for the edaphic community, increasing biodiversity. In addition, it increases soil organic matter and other indicators of soil fertility and contributes to carbon sequestration in soil.
------	--

Application frequency	1
Application date	From February to July
Stage of development of the crop	Bud break, Flowering, Fruit set
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	<u>Application of compost and organic matter</u> : to improve soil health, enhance nutrient availability, increase soil organic matter. Healthy soils support strong, disease-resistant plants, which are less susceptible to pest attacks.
Application frequency	1
Application date	From February to March
Stage of development of the crop	During dormant season
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	<u>Irrigation</u> : Adequate management of irrigation (frequency and doses) may help reduce the incidence of pests and diseases.
Application frequency	When necessary
Application date	Critical stages: on February and on May, if there is no adequate humidity. From June to September
Stage of development of the crop	Fruit set & Fruit development
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	<u>Forecasting Systems</u> : They are used to identify the risk level linked to the attack of a pest or a disease and to decide the tool and moment to apply the precise management practice The availability of Information Technology (IT) tools such as wireless sensors to constantly monitor climatic and vegetation data enables the implementation of precision plant protection techniques.
Application frequency	Throughout the whole year
Application date	Throughout the whole year
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the growing cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and Diseases

Tool	<u>Planting Material</u> : The use of certified planting material is crucial, not only to ensure the identity of the olive variety or the quality of the plant but also its health status. The use of certified material from officially licensed producers is particularly important to avoid later problems associated with scales, mealybugs and other biting sucking insects, or
------	--

	pathogens that cause systemic infections, which can remain asymptomatic in the plant for several months or years after planting until the appearance of symptoms.
Application frequency	
Application date	Throughout the year, except in summer
Stage of development of the crop	
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	Trap Crops: Plant specific crops that pests prefer in order to draw them away from the main crop. This can help protect the primary crop from infestation.
Application frequency	Whenever needed
Application date	Whenever needed
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the growing cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	180 trees/ha
Cropping cycle	Start: January/end date: December (Note: Depending on the year, there are growers who in January of the following year have not completed the previous season's harvest.)
Estimated annual yield	1,5 t olive oil/ha
Price per kg product	5 €/kg (VAT excluded)
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	350 €/ha
Storage loss	0 X kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 4 Insecticides: 2 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	15-20 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	15 m
Crop rotation	No
	With which crops?
Intercropping	No

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	<u>Use of High Technology:</u> The integration of high technology in olive cultivation offers numerous benefits, including increased efficiency, reduced costs, improved yield and quality, and enhanced sustainability. By adopting these advanced technologies, olive growers can better manage their orchards, respond to environmental challenges, and meet the growing demand for high-quality olives and olive oil.
Application frequency	Throughout the whole year
Application date	Throughout the whole year
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the growing cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	<u>Use of AI:</u> AI as an IPM tool for olive groves offers a transformative approach to pest management, enhancing detection, monitoring, and intervention strategies. By leveraging AI technologies, olive growers can achieve higher efficiency, improved crop health, and greater sustainability in their farming practices.
Application frequency	Throughout the whole year
Application date	Throughout the whole year
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the growing cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	<u>Use of Biostimulants:</u> The use of biostimulants in olive cultivation offers a promising approach to improving tree health, enhancing stress tolerance, and increasing yields and quality. By incorporating biostimulants into a comprehensive orchard management program, olive growers can achieve more sustainable and productive farming practices.
Application frequency	Depends on various factors
Application date	
Stage of development of the crop	Early growth stages, Pre-flowering and fruit set, Stress periods & Post-harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	For fertilization

6.2.2 Italy

Contact person: Simona Fabroni (simona.fabroni@crea.gov.it)

Alberto Sturla (alberto.sturla@crea.gov.it)

Strategy 2 – state of the art scenario: [high-density open field olive growing]

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario: [high-density open field olive growing]

IPM strategies for [OLIVE]

Strategy selection

Italian olive culture is typically split in two, both geographically and cropping system-wise. On one hand there is the extensive olive tree growing, mostly distributed over the Tirreanean coast of the northern regions, while on the other side there is the more modern, high yield oliviculture of the southern regions (Puglia, Campania, Calabria e Sicilia, above all). While the first tends to be grown over terraced land, hardly mechanizable and not irrigated, the second one is characterized by more a more efficient approach to cultivation, with high input supply, rational plant spacing and regular pruning. Given the mechanization problems in extensive oliviculture, there's a wider tendency towards exclusion of synthetic chemicals, thus avoiding the alteration of the environment and healthiness of the productions obtained; the use of suitable agronomic techniques, towards the use of resistant plants and predatory insects against pests; the increase and maintenance of natural soil fertility through the use of non-destructive tillage techniques; and the adoption of green manure techniques.

On the other hand, in intensive oliviculture where the main productive objectives are: early entry into production and halving the payback time of the invested capital, any obstacle to achieving these goals severely affects the profitability of the investment. Therefore, the prompt control of pathogens is compulsory, and when chemicals are not the solution, monitoring becomes of paramount importance.

Description reference year:

2022

Strategy 1: [Extensive oliviculture]

Description

Number of growers	225.373
Acreage (ha)	293.315
% of total acreage	25,8
Production (tonnes/year)	463.736
% of the total production	16,7

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar LECCINO	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? no
Cropping density	400 - 600 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	January/November
Estimated annual yield	3 t/ha
Price per kg product	1.00-1.10 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	700 €/ha (base payment greening, coupled payment)
Storage loss	10 %

PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 3 Insecticides: 3 Herbicides: 1
% drift reduction	35-40 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	4-6 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? Not applicable
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Choice of the right cultivar
Application frequency	n.a.
Application date	October - April
Stage of development of the crop	
Target pest/disease/weed	Generic

Tool	Monitoring of climatic parameters
Application frequency	January - December
Application date	Monthly
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Bactrocera oleae</i> . In combination with mass trapping provides a better understanding of oil fly population trends

Tool	Treatments after pruning with covering products (e.g., Bordeaux mixture)
Application frequency	Every year after pruning
Application date	January - April
Stage of development of the crop	Vegetative restart
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Pseudomonas savastanoi</i> ; <i>Venturia oleaginea</i> .

Tool	Canopy management
Application frequency	Once/year
Application date	November - February
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Bacterial</i> (e.g., (<i>Pseudomonas savastanoi</i>) and <i>fungal diseases</i> (e.g., <i>Mycocentrospora cladosporioides</i> ; <i>Colletotrichum spp.</i>). A well-structured canopy favours the penetration of light and air circulation to reduce the risk of diseases.

Tool	Agroecological support structures
Application frequency	n.a
Application date	n.a
Stage of development of the crop	n.a.
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Weeds. Pest and diseases</i>

Tool	Deltamethrin for fighting olive fly
Application frequency	If necessary (in average 2 times per year)
Application date	June - October
Stage of development of the crop	Development of fruit
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Bactrocera oleae</i>

Tool	Pest monitoring and intervention thresholds
Application frequency	From daily to weekly
Application date	June September
Stage of development of the crop	From fruit setting to ripening
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Bactrocera oleae</i>

Tool	Removal of infected material
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	December - May
Stage of development of the crop	After pruning
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Pseudomonas savastanoi</i>

Tool	Technical Means against <i>Bactrocera oleae</i> (mass trapping)
Application frequency	1 time
Application date	June October
Stage of development of the crop	From fruit setting to ripening
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Bactrocera oleae</i>

Tool	Use of insecticide			
Application frequency	1 -2 (3)/ cropping season according to regional IPM disciplinarys			
Application date	March - September			
Stage of development of the crop	From fruit setting to ripening			
Target pest/disease/weed	Insect	Stage of intervention	Period	Product

	<i>Liothrips oleae</i>	adult individuals	march	chemicals
	<i>Metcalfa pruinosa</i>	juveniles	may - september	wash with water and potassium nitrate
	<i>Saissetia oleae</i>	Larvae - juveniles	april - september	growth regulators chemicals
	<i>Prays oleae</i>	Larvae - juveniles	may june	chemicals
	<i>Bactrocera oleae</i>	larvae - adults	may june	spray chemicals

Tool	Use of fungicides			
Application frequency	1 -2 (3)/ cropping season according to regional IPM disciplinaries			
Application date	March - September			
Stage of development of the crop	From blossoming to ripening			
Target pest/disease/weed	Criptogames	Stage of intervenuion	Period	Product
	<i>Spilocaea oleaginea</i>	Zoospores germination	March and september/october	Copper based fungicides
	<i>Mycocentrospora cladosporioides</i>	Zoospores germination	March and september/october	Copper based fungicides
	<i>Verticillium dahliae</i>	Spawn	May - June / March - April	chemical through stem inoculation; soil disinfectants
	<i>Capnodium spp., Alternaria spp.,</i>	Zoospores germination	March and september/october	Copper based fungicides
	<i>Spilocaea oleaginea</i>	Zoospores germination	March and september/october	Copper based fungicides

Tool	Chemical weeding with contact herbicides and residual herbicides
Application frequency	1 time
Application date	March-April
Stage of development of the crop	n.a.
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar LECCINO	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? no
Cropping density	400 - 600 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	January/November
Estimated annual yield	3 t/ha
Price per kg product	1.00 – 1.10 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	950 €/ha (770 + ecoscheme 2 – grassing) and decoupled payment
Storage loss	5 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 2 Insecticides: 2 Herbicides: 1
% drift reduction	60 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	4-6 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? NOT APPLICABLE
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use of kaolin foliar treatments on olives
Application frequency	From June, every 20 days until the olive harvest
Application date	From the end of June till the end of October
Stage of development of the crop	Fruit development
Target pest/disease/weed	(<i>Bactrocera oleae</i> or <i>Dacus oleae</i>)

Tool	Cover crops or grassing
Application frequency	Perennial
Application date	From September to June
Stage of development of the crop	All the year (In Italy it is compulsory because Ecoschemes n. 2)
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Phytosanitary inspection and alert network warned olive growers news about whether
------	--

	which could increase the development and spread of disease.
Application frequency	If necessary (invitation to adopt preventive measures to control this phenomenon)
Application date	July and August
Stage of development of the crop	Maturation of fruits
Target pest/disease/weed	Peacock eye (<i>Cycloconio</i>)

Tool	Control of Olive fruit fly with the use of traps
Application frequency	1 time (single application) per seasons
Application date	June
Stage of development of the crop	Fruit development
Target pest/disease/weed	(<i>Bactrocera oleae</i> or <i>Dacus oleae</i>)

Tool	Olive fly monitoring
Application frequency	Every 15 days
Application date	From June to end of September
Stage of development of the crop	Fruit development
Target pest/disease/weed	(<i>Bactrocera oleae</i> or <i>Dacus oleae</i>)

Strategy 2: [Intensive oliviculture]

Number of growers	394.915
Acreage (ha)	773.238
% of total acreage	68,1
Production (tonnes/year)	2.318.402
% of the total production	80

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar ARBEQUINA	Yes
	Seed coating? no
Cropping density	800-1200 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	JANUARY-NOVEMBER
Estimated annual yield	10 t/ha
Price per kg product	0.80-0.90 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	1300 €/ha Direct payments , and all 3 ecoschemes
Storage loss	10 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 3 Insecticides: 3 Herbicides: 1
% drift reduction	50 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	4-6 m

Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? NOT APPLICABLE
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools: CREA OFA

Tool	The Control of Olive fruit fly remains almost exclusively based on insecticides, particularly organophosphates (OPs)
Application frequency	3 or 4 times per seasons
Application date	From June to September
Stage of development of the crop	fruit development and fruit maturity
Target pest/disease/weed	(Olive fly <i>Bactrocera oleae</i> or <i>Dacus oleae</i>)

Tool	Removal of infected material
Application frequency	Any time an infection is suspected
Application date	All year
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	Xylella fastidiosa

Tool	Irrigation management (micro irrigation)
Application frequency	X
Application date	From April to October
Stage of development of the crop	From flowering to fruit ripening
Target pest/disease/weed	Prevents root rot

Tool	Pests monitoring and intervention threshold
Application frequency	X
Application date	From mid-May to end of September
Stage of development of the crop	Fruit development
Target pest/disease/weed	Olive fly, olive moth (<i>Prays oleae</i>)

Tool	Fertilization
Application frequency	X
Application date	From February to April
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungal diseases. Compost and vegetation waters seem to contrast several pathogens

Tool	Use of certified planting material
Application frequency	October - December
Application date	From February to Aprile and from mid-September to December
Stage of development of the crop	Planting

Target pest/disease/weed	Scales, mealybugs and other biting sucking insects or pathogens that cause systemic infections
--------------------------	--

Tool	Canopy management to allow ventilation and avoid the formation of a microclimate favourable to the development of pathogens and insects
Application frequency	1 time per season
Application date	From February to March or from mid-October to mid-December
Stage of development of the crop	Quiescence
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Spilocaea oleaginea</i> (Peacock eye spot), <i>Colletotrichum gloeosporioides</i> , <i>C. acutatum</i> , <i>Glomerella cingulata</i> (Anthracnose olives) and <i>Mycocentrospora cladosporioides</i> (Cercospora leaf spot), Black scale (<i>Saissetia oleae</i>), olive psyllid (<i>Euphyllura olivina</i>)

Tool	Treatment after pruning to avoid infections and diseases spread
Application frequency	Once per season
Application date	From mid-October to mid-December or from January to March
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Pseudomonas savastanoi</i>

Tool	Monitoring climatic parameters
Application frequency	All year long,
Application date	All year
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Olive Fly

Tool	Choice of the right cultivar to minimize the susceptibility to pathogens and insects
Application frequency	No application frequency
Application date	From January to March or from mid-September to November
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Olive fly and olive moth (Prays oleae)

Tool	Choice and design of the olive grove
Application frequency	No application frequency
Application date	From mid-September to March

Stage of development of the crop	Plantation
Target pest/disease/weed	Spilocaea oleaginea; Bactrocera oleae; anthracnosis; Saissetia oleae

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar ARBEQUINA	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? no
Cropping density	800-1200 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	JANUARY-NOVEMBER
Estimated annual yield	10 t/ha
Price per kg product	0.80-0.90 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	1600 €/ha Direct payments including decoupled payments , and all 3 ecoschemes, payment for organic farming
Storage loss	5 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 2 Insecticides: 2 Herbicides: 1
% drift reduction	60 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	4-6 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? NOT APPLICABLE
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use of mycorrhizae
Application frequency	X
Application date	All the year
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Organic mulching
Application frequency	Once per season
Application date	From April to September
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Kaolin to create a physical barrier that prevents the attack of insects
Application frequency	X
Application date	From mid-June to October
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	OLive fly <i>Bactrocera olea</i>

Tool	Natural insecticide - Spinosad
Application frequency	
Application date	Mid-June to October
Stage of development of the crop	Fruits development
Target pest/disease/weed	Olive fly

Tool	Phyosanitary alerts networks
Application frequency	No application frequency
Application date	All the year
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Main diseases and pests

Tool	Pheromone traps
Application frequency	Once per season
Application date	From March to November
Stage of development of the crop	Flowering, fruit development and ripening
Target pest/disease/weed	Olive fly and olive moth (<i>Prays oleae</i>), <i>Otiorynchus cribrycollis</i>

6.2.3 Spain

Contact person: Celeste Oliveira (oliveira@agro-alimentarias.coop)

Juan Sagarna (Sagarna@agro-alimentarias.coop)

Strategy 1 - current situation : [rainfed olive grove].

Strategy 1 - Integrated pest management improved scenario : [rainfed olive grove].

Integrated pest management strategies for olive groves

Strategy selection

In 2021, the area of olive grove hectares was 2,573,395 hectares, of which 1,777,498 hectares were rainfed and 795,897 hectares were irrigated.

- 3) Rainfed: in Spain, approximately 69.07% of the cultivated olive grove area is rainfed. It is not very profitable but the limited water resources mean that dry farming is still viable.
- 4) Irrigation: the irrigated area in Spain has increased considerably in recent years. Olive groves are the crop with the largest irrigated area in Spain, the most widely used method being localised irrigation.

The year 2021 has been chosen as a representative year with average production values for the last few years. In the 2022/2023 season, production was greatly reduced by the drought, although it recovered by 15% in the 2023/2024 season, although it was not a representative production year either. The climatic situation in recent months is the main conditioning factor for the expected production. Episodes of high temperatures in the middle of flowering during the drought caused flower losses and a reduction in fruit set. However, the trees have presented heterogeneous conditions in the different production areas.

Strategy 1: Current situation

DRYLAND OLIVE GROVES

Number of producers	105,665 holdings
Area (ha)	1,777,498 ha
of total area	69,07%
Production (tonnes/year)	10-15 million t/year olives
of total production	38%

Current situation

Cultivate	Resilient? No
	Seed coating? NA
Crop density	100 plants/ha
Growing cycle	Start date March-April/end January-February
Estimated annual yield	2,249kg/ha
Price per kg of product	0,4308 EUR/kg of olives
Amount of direct payments for the scenario specific tools	0
Loss of storage	NA
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 1 copper oxychloride Insecticides:0 Herbicides: 1 glyphosate

% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface waters	5 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? none
Intercropping	In areas other than arid areas, cover crops are common but not productive.

Top 10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Farmers' access to expert advice.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	All year round
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Inspection and cleaning of treatment equipment before each application.
Frequency of application	Whenever the equipment is used.
Date of application	April - May
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Correct and regular maintenance of machinery.
Frequency of application	Whenever machinery is used
Date of application	All year round
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pests/diseases/weeds

Tool	Phytosanitary alert networks.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	April-June
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Olive fruit fly (<i>Bractocera oleae</i>)

Tool	Use of healthy planting material.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	September-October
Crop stage of development	October is when the incidence of repilo is at its highest.
Pest/disease/target weed	Repilo (<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> / <i>Spilocaea oleagina</i>)

Tool	Treatment with herbicide (Glyphosate or similar)
Frequency of application	yearly
Date of application	February
Crop stage of development	Vegetative rest
Pest/disease/target weed	Weeds in rows and around the tree

Tool	Treatment with fungicide (copper oxychloride)
Frequency of application	yearly
Date of application	April
Crop stage of development	Flowering
Pest/disease/target weed	Repilo (<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> / <i>Spilocaea oleagina</i>)

IPM enhanced scenario

Cultivate	Resilient? No
	Seed coating? NA
Crop density	100 plants/ha
Growing cycle	Start date March-April/end January-February
Estimated annual yield	2,249kg/ha
Price per kg of product	0,4308 EUR/kg of olives
Amount of direct payments for the scenario-specific tools	0
Loss of storage	NA
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 1 copper oxychloride Insecticides:0 Herbicides: 1 glyphosate
% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface waters	5 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? none
Intercropping	In areas other than arid areas, cover crops are common but not productive.

Top 10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Anti-drift nozzles on machinery.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	March-April
Crop stage of development	X
Pest/disease/target weed	Olive fruit fly and leaf fly (<i>Bractocera oleae</i> and <i>Liriomyza huidobrensis</i>)

Tool	Pest prediction to reduce the use of fungal treatments.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	May
Crop stage of development	X
Pest/disease/target weed	Olive fruit fly (<i>Bractocera oleae</i>)

Tool	Avoid the abusive use of phytosanitary treatments that may eliminate the pest's natural enemies.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	Each application
Crop stage of development	X
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Treatment with herbicide (Glyphosate or similar)
Frequency of application	yearly
Date of application	February
Crop stage of development	Vegetative rest
Pest/disease/target weed	Weeds around the tree. In rows depend if the strategy includes cover crops

Tool	Treatment with fungicide (copper oxychloride)
Frequency of application	Only when indicators go up threshold
Date of application	April
Crop stage of development	Flowering
Pest/disease/target weed	Repilo (<i>Fusicladium oleagineum</i> / <i>Spilocaea oleagina</i>)

Strategy 2: Current situation

IRRIGATED OLIVE GROVES

Number of producers	31,542 holdings
Area (ha)	795.897ha
of total area	30,93%
Production (tonnes/year)	10-15 million t/year olives
of total production	62%

Current situation

Cultivate	Resilient? No
	Seed coating? NA
Crop density	500 plants/ha
Growing cycle	Start date March-April/end January-February

Estimated annual yield	4,867kg/ha
Price per kg of product	0,4308 EUR/kg of olives
Amount of direct payments for the scenario-specific tools	0
Loss of storage	NA
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 1 copper oxychloride Insecticides: 1 Dimethoate Herbicides: 2 glyphosate
% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface waters	5 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? none
Intercropping	no

Top 10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Farmers' access to expert advice.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	All year round
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pests/diseases/weeds

Tool	Inspection and cleaning of treatment equipment before each application.
Frequency of application	Whenever the equipment is used.
Date of application	April - May
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pests/diseases/weeds

Tool	Correct and regular maintenance of machinery.
Frequency of application	Whenever machinery is used
Date of application	February-March
Crop stage of development	X
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Phytosanitary alert networks.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	April-May
Crop stage of development	X

Pest/disease/target weed	Olive fruit fly (<i>Bractocera oleae</i>)
--------------------------	---

Tool	Use of healthy planting material.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	September-October
Crop stage of development	October is when the incidence of repilo is at its highest.
Pest/disease/target weed	Repilo (<i>Fusicladium oleagineum/Spilocaea oleagina</i>)

Tool	Treatment with herbicide (glyphosate)
Frequency of application	Yearly
Date of application	February-march and June-July
Crop stage of development	rest
Pest/disease/target weed	Weeds around the tree. In rows depends if the strategy includes cover crops

Tool	Treatment with insecticide (dimethoate)
Frequency of application	Only when indicators go up threshold
Date of application	April
Crop stage of development	Flowering
Pest/disease/target weed	olive fruit fly (<i>Bractocera oleae</i>)

Tool	Treatment with fungicide (copper oxychloride)
Frequency of application	Only when indicators go up threshold
Date of application	September
Crop stage of development	veraison
Pest/disease/target weed	Repilo (<i>Fusicladium oleagineum/ Spilocaea oleagina</i>)

IPM enhanced scenario

Cultivate	Resilient? No
	Seed coating? NA
Crop density	500 plants/ha
Growing cycle	Start date March-April/end January-February
Estimated annual yield	4,867kg/ha
Price per kg of product	0,4308 EUR/kg of olives
Amount of direct payments for scenario specific tools	0
Loss of storage	NA
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 1 copper oxychloride Insecticides: 1 Dimethoate Herbicides: 2 glyphosate
% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface waters	5 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? none
Intercropping	no

Top 10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Anti-drift nozzles on machinery.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	March-April
Crop stage of development	X
Pest/disease/target weed	Olive fruit fly and leaf fly (<i>Bractocera oleae</i> and <i>Liriomyza huidobrensis</i>)

Tool	Pest prediction to reduce the use of fungal treatments.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	May
Crop stage of development	X
Pest/disease/target weed	Olive fruit fly (<i>Bractocera oleae</i>)

Tool	Avoid the abusive use of phytosanitary treatments that may eliminate the pest's natural enemies.
Frequency of application	Each application

Date of application	Each application
Crop stage of development	X
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Treatment with herbicide (glyphosate)
Frequency of application	Yearly
Date of application	February-march and june-july
Crop stage of development	rest
Pest/disease/target weed	Weeds around the tree. In rows depend if the strategy includes cover crops

Tool	Treatment with insecticide (dimethoate)
Frequency of application	Only when indicators go up threshold
Date of application	April
Crop stage of development	Flowering
Pest/disease/target weed	olive fruit fly (<i>Bractocera oleae</i>)

Tool	Treatment with fungicide (copper oxychloride)
Frequency of application	Only when indicators go up threshold
Date of application	September
Crop stage of development	veraison
Pest/disease/target weed	Repilo (<i>Fusicladium oleagineum/ Spilocaea oleagina</i>)

6.3 Apple

6.3.1 Italy

Contact person: Simona Fabroni (simona.fabroni@crea.gov.it)

Alberto Sturla (alberto.sturla@crea.gov.it)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: **[high-density open field apple growing]**

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: **high-density open field apple growing**

Strategy 2 – state of the art scenario: **low-density open field apple growing**

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario: **low-density open field apple growing**

IPM strategies for Apple

Strategy selection

Intensive apple growing is mostly done in Northern Italian regions (Trentino and Emilia Romagna, above all). Density is 2500-3000 (4000) plants per hectare that are replaced every 10-15 years or so. The highly intensive production allows highest yields sold in national and international markets.

Apple monoculture has certainly optimized economic productivity but at the same time has greatly compromised the natural variety present in the original environments. Moreover, high density orchards are more exposed to phytosanitary problems and therefore require heavy treatments, with subsequent higher risks for human health and biodiversity. This is why, in more recent times, to reduce the use of chemicals, much attention is also being paid to complementary agronomic, mechanical, and organic practices. On the other side, there's an extensive apple growing that is widespread all over Italy, mostly devoted to local varieties and targeted to local markets. It's a low density cropping system, with plants grown in polyconic vase shape, although it is shifting toward more efficient and dense plant spacing. Prevention and monitoring methods are generally preferred to active pests contrast, because of ecological and economic reasons.

Description reference year:

2022. 2022 has been chosen as a reference year because 2023 has been characterized by a high climatic instability that has brought a loss in the average yields, especially in extensive apple growing. High minimum temperatures and humidity have favoured parasitic nuisances and the upsurge as various pathogens that required extra treatments.

Strategy 1: [High-density open field apple growing]

Piemonte, Trentino Alto Adige (Sudtirolo), Veneto, Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia

Description

Number of growers	na
Acreage (ha)	48.132
% of total acreage	85,5
Production (tonnes/year)	2.122.099
% of the total production	93.0

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar GOLDEN DELICIOUS	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	1500-4000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	January/October
Estimated annual yield	35-40 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,35 - 0,45 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario (€/ha, national average)	160 Basic income support + 500 integrated production
Storage loss	About 30 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 5-7

	Insecticides: 3-5 Herbicides: 2-3
% drift reduction	50 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	4-6 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? Not applicable
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Pruning cuts are made to reduce sensitivity to adversity and to eliminate all the portion damaged by biotic and abiotic factors.
Application frequency	Once per year
Application date	mid-October - March
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Monitored nursery material
Application frequency	X
Application date	February - April or October - December
Target pest/disease/weed	Viruses

Tool	Agrometeorological monitoring
Application frequency	1 – 2 times per week
Application date	All the year
Target pest/disease/weed	<p>Aphis pomi, Dysaphis plantaginea, Quadraspidiotus perniciosus, Cacopsylla melanoneura, Panonychus ulmi, Scolytus rugulosus, bAnthonomus pomorum, Leucoptera malifoliella, Eriosoma lanigerum, Argyrotaenia ijungiana, Hoplocampa spp., Leucoptera malifoliella, Aculus schlechtendali, Zeuzera pyrina, Cydia pomonella, Halyomorpha halys, Scolytus rugulosus, Pandemis spp., Adoxophyes orana, Archips spp. Ceratitis capitata,</p> <p>Bacteria: Pseudomonas syringae pv. syringae; Erwinia amylovora,</p> <p>fungal diseases: Podosphaera leucotricha; Venturia inaequalis</p> <p>Branch Cancers: Nectria galligena - Cylindrocarpon mali, Sphaeropsis malorum - Botryosphaeria obtusa, Diaporthe perniciososa - Phomopsis mali</p>

Tool	Use of biostimulants help promote natural processes in the soil-plant system and improve the crop's nutrient use efficiency
Application frequency	Monthly
Application date	March - August
Target pest/disease/weed	Direct on abiotic stress, indirect of biotic stresses

Tool	Use of corroborants to protect the crop from abiotic stresses or enhance its natural defence against biotic stresses
Application frequency	Monthly
Application date	March - August
Target pest/disease/weed	Oidium spp; Venturia Inequalis; Dysaphis plantaginea

Tool	Grassing of apple orchard for soil improvement and protection from the risk of erosion
Application frequency	X
Application date	February - December
Target pest/disease/weed	The permanent presence of herbaceous species allows the increased presence of beneficial insects, pollinators, predators or parasitoids of many harmful insects

Tool	Beehives placement to improve pollination
Application frequency	Once per season
Application date	April - June
Target pest/disease/weed	Bees are vector s of several fungi antagonist to parasitc fungi (e.g.. <i>Oidium farinosum</i>)

Tool	Irrigation
Application frequency	2-6 times a week depending on the metereological conditions
Application date	May - October
Target pest/disease/weed	Indirect on abiotic and biotic stressors

Tool	Pests monitoring
Application frequency	X
Application date	February - October
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> , <i>Cossus cossus</i> and <i>Zeuzera pirina</i>

Tool	Removal of infected material
Application frequency	Whenever deemed necessary according to monitoring

Application date	All the year
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> , Powdery mildew of apple and other fungal diseases (<i>Nectria galligena</i> ; <i>Sphaeropsis malorum</i> ; <i>Phomopsis mali</i>)

Tool	Sexual confusion and disorientation methods, very much used because there's a tendency to reduce the use of chemicals
Application frequency	Pheromone is automatically emitted at regular pace , daily
Application date	April – October. diffusers should be distributed in the field before the start of the flight of adults of the overwintering generation
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest flies

Tool	Biological control using natural enemies and entomopathogens
Application frequency	X
Application date	April – October.
Target pest/disease/weed	Depending on the treatment

Tool	Use of insecticide			
Application frequency	1 -3 (4)/ cropping season according to regional IPM disciplinarys			
Application date	March - September			
Stage of development of the crop	From fruit setting to ripening			
Target pest/disease/weed	Insect	Stage of intervention	Period	Product
	<i>Cydia pomonella</i>)	Eggs, Larvae	March September	Spray chemicals ; granulovirus
	<i>Dysaphis plantaginea</i>	Overwintering generation	March April	azadirachtin
	<i>Erisoma Lanigerum</i>	Overwintering generation	March April	Spray chemicals ; granulovirus

Tool	Use of fungicides			
Application frequency	4-16/ cropping season according to regional IPM disciplinarys and disease			
Application date	March - September			
Stage of development of the crop	From blossoming to ripening			
Target pest/disease/weed	Criptogames	Stage of interveniuon	Period	Product
	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i>	Ascospores	March - May	Spray chemicals (sistemic/contact)
	<i>Podosphaera leucotricha</i>	Overwintering spawn Ascospores	March - May	Spray chemicals (sistemic/contact)
	<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>		March April	Copper -based products, Spray chemicals

Tool	Chemical weeding with contact herbicides and residual herbicides
Application frequency	1 time
Application date	March-April
Stage of development of the crop	N.A.
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Weeds</i>

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar GOLDEN DELICIOUS	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	1500-4000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	January/October
Estimated annual yield	35-40 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,35 - 0,45 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario (€/ha, national average)	160 Basic income support + 500 integrated production + 90 Complementary redistributive income support for sustainability
Storage loss	About 25 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 3-5

	Insecticides: 1-3 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	60 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	4-6 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? NOT APPLICABLE
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Mycorrhizal colonization
Application frequency	Once at implantation
Application date	March – May, August - October
Target pest/disease/weed	Control of plant pathogens through the production of siderophores and antibiotics

Tool	Pre-sprouting
Application frequency	X
Application date	Mid-August - October
Target pest/disease/weed	Control of various plant pathogens/insects/ weeds

Tool	Mulch along the orchard
Application frequency	Once per season
Application date	All the year
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Preservation of natural agro-ecosystems
Application frequency	na
Application date	na
Target pest/disease/weed	It's an integrated strategy aimed at the equilibrium of the ecosystem.

Tool	Use of anti-hail and photo selective nets
Application frequency	Once at implantation
Application date	All the year
Target pest/disease/weed	Cydia pomonella, fungal disease, Miridae, birds

Tool	Early detection for pests monitoring
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	January – December
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> , <i>Podosphaera leucotricha</i> , <i>Nectria galligena</i>

Tool	Rationalization of the use of plant protection products: use Low impact products boric acid, laminarin, potassium bicarbonate and sulfur.
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	February - August
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Venturia inequalis</i> ; Integrated Strategy

Tool	Microbial antagonism occurs by the application of fungi, bacteria and virus
Application frequency	X
Application date	March - July
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytoplasma spp.</i> ; <i>Fungi, bacteria and nematodes</i> . Also for post-harvest rotting

Tool	Innovative physical methods for weeding (water vapour/foaming)
Application frequency	At the occurrence
Application date	March – June, September - October
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Strategy 2: [low-density open field apple growing]

Valle d'Aosta; Liguria, Toscana, Umbria, Marche, Lazio, Abruzzo, Molise, Campania, Puglia, Basilicata, Calabria, Sicilia; Sardegna

Description

Number of growers	na
Acreage (ha)	8146
% of total acreage	14,5
Production (tonnes/year)	159.998
% of the total production	7,1

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar: Local cultivars (e.g. 'Annurca' in Campania)	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	800-1200 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	January/October
Estimated annual yield	20-30 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,40 – 0,50 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario (€/ha, national average)	160 Basic income support + 90 Complementary redistributive income support for sustainability + 500 integrated production + 150 eligible Ecoscheme
Storage loss	35 %

PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 5-7 Insecticides: 3-5 Herbicides: 1-2
% drift reduction	35-40 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	4-6 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? Not applicable
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Pruning
Application frequency	Once a year + when needed (pests or diseases income)
Application date	November - March
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Eriosoma Lanigerum</i> , <i>Oidium farinosum</i> and other Fungal diseases

Tool	Certified nursery material
Application frequency	X
Application date	November - March
Target pest/disease/weed	Erwinia Amylovora; Viruses, bacteria fungal diseases

Tool	Pest monitoring
Application frequency	Weekly, bi-weekly
Application date	All Year round
Target pest/disease/weed	Aphis pomi, Dysaphis plantaginea, Quadraspidiotus perniciosus, Cacopsylla melanoneura, Panonychus ulmi, Scolytus rugulosus, Anthonomus pomorum, Leucoptera malifoliella, Eriosoma lanigerum, Argyrotaenia ijungiana, Hoplocampa spp., Leucoptera malifoliella, Aculus schlechtendali, Zeuzera pyrina, Cydia pomonella, Halyomorpha halys, Scolytus rugulosus, Pandemis spp., Adoxophyes orana, Archips spp. Ceratitis capitata, Bacteria: Pseudomonas syringae pv. syringae; Erwinia amylovora, fungal diseases: Podosphaera leucotricha; Venturia inaequalis Branch Cancers: Nectria galligena - Cylindrocarpon mali, Sphaeropsis malorum - Botryosphaeria obtusa, Diaporthe perniciososa - Phomopsis mali

Tool	Use of Biostimulants
Application frequency	Depending of phenological phases
Application date	March- September
Target pest/disease/weed	Direct on abiotic stress, indirect of biotic stresses

Tool	Use of corroborants
Application frequency	Monthly
Application date	March- September
Target pest/disease/weed	Oidium spp; Venturia Inequalis; Dysaphis plantaginea

Tool	Intra rows Grassing
Application frequency	Once per year
Application date	February (sowing) to december
Target pest/disease/weed	The permanent presence of herbaceous species allows the increased presence of beneficial insects, pollinators, predators or parasitoids of many harmful insects

Tool	Beehives displacements
Application frequency	Once a year
Application date	April - May
Target pest/disease/weed	Bees are vector s of several fungi antagonist to parasitc fungi (e.g.. <i>Oidium farinosum</i>)

Tool	Irrigation
Application frequency	Weekly
Application date	May October
Target pest/disease/weed	Indirect on abiotic and biotic stressors

Tool	Removal of infected material
Application frequency	Whenever deemed necessary according to motoring
Application date	All year round
Target pest/disease/weed	Branch Cancers(<i>Nectria galligena</i>);

Tool	Sexual confusion and disorientation method
Application frequency	Pheromone is authomatically emitted at regular pace , daily
Application date	April – October. diffusers should be distributed in the field before the start of the flight of adults of the overwintering generation

Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Cydia pomonella</i> ; <i>Synanthedon myopaeformis</i>
--------------------------	--

Tool	Biological Control (alternative to chemical control in blooming)
Application frequency	X
Application date	April – October.
Target pest/disease/weed	Depending on the treatment

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar: Local cultivars (e.g. 'Annurca' in Campania)	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	800 - 1200 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	January - October
Estimated annual yield	20- 30 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,40 – 0,50 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	160 Basic income support + 90 Complementary redistributive income support for sustainability + 150 eligible Ecoscheme + 700 Organic Farming + 500 eligible Agro-Environmental measures
Storage loss	30 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 3-5 Insecticides: 1-3 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	50 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	4-6 m
Crop rotation	No With which crops? Not applicable
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Preservation of the agro-ecosystem in apple orchards
Application frequency	na
Application date	na
Target pest/disease/weed	It's an integrated strategy aimed at the equilibrium of the ecosystem.

Tool	Calcium Hydroxide - $Ca(OH)_2$ spray treatment
Application frequency	From 2 to 7 applications in the period
Application date	February - April
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Neonectria galligena</i>

Tool	Mulching
Application frequency	Na
Application date	January – December
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Early detection systems for pests monitoring (
Application frequency	Continuous
Application date	January – December
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Venturia inaequalis</i> , <i>Podosphaera leucotricha</i> , <i>Nectria galligena</i>

Tool	Kaolin
Application frequency	Depending on film deterioration rate
Application date	January – December
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Halyomorpha halys</i> , <i>Cacopsylla melanoneura</i> ; <i>Dysaphys plantaginea</i> ; <i>Erwinia amylovora</i> , <i>Venturia inaequalis</i>

Tool	Rationalization of the use of plant protection products
Application frequency	x
Application date	February - January
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

6.3.2 Netherlands

Contact person: Carolina Gattorno (carolina.gattorno@zlto.nl)

Yaite Cuesta Arenas (yaite.cuesta.arenas@zlto.nl)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: open field apple cultivation NL

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: open field apple cultivation NL

IPM strategies for Apple, The Netherlands

Strategy selection

The main, and only, growing strategy for apples in the Netherlands is in open orchards. Many IPM tools are aimed at prevention and creating a healthy tree in a healthy environment which is in balance with pests and natural enemies. In general, apple farming is already using a very integrated approach. Only a limited number of chemicals are still allowed to be used. For some pests no chemicals are available so for years integrated methods are used. Many methods are aimed at preventing the spread of diseases, since apple trees are grown for at least 15 years before being replaced. Therefore, no risks can be taken regarding the health of the trees.

Source: interviews with advisors

Description reference year:

2023. It was a typical growing year with mild temperatures in spring and autumn. Summer occasionally had some warm and hot periods but no extremes for a prolonged period. Precipitation was higher than average and much higher compared to the previous years. Previous years were however extremely dry compared to average. In 2023 very wet periods alternated with very dry periods. In terms of pests and diseases, the apple blossom weevil posed serious problems for apple growers and led to quite some losses in harvest.

Strategy 1: Apple Orchards

Description

Number of growers	913
Acreage (ha)	5502 ha
% of total acreage	17,3 % (of open field horticulture area)
Production (tonnes/year)	198.000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	3.54 % (of total fruit and vegetable production)

Source: CBS Statline: <https://opendata.cbs.nl/#/CBS/nl/dataset/84499NED/table?dl=A6E5B>

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar <i>Source: Personal Communication, Peter van 't Westeinde (Policy Specialist Trees, Plants & Field Vegetation, ZLTO)</i>	Resistant? Yes (<i>not all cultivars however</i>)
	Seed coating?
Cropping density <i>Source: Fruit Consult</i>	2400-3200 plants/ha
Cropping cycle <i>Source: Fruit Consult</i>	15-20 years
Estimated annual yield <i>Source: CBS Statline</i>	36 t/ha
Price per kg product <i>Sources: Fresh Plaza, Personal communication Peter van 't Westeinde (Policy Specialist Trees, Plants & Field Vegetation, ZLTO)</i>	€0,40 - €0,60 /kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario <i>Source: Farm EU</i>	Eco-scheme by CAP regulated by (RVO): €160-200 per ha
Storage loss	<1 >10 % depends on length of storage
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products):

Sources: CBS Statline, Personal communication Peter van 't Westeinde (Policy Specialist Trees, Plants & Field Vegetation, ZLTO)	Fungicides: 10-15 Insecticides: 2-5 Herbicides: 2
% drift reduction Source: Personal communication Peter van 't Westeinde (Policy Specialist Trees, Plants & Field Vegetation, ZLTO)	90-99 % depends on pesticide
Minimum buffer zone to surface water Source: Personal communication Peter van 't Westeinde (Policy Specialist Trees, Plants & Field Vegetation, ZLTO)	3 m
Crop rotation Source: Personal communication Peter van 't Westeinde (Policy Specialist Trees, Plants & Field Vegetation, ZLTO)	no
Intercropping	no

Sources:

FruitConsult: <https://proeftuinrandwijk.nl/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/proeftuin-sponsorenbijeenkomst-mei-2022.pdf>

CBS Statline: [StatLine - Gebruik gewasbeschermingsmiddelen landbouw; gewas en toepassing, 2012-2016 \(cbs.nl\)](https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/onderwerpen/landbouw-voedsel-landbouw-gebruik-gewasbeschermingsmiddelen-landbouw-gewas-en-toepassing-2012-2016)

Vlaanderen: [Prijzen van appels en peren | Landbouw & Visserij \(vlaanderen.be\)](https://www.vlaanderen.be/landbouw-visserij)

Fresh Plaza: [Average weighted price for apples at €90 per 100 kgs in November \(freshplaza.com\)](https://www.freshplaza.com/)

Farm EU: [Netherlands: CAP Strategic Plan 2023-27 – FarmEurope \(farm-europe.eu\)](https://www.farm-europe.eu/)

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Chemical Interventions:

* Important to note that rainfall, temperature and humidity can influence the frequency of fungicide applications. Additionally, some products have a maximum residue limit (MRLs) and a specific number of allowed applications per season.

Source: advisors and public regulatory authorities (Ctgb)

Name:	Captosan, Merpan
Application frequency	10-15 times per season
Application date	First application in early spring (March-April) when green leaf tips appear, repeated every 7-10 days until harvest, especially during wet conditions.
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide (Scab and Neonectria)

Name:	Dithianon (Delan Pro)
Application frequency	6-8 times per season
Application date	Starts at the green tip stage (march) and continues during 7–14-day intervals, depending on disease pressure.
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide (powdery mildew)

Name:	Fludioxonil (Geoxe)
Application frequency	1-2 times per season
Application date	Post harvest near harvest to protect fruit storage.
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide

Name:	Boscalid (Signum)
Application frequency	2-3 times per season
Application date	During petal fall (May) and early fruit set stages.
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide

Name:	Copper Compounds (Copper Oxchloride)
Application frequency	1-2 times per season
Application date	Applied in early spring (bud break) for disease prevention especially in organic orchards.
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide

Name:	Sulfur (Thiovit Jet)
Application frequency	3-5 times per season
Application date	Starts at the green tip stage and continues every 7-10 days during high disease pressure, mainly for powdery mildew
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide (powdery mildew)

Name:	Chlorantraniliprole (Coragen)
Application frequency	1-2 times per season
Application date	Applied at the beginning of egg hatch of the codling moth, usually in late May or early June.
Target pest/disease/weed	Insecticide (codling moth)

Name:	Flonicamid (Teppeki)
Application frequency	1-2 times per season
Application date	Mainly used for aphid control, applied in early spring or as needed based on pest scouting.
Target pest/disease/weed	Insecticide (aphids)

Name:	Glyphosate
Application frequency	2-3 times per season
Application date	Typically applied in early spring (April) and mid-summer (June-July).
Target pest/disease/weed	Herbicide

Name:	Glufosinate-ammonium (Basta)
Application frequency	1-2 times per season

Application date	Spring and mid-season, usually in orchards with significant weed pressure.
Target pest/disease/weed	Herbicide

Name:	MCPA (2-methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid)
Application frequency	1x per season
Application date	Typically applied in start of season when there is more weed pressure and before fruit set. (April-June)
Target pest/disease/weed	Herbicide

Name:	MaxCel
Application frequency	1-2 times per season
Application date	Used during the thinning window, usually 10-20 days after full bloom (late April to early May).
Target pest/disease/weed	Growth regulator

Name:	Ethephon (Ethrel)
Application frequency	1-2 times per season
Application date	Applied in late spring to early summer for thinning; again, closer to harvest for colour enhancement.
Target pest/disease/weed	Growth regulator

Tool	Sanitation: Proper sanitation is of huge importance to prevent spreading and remove sources of contamination. Activities include removal of contaminated branches, bark, fruits and leaves, and sterilization of the used tools.
Application frequency	Whole season
Application date	Start of season
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Adequate fertilization: Fertilization should be balanced out. It is important to monitor the trees' health and growth and apply fertilizers accordingly. Excessive fertilization can result in more weed growth and defects in root growth.
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Natural ecosystem: The ecosystem in and around the apple orchard can provide a natural habitat for predatory insects and increase biodiversity. Also, elements like coniferous hedges provide protection against weather influences
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Biocontrol
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	
Target pest/disease/weed	Predatory mites are used against spider mite, they cannot be cultivated but after many years of developing the proper environment their populations develop naturally. Earwigs are also used against aphids.

Tool	Soil quality: Soil quality and health is an important topic to which more and more focus goes. Good soil quality harbors beneficial microorganisms, that for example increase nutrient uptake and decomposition of course material, and insects that can act as natural enemies against pests. The percentage organic matter is a key parameter in soil health and should be promoted.
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	Water management: adequate water management is important to ensure plant health and to prevent the growth of pests and diseases. Optimal drainage has to be ensured to prevent, for example, stagnant pools of water. Water quality is an important aspect. Water quality has improved in the Netherlands but still needs attention in certain regions. For example, in the region Zeeland fresh water can be very scarce. Water in the streams can be brackish and is therefore not suitable for irrigation.
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Drip Irrigation
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Bio-stimulant application: Bio-stimulants can be applied to improve growth characteristics of the trees which ultimately makes them more resilient against adverse conditions and pests and diseases.
Application frequency	Depends on many factors (weather, outbreak, perceived usefulness by farmers)
Application date	Start/during growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Used against all pests. Examples of bio stimulants used by Dutch growers: Hicure, DSM Vitact, DSM impuls TD, ProAct and Agro-Mos.

Tool	Shredding of fallen leaves: Fallen leaves are shredded to facilitate decaying by soils micro- and macrobiome. This provides nutrients for the soil and trees. Faster decaying of the leaves also prevents the build-up of harmful fungi in the wet microclimate between the leaves.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	Pests monitoring: Monitoring of diseases and pests is important to make well and informed decisions about whether or not to apply plant protection measures and/or pesticides. Monitoring can be done using sticky traps or other ways to collect insect samples. Regularly monitoring in the orchard is of key importance to limit chemical use.
Application frequency	Throughout the growing season
Application date	Throughout the growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Check the outbreak of pests, for decision making purposes. Example of a tool used in apple is RIMpro which allows growers to monitor pest and disease and reduce the use of pesticides.

Tool	Rotation of active ingredients: Rotation of different pesticides with different modes of action reduces the risk of developing resistance against active ingredients in pest species. Reports of, for example codling moth already reported resistance against certain common pesticides. Additionally, evidence suggests that multiple applications with a lower dose compared to a single application with a high dose is equally as effective or more effective in the eradication/suppression of pests.
Application frequency	Throughout the growing season
Application date	Throughout the growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Use of anti-hail nets: A secondary use of hail nets in apple and pear orchards to reduce codling moths.
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	During winter
Target pest/disease/weed	Codling moths

Tool	Pheromone traps: Monitoring is essential in order to determine if countermeasures have to be taken. Traps with specific pheromones can be used as a monitoring tool for harmful insects.
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season

Target pest/disease/weed	Pest insects
--------------------------	--------------

Tool	Pruning/thinning: By pruning the apple trees, more open spaces are created which facilitates airflow and reduces humidity in the trees. This leads to less chances of fungi infection and thus a reduced loss of healthy leaf area and fruits.
Application frequency	During winter
Application date	During winter (December-
Target pest/disease/weed	Apple scab

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes (but not all cultivars are resistant)
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	2400-3200 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	Start/end date
Estimated annual yield	36 t/ha
Price per kg product	€0,40- €0,60/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	Eco-scheme by CAP regulated by (RVO): €160-200 per ha
Storage loss	1-1,5 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 10-15 Insecticides: 2-5 Herbicides: 2
% drift reduction	99%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	3 m
Crop rotation	NO
	With which crops?
Intercropping	NO

Sources: Same as State of the Art Scenario

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Mechanical weeding. Weeding until barren soil will aid in the prevention of flower freezing in early spring. Barren black soil will emit heat during the night.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	Early spring.
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Flower Strips (in-between rows) for pollinators
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	March-Sep
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Intermediate Mowing
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	End of Nov-March
Target pest/disease/weed	All. Delaying mowing and allowing grass to grow.

6.3.3 Poland

Contact person: Dorota Labanowska-Bury (dorota.labanowska@gmail.com)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: **high-density open field apple growing**

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: **high-density open field apple growing**

Strategy 2 – state of the art scenario: [low-density open field apple growing]

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario: [low-density open field apple growing]

IPM strategies for Apple, Poland

Strategy selection

The main growing strategy for apples in Poland is open orchards (some percentage is covered with the anti-hail net protection). Large percentage of apple orchards are based on selected IPM tools. Majority of plantations are established with the use of virus-free nursery stock. Farmers are caring about the environment leaving the shelters for beneficials in the form of hedges and wind-protection around the orchard. In many orchards there is a grass-cover in between the rows.

Regarding the use of chemicals, most of farmers are still using the chemical plant protection products, however more are willing to introduce more environment-friendly methods. The biggest issue every year is the protection against diseases such as apple-scab and powdery mildew as well as against aphids.

Prevention treatments are applied, such as sanitary pruning and shredding of the fallen leaves plus application of ammonium nitrate for speeding the disposition and therefore reduce the source of infection for the following year. However every year there is a battle with the fungi *Podosphaera leucotricha* and *Venturia inaequalis* to first stop the spring infection and later to prevent the summer infection.

Regarding the control of codling moth some farmers are already using the products containing the Codling Moth granulovirus to secure the yield.

Source: interviews with advisors

Description reference year:

According to CSO data, in 2023, the harvest from apple orchards in Poland exceeded 3.9 million tons and was almost 9 percent lower compared to the previous year. However, we have to bear in mind that many apple growers stopped planting new orchard due to lowering profitability.

2023 was quite a good year regarding the average yield. Temperatures varied during the growing season as it was quite high in spring and summer, with low precipitation in June however there were some extreme water volumes in July and August.

The spring of 2023 will be remembered as rainy, cold and frosty - frosts occurred several times in some areas of the country, so the weather was difficult for conservation, as well as unfavourable for bee pollination/circulation. As a result of such aura, the past season was recorded as very scabby.

In April/May it was cold, the rains may not have been intense, but quite frequent. Under such conditions, the moisture in the developing buds lasted a very long time (the artificial leaf of the weather station dried out faster than the inside of the developing buds). Guided only by the low temperature and not by the length of tissue wetness, fruit growers did not assume the presence of scab infection, relying too long on copper treatments and/or only contact fungicides in the spring. And in practice, despite the cold weather, infections (small or medium enough) were already occurring early in the growing season.

A very important element that should have been additionally taken into account in the past season when planning scab control strategies was the fact that the warm winter, and especially January, caused an acceleration of the maturation of sack spores, which were ready for infection earlier than in other summers (as early as early April). Advisory companies reported a real threat from scab in the early stages of development, but many fruit growers did not take this into account when making protection decisions.

Apple powdery mildew had somewhat worse conditions for development, as it was too cold and rainy in the spring, but the weather improved in the second half of May and June, which is when the most abundant seeding of conidial spores is recorded. If the orchardist did not continue the fight against powdery mildew until the end of the activity of the apical buds on the long shoots, the disease continued to develop intensively, producing a huge infectious potential for the next season in the location.

A group of pests that have been giving many locations a hard time over the years are aphids, mainly the rosy apple aphid (*Dysaphis plantaginea*) and the woolly-aphid (*Eriosoma lanigerum*). The former species has only one strategic/decisive control date - the green to pink bud stage. However, during the pink bud period it was very cold last season, even frosty, and it was better to schedule the treatment a little earlier, at the end of the green bud, when there was a warmer weather window of a few days (it was the penultimate week of April).

Strategy 1: Apple Orchards high-density open field apple growing

Description

Number of growers	?
Acreage (ha)	Total acreage 50 thousand ha
% of total acreage	
Production (tonnes/year)	1,9 million tonnes /year
% of the total production	

Source: CSO/ KUPS

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	Resistant? Very seldom as there is no market value for pest resistant varieties Seed coating? n/a
Cropping density <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	3125-6666 plants/ha
Cropping cycle <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	15-20 years
Estimated annual yield <i>Source: www.stat.gov.pl</i>	40-55 t/ha
Price per kg product <i>Sources: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	€0,30 - €0,50 /kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario <i>Source: Farm EU</i>	€160-280 per ha (including eco-schemes)
Storage loss	5 %

PPP-use <i>Sources: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 8-13 Insecticides: 5-7 Herbicides: 0-2
% drift reduction <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	95 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	3 m
Crop rotation <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	Crop rotation in between new orchard planting – usually a gap-year with green fertilizers
Intercropping <i>Personal communication with apple growers</i>	No / at organic orchards living mulch can be introduced or herbal plants for processing/

Sources:

Cap Strategic Plan

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Source: SUPPORT inventory tool

Tool	Pests monitoring: Pest monitoring to support farmers in the decision whether or not to carry out the plant protection measures or pesticides application.
Application frequency	from the beginning of May to the end of August
Application date	from the beginning of May to the end of August
Target pest/disease/weed	Apple scab (sporetrap), <i>Cydia pomonella</i> (delta pheromone trap), leaf rollers of Tortricidae (delta pheromone traps), sticky traps, visual inspection

Tool	Disease forecasting: pathogen outbreak forecasting to support farmers in the decision whether or not to carry out the plant protection measures or fungicides application.
Application frequency	from the beginning of March to the end of August
Application date	from the beginning of March to the end of August
Target pest/disease/weed	Apple scab (sporetrap)

Tool	Biological control – Introduction of beneficial organisms, ie. <i>Typhlodromus pyri</i> (Phytoseiidae)
Application frequency	In the first year after planting or every year
Application date	In late winter and early spring, from late January to early April, bands are attached tightly to the trunks or thicker shoots of shrubs and trees.
Target pest/disease/weed	spider-mites (<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>), european red mite (<i>Panonychus ulmi</i>), rust-mites (<i>Eriophyidae</i>)

Tool	Biological control – natural enemies conservation strategy. Pests and their natural enemies are part of complex food-webs and interact with other species, notably at upper trophic levels such as hyperparasitoids and predators. Biological control using natural enemies and entomopathogens, play an important role in limiting the densities of potential pests. These natural enemies include predators, parasitoids, and pathogens. An effective control is achievable in orchards that support and promote a healthy and diverse natural enemy network.
Application frequency	When needed/ throughout growing season
Application date	When needed/ throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Predatory mites against spider mite Earwigs against aphids and pear psyllid Ladybirds against aphids Chrysoperla carnea against aphids

Tool	Rotation of active ingredients. Anti-resistance strategy. Rotation of active ingredients. The use of alternative pest control methods to minimize the risk of resistance development. Reduction of selection pressure on pest populations and delay the development of resistance. Prevention of buildup of residues in the soil. Reduction of the risk of environmental contamination. Reduction of exposure of non-target organisms to pesticides. Reduction of the risk of cross-resistance.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Whole growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	codling moth (<i>Cydia pomonella</i>), apple maggot (<i>Rhagoletis pomonella</i>), european red mite (<i>Panonychus ulmi</i>), green apple aphid (<i>Aphis pomi</i>). Aphids (<i>Aphididae</i>)

Tool	Removal of infected plants materials. Eradication of plant pathogen infections is very important for plant protection. The current strategy for eradication of a pathogen also relies on techniques for the removal and disposal of affected plant parts.
Application frequency	Whole season
Application date	Start of season
Target pest/disease/weed	apple scab (<i>Venturia inaequalis</i>), powdery mildew of apple (<i>Podosphaera leucotricha</i>) and other fungal diseases (<i>Nectria galligena</i> ; <i>Sphaeropsis malorum</i> ; <i>Phomopsis mali</i>)

Tool	Shredding of fallen leaves: Fallen leaves are shredded to facilitate decaying by soils micro- and macrobiome. This
------	---

	provides nutrients for the soil and trees. Faster decaying of the leaves also prevents the build-up of harmful fungi in the wet microclimate between the leaves.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Autumn
Target pest/disease/weed	Apple scab, different pest species

Tool	Adequate fertilization: Fertilization should be based on the results of soil and plant analysis. Analyzes should be carried out both before the establishment of the orchard and in the later period every 2-3 years. In addition, additional analyzes should be performed when irregularities in the appearance and development of plants are found, as well as when changing the method of cultivation, e.g. irrigation. Excessive fertilization can have negative effects on the plants and its growth. Too much fertilizer can cause dehydration and root tissue damage. In addition, an excess of certain components, e.g. nitrogen, may stimulate the development of certain pests.
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Aphids, spider mites, pathogens (apple scab, mildew, grey mould)

Tool	Monitored planting material. Use virus-free (VF) or virus-controlled (VT) nursery material purchased from nurseries accredited by the Regional Phytosanitary Service (SFR) and accompanied by the passport and marketing document certifying "quality CAC"
Application frequency	When establishing new orchard
Application date	When establishing new orchard
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest and disease transferred with nursery stock

Tool	Soil quality: Soil quality and health is an important topic to which more and more focus goes. Good soil quality harbors beneficial microorganisms, that for example increase nutrient uptake and decomposition of course material, and insects that can act as natural enemies against pests. The percentage organic matter is a key parameter in soil health and should be promoted.
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	Cost-effective irrigation under the trees.
------	---

	<p>Mini-sprinklers: irrigation is based on sprinkling. Depending on the type of impact insert used, mini-sprinklers deliver water in the form of droplets or streams. The type of insert used also affects the shape of the wetted surface.</p> <p>Drip irrigation: it is an irrigation system with a much lower unit water requirement compared to a sprinkler system.</p> <p>Water is delivered directly under the trees, to the root system of trees, there is no risk of wetting the leaves, which reduces the pressure of pathogen development</p>
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease outbreak: mildew, grey mould, apple scab

Tool	Biostimulant application: Biostimulants can be applied to improve growth characteristics of the trees which ultimately makes them more resilient against adverse conditions and pests and diseases.
Application frequency	Depends on many factors (weather, outbreak, perceived usefulness by farmers)
Application date	Start/during growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Used against all pests. Examples: Asahi SL, Tytanit, NaturalCrop SL, GumiSil, Agro-Sorb Folium

Tool	Application of organic amendments as alternative to mineral fertilizers can improve soil functionality and soil biodiversity with an effect on tree resilience to soilborne diseases
Application frequency	Start/during growing season
Application date	Start/during growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Used against all soilborne diseases Examples: products containing beneficial microorganisms such as Bacillus, Trichoderma, humic acid

Tool	Rotation of active ingredients: Rotation of different pesticides with different modes of action reduces the risk of developing resistance against active ingredients in pest species. Reports of, for example codling moth already reported resistance against certain common pesticides. Additionally, evidence suggests that multiple applications with a lower dose compared to a single application with a high dose is equally as effective or more effective in the eradication/suppression of pests.
Application frequency	Throughout the growing season
Application date	Throughout the growing season

Target pest/disease/weed	All
--------------------------	-----

Tool	Use of anti-hail nets. Creating optimal conditions for tree growth and fruit growing. Reduction of the outbreak of pests. Reduction of the apple disease pressure.
Application frequency	Throughout the season
Application date	Throughout the season
Target pest/disease/weed	Codling moth, apple scab, mildew, grey mould, reduction of damage caused by Miridae (deformed fruit), protection of fruits from birds

Tool	Hygiene measures. For some pathogens, it is important to disinfect tools such as pruning shears.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	During tree pruning
Target pest/disease/weed	bark and wood diseases, bacterial canker, Pseudomonas

Tool	Cuprum application after pruning. It is especially important in varieties susceptible to diseases of bark and wood like ie Gala. Cuprum products should be applied directly after winter pruning of tress with no risk to beneficial organisms.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	after tree pruning
Target pest/disease/weed	bark and wood diseases, bacterial canker, Pseudomonas

Tool	Grassing of apple orchards. It is an agronomic practice with low environmental impact for the control of weeds in the inter-row of apple orchards. the chemical-physical and microbiological characteristics of the soil are improved due to the lower consumption of organic matter. An increase in the lift for the transit of machines in ordinary cultivation practices is also ensured. Grassed sloping soils are better protected from the risks of erosion thanks to the combination of two factors: on the one hand, the better permeability of the soil favors the infiltration of water, on the other, the grass cover reduces the surface water flow rate
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	autumn
Target pest/disease/weed	Shelter for beneficial insects, attractant for pollinators, reduction of weeds.

Tool	Pruning/thinning: By pruning the apple trees, more open spaces are created which facilitates airflow and reduces humidity in the trees. This leads to less chances of fungi infection and thus a reduced loss of healthy leaf area and fruits.
Application frequency	During winter
Application date	During winter (December- March)
Target pest/disease/weed	Apple scab

Tool	Application of biological plant protection products such as plant oils and silicone products. The product on pests works intervening, physically, by forming a polymeric network. After spraying on the surface of the plant and on the bodies of the pests, a coating is formed that prevents agrophages from moving, resulting in inhibition of feeding and eventually death.
Application frequency	Throughout whole season
Application date	Throughout whole season
Target pest/disease/weed	Aphids, spider-mites, rust-mites K-PAK, SILTAC

Tool	Fruit storage in modified atmosphere
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	September-july
Target pest/disease/weed	Post-harvest diseases

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes (but not all cultivars are resistant)
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	3125-6666 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	15-20 years
Estimated annual yield	36 t/ha
Price per kg product	€1,0- €1,25/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	3 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 8-13 Insecticides: 5-7 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	99%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	3 m
Crop rotation	NO – only a gap between the plantings

	With which crops?
Intercropping	Use of living mulches, ie herbs or perennial crops such as <i>Fragaria vesca</i> , pumpkin crop

Sources:

Based on interviews with farmers and advisors

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Source: SUPPORT inventory tool, interviews with advisors, interviews with apple growers

Tool	Choice of cultivar and pathogen resistant varieties. An effective tool for containing phytosanitary problems is represented by the use of resistant varieties. Introduction of new scab-resistant apple varieties for the enhancement of Valtellina fruit growing with a significant reduction in pesticide treatments and protection of the environment and consumers.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	Planting time: march, september, october
Target pest/disease/weed	apple scab, mildew, aphids

Tool	Mulch along the apple orchard row. The under-row of the apple orchard can be managed conservatively with the mulching technique. It consists in distributing along the rows organic material: straw, processing by-products, wood shavings etc or plastic film to reduce the emergence of weeds.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Spring
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	INNOVATIVE PHYSICAL METHODS FOR WEEDING IE HOT WATER OR FLAME. The under-row of the apple orchard can be managed with the use of hot water. It kills the growing weeds and reduces the outbreak of new weeds.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Spring-fall
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Preservation of natural agro ecosystems (flower strips establishment). Building shelters for beneficials like earwigs or <i>chrysoperla carnea</i> in order to build up the large population for the spring. Nice way to encourage the build-up of beneficials for the whole season to help with biological control of aphids, psyllidae and other small insect pests
Application frequency	Throughout growing season

Application date	March-Sep
Target pest/disease/weed	Reduction of pest due to increase of natural enemies population

Tool	Agronomic treatments on mycorrhizal colonization in apple orchards. Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) colonize plant roots and spread in the surrounding bulk soil enhancing the nutrient uptake from the soil to the plant and stimulating the transfer of photosynthates from the plant to the soil. The importance of this symbiotic association in agro-ecosystems is related to an increasing attention to management sustainability and to the role of these systems as sinks of carbon dioxide (CO ₂).
Application frequency	During orchard establishment
Application date	Spring or autumn
Target pest/disease/weed	All pest and disease – plant resilience improvement

Tool	Mating disruption. Mating disruption is a method of pest control that uses synthetic pheromones to disrupt the mating behaviour of insects. This method uses both hand-applied dispensers and aerosol dispensers. The method is effective under certain conditions. One of them is the size of the orchard, which should not be less than 4 ha. In addition, the effectiveness of the method may be limited under very high pest pressure. The shape of the field should be such that border edges are minimized. That is, mating disruption works better in a square-shaped orchard than in a narrow rectangular orchard. Applying this method to neighbouring orchards will usually improve its effectiveness. By using this method, we reduce the use of pesticides, which has a positive effect on biodiversity, including beneficial fauna, and also reduces the likelihood of the emergence races of pests resistant to insecticides.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Spring-summer
Target pest/disease/weed	Cydia pomonella, Tortricidae

Tool	RATIONAL USE OF THE PLANT PROTECTION PRODUCTS
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	the whole growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All pest and disease population over the economic threshold level

Tool	Granulosis virus-based products. Products based on the <i>Cydia pomonella</i> granulosis virus (CpGV), may provide alternative control tools that can be applied with other approaches, for a sustainable control strategy.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Spring-summer
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Cydia pomonella</i> , Tortricidae Products based on the <i>Cydia pomonella</i> granulosis virus (CpGV), such as Madex®

Tool	Fruit storage in modified atmosphere
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	September-july
Target pest/disease/weed	Post-harvest diseases

Strategy 2: Apple Orchards low-density open field apple growing

Description

Number of growers	?
Acreage (ha)	Total acreage 100 thousand ha
% of total acreage	
Production (tonnes/year)	2 million tons /year
% of the total production	

Source: CSO/ KUPS

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	Resistant? Very seldom as there is no market value for pest resistant varieties Seed coating? n/a
Cropping density <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	1250-1666 plants/ha
Cropping cycle <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	20-25 years
Estimated annual yield <i>Source: www.stat.gov.pl</i>	26 t/ha
Price per kg product <i>Sources: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	€0,20 - €0,40 /kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario <i>Source: Farm EU</i>	€160-280 per ha (including eco-schemes)
Storage loss	20 %

PPP-use <i>Sources: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 4-9 Insecticides: 2-4 Herbicides: 0-1
% drift reduction <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	95 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	3 m
Crop rotation <i>Source: Personal communication with apple growers</i>	Crop rotation in between new orchard planting – usually a gap-year with green fertilizers
Intercropping <i>Personal communication with apple growers</i>	No / at organic orchards living mulch can be introduced or herbal plants for processing/

Sources:

Cap Strategic Plan

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Source: SUPPORT inventory tool

Tool	Pests monitoring: Pest monitoring to support farmers in the decision whether or not to carry out the plant protection measures or pesticides application.
Application frequency	from the beginning of May to the end of August
Application date	from the beginning of May to the end of August
Target pest/disease/weed	Apple scab (sporetrap), <i>Cydia pomonella</i> (delta pheromone trap), leaf rollers of Tortricidae (delta pheromone traps), sticky traps, visual inspection

Tool	Biological control – Introduction of beneficial organisms , ie. <i>Typhlodromus pyri</i> (<i>Phytoseiidae</i>)
Application frequency	In the first year after planting or every year
Application date	In late winter and early spring, from late January to early April, bands are attached tightly to the trunks or thicker shoots of shrubs and trees.
Target pest/disease/weed	spider-mites (<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>), european red mite (<i>Panonychus ulmi</i>), rust-mites (<i>Eriophyidae</i>)

Tool	Rotation of active ingredients. Anti-resistance strategy. Rotation of active ingredients. The use of alternative
------	---

	pest control methods to minimize the risk of resistance development. Reduction of selection pressure on pest populations and delay the development of resistance. Prevention of buildup of residues in the soil. Reduction of the risk of environmental contamination. Reduction of exposure of non-target organisms to pesticides. Reduction of the risk of cross-resistance.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Whole growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	codling moth (<i>Cydia pomonella</i>), apple maggot (<i>Rhagoletis pomonella</i>), european red mite (<i>Panonychus ulmi</i>), green apple aphid (<i>Aphis pomi</i>). Aphids (<i>Aphididae</i>)

Tool	Removal of infected plants materials. Eradication of plant pathogen infections is very important for plant protection. The current strategy for eradication of a pathogen also relies on techniques for the removal and disposal of affected plant parts.
Application frequency	Whole season
Application date	Start of season
Target pest/disease/weed	apple scab (<i>Venturia inaequalis</i>), powdery mildew of apple (<i>Podosphaera leucotricha</i>) and other fungal diseases (<i>Nectria galligena</i> ; <i>Sphaeropsis malorum</i> ; <i>Phomopsis mali</i>)

Tool	Shredding of fallen leaves: Fallen leaves are shredded to facilitate decaying by soils micro- and macrobiome. This provides nutrients for the soil and trees. Faster decaying of the leaves also prevents the build-up of harmful fungi in the wet microclimate between the leaves.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Autumn
Target pest/disease/weed	Apple scab, different pest species

Tool	Adequate fertilization: Fertilization should be based on the results of soil and plant analysis. Analyzes should be carried out both before the establishment of the orchard and in the later period every 2-3 years. In addition, additional analyzes should be performed when irregularities in the appearance and development of plants are found, as well as when changing the method of cultivation, e.g. irrigation. Excessive fertilization can have negative effects on the plants and its growth. Too much fertilizer can cause dehydration and root tissue
------	---

	damage. In addition, an excess of certain components, e.g. nitrogen, may stimulate the development of certain pests.
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Aphids, spider mites, pathogens (apple scab, mildew, grey mould)

Tool	Monitored planting material. Use virus-free (VF) or virus-controlled (VT) nursery material purchased from nurseries accredited by the Regional Phytosanitary Service (SFR) and accompanied by the passport and marketing document certifying "quality CAC"
Application frequency	When establishing new orchard
Application date	When establishing new orchard
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest and disease transferred with nursery stock

Tool	Soil quality: Soil quality and health is an important topic to which more and more focus goes. Good soil quality harbors beneficial microorganisms, that for example increase nutrient uptake and decomposition of course material, and insects that can act as natural enemies against pests. The percentage organic matter is a key parameter in soil health and should be promoted.
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases

Tool	Biostimulant application: Biostimulants can be applied to improve growth characteristics of the trees which ultimately makes them more resilient against adverse conditions and pests and diseases.
Application frequency	Depends on many factors (weather, outbreak, perceived usefulness by farmers)
Application date	Start/during growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Used against all pests. Examples: Asahi SL, Tytanit, NaturalCrop SL, GumiSil, Agro-Sorb Folium

Tool	Rotation of active ingredients: Rotation of different pesticides with different modes of action reduces the risk of developing resistance against active ingredients in pest species. Reports of, for example codling moth already
------	---

	reported resistance against certain common pesticides. Additionally, evidence suggests that multiple applications with a lower dose compared to a single application with a high dose is equally as effective or more effective in the eradication/suppression of pests.
Application frequency	Throughout the growing season
Application date	Throughout the growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Hygiene measures. For some pathogens, it is important to disinfect tools such as pruning shears.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	During tree pruning
Target pest/disease/weed	bark and wood diseases, bacterial canker, Pseudomonas

Tool	Cuprum application after pruning. It is especially important in varieties susceptible to diseases of bark and wood like ie Gala. Cuprum products should be applied directly after winter pruning of trees with no risk to beneficial organisms.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	after tree pruning
Target pest/disease/weed	bark and wood diseases, bacterial canker, Pseudomonas

Tool	Grassing of apple orchards. It is an agronomic practice with low environmental impact for the control of weeds in the inter-row of apple orchards. the chemical-physical and microbiological characteristics of the soil are improved due to the lower consumption of organic matter. An increase in the lift for the transit of machines in ordinary cultivation practices is also ensured. Grassed sloping soils are better protected from the risks of erosion thanks to the combination of two factors: on the one hand, the better permeability of the soil favors the infiltration of water, on the other, the grass cover reduces the surface water flow rate
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	autumn
Target pest/disease/weed	Shelter for beneficial insects, attractant for pollinators, reduction of weeds.

Tool	Pruning/thinning: By pruning the apple trees, more open spaces are created which facilitates airflow and
------	---

	reduces humidity in the trees. This leads to less chances of fungi infection and thus a reduced loss of healthy leaf area and fruits.
Application frequency	During winter
Application date	During winter (December- March)
Target pest/disease/weed	Apple scab

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes (but not all cultivars are resistant)
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	1666-3000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	20-25 years
Estimated annual yield	36 t/ha
Price per kg product	€0,5- €0,8/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	€160-280 per ha (including eco-schemes)
Storage loss	3 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 4-9 Insecticides: 2-4 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	99%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	3 m
Crop rotation	NO – only a gap between the plantings
	With which crops?
Intercropping	Use of living mulches, ie herbs or perennial crops such as <i>Fragaria vesca</i> , pumpkin crop

Sources:

Based on interviews with farmers and advisors

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Source: SUPPORT inventory tool, interviews with advisors, interviews with apple growers

Tool	RATIONAL USE OF THE PLANT PROTECTION PRODUCTS
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	the whole growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All pest and disease population over the economic threshold level

Tool	Mulch along the apple orchard row. The under-row of the apple orchard can be managed conservatively with the mulching technique. It consists in distributing along the rows organic material: straw, processing by-
------	--

	products, wood shavings etc or plastic film to reduce the emergence of weeds.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Spring
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Preservation of natural agro ecosystems (flower strips establishment). Building shelters for beneficials like earwigs or chrysoperla carnea in order to build up the large population for the spring. Nice way to encourage the build-up of beneficials for the whole season to help with biological control of aphids, psyllidae and other small insect pests
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	March-Sep
Target pest/disease/weed	Reduction of pest due to increase of natural enemies population

Tool	Mating disruption. Mating disruption is a method of pest control that uses synthetic pheromones to disrupt the mating behaviour of insects. This method uses both hand-applied dispensers and aerosol dispensers. The method is effective under certain conditions. One of them is the size of the orchard, which should not be less than 4 ha. In addition, the effectiveness of the method may be limited under very high pest pressure. The shape of the field should be such that border edges are minimized. That is, mating disruption works better in a square-shaped orchard than in a narrow rectangular orchard. Applying this method to neighbouring orchards will usually improve its effectiveness. By using this method, we reduce the use of pesticides, which has a positive effect on biodiversity, including beneficial fauna, and also reduces the likelihood of the emergence races of pests resistant to insecticides.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Spring-summer
Target pest/disease/weed	Cydia pomonella, Tortricidae

Tool	Granulosis virus-based products. Products based on the Cydia pomonella granulosis virus (CpGV), may provide alternative control tools that can be applied
------	--

	with other approaches, for a sustainable control strategy.
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Spring-summer
Target pest/disease/weed	Cydia pomonella, Tortricidae Products based on the Cydia pomonella granulosis virus (CpGV), such as Madex [®]

Tool	Fruit storage in modified atmosphere
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	September-july
Target pest/disease/weed	Post-harvest diseases

6.4 Strawberry

6.4.1 Belgium

Contact person: Clara Sciffer (clara.sciffer@ilvo.vlaanderen.be)

Kaat Peeters (kaat.peeters@ilvo.vlaanderen.be)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: **Strawberry in full soil: open & sheltered – June bearing**

Strategy 1 – IPM improved: **Strawberry in full soil: open & sheltered – June bearing**

Strategy 2 – state of the art scenario: Strawberry on substrate, sheltered, not heated– Junebearing/everbearing

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario: Strawberry on substrate, sheltered, not heated– Junebearing/everbearing

Strategy 3 – state of the art scenario: Strawberry on substrate, sheltered, heated – Junebearing, everbearing

Strategy 3 – IPM improved scenario: Strawberry on substrate, sheltered, heated – Junebearing, everbearing

Strategy 4 – state of the art scenario: **plant propagation + trayfields**

Strategy 4 – IPM improved scenario: **plant propagation + trayfields**

IPM strategies for strawberry production in Flanders

Strategy selection

For strawberry production in Flanders, 4 strategies are chosen based on the used cropping system:

- Strawberry production in full soil, both open and sheltered cultivation. Here, only June bearing cultivars are included.
- Strawberry production on substrate, sheltered cultivation not heated. Both June bearing and everbearing cultivars are discussed.
- Strawberry production on substrate, sheltered cultivation, heated. Both June bearing and everbearing cultivars are discussed.
- Strawberry propagation and cultivation on trayfields. This can actually be seen as 2 separate yet contiguous cultivation systems. Most farmers will only do the second part, the cultivation of strawberry plants on trayfields, as the propagation of strawberry plants is in some cases legally not allowed (in some cases only licensed farmers or only certain licensed producers can do the propagation part).

Strawberry production in Belgium is mainly a Flemish affair. Flanders accounts for 80 percent of the companies, 88 percent of the open-air production area and 93 percent of the sheltered production area in Belgium (De Samber J. (2019) Aardbeienteelt in Vlaanderen. Resultaten uit het Landbouwmonitoringsnetwerk, Departement Landbouw en Visserij, Brussel.). No relevant region-specific differences in the 4 production strategies are present.

Description reference year:

Strawberry production in 2023 was characterised by a heavy fungal disease pressure, and very short production cycles because of a heat wave in June and a warm September. In 2022, the quality of the strawberries was very good because of lots of sun during the summer months. However, the prices farmers received for their strawberries disappointed. In 2021, this was the other way around: less quality, better prices. 2020 on the other hand was a good year in terms of price, quality and quantity and will therefore be chosen as the reference year. In 2020, there were 613 strawberry farms and 1140 ha was used for strawberry production in Flanders. The ratio open versus sheltered production is about 40/60.

Strategy 1: Full soil production, open and sheltered, June bearing cultivars

Description

Number of growers	X
Acreage (ha)	X ha
% of total acreage	X %
Production (tonnes/year)	% tonnes/year
% of the total production	X %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	X plants/ha

Cropping cycle	Half February-September
Estimated annual yield	Full soil open: 205 kg/are (20,500 kg/ha)
Price per kg product	Full soil open: €44,800/ha
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	/
Storage loss	No storage; fresh market products
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X Amount of products used depends on the length of the cropping cycle
% drift reduction	75 % in open air
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1 m
Crop rotation	Yes/no (frequency: 1:3) With which crops?
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Crop rotation of 1:3 (is legally required; IPM checklist)
Application frequency	Always in full soil production
Application date	Always in full soil production
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil pests/diseases/weeds

Tool	Soil analysis and fertilizer use: at least 1x per cropping cycle a soil analysis is done. Avoid too much nitrogen fertilizer as it enhances powdery mildew, botrytis fruit rot and aphids. Avoid too little nitrogen for optimal plant resilience. Application in full soil systems: before and during the production cycle with a drip line.
Application frequency	1 analysis per year
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Soil analysis before planting, fertilizer before/during growing cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests

Tool	Resistant cultivars. The choice of cultivar is mostly market driven, but there are some cultivars (mostly June-bearing cultivars like Sonata) that are being used less and less because of their sensitivity for <i>Phytophthora</i> .
------	--

	Some other cultivars (mostly day-neutral cultivars) are more resistant against powdery mildew than June-bearing cultivars (like Elsanta).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Healthy plant material. Use strong and healthy plant material (certified planting material, visual control before use).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests/weeds

Tool	Remove ripe/affected strawberries. Remove sick/affected strawberries when going through the crop (mostly during the harvest) (strawberries affected: with powdery mildew, mucor and spotted wing drosophila).
Application frequency	As much as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests

Tool	Drift reduction. Drift-reduction application techniques ($\geq 75\%$ DR) in open field systems. Drift reduction caps can also improve the effectiveness of the pesticide application.
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Buffer zone: a minimal 1-3m 'crop protection free' buffer zone from water courses is mandatory. This buffer zone can be larger depending on the crop protection product.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Use of extension services or experts for advice.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool	Physical barriers (plastic/fabric) to avoid weeds in an open field on soil cropping system.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Planting
Stage of development of the crop	Planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Chemical weed control with herbicides.
Application frequency	Generally 2 applications
Application date	Generally 1-2 weeks after planting and 4-5 weeks after planting
Stage of development of the crop	Generally shortly after planting and a second application before flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Fungicide application against <i>Botrytis</i> .
Application frequency	Weekly, as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (<i>Botrytis</i>)

Tool	Fungicide application against powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera aphanis</i>).
Application frequency	Weekly (every 5 days), as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (powdery mildew)

Tool	Soil fungi: fungicide application.
Application frequency	1-2x
Application date	After planting
Stage of development of the crop	After planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Insecticide application against aphids, as they carry viruses.
Application frequency	When needed
Application date	March-August

Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: aphids

Tool	Insecticides application against spider mites.
Application frequency	1-2 times
Application date	In case of spring planting: 1-2x during flowering. In case of August (autumn) planting: 1x in the 2 nd half of September.
Stage of development of the crop	Flowering/after planting (depending on spring/autumn planting)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: spider mites

Tool	Insecticide application against the Suzukii fly.
Application frequency	When needed, probably 2-3 times
Application date	April-August
Stage of development of the crop	During harvest (from the moment there are fruits that could get infected)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: Suzukii fly

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	X plants/ha
Cropping cycle	Half February-September
Estimated annual yield	Full soil open: 205 kg/are (20500 kg/ha)
Price per kg product	Full soil open: €44,800/ha
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	/
Storage loss	No storage; fresh market products
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X Amount of products used depends on the length of the cropping cycle
% drift reduction	75 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1 m
Crop rotation	Yes/no (frequency: 1:3)
	With which crops?
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Crop rotation of 1:3 (is legally required; IPM checklist)
Application frequency	Always in full soil production
Application date	Always in full soil production
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil pests/diseases/weeds

Tool	Soil analysis and fertilizer use: at least 1x per cropping cycle a soil analysis is done. Avoid too much nitrogen fertilizer as it enhances powdery mildew, botrytis fruit rot and aphids. Avoid too little nitrogen for optimal plant resilience. Application in full soil systems: before and during the production cycle with a drip line. An adapted fertilizer use can increase plant resilience.
Application frequency	1 analysis per year
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Soil analysis before planting, fertilizer before/during growing cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests

Tool	Resistant cultivars. The choice of cultivar is mostly market driven, but there are some cultivars (mostly June-bearing cultivars like Sonata) that are being used less and less because of their sensitivity for <i>Phytophthora</i> . Some other cultivars (mostly day-neutral cultivars) are more resistant against powdery mildew than June-bearing cultivars (like Elsanta).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Healthy plant material. Use strong and healthy plant material (certified planting material, visual control before use).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests/weeds

Tool	Remove ripe/affected strawberries. Remove sick/affected strawberries when going through
------	---

	the crop (mostly during the harvest) (strawberries affected: with powdery mildew, mucor and spotted wing drosophila).
Application frequency	As much as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests

Tool	Drift reduction. Drift-reduction application techniques ($\geq 75\%$ DR) in open field systems. Drift reduction caps can also improve the effectiveness of the pesticide application.
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Buffer zone: a minimal 1-3m 'crop protection free' buffer zone from water courses is mandatory. This buffer zone can be larger depending on the crop protection product.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Use of extension services or experts for advice.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool	Physical barriers (plastic/fabric) to avoid weeds in an open field on soil cropping system.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Planting
Stage of development of the crop	Planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Chemical weed control with herbicides.
Application frequency	Generally 2 applications
Application date	Generally 1-2 weeks after planting and 4-5 weeks after planting

Stage of development of the crop	Generally shortly after planting and a second application before flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Fungicide and bio fungicide application against <i>Botrytis</i> .
Application frequency	Weekly, as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (<i>Botrytis</i>)

Tool	Fungicide and bio fungicide application against powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera aphanis</i>).
Application frequency	Weekly (every 5 days), as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (powdery mildew)

Tool	Soil fungi: fungicide and bio fungicide application.
Application frequency	1-2x
Application date	After planting
Stage of development of the crop	After planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Insecticide application against aphids, as they carry viruses.
Application frequency	When needed
Application date	March-August
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: aphids

Tool	Insecticides application against spider mites.
Application frequency	1-2 times
Application date	In case of spring planting: 1-2x during flowering. In case of August (autumn) planting: 1x in the 2 nd half of September.
Stage of development of the crop	Flowering/after planting (depending on spring/autumn planting)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: spider mites

Tool	Insecticide application against the Suzukii fly.
Application frequency	When needed, probably 2-3 times
Application date	April-August

Stage of development of the crop	During harvest (from the moment there are fruits that could get infected)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: Suzukii fly

Strategy 2: Production on substrate, sheltered, not heated, June and everbearing cultivars

Description

Number of growers	X
Acreage (ha)	X ha
% of total acreage	X %
Production (tonnes/year)	% tonnes/year
% of the total production	X %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	X plants/ha
Cropping cycle	End of December/January-October
Estimated annual yield	33,300 kg/ha
Price per kg product	€83,300/ha
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	/
Storage loss	No storage; fresh market products
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X Amount of products used depends on the length of the cropping cycle
% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	NA
Crop rotation	Yes/no: NA for substrate grown strawberries
	With which crops?
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Cleaning the gutters: after every production cycle in the greenhouse, the gutters are cleaned (mostly with high-pressure water, but at least once a year also with cleaning agents).
Application frequency	1x or 2x (after every production cycle)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/Pests/Weeds

Tool	Washing the truss support ribbons: in case of <i>Mucor</i> : the tape that gives support to the strawberries has to be washed off + disinfected.
Application frequency	1x or 2x (after every production cycle)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases: <i>Mucor</i>

Tool	Resistant cultivars. The choice of cultivar is mostly market driven, but there are some cultivars (mostly June-bearing cultivars like Sonata) that are being used less and less because of their sensitivity for <i>Phytophthora</i> . Some other cultivars (mostly day-neutral cultivars) are more resistant against powdery mildew than June-bearing cultivars (like Elsanta).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Healthy plant material. Use strong and healthy plant material (certified planting material, visual control before use).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests/weeds

Tool	Remove ripe/affected strawberries. Remove sick/affected strawberries when going through the crop (mostly during the harvest) (strawberries affected: with powdery mildew, mucor and spotted wing drosophila).
Application frequency	As much as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests

Tool	Steaming: the pots get steamed when using cultivars sensitive to <i>Phytophthora</i> .
Application frequency	1x
Application date	At the end of the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	At the end of the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease: <i>Phytophthora</i>

Tool	Pushing the flower clusters forwards: the flower clusters are pushed forwards, so they can dry faster as they are not influenced anymore by the micro climate of the leaves. This also ensures a better contact during the application of pesticides. By pushing the flower clusters forwards, harvesting becomes also easier.
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease: <i>Botrytis</i> + easy harvesting

Tool	Use of extension services or experts for advice.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool	Ventilation + fertilizer use. Ventilation in greenhouse systems is important for lowering the moisture level in the greenhouse; this helps against fungi (e.g. botrytis fruit rot). However, ventilation can also higher the powdery mildew pressure. Fertilizer is applied to the circulation water. Avoid too much nitrogen fertilizer as it enhances powdery mildew, botrytis fruit rot and aphids. Avoid too little nitrogen for optimal plant resilience.
Application frequency	During cropping cycle
Application date	During cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/Pests + plant growth regulation

Tool	Sticky/pheromone/food traps for monitoring. Close and frequent visual monitoring of the crop. For this, traps are being placed in strategic corners of the crop to monitor thrips, whiteflies and the <i>Suzukii</i> fruit fly.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Traps are placed at the start of the production cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Traps are placed at the start of the production cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests (thrips, whiteflies, <i>Suzukii</i> fruit fly)

Tool	Fungicide application against <i>Botrytis</i> .
Application frequency	3-4x, as needed (June bearing) or weekly throughout the flowering (everbearing)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (<i>Botrytis</i>)

Tool	Fungicide application against powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera aphanis</i>).
Application frequency	Weekly (every 5 days), as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (powdery mildew)

Tool	Insecticide application against aphids, as they carry viruses.
Application frequency	When needed
Application date	March-October
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: aphids

Tool	Predatory mites and bugs against spider mites and thrips.
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	At the beginning of the cropping cycle, after planting
Stage of development of the crop	After planting or whenever needed throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: spider mites and thrips

Tool	Insecticide application against the Suzukii fly.
Application frequency	When needed, probably 2-3 times
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During harvest (from the moment there are fruits that could get infected)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: Suzukii fly

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	X plants/ha
Cropping cycle	End of December/January-October
Estimated annual yield	33,300 kg/ha

Price per kg product	€83,300/ha
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	/
Storage loss	No storage; fresh market products
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X Amount of products used depends on the length of the cropping cycle
% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	NA
Crop rotation	Yes/ no : NA for substrate grown strawberries With which crops?
Intercropping	Yes/ no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Cleaning the gutters: after every production cycle in the greenhouse, the gutters are cleaned (mostly with high-pressure water, but at least once a year also with cleaning agents).
Application frequency	1x or 2x (after every production cycle)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/Pests/Weeds

Tool	Washing the truss support ribbons: In case of mucor: the tape that gives support to the strawberries has to be washed off + disinfected.
Application frequency	1x or 2x (after every production cycle)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases: <i>Mucor</i>

Tool	Resistant cultivars. The choice of cultivar is mostly market driven, but there are some cultivars (mostly June-bearing cultivars like Sonata) that are being used less and less because of their sensitivity for <i>Phytophthora</i> . Some other cultivars (mostly day-neutral cultivars) are more resistant against powdery mildew than June-bearing cultivars (like Elsanta).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA

Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Healthy plant material. Use strong and healthy plant material (certified planting material, visual control before use).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests/weeds

Tool	Remove ripe/affected strawberries. Remove sick/affected strawberries when going through the crop (mostly during the harvest) (strawberries affected: with powdery mildew, mucor and spotted wing drosophila).
Application frequency	As much as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests

Tool	Steaming: the pots get steamed when using cultivars sensitive to <i>Phytophthora</i> .
Application frequency	1x
Application date	At the end of the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	At the end of the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease: <i>Phytophthora</i>

Tool	Pushing the flower clusters forwards: the flower clusters are pushed forwards, so they can dry faster as they are not influenced anymore by the micro climate of the leaves. This also ensures a better contact during the application of pesticides. By pushing the flower clusters forwards, harvesting becomes also easier.
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease: <i>Botrytis</i> + easy harvesting

Tool	Use of extension services or experts for advice.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA

Target pest/disease/weed	NA
--------------------------	----

Tool	Ventilation + fertilizer use. Ventilation in greenhouse systems is important for lowering the moisture level in the greenhouse; this helps against fungi (e.g. botrytis fruit rot). However, ventilation can also higher the powdery mildew pressure. Fertilizer is applied to the circulation water. Avoid too much nitrogen fertilizer as it enhances powdery mildew, botrytis fruit rot and aphids. Avoid too little nitrogen for optimal plant resilience. An adapted fertilizer use can increase plant resilience.
Application frequency	During cropping cycle
Application date	During cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/Pests + plant growth regulation

Tool	Sticky and pheromone/food traps for monitoring. Close and frequent visual monitoring of the crop. For this, sticky traps are being placed in strategic corners of the crop to monitor thrips, whiteflies and the <i>Suzukii</i> fruit fly.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Traps are placed at the start of the production cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Traps are placed at the start of the production cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests (thrips, whiteflies, <i>Suzukii</i> fruit fly)

Tool	Fungicide + bio fungicide application against <i>Botrytis</i> .
Application frequency	3-4x, as needed (June bearing) or weekly throughout the flowering (everbearing)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (<i>Botrytis</i>)

Tool	Fungicide + bio fungicide application against powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera aphanis</i>). Use of an UV-C robot is also possible.
Application frequency	Weekly (every 5 days), as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (powdery mildew)

Tool	Insecticide application against aphids, as they carry viruses.
Application frequency	When needed
Application date	March-October
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: aphids

Tool	Predatory mites and bugs against spider mites and thrips.
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	At the beginning of the cropping cycle, after planting
Stage of development of the crop	After planting or whenever needed throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: spider mites and thrips

Tool	Insecticide application against the Suzukii fly.
Application frequency	When needed, probably 2-3 times
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During harvest (from the moment there are fruits that could get infected)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: <i>Suzukii</i> fly

Strategy 3: Production on substrate, sheltered, heated, June and everbearing cultivars

Description

Number of growers	X
Acreage (ha)	X ha
% of total acreage	X %
Production (tonnes/year)	% tonnes/year
% of the total production	X %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	X plants/ha
Cropping cycle	January-December
Estimated annual yield	55,000 kg/ha
Price per kg product	€204,500/ha
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	No storage: fresh market products
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X

	Insecticides: X Herbicides: X Amount of products used depends on the length of the cropping cycle
% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	NA
Crop rotation	Yes/no: NA for substrate grown strawberries With which crops?
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Cleaning the gutters: after 1 year of production in the greenhouse, the gutters are cleaned after the last harvest (with high-pressure water and with cleaning agents).
Application frequency	1x/year
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After the last harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/Pests/Weeds

Tool	Washing the truss support ribbons: in case of <i>Mucor</i> : the tape that gives support to the strawberries has to be washed off + disinfected.
Application frequency	3x (after every production cycle) (not in everbearing cultivars)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases: <i>Mucor</i>

Tool	Resistant cultivars. The choice of cultivar is mostly market driven, but there are some cultivars (mostly June-bearing cultivars like Sonata) that are being used less and less because of their sensitivity for <i>Phytophthora</i> . Some other cultivars (mostly day-neutral cultivars) are more resistant against powdery mildew than June-bearing cultivars (like Elsanta).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Healthy plant material. Use strong and healthy plant material (certified planting material, visual control before use).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests/weeds

Tool	Remove ripe/affected strawberries. Remove sick/affected strawberries when going through the crop (mostly during the harvest) (strawberries affected: with powdery mildew, mucor and spotted wing drosophila).
Application frequency	As much as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests

Tool	Steaming: the pots get steamed when using cultivars sensitive to <i>Phytophthora</i> .
Application frequency	1x
Application date	At the end of the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	At the end of the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease: <i>Phytophthora</i>

Tool	Pushing the flower clusters forwards: the flower clusters are pushed forwards, so they can dry faster as they are not influenced anymore by the micro climate of the leaves. This also ensures a better contact during the application of pesticides. By pushing the flower clusters forwards, harvesting becomes also easier.
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease: <i>Botrytis</i> + easy harvesting

Tool	Use of extension services or experts for advice.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool	Ventilation + fertilizer use. Ventilation in greenhouse systems is important for lowering the moisture level in the greenhouse; this helps against fungi (e.g. botrytis fruit rot). However, ventilation can also higher the powdery mildew pressure. Fertilizer is applied to the circulation water. Avoid too much nitrogen fertilizer as it enhances powdery mildew, botrytis fruit rot and aphids. Avoid too little nitrogen for optimal plant resilience.
Application frequency	During cropping cycle
Application date	During cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/Pests + plant growth regulation

Tool	Sticky/pheromone/food traps for monitoring. Close and frequent visual monitoring of the crop. For this, traps are being placed in strategic corners of the crop to monitor thrips, whiteflies and the <i>Suzukii</i> fruit fly.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Traps are placed at the start of the production cycle, mostly during the first and last production cycle (the second cycle is generally too short)
Stage of development of the crop	Traps are placed at the start of the production cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests (thrips, whiteflies, <i>Suzukii</i> fruit fly)

Tool	Fungicide application against <i>Botrytis</i> .
Application frequency	3-4x, as needed (June bearing) or weekly throughout the flowering (everbearing)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (<i>Botrytis</i>)

Tool	Fungicide application against powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera aphanis</i>).
Application frequency	Weekly (every 5 days), as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (powdery mildew)

Tool	Insecticide application against aphids, as they carry viruses.
Application frequency	When needed

Application date	February-December
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: aphids

Tool	Predatory mites and bugs against spider mites and thrips.
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	At the beginning of the cropping cycle, after planting
Stage of development of the crop	After planting or whenever needed throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: spider mites and thrips

Tool	Insecticide application against the Suzukii fly.
Application frequency	When needed, probably 2-3 times
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During harvest (from the moment there are fruits that could get infected)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: Suzukii fly

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes /no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/ NA
Cropping density	X plants/ha
Cropping cycle	January-December
Estimated annual yield	55,000 kg/ha
Price per kg product	€204,500/ha
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	/
Storage loss	No storage: fresh market products
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X Amount of products used depends on the length of the cropping cycle
% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	NA
Crop rotation	Yes/ no : NA for substrate grown strawberries
	With which crops?
Intercropping	Yes/ no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Cleaning the gutters: after 1 year of production in the greenhouse, the gutters are cleaned after the last harvest (with high-pressure water and with cleaning agents).
Application frequency	1x/year
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After the last harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/Pests/Weeds

Tool	Washing the truss support ribbons: in case of <i>Mucor</i> : the tape that gives support to the strawberries has to be washed off + disinfected.
Application frequency	3x (after every production cycle) (not in everbearing cultivars)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases: <i>Mucor</i>

Tool	Resistant cultivars. The choice of cultivar is mostly market driven, but there are some cultivars (mostly June-bearing cultivars like Sonata) that are being used less and less because of their sensitivity for <i>Phytophthora</i> . Some other cultivars (mostly day-neutral cultivars) are more resistant against powdery mildew than June-bearing cultivars (like Elsanta).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Healthy plant material. Use strong and healthy plant material (certified planting material, visual control before use).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests/weeds

Tool	Remove ripe/affected strawberries. Remove sick/affected strawberries when going through the crop (mostly during the harvest) (strawberries affected: with powdery mildew, mucor and spotted wing drosophila).
Application frequency	As much as needed

Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests

Tool	Steaming: the pots get steamed when using cultivars sensitive to <i>Phytophthora</i> .
Application frequency	1x
Application date	At the end of the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	At the end of the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease: <i>Phytophthora</i>

Tool	Pushing the flower clusters forwards: the flower clusters are pushed forwards, so they can dry faster as they are not influenced anymore by the micro climate of the leaves. This also ensures a better contact during the application of pesticides. By pushing the flower clusters forwards, harvesting becomes also easier.
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease: <i>Botrytis</i> + easy harvesting

Tool	Use of extension services or experts for advice.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool	Ventilation + fertilizer use. Ventilation in greenhouse systems is important for lowering the moisture level in the greenhouse; this helps against fungi (e.g. botrytis fruit rot). However, ventilation can also higher the powdery mildew pressure. Fertilizer is applied to the circulation water. Avoid too much nitrogen fertilizer as it enhances powdery mildew, botrytis fruit rot and aphids. Avoid too little nitrogen for optimal plant resilience. An adapted fertilizer use can increase plant resilience.
Application frequency	During cropping cycle
Application date	During cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/Pests + plant growth regulation

Tool	Sticky/pheromone/food traps for monitoring. Close and frequent visual monitoring of the crop. For this, traps are being placed in strategic corners of the crop to monitor thrips, whiteflies and the <i>Suzukii</i> fruit fly.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Traps are placed at the start of the production cycle, mostly during the first and last production cycle (the second cycle is generally too short)
Stage of development of the crop	Traps are placed at the start of the production cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests (thrips, whiteflies, <i>Suzukii</i> fruit fly)

Tool	Fungicide and bio fungicide application against <i>Botrytis</i> .
Application frequency	3-4x, as needed (June bearing) or weekly throughout the flowering (everbearing)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (<i>Botrytis</i>)

Tool	Fungicide and bio fungicide application against powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera aphanis</i>) + use of an UV-C robot is also possible.
Application frequency	Weekly (every 5 days), as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (powdery mildew)

Tool	Insecticide application against aphids, as they carry viruses.
Application frequency	When needed
Application date	February-December
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: aphids

Tool	Predatory mites and bugs against spider mites and thrips.
Application frequency	As needed
Application date	At the beginning of the cropping cycle, after planting
Stage of development of the crop	After planting or whenever needed throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: spider mites and thrips

Tool	Insecticide application against the Suzukii fly.
Application frequency	When needed, probably 2-3 times
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During harvest (from the moment there are fruits that could get infected)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: Suzukii fly

Strategy 4: Strawberry propagation and cultivation on trayfields

Description

Number of growers	X
Acreage (ha)	X ha
% of total acreage	X %
Production (tonnes/year)	% tonnes/year
% of the total production	X %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	X plants/ha
Cropping cycle	Planting: March; Harvest + planting in trays: July; Cooling: December
Estimated annual yield	X t/ha
Price per kg product	X €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	/
Storage loss	No storage; fresh market products
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X
% drift reduction	75 % in open air
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1 m
Crop rotation	Yes/no (frequency: 1:3)
	With which crops?
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Fertilizer + irrigation use: at least 1x per cropping cycle a soil analysis is done. Avoid too much nitrogen fertilizer as it enhances powdery mildew, botrytis fruit rot and aphids. Avoid too little nitrogen for optimal plant resilience. Application in full soil systems:
------	--

	before and during the production cycle with a drip line.
Application frequency	1 analysis per year
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Fertilizer + irrigation before/during growing cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests

Tool	Resistant cultivars. The choice of cultivar is mostly market driven, but there are some cultivars (mostly June-bearing cultivars like Sonata) that are being used less and less because of their sensitivity for <i>Phytophthora</i> . Some other cultivars (mostly day-neutral cultivars) are more resistant against powdery mildew than June-bearing cultivars (like Elsanta).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Healthy plant material. Use strong and healthy plant material (certified planting material, visual control before use).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests/weeds

Tool	Remove ripe/affected plants. Remove sick/affected plants when going through the crop.
Application frequency	As much as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests

Tool	Drift reduction. Drift-reduction application techniques ($\geq 75\%$ DR) in open field systems. Drift reduction caps can also improve the effectiveness of the pesticide application.
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/

Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.
--------------------------	--

Tool	Buffer zone: a minimal 1-3m 'crop protection free' buffer zone from water courses is mandatory. This buffer zone can be larger depending on the crop protection product.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Use of extension services or experts for advice.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool	Mechanical weed control to control weeds in an open field on soil cropping system.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	End of April-beginning of May
Stage of development of the crop	After planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Chemical weed control with herbicides.
Application frequency	Generally 3 applications
Application date	Half May until the beginning of July: one week after the mechanical weed control. 3-4 weeks between chemical applications.
Stage of development of the crop	Flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Fungicide application against powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera aphanis</i>).
Application frequency	Weekly (every 5 days), as needed
Application date	During cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (powdery mildew)

Tool	Soil fungi: fungicide application.
Application frequency	2-3x in plant propagation, 1x in trayfields
Application date	NA

Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Insecticide application against aphids, as they carry viruses.
Application frequency	When needed
Application date	March-August or later if needed
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: aphids

Tool	Insecticides application against spider mites.
Application frequency	1-2 times
Application date	In case of spring planting: 1-2x during flowering. In case of August (autumn) planting: 1x in the 2 nd half of September.
Stage of development of the crop	Flowering/after planting (depending on spring/autumn planting)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: spider mites

Tool	Insecticide application against the strawberry mite (<i>Tarsonemus pallidus</i>)
Application frequency	2x, 8-10 days in between applications
Application date	Beginning of May
Stage of development of the crop	When the stolons are appearing
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: strawberry mite

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes /no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/ NA
Cropping density	X plants/ha
Cropping cycle	Planting: March; Harvest + planting in trays: July; Cooling: December
Estimated annual yield	X t/ha
Price per kg product	X €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	/
Storage loss	No storage; fresh market products
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X
% drift reduction	75 % in open air
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1 m
Crop rotation	Yes /no (frequency: 1:3)
	With which crops?

Intercropping	Yes/no
---------------	--------

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Fertilizer + irrigation use: at least 1x per cropping cycle a soil analysis is done. Avoid too much nitrogen fertilizer as it enhances powdery mildew, botrytis fruit rot and aphids. Avoid too little nitrogen for optimal plant resilience. Application in full soil systems: before and during the production cycle with a drip line. An adapted fertilizer use can increase plant resilience.
Application frequency	1 analysis per year
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Fertilizer + irrigation before/during growing cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests

Tool	Resistant cultivars. The choice of cultivar is mostly market driven, but there are some cultivars (mostly June-bearing cultivars like Sonata) that are being used less and less because of their sensitivity for <i>Phytophthora</i> . Some other cultivars (mostly day-neutral cultivars) are more resistant against powdery mildew than June-bearing cultivars (like Elsanta).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Healthy plant material. Use strong and healthy plant material (certified planting material, visual control before use).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests/weeds

Tool	Remove ripe/affected plants. Remove sick/affected plants when going through the crop.
Application frequency	As much as needed
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During the cropping cycle

Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases/pests
--------------------------	----------------

Tool	Drift reduction. Drift-reduction application techniques ($\geq 75\%$ DR) in open field systems. Drift reduction caps can also improve the effectiveness of the pesticide application.
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Buffer zone: a minimal 1-3m 'crop protection free' buffer zone from water courses is mandatory. This buffer zone can be larger depending on the crop protection product.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Use of extension services or experts for advice.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool	Mechanical weed control to control weeds in an open field on soil cropping system.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	End of April-beginning of May
Stage of development of the crop	After planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Chemical weed control with herbicides.
Application frequency	Generally 3 applications
Application date	Half May until the beginning of July: one week after the mechanical weed control. 3-4 weeks between chemical applications.
Stage of development of the crop	Flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Fungicide application and bio fungicide application against powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera aphanis</i>).
Application frequency	Weekly (every 5 days), as needed
Application date	During cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease (powdery mildew)

Tool	Soil fungi: fungicide application.
Application frequency	2-3x in plant propagation, 1x in trayfields
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	During cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool	Insecticide application against aphids, as they carry viruses.
Application frequency	When needed
Application date	March-August or later if needed
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: aphids

Tool	Insecticides application against spider mites.
Application frequency	1-2 times
Application date	In case of spring planting: 1-2x during flowering. In case of August (autumn) planting: 1x in the 2 nd half of September.
Stage of development of the crop	Flowering/after planting (depending on spring/autumn planting)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: spider mites

Tool	Insecticide application against the strawberry mite (<i>Tarsonemus pallidus</i>)
Application frequency	2x, 8-10 days in between applications
Application date	Beginning of May
Stage of development of the crop	When the stolons are appearing
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest: strawberry mite

References

Personal communication with strawberry advisors De Samber J. (2019) Aardbeienteelt in Vlaanderen. Resultaten uit het Landbouwmonitoringsnetwerk, Departement Landbouw en Visserij, Brussel

6.4.2 The Netherlands

Contact person: Carolina Gattorno (carolina.gattorno@zlto.nl)

Yaite Cuesta Arenas (yaite.cuesta.arenas@zlto.nl)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: Indoor Production (greenhouse/tunnel)

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: Indoor Production (greenhouse/tunnel)

Strategy 2 – state of the art scenario: Mixed Nursery System: outdoor, greenhouse, tray fields

Strategy 2 – IPM Improved scenario: Mixed Nursery System: outdoor, greenhouse, tray fields

IPM strategies for strawberry: The Netherlands

Strategy selection

Strawberries are the third largest crop in the Netherlands by cropping area, with a total of 1,420 hectares cultivated in 2023 (CBS Statline). Of this area, 571 hectares were grown under glass or plastic tunnels, and 850 hectares in open fields (CBS Statline).

Strawberry production in the Netherlands has transitioned from seasonal outdoor cultivation, where strawberries were grown in soil and harvested in June-July, to year-round and increasingly indoor production. This shift is driven by advancements in cultivation techniques (such as the introduction of substrates for strawberries), technology (like controlling the greenhouse environment), and new varieties (such as ever-bearers). Additionally, there is a growing consumer demand for high-quality, sustainable strawberries throughout the year. Stricter regulations aimed at reducing chemical usage and minimizing environmental and health impacts have also contributed to this trend.

The propagation of strawberries is a highly specialized and significant sector within the Dutch strawberry industry, occupying half of the total land used for strawberry production. In 2023, 900 hectares were used for propagation (CBS Statline).

Considering these trends, two strategies have been selected for the NCC strawberry in the Netherlands, which take into account the major cultivation systems and sectors. Geographic variability does not lead to significant differences and is therefore not included in these strategies (*Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy*).

Strategy 1: Indoor Production (greenhouse/tunnel)

Strategy 2: Mixed System Cuttings/Propagation (outdoor, greenhouse, tray field)

Currently there are not yet strawberry plants which are rooted in glasshouses. A part is outdoor cultivation which is mainly for export and partly for Dutch production (both indoor and outdoor). The main form of propagation is done outdoors in tray fields (around 80%) but also partly under glass. (*Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy*).

Description reference year 2023:

The start of 2023 was categorized by lots of rain and warm weather. On average, some 1060 millimetres of rain fell, compared with 795 in a normal year – the average between 1991 and 2022 (these years were however categorized with below average rain).

Additionally, there was a late summer which started with little sun and lots of rain (*Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy*). Given that the major strategy chosen for strawberry was indoor cultivation the reference year of 2023 is a good reference. Additionally, the 'extreme' weather conditions listed were again in comparison to the previous years which were also extreme, therefore it is still a better year to choose in comparison to the previous years.

For strawberry production, this led to fast growth of the autumn crop in 2023, planted in mid-August, leading to a surplus in September and early October. This caused a sharp decline in volumes by late October, with Dutch and Belgian production falling to less than a third of typical levels (when compared to that week from previous years). The oversupply initially pressured prices down to around 3 euros per kilo, but shortages from mid-October led to a price surge, reaching 11.50-12.50 euros per kilo by early November (Fresh Plaza, 2023).

Strategy 1: Indoor Production (greenhouse/tunnel)

Description

Number of growers	Greenhouse: 181 Tunnel: 51
Acreage (ha)	Greenhouse: 480 ha Tunnel: 90 ha
% of total acreage	Total indoor production 40 % <i>Greenhouse: 33%</i> <i>Tunnel: 6%</i>
Production (tonnes/year)	59,700 tonnes in 2023
% of the total production	75 %

Source: CBS Statline 2023

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? No (only tolerant against phytophthora and mildew) Seed coating? No
Cropping density <i>Source: Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy</i>	Glass/tunnel June bearers: 100.000 plants/ha Ever bearers: 60.000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle <i>Source: Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy</i>	<u>June bearers:</u> Plant: Jan Harvest: May-June <u>Ever bearers:</u> Plant: Jan-Dec Harvest: March-Dec (there is year-round cultivation)
Estimated annual yield <i>Source: CBS Statline</i>	70 t/ha
Price per kg product <i>Source: Vlaanderen, Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy</i>	Highest: €12,00 /kg (during winter) Lowest: €2,00/kg (during peaks summer) Average: €4-7
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario <i>Source: Farm EU</i>	Eco-Scheme payments (GBL): depends on points given. Average is between €160-200/ha.
Storage loss	Loss doesn't happen on from the grower but during transportation or retail.
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): (open field) Fungicides: 7-9

Source: KWIN 2022, Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy See appendix for list of PPPs used.	Insecticides: 3-5 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction Source: Ctgb	75 % with a 4.5 m min buffer 90% with a 3 m min buffer
Minimum buffer zone to surface water Source: Ctgb EM2.7 Ch. 6	3 - 4.5 meters
Crop rotation Source: Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy	No With which crops?
Intercropping Source: Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy	No

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Chemical Intervention (List of chemical and biological products used in Strawberry)

Tool	azadirachtine
Application frequency	2 times a year
Application date	4-6 week after planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Insecticide biological (aphids, spider mites, thrips, white fly)

Tool	fludioxonil (25%), cyprodinil (38%)
Application frequency	2 times a year
Application date	During flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide chemical (botrytis)

Tool	cyantraniliprole (100)
Application frequency	2 times a year
Application date	Second half of the year , end of harvest against Drosophila Suzuki. Not in glasshouse
Target pest/disease/weed	Insecticide chemical (D. Suzuki)

Tool	spinosad (480)
Application frequency	3x a year
Application date	During flowering or during picking
Target pest/disease/weed	Insecticide , biological SKAL certified (thrips, D. Suzuki)

Tool	fenhexamide (50%)
Application frequency	1 time average
Application date	Flowering

Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide (Botrytis)
--------------------------	----------------------

Tool	Fatty acids, potassium salts (480)
Application frequency	2 times a year
Application date	During growing
Target pest/disease/weed	Insecticide biological (spider mites, white fly)

Tool	boscalid (27%), pyraclostrobine (7%)
Application frequency	2 times a year
Application date	flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide chemical (botrytis, powdery mildew)

Tool	Bacillus thuringiensis
Application frequency	4 times a year
Application date	During growing
Target pest/disease/weed	Insecticide, biological (caterpillars)

Tool	Difenoconazole + fluxapyroxad
Application frequency	2 times a year
Application date	flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide chemical (powdery mildew, botrytis)

Tool	Potassium hydrogen carbonate
Application frequency	8 times a year
Application date	During growing. Biological. Mildew biggest problem
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide biological (powdery mildew)

Tool	Bacillus amyloliquefaciens
Application frequency	6 times
Application date	During growing. Biological
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungicide biological (powdery mildew)

Preventative Measures

Tool	Use of certified planting material
Application frequency	1X
Application date	Start of growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Drip Irrigation
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Watering, fertigation of minerals

Tool	Use of natural enemies
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed <i>Source: Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy</i>	Depends on target pest, disease Main natural enemies in strawberry are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - mites against thrips, fungus gnat, bulb mite, nematodes - lacewing against aphids, leafhoppers, thrips, mites, beetle's larvae and young caterpillars - Parasitic Wasps against caterpillars, aphids, other insects - Parasitic nematodes against fungus fly, grub rose beetles, vine beetle larvae

Tool	Sticky Traps /field plates
Application frequency	Replaced around every 30 days (depends on level of outbreak)
Application date	Throughout the growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Aphids, whitefly, trips

Tool	UV/Sand filter for water disinfection
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Sand filter is used for phytophthora and Pythium species</i> High dose and extended duration of UV light for all types of fungi, bacteria, viruses, and nematodes.

Tool	Monitoring. Field scouting
Application frequency	1-2 per week
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Check for leaf curl/ coloration (powdery mildew), check balance of natural enemy populations to pests, etc.

Tool	Removing dead plant material, preventative intervention of diseased plants
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly prevents diseases such as mildew, phytophthora and pest build up in dead plant material effective against strawberry blossom beetle.

Tool	Climate control
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Insect pathogenic fungi <i>Beauveria bassiana</i>
Application frequency	4X

Application date	During growing
Target pest/disease/weed	White fly, Thrips

Tool	Securing air vents
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Aphids

Tool	Foliar feedings
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Powdery Mildew

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	No: tolerant against phytophthora and mildew Seed coating? No
Cropping density <i>Source: Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy</i>	Glass/tunnel June bearers: 100.000 plants/ha Ever bearers: 60.000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	<u>June bearers:</u> Plant: Jan Harvest: May-June <u>Ever bearers:</u> Plant: Jan-Dec Harvest: March-Dec (there is year-round cultivation)
Estimated annual yield	70 t/ha
Price per kg product <i>Source: Vlaanderen, Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy</i>	Highest: €12/kg (during winter) Lowest: €2/kg (during summer) Average: €4-7
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	Eco-Scheme payments (GBL): depends on points given. Average is between €160-200/ha.
Storage loss	Loss doesn't happen on the grower's side, mainly in transportation and retail.
PPP-use <i>Source: Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy</i>	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 7-9 Insecticides: 3-5 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	75 % - 90%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	3- 4.5 m
Crop rotation	No. open field With which crops? Tagetes, Japanese Weed
Intercropping	No

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	UV-C treatment
Application frequency	50 J m ⁻² every 3-4 d from bloom until harvest
Application date	Nighttime pre-harvest and throughout production
Target pest/disease/weed	Powdery mildew, arthropod pests, grey mold

Tool	Plant enhancers: algae extracts, plant extracts, oils, acids (Jasmonic acid), herbal extracts
Application frequency	Based on level of infestation
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Mildew, thrips, aphids

Tool	Neem/Citrus based Insecticide
Application frequency	Recommend application 1x per week
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Aphids, mites, thrips

Tool	PATS-C monitoring by Biobest
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Moths

Tool	Spot Spraying
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Depends on outbreak
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Strategy 2: Indoor Propagation/Cuttings

Description

Number of growers	96
Acreage (ha)	90 ha
% of total acreage	16%
Production (tonnes/year) <i>Source: Personal communication Harrie Pijnenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy</i>	Outdoor: 250.000 – 400.000 (cuttings) (difficult to estimate for greenhouses since there is a constant rotation)
% of the total production	X

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? No: tolerant against phytophthora and mildew Seed coating? no
Cropping density <i>Source: Personal communication Harrie Pijenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy</i>	Runners (glasshouse): 500,000 to 1 million plants per hectare. Trayplants (outdoor): 450,000 plants per hectare. Trayplants (glasshouse): 600,000 plants per hectare. Minitrays (glasshouse): 50% more than trayplants, which translates to 900,000 plants per hectare (50% more than 600,000 plants/ha).
Cropping cycle	<u>Indoor:</u> Year-round production <u>Open field</u> Start date: July End date: September
Estimated annual yield	x
Price per kg product	Per piece: €0.15-1.00 (difference in price for with roots or with bud)
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	Eco-Scheme payments (GBL): depends on points given. Average is between €160-200/ha.
Storage loss	Loss doesn't happen from growers but from transportation and retail.
PPP-use <i>Source: Personal communication Harrie Pijenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy</i>	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 15 Insecticides: 8 Herbicides: - Outdoor: 8-15 - Glass house: 0
% drift reduction	75 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	50 m
Crop rotation <i>Source: Personal communication Harrie Pijenburg, Senior Advisor open field vegetables and strawberry, Delphy</i>	Short cropping period. In open field cultivation: runners 1:3 In tray fields no crop rotation. With which crops?
Intercropping	Yes/(open field): tagetes (against nematodes), grass, common oat

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use of resistant cultivars
Application frequency	1x
Application date	Before growing season

Target pest/disease/weed	For resistance it is mainly (<i>Phytophthora fragariae</i>) For tolerance it mainly powdery mildew (<i>Podosphaera aphanis</i>)
--------------------------	--

Tool	Soil health fertilization/ good starting material
Application frequency	Throughout growing
Application date	Before start of growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All. Open field: Applying organic fertilizer, compost and preparing soil for the start of growing season is at the basis of a healthy crop. Indoor cultivation: use of certified planting material, which is free of any pests, diseases and is properly sanitized.

Tool	CATT (Controlled Atmosphere Temperature Treatment)/Plant sauna
Application frequency	1x Before planting
Application date	March/April
Target pest/disease/weed	Used in nurseries on mother plants. Most effective against Tarsonemidae mites.

Tool	Sanitation of trays, gutters (steaming, high pressure water, disinfectant agents)
Application frequency	2x Before cuttings are brought in and after they are sold
Application date	1 st time in March 2 nd time in September (depends on the start/end of growing season that year)
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Proper ventilation of cutting box
Application frequency	1x start of growing season
Application date	Start of growing
Target pest/disease/weed	Botrytis

Tool	Avoid densely planted cuttings
Application frequency	1x start of growing season
Application date	Start of growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Botrytis

Tool	Clean starting material
Application frequency	1X start of growing season
Application date	Start of growing season

Target pest/disease/weed	All.
--------------------------	------

Tool	Straw in between rows (outdoor)
Application frequency	1x start of growing season (straw replaced as needed)
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Against weeds and mold build up.

Tool	Sand Filter/Heat water
Application frequency	Throughout growing
Application date	Throughout growing
Target pest/disease/weed	Growers in the NL have to recirculate water to limit fertilizer emissions, however this carries a risk of diseases. To avoid diseases such like the water mold (<i>phytophthora cactorum</i>), growers disinfect the water using a sand filter or heat the water.

Tool	Removing dead plant material, preventative intervention of diseased plants
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly prevents diseases such as mildew, phytophthora and pest build up in dead plant material effective against strawberry blossom beetle.

Tool	Monitoring. Field scouting
Application frequency	1-2 per week
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Check for leaf curl/ coloration (powdery mildew), check balance of natural enemy populations to pests, etc.

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	Runners (glasshouse): 500,000 to 1 million plants per hectare. Trayplants (outdoor): 450,000 plants per hectare. Trayplants (glasshouse): 600,000 plants per hectare. Minitrays (glasshouse): 50% more than trayplants, which translates to 900,000 plants

	per hectare (50% more than 600,000 plants/ha).
Cropping cycle	<u>Indoor:</u> Year-round production <u>Open field</u> Start date: July End date: September
Estimated annual yield	x
Price per kg product	Per piece: €0.15-1.00 (difference in price for with roots or with bud)
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	Eco-Scheme payments (GBL): depends on points given. Average is between €160-200/ha.
Storage loss	No loss from growers but from transport or retail.
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 15 Insecticides: 8 Herbicides: - Outdoor: 8-15 Glass house: 0
% drift reduction	75- 90 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	3.5 – 5 m
Crop rotation	no With which crops?
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Non- chemical/Biological control agents
Application frequency	Depends on outbreak
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Biological: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parasitic wasps: trips and strawberry mite • Predatory mite (<i>Neoseiulus californicus</i>) against spider mite. • <i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> Non-chemical <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • potassium-carbonite.

Tool	UV water disinfectant
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora</i>

Tool	Fertilization strategy
------	-------------------------------

Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All.

Tool	Plant enhancers
Application frequency	1x start of growing season (also possible to apply throughout growing season)
Application date	Start of growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Mechanical weeding robots (outdoor cultivation)
Application frequency	Throughout growing season
Application date	Throughout growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds.

Sources:

1. *Harrie Pijnenburg Advisor Specialist for field vegetable and strawberry at Delphy*

Harrie is a specialist in crop protection for strawberry and field vegetables. He gives cultivation advice on strawberry farms with outdoor cultivation, tabletop cultivation and cultivation in tunnels, production and propagation.

Contact Information:

Email: h.pijnenburg@delphy.nl

Phone: +31 (0)6 53 42 75 07

2. *CBS Statline. (March, 2024) [StatLine - Landbouw; gewassen, dieren en grondgebruik naar regio \(cbs.nl\)](https://statline.cbs.nl)*

Vegetables ▼	Gross yield										Cropping area									
	1998	2000	2005	2006	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023	1998	2000	2005	2006	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023
	mIn kg										hectares									
Strawberries (total)	35.9	34.3	39.0	39.2	42.7	57.7	77.6	85.8	87.1	79.1	1,527	1,384	1,600	1,702	1,632	1,768	1,525	1,541	1,441	1,420
Strawberries, production	21.7	19.3	22.0	19.7	21.3	29.1	20.7	19.9	19.9	19.4	1,357	1,204	1,375	1,457	1,347	1,411	1,021	968	874	849
Strawberries under glass (total)	14.2	15.0	17.0	19.5	21.4	28.6	56.8	65.9	67.2	59.7	170	180	225	245	285	357	504	574	568	571

Source: CBS

Used for: Number of farms and area under cultivation for open field cultivation, under glass cultivation and tunnels.

		2000	2005	2010	2015	2020	2022	2023
Aantal landbouwbedrijven, totaal	aantal	97 389	81 750	72 324	63 913	52 695	50 975	50 634
Tuinbouw open grond								
Oppervlakte								
Tuinbouwgroenten								
Aardbeien								
Aardbeien, totaal	are	174 551	230 089	311 100	277 170	244 005	213 208	198 954
Aardbeien, productie	are	.	.	134 669	141 250	100 923	83 919	83 408
Aardbeien, vermeerdering	are	.	.	116 315	116 756	115 133	106 402	90 886
Aardbeien, wachtbed	are	.	.	60 116	19 164	27 949	22 887	24 660
Aantal bedrijven								
Tuinbouwgroenten								
Aardbeien								
Aardbeien, totaal	aantal	1 003	710	516	463	402	353	349
Aardbeien, productie	aantal	.	.	417	361	300	269	261
Aardbeien, vermeerdering	aantal	.	.	134	120	103	89	96
Aardbeien, wachtbed	aantal	.	.	140	81	64	49	44
Tuinbouw onder glas								
Oppervlakte								
Glasgroenten								
Aardbeien								
Aardbeien, totaal	m2	1 629 854	2 266 020	2 551 953	3 365 863	5 042 522	5 675 210	5 711 109
Aardbeien onder glas	m2	1 102 548	1 608 212	2 057 257	2 822 063	4 210 200	4 835 816	4 805 264
Aardbeien onder plastic tunnels	m2	527 306	657 808	494 696	543 800	832 322	839 394	905 845
Aantal bedrijven								
Glasgroenten								
Aardbeien								
Aardbeien, totaal	aantal	457	435	299	254	241	209	211
Aardbeien onder glas	aantal	297	288	233	202	201	183	181
Aardbeien onder plastic tunnels	aantal	225	211	118	89	74	54	56

3. Ctgb: [6. Fate behaviour in water NL part EM2.7 | Assessment framework PPP | Board for the Authorisation of Plant Protection Products and Biocides \(ctgb.nl\)](#)

Latest version of chapter 6 Fate behavior in water NL of the Evaluation Manual

4. Full list of approved PPPs in Strawberry: [2023-003-010-middelenlijst-aardbeien.pdf \(agruniekrijnvallei.nl\)](#)

5. Fresh Plaza, [GLOBAL MARKET OVERVIEW STRAWBERRIES \(freshplaza.com\)](#)

6. Vlaanderen, [Prijzen van aardbeien, kersen en bessen | Landbouw & Visserij \(vlaanderen.be\)](#)

7. KWIN 2022: [KWIN-AGV - Boek beheer](#)

8. [Netherlands: CAP Strategic Plan 2023-27 – FarmEurope \(farm-europe.eu\)](#)

6.4.3 Spain

Contact person: Celeste Oliveira (oliveira@agro-alimentarias.coop)

Juan Sagarna (Sagarna@agro-alimentarias.coop)

Strategy 1 - Current situation: state-of-the-art scenario [Strawberry]

Strategy 1 - Current situation: IPM improved scenario [Strawberry]

Integrated pest management strategies for strawberries

Strategy selection

The cultivation process begins with careful soil preparation and selection of high-quality plants, typically using varieties suited to the region's climate and market demands.

The fields are prepared by creating raised beds, which improve drainage and root development. Plastic mulch is commonly used to cover the beds, aiding in weed control, moisture retention, and fruit cleanliness. Drip irrigation systems are installed to provide precise water and nutrient delivery, optimizing plant health and fruit yield.

Planting usually occurs in the fall, around October, allowing the plants to establish roots before the cooler winter months. The use of tunnel structures, or low tunnels, is widespread. These are simple, temporary structures made of plastic sheeting that protect young plants from cold weather and pests, fostering a microclimate that promotes early growth and extends the growing season.

Harvesting typically begins in late December and continues until June. Strawberries are picked by hand to ensure that only ripe, high-quality fruit is collected. The berries are immediately cooled to preserve freshness and extend shelf life.

The year 2023 is considered a representative year as the area data for strawberries remain relatively stable compared to previous years. In terms of production, during the year 2022/2023 there is a recovery in quantities compared to the previous season (+6.3%) due to the recovery of strawberry/strawberry as it is the main fruit in terms of volume.

Strategy 1: Current situation

Description

Number of producers	718 holdings
Area (ha)	7,328 ha in fruit vegetables - strawberries and strawberries
of total area	54.50% strawberry/strawberry as a percentage of total berries
Production (tonnes/year)	346,484 t/year in fruit-strawberry and strawberry vegetables
of total production	75.79% strawberry/strawberry as a percentage of total berries

Current situation

Cultivate	Resistant? Yes/No
	Seed coating? NA
Crop density	50000-70000 plants/ha
Growing cycle	Start date October / end April-May
Estimated annual yield	20,605 kg/ha
Price per kg of product	2,139 euros/kg
Amount of direct payments for the scenario specific tools	0 Euro

Loss of storage	NA
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 5 (Fosetyl-al) Insecticides: 5 (Spinosad) Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface waters	5 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? none
Intercropping	no

Top 10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use healthy plant material from an approved nursery.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	October-November: this is the planting season.
Crop stage of development	When planting takes place
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Pest control in nursery and plant production
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	Each application
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No pest/disease/target weed

Tool	Use appropriate planting density
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	Each application
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pests/diseases/weeds

Tool	Locate pest hotspots to minimise spread to other plots.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	Each application
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Red spider mite (<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>)

Tool	Avoid waterlogging, provide good drainage, ventilation of tunnels and tunnels to avoid wetting of the fruit.
------	--

Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	Each application
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Minimise nitrogen fertilisers as much as possible
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	Each solitude
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Use of resistant cultivars
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	Each application
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	No specific pest/disease/weed

Tool	Treatment with fungicide (fosetyl-al)
Frequency of application	Yearly
Date of application	January-march and October-December
Crop stage of development	Vegetative growth and vegetative rest
Pest/disease/target weed	Botrytis cinerea

Tool	Treatment with insecticide (spinosad)
Frequency of application	Yearly
Date of application	January-march and October- December
Crop stage of development	Vegetative growth and vegetative rest
Pest/disease/target weed	Red spider mite (<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>)

Tool	Plastic mulch against weeds and to aid moisture retention and fruit cleanliness.
Frequency of application	Yearly
Date of application	October-November: this is the planting season.
Crop stage of development	When planting takes place
Pest/disease/target weed	Weeds

IPM enhanced scenario

Cultivate	Resistant? Yes/No
	Seed coating? NA
Crop density	50000-70000plants/ha
Growing cycle	Start date October / end April-May
Estimated annual yield	20,605 kg/ha
Price per kg of product	2,139/kg
Amount of direct payments for the scenario-specific tools	0 Euro
Loss of storage	NA
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 5 (Fosetyl-al) Insecticides: 5 (Spinosad) Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	NA
Minimum buffer zone to surface waters	5 m
Crop rotation	no
	With which crops? none
Intercropping	no

Top 10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use <i>Trichoderma</i> spp.
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	Each application
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Soil borne diseases, stimulates plant growth/health

Tool	Use of ladybirds and lacewings
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	Each application
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Aphids

Tool	Use of predatory mites and bedbugs
Frequency of application	Each application
Date of application	Each application
Crop stage of development	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Pest/disease/target weed	Spider mites and thrips

Tool	Treatment with fungicide (fosetyl-al)
Frequency of application	Yearly
Date of application	January-march and October-December
Crop stage of development	Vegetative growth and vegetative rest
Pest/disease/target weed	Botrytis cinerea

Tool	Treatment with insecticide (spinosad)
Frequency of application	Yearly
Date of application	January-march and October- December
Crop stage of development	Vegetative growth and vegetative rest
Pest/disease/target weed	Red spider mite (<i>Tetranychus urticae</i>)

6.5 Wheat

6.5.1 Denmark

Contact person: Jens Erik Jensen (inj@seges.dk)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: [Winter wheat, current IPM in Denmark, autumn+winter operations]

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: [Winter wheat, current IPM in Denmark, spring operations]

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: [Winter wheat, improved IPM in Denmark, autumn+winter operations]

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: [Winter wheat, improved IPM in Denmark, spring operations]

IPM strategies for [Winter wheat in Denmark]

Strategy selection

The strategy below is based on the NCC meeting for winter wheat held on 29 June 2023. All the strategies mentioned below were suggested by participating farmers and advisers as being common in practice. A lot of more experimental tools were also discussed, but as they are not commonly used in practice, they are not mentioned here.

Winter wheat is the most commonly grown winter cereal crop in Denmark, and the second most common crop. Only spring barley is grown on a larger acreage. Winter wheat is typically grown for feed production at farms with pig production, whereas wheat for bread or biscuits is only grown to a lesser extent. The strategies below are based on cereal-dominated rotations on farms with pig production.

Map of winter wheat production in Denmark 2024 – each yellow dot represents a winter wheat field.:

Winter wheat 2024

Description reference year:

With respect to applied IPM-tools, we have attempted to use an “average year” as the recent growing seasons have been quite variable. However, to get accurate numbers regarding growers, acreage etc. correct, we have chosen to take the year 2023 as a reference.

Strategy 1: [Current IPM in Denmark]

Description

Number of growers	Approx. 10.000 – most grown crop in Denmark
Acreage (ha)	470.000 ha
% of total acreage	24 %
Production (tonnes/year)	7,5 tonnes/hectare – average 2013-2022: 7,8 tonnes/hectare
% of the total production	Approx. 95 % of wheat production, only a small proportion of the wheat is grown for bread.

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes – selecting cultivars less susceptible to diseases is a big priority
	Seed coating? Yes – normally seed is dressed with fungicides
Cropping density	Depends on time of sowing. When sowing September 1 st (very early sowing), it is common to aim for 200 plants/m ² . This number increases by approx. 6 for each day the sowing time is delayed, with the aim for 400 plants/m ² when sowing October 1 st
Cropping cycle	Typically second half of September – Mid August
Estimated annual yield	7,5 t/ha
Price per kg product	1,65 DKK corresponding to 0,22 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	None
Storage loss	0-5 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 3-4 (2 applications most common) Insecticides: 1-3 (0-2 applications most common) Herbicides: 3-4 (2 applications most common) Growth regulators: 0-1 applications There is a long tradition of applying all pesticides at reduced dosages according to results obtained in independent field trials and advice given by the Danish decision support system named 'Crop Protection Online'
% drift reduction	Normally minimum 50 %, but often 75 or 90 %, depending on product used
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	2-3 m, buffers are 2 to 20 meters, depending on pesticide product and drift reduction measures used.
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3) Most common to have 2 free years between winter wheat although actual rotations are quite diverse. Some farms

	with a high proportion of cereals may have some second year wheat, but that is generally discouraged.
	With which crops? Typically other cereal species, oilseed rape, grass for seed production and legumes (particularly spring beans)
Intercropping	Undersown catch crops used to minimize leaching of nitrogen, before spring sown crops in the rotation

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Crop rotation with annual and/or perennial crops, or with broadleaved crops such as oilseed rape and field beans
Application frequency	100 %
Application date	Not applicable
Stage of development of the crop	Not applicable
Target pest/disease/weed	Particularly against grass weeds, but also soil-borne diseases like take-all

Tool	Use of certified seeding material, dressed with fungicides
Application frequency	80-90 %
Application date	Not applicable
Stage of development of the crop	0, Before crop establishment
Target pest/disease/weed	Soil and seed borne diseases

Tool	Stale seedbed to minimize emergence of grass weeds. This tool is often combined with delayed sowing, see elsewhere.
Application frequency	5-10 %
Application date	September
Stage of development of the crop	0, Before crop establishment
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual grass weeds, particularly <i>Alopecurus myosuroides</i> , <i>Lolium</i> species, <i>Vulpia</i> etc.

Tool	Cultivar comparison/selection by using the online system SortInfo.dk giving a lot of information on varieties on the market, including approved variety mixtures. Information includes disease susceptibility, yield level, and many other parameters. It also gives a general IPM score of the different cultivars, where different IPM-relevant properties of cultivars are weighted together.
Application frequency	1X, 80 % of fields

Application date	June-July when planning which varieties to grow next year.
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases, particularly Septoria, rust, DTR, Pests: Orange wheat blossom midge, BYDV

Tool	Variety mixtures with three or four different varieties with different disease susceptibility
Application frequency	1X, 40-50 % of fields
Application date	Autumn (sowing)
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Primarily diseases, to small extents other pests and weeds

Tool	Delayed sowing time (after 20 September)– or at least not early sowing time (which means before 7 September)
Application frequency	1X, 50-60 % of fields - approx. 20 % of fields are sown early
Application date	September – October
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds, dicot weeds, certain diseases, aphids transmitting BYDV

Tool	Adjustment of seeding rate to sowing time + increased seeding rate to better compete against weeds
Application frequency	25 %
Application date	September - October
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds

Tool	Untouched stubble before sowing of wheat crop to favour the decay of weed seeds shed by previous crop (can be a disadvantage if slugs are a problem and/or if there is a lot of crop residues on the soil surface)
Application frequency	1X, 50-70 % of fields.
Application date	August - September
Stage of development of the crop	Pre 0
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual weeds, in particular grass weeds

Tool	Seed bank management and strategic ploughing – to control where the weed seed bank is located in the upper 30 cm of the soil. If
------	--

	e.g. weed seed production has been intensive, it may pay off to plough once to ensure that seeds are buried to 25-30 cm depth and will decay before next ploughing
Application frequency	25 %
Application date	September - October
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds

Tool	Glyphosate before sowing. This is relevant mostly on farms practising Conservation Agriculture or reduced tillage, or where soil is heavy, and ploughing is not sufficient to clear weeds before drilling.
Application frequency	1X
Application date	September
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass and dicot weeds

Tool	Soil applied herbicide before or around crop emergence in autumn, Mixture of 2-3 soil acting herbicides at low dosage is most common. Optimal timing for soil applied herbicides is generally around BBCH 10-11.
Application frequency	1 application, 95 % of fields
Application date	Approx 1-15 October
Stage of development of the crop	09-11
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual grass weeds, dicot weeds

Tool	Drift reduction. Some products have obligatory drift reduction on the label. For other products, drift reduction is obligatory if growers want to reduce buffer zones to the water environment or nature areas. Buffer zones to houses, institutions, public areas and roads cannot be reduced by drift reduction measures.
Application frequency	Applicable for all pesticide applications
Application date	Full cropping year
Stage of development of the crop	09-90
Target pest/disease/weed	All pests, diseases and weeds

Tool	Prosulfocarb stewardship – prosulfocarb is one of the most used herbicides in winter cereals in Denmark. Growers are strongly encouraged to use stewardship measures to optimize efficacy in the field, and most importantly, to avoid
------	--

	contamination of crops (fruits, vegetables, etc.) where prosulfocarb is not authorized.
Application frequency	1 application, 95 % of fields
Application date	Approx 1-15 October
Stage of development of the crop	09-11
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual grass weeds, dicot weeds

Tool	Field specific weed information in the autumn is based on either notes on the weed floras in the field or by field inspection. When applying soil applied herbicides in autumn, weeds may not yet have germinated, making it relevant to use notes from previous crops.
Application frequency	1 application in the autumn
Application date	Autumn (September-October)
Stage of development of the crop	9-14 (autumn)
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual and perennial dicot and grass weeds

Tool	“DSS Crop Protection Online”: Low, adjusted dosages and mixtures of herbicides, mixtures and dosages optimized based either directly or indirectly on results of independent field trials and recommendations from the online DSS “Crop Protection Online”
Application frequency	1-3 applications, most commonly only 1 application in the fall and 1 in the spring, 100 % of fields
Application date	Autumn (October) and/or spring (April/May)
Stage of development of the crop	9-14 (autumn) and 25-39 (spring)
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual and perennial dicot and grass weeds

Tool	Foliar acting herbicide application based on recommendations from DSS Crop Protection Online, see above
Application frequency	1-2 applications, most commonly only 1 in the spring, 100 % of fields
Application date	Autumn (October) and/or spring (April/May)
Stage of development of the crop	9-14 (autumn) and 25-39 (spring)
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual and perennial dicot and grass weeds

Tool	Rotation of modes of action of herbicides to minimize or delay the development of herbicide resistant weeds
Application frequency	1X, 80-100 % of fields
Application date	Autumn and spring
Stage of development of the crop	9-13 (autumn) and 25-39 (spring)

Target pest/disease/weed	Dicot and grass weeds
--------------------------	-----------------------

Tool	Assessment/monitoring of overwintering of crop, evaluation whether it may be relevant to terminate the crop or more commonly to undersow a spring cereal to ensure a good crop coverage in spring.
Application frequency	1X, 60-90 % of fields
Application date	Early spring
Stage of development of the crop	25-31
Target pest/disease/weed	Dicot and grass weeds

Tool	Monitor overwintering and germinating weeds in early spring based on field inspection, often done by or with advisers.
Application frequency	1 application in the spring
Application date	Spring (March – April)
Stage of development of the crop	25-32 (spring)
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual and perennial dicot and grass weeds

Tool	Assessment of the need for growth regulation at the field level by using the model in the Danish online CropManager system, or by manually assessing risk factors favouring crop lodging before harvest.
Application frequency	1X, 20-40 % of fields
Application date	May
Stage of development of the crop	30-39
Target pest/disease/weed	Crop lodging

Tool	Management of Septoria using models based on days with rain or hours with high humidity. Advise are offered either regionally by local advisory centres or at the field level by using the Septoria model in the Danish online CropManager system. Advise is supported by many field trials every year, giving a strong basis for using reduced fungicide dosages against diseases, including Septoria which is the most important
Application frequency	1-3X, 90 % of fields
Application date	May – June
Stage of development of the crop	32-69
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases, particularly Septoria

Tool	Fungicide sprayings against leaf diseases, mainly Septoria, powdery mildew and rust diseases. Application timings are shown as T1 (BBCH 32-33), T2 (BBCH 37-39), and T3 (BBCH 55-65) in figure.
Application frequency	1-3X (most commonly 2X), 90 % of fields
Application date	May – June
Stage of development of the crop	32-69
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases, particularly Septoria

Tool	Use of action thresholds when controlling pests, thresholds adjusted to developmental stage of the crop. Thresholds are to a large extent informed by advisers, fewer farmers do the field inspection themselves.
Application frequency	2X, 50-80 % of fields
Application date	September-October (aphids), June – July (aphids and other pests)
Stage of development of the crop	13-14 and 51-75
Target pest/disease/weed	Insect pests.

Tool	Insecticides against aphids + other pests, based on monitoring and action thresholds described above
Application frequency	0-2X, 50-80 % of fields
Application date	September-October (aphids), June – July (aphids and other pests)
Stage of development of the crop	13-14 and 51-75
Target pest/disease/weed	Insect pests.

Tool	Increased focus on beneficials – particularly farmers practising Conservation Agriculture or non-inversion tillage are becoming more and more aware about beneficial organisms. If e.g. aphids are present, those farmers will tend to use a narrow-spectrum insecticide (e.g. pirimicarb), which will not kill the beneficials.
Application frequency	10-20 %
Application date	Spring period, May – July
Stage of development of the crop	32 - 75
Target pest/disease/weed	Insect pests

Tool	Evaluation of weed management success by having pre-harvest visits with advisers in most fields – this will be the basis of adjusting the weed strategy going forward in the rotation
------	---

Application frequency	50 %
Application date	July – Early August
Stage of development of the crop	80-90
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds, dicot weeds, perennial weeds

Tool	Sampling seeds of surviving weeds to test for herbicide resistance
Application frequency	0-10 %
Application date	July – Early August
Stage of development of the crop	80-90
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds, dicot weeds

Tool	Monitor/map perennial weeds: Assess the need for using glyphosate against perennial weeds – this is done by walking the field and adding weed patches to a map, or by drone-based monitoring
Application frequency	50-60
Application date	July
Stage of development of the crop	80
Target pest/disease/weed	Perennial weeds, in particular <i>Elymus repens</i> and thistles

Tool	Patch spraying against perennial weeds – only permitted in crops for fodder, not in crops for human consumption
Application frequency	1X, 10-25 % of fields
Application date	Late July – Early August
Stage of development of the crop	80-90
Target pest/disease/weed	Perennial weeds, in particular <i>Elymus repens</i> and thistles

Tool	Prevention spread of weed seeds by machinery, experience shows that combines, balers and other vehicles in the fields around harvest can contribute to the spread of weed seeds from field to field. Cleaning before entering new farms and/or fields will prevent or reduce spread of weeds.
Application frequency	1X, 50-80 % of fields
Application date	September-October (aphids), June – July (aphids and other pests)
Stage of development of the crop	13-14 and 51-75
Target pest/disease/weed	Insect pests.

Tool	Follow-up on previous years IPM-measures, using an official online IPM-evaluation form provided by Danish Environmental Protection Agency – this is an obligatory requirement by Danish law.
Application frequency	1X, 100 % of growers
Application date	September – March in the cropping year following the wheat crop.
Stage of development of the crop	After harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	All

IPM improved scenario

An improved IPM scenario for winter wheat in Denmark would look very much like the current scenario. The reason is that pesticide inputs have been optimized during many years in the form of reduced dosages and optimized mixtures, as we have had governmental pesticide action plans since 1986.

This does not mean that no improvements can be made, but it is going to be more risky or costly to the growers, and it will mean big losses in some unfavourable years.

For instance, even more focus can be made on diverse rotations, where second year wheat could e.g. be eliminated.

An important tool for combating increasing problems with grass weeds is to drill later in the autumn, but given the Danish climate and particularly wet autumn conditions, there is a significant risk that it is going to be impossible to drill late, and the alternative would be a spring sown crop, which has lower yield and profitability, and which is also risky given the dry springs that we have seen more frequently in recent years.

Another area of interest is mapping of weeds and precision spraying. This is an emerging technology that has potential for reducing herbicide inputs on the long term. Also, graduation of dosages of fungicides and growth regulators based on crop biomass mapping is catching on, but still at the emerging stages. It is questionable what the economic benefits are for the farmer, but most certainly there is environmental advantages.

Many trials have been done looking at mechanical weed management in cereals, and efficacy against weeds can be OK if crop row distance is increased to allow for interrow cultivation. But even with the world's highest pesticide taxes which we have in Denmark, it is currently not considered profitable to do mechanical weed management in conventionally grown wheat.

Improved IPM-scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes – selecting cultivars less susceptible to diseases is a big priority
	Seed coating? Yes – normally seed is dressed with fungicides
Cropping density	Depends on time of sowing. When sowing 1. September (very early sowing), it is common to aim for 200 plants/m ² . This number increases by approx. 6 for each day the sowing time is

	delayed, with the aim for 400 plants/m ² when sowing 1. October
Cropping cycle	Typically second half of September – Mid August
Estimated annual yield	7,5 t/ha
Price per kg product	1,65 DKK corresponding to 0,22 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	None
Storage loss	0-5 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 3-4 (2 applications most common) Insecticides: 1-3 (0-2 applications most common) Herbicides: 3-4 (2 applications most common) Growth regulators: 0-1 applications There is a long tradition of applying all pesticides at reduced dosages according to results obtained in independent field trials and advice given by the Danish decision support system named 'Crop Protection Online'
% drift reduction	Normally minimum 50 %, but often 75 or 90 %, depending on product used
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	2-3 m, buffers are 2 to 20 meters, depending on product and drift reduction.
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3) Most common to have 2 free years between winter wheat although actual rotations are quite diverse. Some farms with a high proportion of cereals may have some 2. year wheat, but that is generally discouraged. With which crops? Typically other cereal species, oilseed rape, grass for seed production and legumes (particularly spring beans)
Intercropping	Undersown catch crops used to minimize leaching of nitrogen, before spring sown crops in the rotation

Additional used IPM-tools in the improved scenario:

Tool	Longer crop rotations, at least 2-3 years between wheat, and no 2 nd year wheat in rotation.
Application frequency	1X
Application date	Before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds, dicot weeds, soil borne diseases

Tool	No early sowing (before 7 September) and general use of delayed sowing on areas where experience shows that it is feasible
Application frequency	1X
Application date	Late September – Mid October
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds

Tool	Substitute broadcast herbicide spraying in spring with spot spraying based on weed mapping, and/or sow wheat on wider row distance and use interrow hoeing as an alternative to herbicides.
Application frequency	1X
Application date	April – May
Stage of development of the crop	25-39
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds, dicot weeds

Tool	Use graduated doses of fungicides and growth regulators based on satellite or drone-based monitoring of biomass of the field
Application frequency	2-3X
Application date	May-June
Stage of development of the crop	30-69
Target pest/disease/weed	Leaf diseases, crop lodging

6.5.2 Germany

Contact person: Lars Ole Hingst (Lars-Ole.Hingst@julius-kuehn.de)

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: winter wheat, tillage, in case of herbicide tolerant blackgrass

IPM strategies for winter wheat

Strategy selection

Wheat is usually cultivated in a tight, cereal-heavy crop rotation (sugar beet/wheat/barley/rape/wheat). The reasons for such a crop rotation are the usually profitable contribution margins of the crops mentioned. The corresponding harvested products are in high demand and the infrastructure is generally well available. Pests and weeds that occur more frequently with this cultivation strategy, due to the similar crops, can usually still be controlled very well with plant protection products and make it possible to pursue an appropriate strategy. Nevertheless, weeds and insects are becoming increasingly resistant to pesticides, leading to an adaptation of the cultivation strategy. This includes further crop rotations with more diverse crops, a site-adapted crop selection and changed management strategies (soil cultivation, variety selection, etc.). These changes can be conflicting with the demand and may lead to lower revenues. However, PPPs and fertilizers can also be saved or used more efficiently as a result. Added to this are changing climatic conditions (extreme weather events, e.g. drought, precipitation, etc.).

Description reference year: 2021

The weather year 2021 was fairly average overall in Germany, but also brought exceptional weather extremes with catastrophic consequences. [Link DWD](#)

Strategy 1: winter wheat, tillage

Description

Number of growers	X
Acreage (ha)	2,84 Mio ha
% of total acreage	28,25 % Link DeStatis
Production (tonnes/year)	21,1 Mio tonnes/year
% of the total production	X %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	Early 220-260 seeds/m ² , normal 300-340 seeds/m ² , late 380-420 seeds/m ²
Cropping cycle	Seeding from October, harvest July
Estimated annual yield	6-10 t/ha, depends on the soil
Price per kg product	0,80-0,98 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	/
Storage loss	Storage until removal from storage; 0,1-0,3%, up to 0,1-0,2% respiration losses per month
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): 5,3 total BI (application index)

	Fungicides: 1,75 Insecticides: 0,4 Herbicides: 1,99 Growth regulator: 0,96
% drift reduction	Depends of the used plant protection product, often min 50%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Depends of the used plant protection product, and the drift reduction (e.g. 50% drift reduction often min 5 m)
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3)
	With which crops? Rapeseed, barley
Intercropping	no

Farmers must comply with the following conditions when applying plant protection products:

- max. 5 m/s wind speed
- Temperatures below 25 °C
- Humidity of more than 30 %
- Travelling speeds of max. 8 km/ha for uniform lateral and longitudinal distribution and low-drift application
- Boom height max. 50 cm above the crop

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Healthy seeds
Application frequency	Each time
Application date	Sowing date
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Tool	Check thresholds before spaying, important for decisions, not crop specific, basis for measures
Application frequency	Whole cultivation phase
Application date	-
Target pest/disease/weed	For all pest/disease/weed

Tool	Ploughing, creation of an optimal seedbed all organic material above ground is ploughed under, with enough time before sowing, a false seedbed can be created
Application frequency	Once before seeding
Application date	-
Target pest/disease/weed	Mostly weeds, but also effective against fungi with have spores at old plant residues

Tool	Conventional seed treatment; a coating of the seeds against fungi, sometimes microelements are added for better resistance in the very early
------	--

	growing stages. Advantage; as it is very close to the plant and can therefore have a very specific effect
Application frequency	Once a year
Application date	At seeding
Target pest/disease/weed	Fungi, disease, better and faster development against insects mostly forbidden

Tool	Stale seedbed, fake seedbed. An optimal seedbed is created 2-3 weeks before sowing Weeds grow and can then be removed mechanically during sowing, so the plant has an advantage over the weeds
Application frequency	Once
Application date	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	<p>Sowing date, sowing density and sowing time are one of the most important measures. The earlier the seeds are sown, the better the plant can develop and enter the winter season strongly. This way, it also has an advantage in the spring. However, pests/diseases/weeds can also establish themselves and cause damage; this must be compensated for by plant protection products.</p> <p>The later the sowing date, the less the plant can develop. Accordingly, the sowing density must be increased to compensate for this. This way, pests/diseases/weeds have no chance to establish themselves. However, the conditions for sowing must be right and this optimal sowing date can sometimes not be chosen because of peak workloads due to harvesting. In terms of the reduction of plant protection products a later sowing date is recommended, so a herbicide and maybe an insecticide can be reduced.</p>
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed

Tool	Balanced fertilization. The amount of fertilizer required depends on the production goal. The amount of fertilizer required can then be determined, however, if too much fertilizer is used, the plant is no longer as resistant to pests/diseases. The timing is also very
------	---

	important so that an optimum yield can be achieved, as is the water available at the time of fertilization.
Application frequency	2-3 times per growing season
Application date	Depends but mostly start of vegetation (tillering), stem elongation, booting
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Plant protection strategy. Depending on the sowing date, a herbicide treatment is necessary in autumn. At the beginning of vegetation a herbicide measure is then necessary and, depending on the level of damage, an insecticide measure might be needed. Depending on the growth, a measure with a growth regulator is also necessary. From April onwards, depending on the weather, there is an increased risk of fungal infections that make measures with a fungicide necessary.
Application frequency	5x
Application date	Autumn, vegetation begin till ripening
Target pest/disease/weed	Depends on the weather pest/disease/weed

Tool	Monitoring diseases in order to take specific and precise measures; regular monitoring is of great importance.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed

Strategy 1 - IPM improved scenario: winter wheat, no-tillage, direct sowing

In addition to the consistent application of many other measures, the IPM improved scenario has also been expanded to include direct sowing. Especially in regions with low rainfall, this has the advantage of keeping water in the soil better due to less tillage and can therefore give the plants an advantage in their development. For this method to work, however, herbicides must be used pre- and post-emergence to minimise weed pressure.

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	Early 220-260 seeds/m ² , normal 300-340 seeds/m ² , late 380-420 seeds/m ²
Cropping cycle	Seeding from October, harvest July
Estimated annual yield	6-10 t/ha, depends on the soil
Price per kg product	0,80-0,98 €/kg

Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	Storage Removal from storage 0,1-0,3%, up to 0,1-0,2% respiration losses per month
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): 5,3 total BI (application index) Fungicides: 1,75 Insecticides: 0,4 Herbicides: 1,99 Growth regulator: 0,96
% drift reduction	Depends of the used plant protection product, often min 50%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Depends of the used plant protection product, and the drift reduction (e.g. 50% drift reduction often min 5 m)
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:5)
	With which crops? Rapeseed, barley, sugar beet, potatoes, maize, peas. Change of summer and winter crops and Stem and leaf fruits
Intercropping	yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Healthy seeds
Application frequency	Each time
Application date	Sowing date
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Tool	Resistant and tolerant varieties
Application frequency	Each time
Application date	Sowing date
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease

Tool	Crop rotation (1:5); a greater crop rotation brings advantages through diversification as diseases cannot survive as well. This is an essential preventive measure.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed

Tool	Check thresholds before spaying as this is important for making decisions.
Application frequency	Whole cultivation phase
Application date	-

Target pest/disease/weed	For all pest/disease/weed
--------------------------	---------------------------

Tool	<p>Plant protection strategy. Depending on the sowing date, a herbicide treatment is necessary in autumn.</p> <p>At the beginning of vegetation a herbicide measure is then necessary and, depending on the level of damage, an insecticide measure might be needed. Depending on the growth, a measure with a growth regulator is also necessary. From April onwards, depending on the weather, there is an increased risk of fungal infections that make measures with a fungicide necessary.</p>
Application frequency	5x
Application date	Autumn, begin vegetation till ripening
Target pest/disease/weed	Depends on the weather pest/disease/weed

Tool	<p>Biological seed treatment; a coating of the seeds for better resistance in the very early growing stages. Advantage; as it is very close to the plant it can therefore have a very specific effect. It is not as effective as a chemical coating, but still has some advantages.</p>
Application frequency	Once a year
Application date	At seeding
Target pest/disease/weed	Better and faster development

Tool	<p>Sowing date, sowing density and sowing time are one of the most important measures. The earlier the seeds are sown, the better the plant can develop and enter the winter season strongly. This way, it also has an advantage in the spring. However, pests/diseases/weeds can also establish themselves and cause damage; this must be compensated for by plant protection products.</p> <p>The later the sowing date, the less the plant can develop. Accordingly, the sowing density must be increased to compensate for this. This way, pests/diseases/weeds have no chance to establish themselves. However, the conditions for sowing must be right and this optimal sowing date can sometimes not be chosen because of peak workloads due to harvesting. In terms of the reduction of plant protection products a later sowing date is recommended,</p>
------	---

	so a herbicide and maybe an insecticide can be reduced.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed

Tool	Adapt plant protection strategy and dose. A specific adjustment of the product and dosage can significantly improve the effectiveness with use of less resources.
Application frequency	See at thresholds
Application date	Every time when applied
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Unsprayed spot; a small area is not treated with chemical plant protection over the entire growing period, so that the effects of measures can be monitored and observed versus what happens without chemical plant protection
Application frequency	/
Application date	From the beginning on
Target pest/disease/weed	All

Tool	Balanced fertilization. The amount of fertilizer required depends on the production goal. The amount of fertilizer required can then be determined, however, if too much fertilizer is used, the plant is no longer as resistant to pests/diseases. The timing is also very important so that an optimum yield can be achieved, as is the water available at the time of fertilization.
Application frequency	2-3 times per growing season
Application date	Depends but mostly start of vegetation (tillering), stem elongation, booting
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Forecast model. The use of forecast models is very helpful in controlling the development of diseases and pathogens. To do this, the current situation in the field must be taken into account so that the optimum time for applying crop protection can be selected.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease

Tool	Thresholds. Plant protection products should only be applied after a threshold has been reached. This includes observing the development in the field at regular intervals and only applying a crop protection product once a specific threshold has been reached, depending on the pest or disease.
Application frequency	X
Application date	Depends
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed

Tool	Unsprayed buffer zones are a habitat for beneficial insects.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest

Tool	Machine hygiene. Clean machines prevent weed seeds and diseases from being spread between different areas.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease/weed

Tool	Site specific application. Only apply plant protection products where an infestation or disease is present.
Application frequency	Every spraying
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed

Tool	CP decisions based on the advice of extension services/experts. To make better decisions, the help of advisors and experts is essential; relying on people who have very specialised knowledge can lead to much better decisions.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed

Tool	Monitoring diseases in order to take specific and precise measures; regular monitoring is of great importance.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X

Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed
--------------------------	-------------------

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: winter wheat, tillage, herbicide tolerant blackgrass

Herbicide-tolerant weeds repeatedly pose major hurdles for arable farming. When growing winter wheat, some weeds, e.g. foxtail and common bindweed, have already tolerant and resistant varieties to herbicides. If the used plant protection products are no longer effective, other agronomic measures must be taken to enable the cultivation of winter wheat. The most important measures are adapted soil cultivation, a more diverse crop rotation, good crop management and an adapted plant protection strategy. These measures are part of an integrated plant protection and emphasize how important they are when chemical plant protection products are not available or are no longer effective.

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	Early 220-260 seeds/m ² , normal 300-340 seeds/m ² , late 380-420 seeds/m ²
Cropping cycle	Seeding from October, harvest July
Estimated annual yield	6-10 t/ha, depends on the soil
Price per kg product	0,80-0,98 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	Storage Removal from storage 0,1-0,3%, up to 0,1-0,2% respiration losses per month
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): 5,3 total BI (application index) Fungicides: 1,75 Insecticides: 0,4 Herbicides: 1,99 Growth regulator: 0,96
% drift reduction	Depends of the used plant protection product, often min 50%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Depends of the used plant protection product, and the drift reduction (e.g. 50% drift reduction often min 5 m)
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:5)
	With which crops? Rapeseed, barley, sugar beet, potatoes, maize, peas. Change of summer and winter crops and Stem and leaf fruits
Intercropping	yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Healthy seeds
Application frequency	Each time
Application date	Sowing date
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Tool	Resistant and tolerant varieties
Application frequency	Each time
Application date	Sowing date
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease

Tool	Crop rotation (1:5); a greater crop rotation brings advantages through diversification as diseases cannot survive as well. This is an essential preventive measure.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed

Tool	Check thresholds before spaying as this is important for making decisions.
Application frequency	Whole cultivation phase
Application date	-
Target pest/disease/weed	For all pests/diseases/weeds

Tool	Check resistance before spraying, in order to find out whether the respective weeds have a resistance, they must be tested; if a resistance is found, the use of plant protection products against it is pointless.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Sowing date and sowing density. An important measure is the optimal sowing time; the later, the less the foxtail can establish itself and there is the possibility of carrying out various soil tillage steps beforehand to favour the emergence of weed seeds. Depending on the sowing time, the sowing density must be adjusted so that a strong competing wheat population can establish itself and thus also reduce the foxtail.
Application frequency	X
Application date	Sowing date
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Ploughing. Ploughing is very useful to bring weed seeds into deeper soil layers, which then rot there.
------	--

Application frequency	X
Application date	Before seeding
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Balanced fertilisation is very important to establish a good and strong wheat crop; especially a good early application is very helpful to make the crop competitive
Application frequency	2-3 times
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	No target

Tool	Undersown crops/intercropping. In addition to a wide crop rotation, catch crops are also important to suppress unwanted weeds and retain nutrients in the soil.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed

Tool	Monitoring diseases in order to take specific and precise measures; regular monitoring is of great importance.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed

Tool	Plant protection strategy From April onwards, depending on the weather, there is an increased risk of fungal infections that make measures with a fungicide necessary.
Application frequency	5x
Application date	Autumn, vegetation begin till ripening
Target pest/disease/weed	Depends on the weather pest/disease/weed

Tool	Stale seedbed, fake seedbed. An optimal seedbed is created 2-3 weeks before sowing. Weeds grow and can then be removed mechanically during sowing, so the plant has an advantage over the weeds.
Application frequency	Once
Application date	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Mechanical weeding; as pesticides are no longer effective due to resistance, weeds must be controlled mechanically.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Change mode of action. After the weeds have been tested for resistance, it is very important to stop using the agents against which resistance exists.
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease/weed

6.5.3 Romania

Contact person: Maria Toader (mirelatoadervali@yahoo.com)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: conventional wheat

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: conventional wheat

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: organic wheat

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: organic wheat

IPM strategies for wheat, Romania

Strategy selection

[IPM of wheat pest/diseases/weeds, in conventional system and organic system]

Description reference year:

[2023]

Romania is a large and traditional producer of wheat. The Romanian farming sector provides sufficient wheat to cover domestic consumption and to generate a substantial (but volatile, in quantitative terms, although quality is generally high) exportable surplus. Agricultural areas in Romania meet suitable conditions for wheat growing (according to studies, 20% of arable land offers very favorable conditions for wheat and 70% offer favorable conditions), which are prerequisites for good yields and high quality (Roman, 2011). The quality for milling wheat depends on a large number of factors, e.g., the choice of the varieties grown; the natural conditions for plant development; the technology employed; the storage, transport and processing conditions (Nitu, 2010).

Agriculture plays an integral and unique role in Romania's economy. About 12 percent of Romanians are employed in agricultural-related activities, compared to the European Union (EU) member average of 4 percent. Romania's 2.9 million agricultural landowners account for one-third of the EU's agricultural holdings. Since the average farm size - 4.42 hectares (HA) - is considerably smaller than the EU average of 15 HA, many of these farms are subsistence and semi-subsistence farms producing for their family's needs (<https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/romania-agricultural-products>). In terms of wheat, Romania ranked fourth both in cultivated area and in terms of production, after France, Germany and Poland.

Source: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/15/20/14793> reading the Romanian National Institute of Statistics

- Areas cultivated with wheat in Romania, by region (Nitu, 2020).

Strategy 1: Wheat – Conventional

Description

Number of growers	2644017
Acreage (ha)	2208000
% of total acreage	84.4%
Production (tonnes/year)	9.635 million tonnes/year
% of the total production	42.7%

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant cultivar
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	450 – 550 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	October -July
Estimated annual yield	4 t/ha
Price per kg product	0.75 lei/kg – 0.15 euro/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	planned amount 96.47 euros/ha, minimum amount 86.82 euros/ha, maximum amount 125.41 euros/ha;
Storage loss	1%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 2-3 Insecticides: 2-3 Herbicides: 2-3
% drift reduction	up to 56% (at a wind speed of 4 m s ⁻¹) and up to 30% (at 10 m s ⁻¹) %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	3-5 m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3 or 1:4)
	With which crops? Maize, barley, sunflower, alfalfa, rapeseed, peas, soybean
Intercropping	no

State-of-the-art scenario: Conventional wheat

Tool	Use of insecticides to control of insects (<i>Agriotes sp.</i> , <i>Zabrus tenebrioides</i> , <i>Mayetiola destructor</i> , <i>Lema melanopa</i>)
Application frequency	every year
Application date	Previous sowing, seed treatment, in 1-30 of September
Stage of development of the crop	seed
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Monitoring of the pest. Through these surveys the future population of the pest can be estimated for <i>Zabrus tenebrioides</i> and <i>Agriotes sp.</i>
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	autumn, 1-30 of September
Stage of development of the crop	soil surveys
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Crop rotation
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Each year
Stage of development of the crop	Previous of wheat crops
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Tool	Weed control by herbicides, pre-emergence
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Autumn, 25 September – 5 of October
Stage of development of the crop	Before emergences of wheat plants
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Apera spica-venti</i> , <i>Poa annua</i> , <i>Alopecurus myosuroides</i> , <i>Lolium multiflorum</i> , respectiv dicotile precum: <i>Galium aparine</i> , <i>Matricaria spp.</i> , <i>Veronica spp.</i> , <i>Viola arvensis</i> , <i>Chenopodium album</i> .

Tool	Weed control by herbicides, post-emergence
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Autumn, 20-30 of October; 1-10 of May
Stage of development of the crop	BBCH 10-29;
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Apera spica-venti</i> , <i>Poa annua</i> , <i>Alopecurus myosuroides</i> , <i>Lolium multiflorum</i> , respectiv dicotile precum: <i>Galium aparine</i> , <i>Matricaria spp.</i> , <i>Veronica spp.</i> , <i>Viola arvensis</i> , <i>Chenopodium album</i> , etc

Tool	Resistant cultivars
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Soil tillage by plowing
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	In autumn
Stage of development of the crop	Previous sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /diseases/weed

Tool	Soil tillage by minimum tillage
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	In autumn
Stage of development of the crop	Previous sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /diseases/weed

Tool	Chemical <i>Eurygaster</i> treatment based on monitoring system and climate conditions or 5-7 adults/m ² or 3-5 larvae/m ²
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Spring, 10-20 of May
Stage of development of the crop	After flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest

Tool	Chemical treatment for diseases control in vegetation, <i>Blumeria graminis</i> , <i>Fusarium sp.</i> , <i>Septoria tritici</i> , <i>Tilletia sp.</i> , <i>Ustilago sp.</i>
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	In spring
Stage of development of the crop	resumption of vegetation in the spring up to first stage of maturity
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Chemical control of aphids in the fall to limit infection with viruses: Wheat streak mosaic, Wheat dwarf virus, based on climatic conditions
Application frequency	Each year, 1-2 treatment
Application date	October-November/ March-April
Stage of development of the crop	tillering
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest

IPM improved scenario: Conventional wheat

Number of growers	2644017
Acreage (ha)	2208000
% of total acreage	84.4%
Production (tonnes/year)	9.635 million tonnes/year
% of the total production	42.7%

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant cultivar Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	450 – 550 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	October -July
Estimated annual yield	4 t/ha
Price per kg product	0.75 lei/kg – 0.15 euro/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	planned amount 96.47 euros/ha, minimum amount 86.82 euros/ha, maximum amount 125.41 euros/ha;
Storage loss	1%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 2-3 Insecticides: 2-3 Herbicides: 2-3
% drift reduction	up to 56% (at a wind speed of 4 m s ⁻¹) and up to 30% (at 10 m s ⁻¹) %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	3-5 m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3 or 1:4) With which crops? Maize, barley, sunflower, alfalfa, rapeseed, peas, soybean
Intercropping	no

Tool	Certified seeds: use of certified seeds which are controlled and meet the requirements to be used for sowing is an effective tool to prevent problems caused by pest and disease.
Application frequency	every year
Application date	1-10 of October
Stage of development of the crop	seed
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Seed treatments: seed treatments with insecticides for controlling the pests <i>Agriotes spp.</i> ; seed treatments with fungicide for controlling the diseases <i>Fusarium sp.</i> , <i>Blumeria graminis</i> , <i>Tilletia sp.</i> , <i>Ustilago tritici</i> , etc
------	---

Application frequency	every year
Application date	Previous sowing, 20 of September – 1st of October
Stage of development of the crop	seed
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Pest monitoring: monitoring of the pests. Through the monitoring process the presence of the pests in the crop can be identified as well as and moment when there is a need of intervention (pest density at economic damage threshold) and limited the disease of wheat
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	01-30 of November for aphids, mites, 1-30 of April and 1-30 of May
Stage of development of the crop	Tillering, elongation of blomering
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest

Tool	Disease field monitoring: monitoring of the diseases. Through the monitoring process the presence of the disease in the crop can be identified as well as and moment when there is a need of intervention (economic damage threshold).
Application frequency	each year
Application date	After sowing and before wheat plant emergence - 20-30 of October, 1-15 of November and 10-20 of May
Stage of development of the crop	Emergence, tillering, stem elongation, heading
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Weed field monitoring: monitoring of the weeds presented within the wheat crop. Through the monitoring process the presence of the weeds, there density and growth stage can be identified, which is an important tool support for establishing the controlling strategy.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	20-30 of October, 1-15 of November, 01 of April up to middle of May
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing, after wheat plant emergence - , tillering
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Crop rotation
------	----------------------

Application frequency	Each year
Application date	before crop establishment
Stage of development of the crop	Previously of the establishment of wheat crops
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Tool	Herbicide weed control: in pre-emergence or/and post-emergence of wheat plants
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Autumn. After sowing and before wheat plant emergence - 20-30 of October, 1-15 of November
Stage of development of the crop	Before emergences/after emergences of wheat plants
Target pest/disease/weed	weed: Dicotyledonous weeds: <i>Abutilon theophrasti</i> , <i>Amaranthus</i> spp., <i>Ambrosia elatorior</i> , <i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> , <i>Chenopodium</i> spp, <i>Cirsium arvensis</i> , <i>Datura stramonium</i> , <i>Euphorbia</i> spp., <i>Galeopsis tetrahit</i> , <i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> , <i>Polygonum</i> spp., <i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i> , <i>Synapis arvensis</i> , <i>Solanum nigrum</i> , <i>Vicia</i> spp., <i>Veronica</i> sp.,). Monocotyledonous weeds: <i>Avena fatua</i> , <i>Apera spica venti</i> , <i>Agropyron repens</i> , <i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> , <i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> , <i>Setaria</i> spp., <i>Panicum</i> spp., <i>Brumus</i> sp.).

Tool	Herbicide weed control in vegetation period of wheat plants
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Spring. 1-15 of May
Stage of development of the crop	stem elongation, heading
Target pest/disease/weed	weed: Dicotyledonous weeds: <i>Abutilon theophrasti</i> , <i>Amaranthus</i> spp., <i>Ambrosia elatorior</i> , <i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> , <i>Chenopodium</i> spp, <i>Cirsium arvensis</i> , <i>Datura stramonium</i> , <i>Euphorbia</i> spp., <i>Galeopsis tetrahit</i> , <i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> , <i>Polygonum</i> spp., <i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i> , <i>Synapis arvensis</i> , <i>Solanum nigrum</i> , <i>Vicia</i> spp., <i>Veronica</i> sp.,). Monocotyledonous weeds: <i>Avena fatua</i> , <i>Apera spica venti</i> , <i>Agropyron repens</i> , <i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> , <i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> , <i>Setaria</i> spp., <i>Panicum</i> spp., <i>Brumus</i> sp.).

Tool	Pest and disease control through insecticide/fungicides application in vegetation
------	--

Application frequency	If necessary – when reaching the economic damage threshold
Application date	at the economic damage threshold
Stage of development of the crop	According to attack
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease

Tool	Control of host weeds for pest and diseases. The destruction of the host weeds around the crop is an important work that will decrease the populations of the pest/diseases among the weeds.
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	October-March-April
Stage of development of the crop	Emergences - until it blooms
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/weed/disease

Tool	Pest biological control: Wasps of the genus <i>Trissolcus</i> (egg parasites) can be used in the biological control of <i>Eurigaster</i> sp.
Application frequency	Application only to the warning, if monitoring the pest requires
Application date	1-10 of April. Adult female parasitic wasps of <i>Trissolcus basalis</i> lay an egg in a host egg. Larvae develop inside the host egg, and after pupation the adult emerges from the host egg by biting a hole in the lid of the stink bug egg.
Stage of development of the crop	stem elongation
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Resistent cultivars
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Tillage: tillage is an effective tool to control pest/disease/weed populations
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	After harvesting the preceding crop up to seedbed preparation
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /diseases/weed

Tool	Balanced fertilization. Nitrogen fertilizers applied unilaterally favour the attack of <i>Erysiphe graminis</i> .
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Before sowing, after sowing, until May
Stage of development of the crop	Emergence, tillering, stem elongation
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Amendments. Calcium amendment of acid soils and drainage of lands with excess moisture has a good control of <i>Agriotes</i> spp.
Application frequency	if necessary – on the same plot the calcium amendment is applied once in four years
Application date	Summer –autumn
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Sowing in optimal parameters : respecting the optimal sowing parameters is an effective tool to prevent pest/weed/diseases and to help wheat plant to fight against pest/weed/diseases.
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	October
Stage of development of the crop	Sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/diseases/weed

Strategy selection

[IPM of wheat pest/diseases/weeds, in organic system]

Description reference year:

[2023]

State-of-the-art scenario: Organic wheat

Description

Number of growers	9815
Acreage (ha)	78327
% of total acreage	3.43%
Production (tonnes/year)	96000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	10% of total organic cereal production

Cultivar	Resistant cultivar
	Seed coating? The most time Yes
Cropping density	450-500 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	1-10 of October
Estimated annual yield	2.5 t/ha

Price per kg product	0.86 lei/kg – 0.30 euro/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	293 euro Conversion 318 certificated products
Storage loss	1%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 0-1 Insecticides: 0-2 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	0 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1-2 m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:4)
	With which crops? Wheat, barley, sunflower, alfalfa, rapeseed, peas, soybean, mustard, flax, oats, chickpea
Intercropping	no

Tool	Biopesticides for seed treatments: neem oil, organic matter, micro-organisms, Trichoderma, humic and seed-protective humic acids. Control of diseases and pest: <i>Fusarium</i> sp., <i>Pythium</i> sp., Sowing flea, as well as bacteria, nematodes, mites, etc.
Application frequency	every year
Application date	seed treatment, in 01-25 of September
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease

Tool	Crop rotation
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Each year
Stage of development of the crop	Previous of wheat crops
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Tool	Soil tillage by plowing
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	In autumn
Stage of development of the crop	Previous sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /diseases/weed

Tool	Soil tillage by minimum tillage
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	In autumn
Stage of development of the crop	Previous sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /diseases/weed

Tool	Resistant cultivars
------	---------------------

Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Biopesticides for <i>Eurygaster</i> treatment based on monitoring system and climate conditions or 5-7 adults/m ² or 3-5 larvae/m ²
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Spring, 10-20 of May
Stage of development of the crop	After flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest

Tool	Biopesticides for diseases control in vegetation, <i>Blumeria graminis</i> , <i>Fusarium sp.</i> , <i>Septoria tritici</i> , <i>Tilletia sp.</i> , <i>Ustilago sp.</i>
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	In spring
Stage of development of the crop	resumption of vegetation in the spring up to first stage of maturity
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Biopesticides of aphids control in the fall to limit infection with viruses: Wheat streak mosaic, Wheat dwarf virus, based on climatic conditions
Application frequency	Each year, 1-2 treatment
Application date	October-November/ March-April
Stage of development of the crop	Tillering, stem elongation, flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest

IPM improve scenario: Organic wheat

Number of growers	9815
Acreage (ha)	78327
% of total acreage	3.43%
Production (tonnes/year)	96000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	10% of total organic cereal production

Cultivar	Resistant cultivar
	Seed coating? The most time Yes
Cropping density	450-500 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	1-10 of October
Estimated annual yield	2.5 t/ha
Price per kg product	0.86 lei/kg – 0.30 euro/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	293 euro Conversion 318 certificated products

Storage loss	1%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 0-1 Insecticides: 0-2 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	0 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1-2 m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:4)
	With which crops? Wheat, barley, sunflower, alfalfa, rapeseed, peas, soybean, mustard, flax, oats, chickpea
Intercropping	no

Tool	Certified seeds: use of certified seeds which are controlled and meet the requirements to be used for sowing is an effective tool to prevent problems caused by pest and disease.
Application frequency	every year
Application date	1-10 of October
Stage of development of the crop	seed
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Biopesticides for seed treatments: neem oil, organic matter, micro-organisms, Trichoderma, humic and seed-protective humic acids. Control of diseases and pest: Fusarium sp., Pythium sp., Sowing flea, as well as bacteria, nematodes, mites, etc.
Application frequency	every year
Application date	seed treatment, in 01-25 of September
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest/disease

Tool	Balanced fertilization: Application of mineral fertilizers, especially those with nitrogen, has a harmful effect on larvae of <i>Agriotes</i> spp.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	Autumn, previous sowing
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Amendments and soil drainage: calcium amendment on acid soils and drainage of lands with excess moisture are useful tool to control the populations of <i>Agriotes</i> spp.
------	--

Application frequency	if necessary – on the same plot the calcium amendment is applied once in four years
Application date	Summer – Autumn
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing for amendments before sowing – emergence for soil drainage
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Sowing in optimal parameters: respecting the optimal sowing parameters is an effective tool to prevent pest /disease/weed and to help maize plant to fight against pest /disease/weed.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	1-10 of October
Stage of development of the crop	sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Tool	Alternating biopesticides with different mode of action: this tool is very effective for preventing the resistance races
Application frequency	each year
Application date	when pesticides are used
Stage of development of the crop	At sowing and in vegetation period
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Pest monitoring: through these surveys the future population of <i>Eurygaster</i> , <i>Aelia</i> , <i>Haplodiplodis</i> , <i>Aphids</i> , etc.
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	spring, from mid-March, and May-June
Stage of development of the crop	Flowering, first stage of maturity
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Disease monitoring: through these surveys the future population of <i>Blumeria</i> , <i>Ustilago</i> , <i>Fusarium</i> , <i>Septoria</i> , <i>Tilletia</i> , etc.
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	spring, from mid-March, and May-June
Stage of development of the crop	Flowering, first stage of maturity
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Crop rotation
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	before crop establishment
Stage of development of the crop	Previously of the establishment of maize crops
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Tool	Resistent cultivars
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Tillage: tillage is an effective tool to control pest/disease/weed populations
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	After harvesting the preceding crop up to seedbed preparation
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /diseases/weed

Tool	Pest biological control: Wasps of the genus <i>Trissolcus</i> (egg parasites) can be used in the biological control of <i>Eurigaster</i> sp.
Application frequency	Application only to the warning, if monitoring the pest requires
Application date	1-10 of April. Adult female parasitic wasps of <i>Trissolcus basalis</i> lay an egg in a host egg. Larvae develop inside the host egg, and after pupation the adult emerges from the host egg by biting a hole in the lid of the stink bug egg.
Stage of development of the crop	stem elongation
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Biopesticides for <i>Eurygaster</i> treatment based on monitoring system and climate conditions or 5-7 adults/m ² or 3-5 larvae/m ²
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Spring, 10-20 of May
Stage of development of the crop	After flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest

Tool	Biopesticides for diseases control in vegetation, <i>Blumeria graminis</i> , <i>Fusarium</i> sp., <i>Septoria tritici</i> , <i>Tilletia</i> sp., <i>Ustilago</i> sp.
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	In spring
Stage of development of the crop	resumption of vegetation in the spring up to first stage of maturity
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Biopesticides of aphids control in the fall to limit infection with viruses: Wheat streak
------	--

	mosaic, Wheat dwarf virus, based on climatic conditions
Application frequency	Each year, 1-2 treatment
Application date	October-November/ March-April
Stage of development of the crop	Tillering, stem elongation, flowering
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest

6.5.4 Switzerland

Contact person: Cordelia Kreft (ckreft@ethz.ch)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: wheat

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario: wheat

IPM strategies for wheat production in Switzerland

Strategy selection

The IPM strategy is created for the entire wheat production in Switzerland. Winter wheat is far more relevant than spring wheat. Moreover, the share of fodder wheat is small (about 10%). There are no relevant region-specific differences.

Description reference year:

2023

Strategy 1: [Entire wheat production]

Description (source: Agristat, Statistische Erhebungen und Schätzungen 2022, Kapitel 2: Pflanzenbau)

Number of growers	14 000
Acreage (ha)	80 000 ha
% of total acreage	100%
Production (tonnes/year)	450 000 t/year
% of the total production	100 %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	60% of production based on resistant cultivars use of seed coating
Cropping density	250-400 seeds/m ² (source: Liebegg, KT Aagrau, Steckbrief Weizen)
Cropping cycle	October (sowing) – July (harvest) (source: Liebegg, KT Aagrau, Steckbrief Weizen)
Estimated annual yield	7 t/ha (source: Möhring&Finger, 2022 (Food Policy))
Price per kg product	52-57 CHF/100 kg (source: SBV, Getreide Preise)
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Production without pesticide use: 400CHF/ha - Production without herbicides: 250 CHF/ha - Flowering strips: 3300CHF/ha - Covering of soil: 200 CHF/ha - Min-till: 250CHF/ha
Storage loss	X kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: Insecticides: Herbicides:
% drift reduction	75-99 % (source: Agridea, Reduktion der Drift und Abschwemmung von PSM im Acker- und Gemüsebau)
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	6 m (source: Agridea, Reduktion der Drift und Abschwemmung von PSM im Acker- und Gemüsebau)

Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:2) (source: Agroscope: Optimale FF im Feldbau (4. Auflage))
	With which crops? (E.g. oat, root crops, legumes, meadow...)
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Fungicides
Application frequency	2
Application date	April - May
Stage of development of the crop	Frist application at stem elongation and second on flag leaf
Target pest/disease/weed	Mildew (blight), septoria, brow and yellow rust, fusarium

Tool	Herbicides
Application frequency	1-2
Application date	Before 10 th October and/or March
Stage of development of the crop	Pre-emergence and/or post-emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Diverse weeds, e.g. black grass, brome grass, couch grass, goosegrass etc.

Tool	Insecticides
Application frequency	1
Application date	April-May
Stage of development of the crop	At lag leaf stage or ear emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Cereal leaf beetle

Tool	Growth regulators
Application frequency	1-2
Application date	April – May
Stage of development of the crop	Stem elongation or bootstage
Target pest/disease/weed	

Tool	Base crop protection decision on observed pest infestation level, official thresholds, extension services, warning/forecasting systems
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Plant stimulants and strengtheners
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Drift-reducing application
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Field and machine hygiene (e.g., manure free from weed seed or removal of crop residues from fields)
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application and after harvest
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Mechanical weeding with plough
Application frequency	Once to prepare seed bed
Application date	September/October
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Site-specific crop rotation (legally required to have at least one year break after wheat)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Mostly diseases and pests

Tool	Use recommended doses
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Reduced application frequency
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Physical measures (Flaming, steaming, freezing or flooding of fields)
Application frequency	Depends on measure
Application date	Depends on measure
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on measure
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control

Tool	Mechanical weeding without plough
Application frequency	Once to prepare seed bed
Application date	September/October
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Sowing time in wheat (Adaption of the sowing time and seed density to support early germination and fast sprouting of wheat)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	September
Stage of development of the crop	Not there
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Field and machine hygiene
Application frequency	as required
Application date	entire cultivation process
Stage of development of the crop	as soon as the wheat sprout from the soil
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Weed competitive/pest resistant cultivars
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	September/October
Stage of development of the crop	Not there
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed&Pest

Tool	Pesticide selection
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Promotion of ecological habitats in wheat production systems (e.g. flowering strips, hedges or wildflower fallow.)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	September/October

Stage of development of the crop	Sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Site specific application (Application of pesticides only on those areas of the field where they are needed (precision agriculture))
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Mulching
Application frequency	1x/season
Application date	after sowing
Stage of development of the crop	Well established
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	80% of production based on resistant cultivars use of seed coating
Cropping density	250-400 seeds/m ² (source: Liebegg, KT Aagrau, Steckbrief Weizen)
Cropping cycle	October (sowing) – July (harvest) (source: Liebegg, KT Aagrau, Steckbrief Weizen)
Estimated annual yield	7 t/ha (source: Möhring&Finger, 2022 (Food Policy))
Price per kg product	65 CHF/100 kg (source: SBV, Getreide Preise)
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Production without pesticide use: 400CHF/ha - Production without herbicides: 250 CHF/ha - Flowering strips: 3300CHF/ha - Covering of soil: 200 CHF/ha Min-till: 250CHF/ha
Storage loss	X kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: Insecticides: Herbicides:
% drift reduction	75-99 % (source: Agridea, Reduktion der Drift und Abschwemmung von PSM im Acker- und Gemüsebau)
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	6 m (source: Agridea, Reduktion der Drift und Abschwemmung von PSM im Acker- und Gemüsebau)
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:2) (source: Agroscope: Optimale FF im Feldbau (4. Auflage)) With which crops? (E.g. oat, root crops, legumes, meadow...)
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Fungicides
Application frequency	2
Application date	April - May
Stage of development of the crop	Frist application at stem elongation and second on flag leaf
Target pest/disease/weed	Mildew (blight), septoria, brow and yellow rust, fusarium

Tool	Site-specific crop rotation (legally required to have at least one year break after wheat)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Mostly diseases and pests

Tool	Site specific application (Application of pesticides only on those areas of the field where they are needed (precision agriculture))
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Sowing time in wheat (Adaption of the sowing time and seed density to support early germination and fast sprouting of wheat)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	September
Stage of development of the crop	Not there
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Base crop protection decision on observed pest infestation level, official thresholds, extension services, warning/forecasting systems
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Mulching
------	-----------------

Application frequency	1x/season
Application date	after sowing
Stage of development of the crop	Well established
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Close monitoring and regular observation
Application frequency	as often as possible
Application date	entire growth until harvest
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Stale seedbed
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	September/October
Stage of development of the crop	Not there
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed

Tool	Beneficials and microbes
Application frequency	as often as need
Application date	entire growth until harvest
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest

Tool	Mating disruption of pests (e.g., food or pheromone traps)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	After sowing
Stage of development of the crop	established before wheat is growing
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest

Tool	Pesticide selection
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Promotion of ecological habitats in wheat production systems (e.g. flowering strips, hedges or wildflower fallow.)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	September/October
Stage of development of the crop	Sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Field and machine hygiene
Application frequency	as required
Application date	entire cultivation process
Stage of development of the crop	as soon as the wheat sprout from the soil
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Weed competitive/pest resistant cultivars
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	September/October
Stage of development of the crop	Not there
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed&Pest

Tool	Physical measures (Flaming, steaming, freezing or flooding of fields)
Application frequency	Depends on measure
Application date	Depends on measure
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on measure
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control

Tool	Mechanical weeding without plough
Application frequency	Once to prepare seed bed
Application date	September/October
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Use recommended doses
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Reduced application frequency
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Plant stimulants and strengtheners
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Drift-reducing application
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Field and machine hygiene (e.g., manure free from weed seed or removal of crop residues from fields)
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application and after harvest
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Mechanical weeding with plough
Application frequency	Once to prepare seed bed
Application date	September/October
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

6.6 Maize

6.6.1 Denmark

Contact person: Jens Erik Jensen (inj@seges.dk)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: [Maize, current IPM in Denmark]

Strategy 1 – improved scenario: [Maize, improved IPM in Denmark]

IPM strategies for [Maize in Denmark]

Strategy selection

The strategy below is based on the NCC meeting for maize held on 28 June 2023 with the participation of maize growers and advisers specializing in maize and roughage production. All the strategies mentioned below were suggested by participating farmers and advisers as being common in practice. Several more experimental tools were also discussed, but as they are not commonly used in practice, they are not mentioned here.

Maize in Denmark is almost entirely grown for silage for feeding dairy cattle. It is mainly located in Jutland, the main peninsula, where the dairy farming is also concentrated. To lesser extent, maize is grown for grain (to feed pigs) or for input into biogas plants, but the described scenario is considered representative of at least 90 % of maize production in Denmark.

Map of maize production in Denmark 2024 – each yellow dot represents a maize field:

Maize 2024

The biggest challenges regarding crop protection in maize is weeds, in particular *Echinochloa crus-galli* which has been spreading enormously during the recent 10-15 years, and now it is present in virtually every maize field. Also perennial weeds and certain annual weeds like *Veronica* species are troublesome.

The weed challenge is to a large extent a result of maize grown frequently in certain fields with favorable location on the farm and particularly with a favorable microclimate for maize cultivation.

Diseases are a smaller problem in maize. Regarding pests, bird damage during the emergence and early growth phases can be a big problem in some areas. Some insect pests are present, but there is normally no need for insecticide spraying.

Description reference year:

[2023]

I have chosen to refer to an “average year” and assume that the maize is grown for silage. However, to get numbers regarding growers, acreage etc. correct, I have chosen to take the year 2023 as a reference.

Strategy 1: [strategy title]

Description

Number of growers	Approx. 2.600
Acreage (ha)	180.000 ha
% of total acreage	9 % of total area in Denmark with rotational crops, but approx. 90 per cent of the maize area
Production (tonnes/year)	14 to 19,5 tonnes dry matter / hectare /year according to field trials – no official statistics available
% of the total production	X % - very difficult to say, most maize is used for fodder (silage) at the farm level, and is normally not sold among farmers, no official statistics available

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? No – not really relevant since very little fungicide is used in maize, and we only have scarce information about susceptibility of cultivars to the two major diseases.
	Seed coating? No – most maize is not dressed, but in areas vulnerable to bird attacks, some seed dressing with products less palatable to birds is used
Cropping density	Approx. 100.000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	May – Late September/October
Estimated annual yield	14 tonnes dry matter/ha, yield corresponds in average to 11.000 to 12.000 Feed Units per hectare
Price per kg product	Not applicable, since most maize is used for silage which is in turn used for cattle feed €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	5 %

PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 0-1, most commonly 0 Insecticides: 0 Herbicides: 2-5 (applied in 1-3 sprayings)
% drift reduction	50-90 % - no legal requirements for drift reduction, only when spraying close to water courses and natural areas.
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	2-3 m, buffers are 2 to 20 meters, depending on product and drift reduction.
Crop rotation	No, most maize is grown without rotation With which crops? Where rotation is practiced, it is most commonly with spring cereal with undersown clover/grass, and subsequently clover/grass ley
Intercropping	Yes – most maize grown with undersown grass to reduce leaching of nitrogen. The grass cover crop is destroyed early spring before establishing the next crop.

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Crop rotation – maize grown in a rotation has tendency for higher yield, and weeds are more easily controlled
Application frequency	30-50 %
Application date	Not relevant
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds, pests, diseases

Tool	Seed treatment of maize to discourage birds from eating germinating seeds – alternatively and to a lesser extent, different bird scaring devices are used
Application frequency	30-50 %
Application date	March – seed dressing
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Birds

Tool	Ploughing in spring before sowing to destroy overwintering weeds
Application frequency	20-50 %
Application date	March-April
Stage of development of the crop	0 – pre sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual and perennial weeds

Tool	One spraying with glyphosate before seed bed preparation
Application frequency	1 application, 10-30 % of farms
Application date	March-April
Stage of development of the crop	0 – pre sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual and perennial weeds

Tool	Precision slurry application – slurry is injected into the soil below seed depth and increases crop competition against weeds (The crop get nutrients, not the weeds)
Application frequency	10-15 %
Application date	April-May
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual weeds

Tool	Monitoring of weeds during the early growing season and application of 1-3 sprayings with herbicide mixtures at low dosages adjusted to the present weed flora and the sizes and numbers of weeds present. No soil residual herbicides are used in maize cultivation in Denmark
Application frequency	1-3 applications, 80-90 % of fields
Application date	May-June
Stage of development of the crop	09-18
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual and perennial weeds

Tool	Inter-row cultivation/hoeing is normally used once in each crop, typically in the same operation as the sowing of the undersown catch crop – typically ryegrass or red fescue, which is obligatory in most maize fields due to concerns about nitrate leaching
Application frequency	1 application, 80-90 % of fields
Application date	June
Stage of development of the crop	15-18
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual weeds

Tool	Monitoring leaf diseases either directly in field or based on action thresholds and the Danish registration network for diseases in maize – the results are communicated largely by local advisers
Application frequency	50-90
Application date	July-August

Stage of development of the crop	55-65
Target pest/disease/weed	Leaf diseases

Tool	Spraying against leaf diseases based on the monitoring. Rarely need for spraying
Application frequency	1 application 5-15 per cent of fields are sprayed
Application date	July-August
Stage of development of the crop	55-65
Target pest/disease/weed	Leaf diseases

Tool	Prevention of spread of particularly Echinochloa crus-galli by cleaning of machinery before going from one field to another
Application frequency	10-20 %
Application date	September – Early October
Stage of development of the crop	90 (Harvest)
Target pest/disease/weed	Echinochloa crus-galli, the most troublesome grass weed in maize in Denmark

Tool	Follow-up of weed control measures by walking the stubble after harvest
Application frequency	10-30 %
Application date	September- October
Stage of development of the crop	Post harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Testing of weeds surviving the spray programme for resistance
Application frequency	0-10 %
Application date	July-August (seed collection)
Stage of development of the crop	60
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual weeds

IPM improved scenario

An improved IPM-scenario would look pretty much like the current scenario. However, farmers and advisers are well aware that one of the biggest challenges is the **lack of diverse rotations** in the maize cropping systems. In fact, maize is grown year after year in many fields.

Some suggest that farmers with different production systems work together – e.g. potato farmers and farmers with dairy production, enabling longer rotations and thereby better control of the critical weeds.

One barrier for this is to enable farmers to see how much they can earn by working together and minimizing their weed problems.

Another challenge is that many dairy farmers have their primary interest focused on what is happening in the stables, and less so in the fields. A solution for this could be to outsource maize production to farmers with more interest in crop production, thereby enabling better timing and generally better work to be done in the field.

Farmers and advisers mention that the **mechanical weed management has a big potential** with precision machinery currently being developed, and also sowing catch crops with machinery with discs can be an advantage as less weeds are provoked to germinate.

Many perennial weeds in maize may be mapped using drones, and when weed control is based on drone maps, there is a big potential for reducing herbicide use.

More advanced IPM scenarios in maize would therefore also include more mechanical weed management in the form of interrow hoeing combined with band spraying in the maize rows, a practice that would reduce herbicide inputs by 60-80 per cent.

Cultivar	Resistant? No – not really relevant since very little fungicide is used in maize, and we only have scarce information about susceptibility of cultivars to the two major diseases.
	Seed coating? No – most maize is not dressed, but in areas vulnerable to bird attacks, some seed dressing with products less palatable to birds is used
Cropping density	Approx. 100.000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	May – Late September/October
Estimated annual yield	14 tonnes dry matter/ha, yield corresponds in average to 11.000 to 12.000 Feed Units per hectare
Price per kg product	Not applicable, since most maize is used for silage which is in turn used for cattle feed €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	5 %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 0-1, most commonly 0 Insecticides: 0 Herbicides: 2-5 (applied in 1-2 sprayings with banded application)
% drift reduction	50-90 % - no legal requirements for drift reduction, only when spraying close to water courses and natural areas.
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	2-3 m, buffers are 2 to 20 meters, depending on product and drift reduction.

Crop rotation	In this scenario, it is obligatory to grow maize in a rotation with other crops, which would primarily be spring cereals and clover/grass leys.
	With which crops? Spring cereal with undersown clover/grass, and subsequently clover/grass ley
Intercropping	Yes – most maize grown with undersown grass to reduce leaching of nitrogen. The grass cover crop is destroyed early spring before establishing the next crop.

Additional IPM tools to current scenario

Tool	Crop rotation – maize grown in a rotation has tendency for higher yield, and weeds are more easily controlled
Application frequency	30-50 %
Application date	Not relevant
Stage of development of the crop	0
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds, pests, diseases

Tool	Monitoring of weeds during the early growing season and banded (in-row) application of 1-2 sprayings with herbicide mixtures at low dosages adjusted to the present weed flora and the sizes and numbers of weeds present. This reduces herbicide use by 60 to 80 per cent
Application frequency	1-2 applications, 80-90 % of fields
Application date	May-June
Stage of development of the crop	09-18
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual and perennial weeds

Tool	Inter-row cultivation/hoeing is used in 2-3 applications as necessary to control emerging weeds. Together with the last cultivation, the catch crop is undersown. Catch crop is typically ryegrass or red fescue, which is obligatory in most maize fields due to concerns about nitrate leaching
Application frequency	2-3 application, 80-90 % of fields
Application date	May-June
Stage of development of the crop	11-18
Target pest/disease/weed	Annual weeds

6.6.2 Romania

Contact person: Maria Toader (mirelatoadervali@yahoo.com)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: conventional maize

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: conventional maize

Strategy 2 – state of the art scenario: organic maize

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario: organic maize

IPM strategies for Maize, Romania

Strategy selection

[IPM of maize pest/diseases/weeds, in conventional system and organic system]

Description reference year:

[2023]

2023 was chosen as the reference year, because the cultivated area and vegetable agricultural production in Romania increased in the year 2023, compared to the year 2022, especially in cereals for grains. At EU level, Romania ranked first regarding the area cultivated with corn grains, and third in terms of production, after France and Poland.

The area cultivated with grain maize in 2023 represents 45.3% of the area cultivated with grains for grains.

According to INS data, Romania had in 2023 a production of 8.5 million tons of corn from an area of over 2.3 million hectares.

Source: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/15/20/14793> reading the Romanian National Institute of Statistics

For organic production:

Counties Galați, Tulcea and Ifov county rank first among the regions with maize cultivated under organic practices. Tulcea region is somehow logical due to the presence of the Danube Delta Reserve and the specific cultivation conditions that this area must comply with. The figure below represents the area under organic production cultivated with maize, by county.

Source: <https://www.incda-fundulea.ro/rar/nr39/rar39.51.pdf>

Strategy 1: Maize – Conventional

Description

Number of growers	1870000
Acreage (ha)	2332684
% of total acreage	98.3%
Production (tonnes/year)	8.424 million tonnes/year
% of the total production	98.9%

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant cultivar
	Seed coating? Yes

Cropping density	55000 – 75000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	April-September
Estimated annual yield	4-5 t/ha
Price per kg product	0.56 lei/kg – 0.12 euro/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	planned amount 96.47 euros/ha, minimum amount 86.82 euros/ha, maximum amount 125.41 euros/ha;
Storage loss	0.5-1%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 0-1 Insecticides: 1-3 Herbicides: 1-3
% drift reduction	up to 56% (at a wind speed of 4 m s ⁻¹) and up to 30% (at 10 m s ⁻¹) %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	3-5 m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3 or 1:4) With which crops? Wheat, barley, sunflower, alfalfa, rapeseed, soybean, peas, chickpea
Intercropping	no

State-of-the-art scenario: Conventional maize

Tool	Use of pesticides (neonicotinoides) to control of <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> and <i>Agriotes</i> spp. in a rate of 6-8 l/t of seeds. According to official EU and MADR legislation, by way of derogation, the using of treated seeds with neonicotinoids will only be done in areas and on surfaces strongly affected by the attack of soil pests (over 5 adults/m ²), and the treatment of maize will be carried out only by authorized service providers, and the plots of land will be marked as such, in period 22 January – 21 May.
Application frequency	every year
Application date	seed treatment, in 20 of March – 20 of April
Stage of development of the crop	seed
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Monitoring of pest (<i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i>) Through these surveys the future population of the pest can be estimated.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	spring, 10-30 of March and 1-20 of April
Stage of development of the crop	soil surveys, BBCH 09 – 11 of maize plants
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Crop rotation
Application frequency	each year

Application date	before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	previous of maize crops
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Tool	Weed control by herbicides, pre-emergence
Application frequency	each year
Application date	10-15 of April
Stage of development of the crop	before emergences of maize plants
Target pest/disease/weed	weed: Dicotyledonous weeds: <i>Abutilon theophrasti</i> , <i>Amaranthus</i> spp., <i>Ambrosia elatorior</i> , <i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> , <i>Chenopodium</i> spp., <i>Datura stramonium</i> , <i>Euphorbia</i> spp., <i>Galeopsis tetrahit</i> , <i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> , <i>Polygonum</i> spp., <i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i> , <i>Synapsis arvensis</i> , <i>Solanum nigrum</i> , <i>Vicia</i> spp. Monocotyledonous weeds: <i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> , <i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> , <i>Setaria</i> spp., <i>Panicum</i> spp., <i>Sorghum halepense</i> (from seed).

Tool	Weed control by herbicides, post-emergence
Application frequency	each year
Application date	1-15 of May
Stage of development of the crop	2-3/4-6 leaves for maize and weeds in the early growth phase (up to 3 leaves).
Target pest/disease/weed	weed: Dicotyledonous weeds (<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i> , <i>Amaranthus</i> spp., <i>Ambrosia elatorior</i> , <i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> , <i>Chenopodium</i> spp., <i>Datura stramonium</i> , <i>Euphorbia</i> spp., <i>Galeopsis tetrahit</i> , <i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> , <i>Polygonum</i> spp., <i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i> , <i>Synapsis arvensis</i> , <i>Solanum nigrum</i> , <i>Vicia</i> spp. Monocotyledonous weeds: <i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> , <i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> , <i>Setaria</i> spp., <i>Panicum</i> spp., <i>Sorghum halepense</i> .

Tool	Mechanical weeding through hoeing (I)
Application frequency	each year
Application date	1-15 of May
Stage of development of the crop	3-5 leafs of maize
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	Mechanical weeding through hoeing (II)
Application frequency	each year
Application date	20-30 of May
Stage of development of the crop	6-8 leafs of maize

Target pest/disease/weed	weed
--------------------------	------

Tool	Biological control. First treatment - the release of the parasitic entomophagus of <i>Trichogramma maydis</i> eggs (100,000 specimens/ha) for <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> , with secondary effect on <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> and other noctuids.
Application frequency	Application only at warning.
Application date	20-30 of June. Launches are made when the maximum flight curve of the adults is recorded.
Stage of development of the crop	the height of 45 cm of the maize plants
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Biological control. Second treatment - the release of the parasitic entomophagus of <i>Trichogramma maydis</i> eggs (100,000 specimens/ha) for <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> , with secondary effect on <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> and other noctuids.
Application frequency	Application only at warning.
Application date	Repeating the treatment is recommended after 7-8 days where the density of the pest is high.
Stage of development of the crop	the height of 45-50 cm of the maize plants
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Resistent cultivars (hybrids)
Application frequency	each year
Application date	before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Tillage by plowing
Application frequency	each year
Application date	autumn of the previous year
Stage of development of the crop	previous sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /disease/weed

Tool	Minimum tillage
Application frequency	each year
Application date	autumn of the previous year
Stage of development of the crop	previous sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /disease/weed

IPM improved scenario: Conventional maize
Description

Number of growers	1870000
Acreage (ha)	2332684
% of total acreage	98.3%
Production (tonnes/year)	8.424 million tonnes/year
% of the total production	98.9%

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant cultivar
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	55000 – 75000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	April-September
Estimated annual yield	4-5 t/ha
Price per kg product	0.56 lei/kg – 0.12 euro/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	planned amount 96.47 euros/ha, minimum amount 86.82 euros/ha, maximum amount 125.41 euros/ha;
Storage loss	0.5-1%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 0-1 Insecticides: 1-3 Herbicides: 1-3
% drift reduction	up to 56% (at a wind speed of 4 m s ⁻¹) and up to 30% (at 10 m s ⁻¹) %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	3-5 m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3 or 1:4)
	With which crops? Wheat, barley, sunflower, alfalfa, rapeseed, soybean, peas, chickpea
Intercropping	no

Tool	Certified seeds: use of certified seeds which are controlled and meet the requirements to be used for sowing is an effective tool to prevent problems caused by pest and disease.
Application frequency	every year
Application date	20 of March - 20 of April
Stage of development of the crop	seed
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Seed treatments: seed treatments with insecticides for controlling the pests <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> and <i>Agriotes spp.</i> ; seed treatments with fungicide for controlling the
------	---

	diseases <i>Fusarium</i> sp., <i>Pythium</i> sp., <i>Sorosporium holci-sorghii</i> .
Application frequency	every year
Application date	20 of March - 20 of April
Stage of development of the crop	seed
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Pest field monitoring: monitoring of the pests <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> , <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> , <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> , <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i> . Through the monitoring process the presence of the pests in the crop can be identified as well as and moment when there is a need of intervention (economic damage threshold).
Application frequency	each year
Application date	01-30 of April for <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> Middle of May - July for <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> , <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> , <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>
Stage of development of the crop	Soil surveys, BBCH 09 – 11 of maize plants for <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> Pheromonal traps for <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> and <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> , and yellow traps for <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i> , starting with BBCH 18.
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Disease field monitoring: monitoring of the diseases <i>Helminthosporium turcicum</i> , <i>Ustilago maydis</i> , and <i>Puccinia sorghi</i> . Through the monitoring process the presence of the disease in the crop can be identified as well as and moment when there is a need of intervention (economic damage threshold).
Application frequency	each year
Application date	Middle of May – middle of July
Stage of development of the crop	starting with BBCH 18
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Weed field monitoring: monitoring of the weeds presented within the maize crop. Through the monitoring process the presence of the weeds, there density and growth stage can be identified, which is an important tool support for establishing the controlling strategy.
Application frequency	each year

Application date	01 of April up to middle of May
Stage of development of the crop	sowing up to 6 leaves stage (BBCH 16)
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Crop rotation: this is an important tool to control the populations of pests, diseases, and weeds
Application frequency	each year
Application date	before crop establishment
Stage of development of the crop	previously of the establishment of maize crop
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Tool	Herbicide weed control: weed control by using herbicides in pre-emergence and/or post-emergence of the maize plants
Application frequency	each year
Application date	After sowing and before maize plant emergence - in April, for herbicides in pre-emergence After maize plant emergence – in May, for herbicides in or post-emergence
Stage of development of the crop	Before emergences of maize plants for herbicides in pre-emergence BBCH 12-16 for herbicides in or post-emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	weed: Dicotyledonous weeds: <i>Abutilon theophrasti</i> , <i>Amaranthus</i> spp., <i>Ambrosia elatorior</i> , <i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> , <i>Chenopodium</i> spp., <i>Cirsium arvensis</i> , <i>Datura stramonium</i> , <i>Euphorbia</i> spp., <i>Galeopsis tetrahit</i> , <i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> , <i>Polygonum</i> spp., <i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i> , <i>Synapsis arvensis</i> , <i>Solanum nigrum</i> , <i>Vicia</i> spp.). Monocotyledonous weeds: <i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> , <i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> , <i>Setaria</i> spp., <i>Panicum</i> spp., <i>Sorghum halepense</i> .

Tool	Insecticide pest control: in certain conditions, there is a need to control the attack of <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> , <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> , <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> , and <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i> through insecticide spraying.
Application frequency	if necessary – when there is reached the economic damage threshold
Application date	at the economic damage threshold for each insect
Stage of development of the crop	according to pest attack

Target pest/disease/weed	pest
--------------------------	------

Tool	Fungicide disease control: in certain conditions there is a need to control the attack of <i>Helminthosporium turcicum</i> and <i>Ustilago maydis</i> through fungicide spraying.
Application frequency	if necessary – when there is reached the economic damage threshold
Application date	at the economic damage threshold
Stage of development of the crop	according to disease attack
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Control of host weeds. The destruction of the host weeds around the crop (field margin management) is an important work that will decrease the populations of the pest, as for example: destruction of <i>Cirsium arvensis</i> which is preferred by <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> ; destruction of <i>Sorghum halepense</i> and <i>Artemisia</i> spp. which are preferred by <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> ; destruction of <i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i> which is preferred by adults of <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i> .
Application frequency	each year
Application date	March-May
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing up to BBGH 18
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/weed

Tool	Mechanical weed control: control of weed through one or two hoeings
Application frequency	if necessary
Application date	1-10 of May for hoeing 1 20-30 of May for hoeing 2
Stage of development of the crop	3-5 leafs of maize (BBCH13-15) for hoeing 1 6-8 leafs of maize (BBCH16-18) for hoeing 1
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	Pest biological control: the release of the parasitic entomophagus of <i>Trichogramma maydis</i> eggs (100,000 specimens/ha) for controlling <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> , with secondary effect on <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> and other noctuids.
Application frequency	If necessary, only at warning, when it is necessary one-two treatments.

Application date	20-30 of June - first treatment. Launches are made when the maximum flight curve of the adults is recorded. Second treatment: after 7-8 days from first treatment, if the pest density is high.
Stage of development of the crop	45 cm height of the maize plants
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Resistent cultivars (hybrids): genetic resistance of the maize hybrid is an effective way of controlling the important pest and disease for the growing area.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Tillage: tillage is an effective tool to control pest/disease/weed populations
Application frequency	each year
Application date	after harvesting the preceding crop up to seedbed preparation
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /disease/weed

Tool	Balanced fertilization: application of phosphorus-based fertilizers, which reduce the occurrence and severity of <i>Gibberella fujikuroi</i> (sin. <i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>) disease. Maize grown on soils with low fertility or soils with high nitrogen content develop a greater sensitivity to infections with <i>Ustilago maydis</i> . Application of mineral fertilizers, especially those with nitrogen, has a harmful effect on larvae of <i>Agriotes</i> spp.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	Autumn of previous year up to spring
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Amendments and soil drainage: calcium amendment on acid soils and drainage of lands with excess moisture are a useful tool to control the populations of <i>Agriotes</i> spp.
Application frequency	if necessary – on the same plot the calcium amendment is applied once in four years
Application date	Summer – Autumn in previous year for amendments

	March-April for soil drainage
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing for amendments before sowing – emergence for soil drainage
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Sowing in optimal parameters: respecting the optimal sowing parameters is an effective tool to prevent pest /disease/weed and to help maize plant to fight against pest /disease/weed.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Tool	Alternating pesticides with different mode of action: this tool is very effective for preventing the resistance races
Application frequency	each year
Application date	when pesticides are used
Stage of development of the crop	when pesticides are used
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

State-of-the-art scenario: Organic maize

Description

Number of growers	9815
Acreage (ha)	40316
% of total acreage	1.7%
Production (tonnes/year)	96000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	1.1%

Cultivar	Resistant cultivar
	Seed coating? Most of the time yes
Cropping density	50000 – 65000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	April-September
Estimated annual yield	2.5 t/ha
Price per kg product	0.86 lei/kg – 0.30 euro/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	283 euro in the conversion period 218 euro for producing certificated products and maintaining certification
Storage loss	1-2%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 0-1 Insecticides: 0-2 Herbicides: 0

% drift reduction	0 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	0 m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:4)
	With which crops? Wheat, barley, sunflower, alfalfa, rapeseed, soybean, peas, chickpea, mustard, flax, oat
Intercropping	no

Tool	Pest monitoring: through this survey the future population of the pest <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> can be estimated.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	Spring, 01 - 20 of April
Stage of development of the crop	soil surveys, BBCH 09 – 11 of maize plants
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Crop rotation
Application frequency	each year
Application date	each year
Stage of development of the crop	previous of maize crops
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Tool	Mechanical weeding through hoeing (I)
Application frequency	each year
Application date	1-15 of May
Stage of development of the crop	3-5 leafs of maize plants
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	Mechanical weeding through hoeing (II)
Application frequency	each year
Application date	20-30 of May
Stage of development of the crop	6-8 leafs of maize plants
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	Biological control. First treatment - the release of the parasitic entomophagus of <i>Trichogramma maydis</i> eggs (100,000 specimens/ha) for <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> , with secondary effect on <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> and other noctuids.
Application frequency	Application only at warning.
Application date	20-30 of June. Launches are made when the maximum flight curve of the adults is recorded.
Stage of development of the crop	the height of 45 cm of the maize plants
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Biological control. Second treatment - the release of the parasitic entomophagus of <i>Trichogramma maydis</i> eggs (100,000 specimens/ha) for <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> , with secondary effect on <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> and other noctuids.
Application frequency	Application only at warning.
Application date	Repeating the treatment is recommended after 7-8 days where the density of the pest is high.
Stage of development of the crop	the height of 45 cm of the maize plants
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Resistent cultivars (hybrids)
Application frequency	each year
Application date	before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Tillage by plowing
Application frequency	each year
Application date	in autumn
Stage of development of the crop	previous sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /diseases/weed

Tool	Minimum tillage
Application frequency	each year
Application date	in autumn
Stage of development of the crop	previous sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /diseases/weed

Tool	Bioinsecticides for seed treatments: control of <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> (maize leaf weevil) by using bioinsecticides (organic extract) from the Fabaceae family, also Neem, and Laser 240 and Bactospeine DF bioinsecticides in a rate of 2.5 g/250 grams of seeds.
Application frequency	every year
Application date	seed treatment, in 01-20 of April
Stage of development of the crop	seed
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Bioinsecticides for vegetation treatment: controlling of <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> (maize leaf weevil) by using of bioinsecticides in early growth stages of maize plants, such as Neem and Laser 240 in rate of 150 ml/ha.
Application frequency	every year/ 1 or 2 applications
Application date	01-15 of May
Stage of development of the crop	3-5 leaf phase of maize plants – BBCH13-15

Target pest/disease/weed	pest
--------------------------	------

IPM improved scenario: Organic maize

Number of growers	9815
Acreage (ha)	40316
% of total acreage	1.7%
Production (tonnes/year)	96000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	1.1%

Cultivar	Resistant cultivar
	Seed coating? The most time Yes
Cropping density	50000 – 65000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	April-September
Estimated annual yield	2.5 t/ha
Price per kg product	0.86 lei/kg – 0.30 euro/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	283 euro in the conversion period 218 euro for producing certificated products and maintaining certification
Storage loss	1-2%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 0-1 Insecticides: 0-2 Herbicides: 0
% drift reduction	0 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	0 m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:4)
	With which crops? Wheat, barley, sunflower, alfalfa, rapeseed, soybean, peas, chickpea, mustard, flax, oat
Intercropping	no

Tool	Certified seeds: use of certified seeds which are controlled and meet the requirements to be used for sowing is an effective tool to prevent problems caused by pest and disease.
Application frequency	every year
Application date	20 of March - 20 of April
Stage of development of the crop	seed
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Bioinsecticides for seed treatments: control of <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> (maize leaf weevil) by using bioinsecticides (organic extract) from the Fabaceae family, also Neem, and Laser 240 and Bactospeine DF bioinsecticides in a rate of 2.5 g/250 grams of seeds.
------	--

Application frequency	every year
Application date	seed treatment, in 01-20 of April
Stage of development of the crop	seed
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Bioinsecticides for vegetation treatment: controlling of <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> (maize leaf weevil) by using of bioinsecticides in early growth stages of maize plants, such as Neem and Laser 240 in rate of 150 ml/ha.
Application frequency	every year/ 1 or 2 applications
Application date	01-15 of May
Stage of development of the crop	3-5 leaf phase of maize plants – BBCH13-15
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Pest field monitoring: monitoring of the pests <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> , <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> , <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> , <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i> . Through the monitoring process the presence of the pests in the crop can be identified as well as their attack intensity.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	01-30 of April for <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> Middle of May - July for <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> , <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> , <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>
Stage of development of the crop	Soil surveys, BBCH 09 – 11 of maize plants for <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> Pheromonal traps for <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> and <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> , and yellow traps for <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i> , starting with BBCH 18.
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Disease field monitoring: monitoring of the diseases <i>Helminthosporium turcicum</i> , <i>Ustilago maydis</i> , and <i>Puccinia sorghi</i> . Through the monitoring process the presence of the disease in the crop can be identified as well as their intensity attack.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	Middle of May – middle of July
Stage of development of the crop	starting with BBCH 18
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Weed field monitoring: monitoring of the weeds presented within the maize crop.
------	--

	Through the monitoring process the presence of the weeds, their density and growth stage can be identified, which is an important tool support for establishing the controlling strategy.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	01 of April up to middle of May
Stage of development of the crop	sowing up to 6 leaves stage (BBCH 16)
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Crop rotation: this is an important tool to control the populations of pests, diseases, and weeds
Application frequency	each year
Application date	before crop establishment
Stage of development of the crop	previously of the establishment of maize crops
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Tool	Control of host weeds. The destruction of the host weeds around the crop (field margin management) is an important work that will decrease the populations of the pest, as for example: destruction of <i>Cirsium arvensis</i> which is preferred by <i>Tanymecus dilaticollis</i> ; destruction of <i>Sorghum halepense</i> and <i>Artemisia</i> spp. which are preferred by <i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> ; destruction of <i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i> which is preferred by adults of <i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i> .
Application frequency	each year
Application date	March-May
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing up to BBGH 18
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/weed

Tool	Mechanical weed control: control of weed through one or two hoeings
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	1-10 of May for hoeing 1 20-30 of May for hoeing 2
Stage of development of the crop	3-5 leaves of maize (BBCH13-15) for hoeing 1 6-8 leaves of maize (BBCH16-18) for hoeing 1
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	Pest biological control: the release of the parasitic entomophagus of <i>Trichogramma maydis</i> eggs (100,000 specimens/ha) for
------	---

	<i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i> , with secondary effect on <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i> and other noctuids.
Application frequency	If necessary, only at warning, when it is necessary one-two treatments.
Application date	20-30 of June - first treatment. Launches are made when the maximum flight curve of the adults is recorded. Second treatment: after 7-8 days from first treatment, if the pest density is high.
Stage of development of the crop	45 cm height of the maize plants
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Disease biological control: use of biofungicides based of <i>Trichoderma asperellum</i> , T34, against <i>Fusarium</i> sp. , in a rate of 10 kg/ha
Application frequency	each year
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	at sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Resistent cultivars (hybrids): genetic rezistence of the maize hybrid is an effective way of controlling the important pest and disease for the growing area.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease

Tool	Tillage: tillage is an effective tool to control pest/disease/weed populations
Application frequency	each year
Application date	after harvesting the preceding crop up to seedbed preparation
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest /disease/weed

Tool	Balanced fertilization. The application of phosphorus-based fertilizers, which reduce the occurrence and severity of <i>Gibberella fujikuroi</i> (sin. <i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>) disease. Maize grown on soils with low fertility or soils with high nitrogen content develop a greater sensitivity to infections with <i>Ustilago maydis</i> . Application of mineral fertilizers, especially those with nitrogen, has a harmful effect on Larvae of <i>Agriotes</i> spp.
------	--

Application frequency	each year
Application date	Autumn in previous year up to spring
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Amendments and soil drainage: calcium amendment on acid soils and drainage of lands with excess moisture are useful tool to control the populations of <i>Agriotes</i> spp.
Application frequency	if necessary – on the same plot the calcium amendment is applied once in four years
Application date	Summer – Autumn in previous year for amendments March-April for soil drainage
Stage of development of the crop	before sowing for amendments before sowing – emergence for soil drainage
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Sowing in optimal parameters: respecting the optimal sowing parameters is an effective tool to prevent pest /disease/weed and to help maize plant to fight against pest /disease/weed.
Application frequency	each year
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Tool	Light traps: using light traps at night and those with pheromones to attract adults of <i>Agrotis segetum</i>
Application frequency	each year
Application date	May and June
Stage of development of the crop	2-4 of maize leaves up to 7-8 leaves – BBCH 12-14 up to BBCH 17-18
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

6.6.3 Switzerland

Contact person: Cordelia Kreft (ckreft@ethz.ch)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: maize

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario: maize

IPM strategies for maize production in Switzerland

Strategy selection

The IPM strategy is created for the entire maize production in Switzerland. There are no relevant region-specific differences.

Description reference year:

2023

Strategy 1: [Entire maize production]

Description (source: Agristat, Statistische Erhebungen und Schätzungen 2022, Kapitel 2: Pflanzenbau)

Number of growers	14 000
Acreage (ha)	62472ha
% of total acreage	100%
Production (tonnes/year)	993000t/year
% of the total production	100 %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Most of the recommended cultivars are resistant varieties LES2024_Koernermais.pdf (swissgranum.ch)
Cropping density	8 – 11 seeds/m ² (source: https://www.strickhof.ch/publikationen/merkblatt-mais/)
Cropping cycle	Mid April to end of May (sowing) – Silage maize: Sept to Oct Grain maize: Oct to Nov (harvest) (source: https://www.strickhof.ch/publikationen/merkblatt-mais/)
Estimated annual yield	Silomais: 185 dt/ha Körnermais: 100 dt/ha (source: https://www.strickhof.ch/publikationen/merkblatt-mais/)
Price per kg product	Silo 4.75 CHF/dt; Körner 39.50 CHF/dt (source: https://redaktion.strickhof.ch/server/api/dokument/GetDokument?id=10295)
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Production without herbicides: 250 CHF/ha - Flowering strips: 3300CHF/ha - Covering of soil: 200 CHF/ha - Min-till: 250CHF/ha
Storage loss	X kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: Insecticides: Herbicides:
% drift reduction	75-99 % (source: Agridea, Reduktion der Drift und Abschwemmung von PSM im Acker- und Gemüsebau)

Minimum buffer zone to surface water	6 m (<i>source: Agridea, Reduktion der Drift und Abschwemmung von PSM im Acker- und Gemüsebau</i>)
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1 year break) (<i>source: https://www.ipsuisse.ch/wp-content/plugins/pdfjs-viewer-shortcode/pdfjs/web/viewer.php?file=https://www.ipsuisse.ch/wp-content/uploads/Richtlinien_Pflanzenbau_A4_DE_RZ.pdf&attachment_id=53962&dButton=true&pButton=true&oButton=false&sButton=true#zoom=auto&pagemode=none&_wpnonce=134ba3ed23</i>) With which crops? Cereal crops such as wheat
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Herbicide
Application frequency	Once
Application date	May
Stage of development of the crop	3-4 leave stage of maize
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds such as blackgrass, ryegrass, millet etc.

Tool	Base crop protection decision on observed pest infestation level, official thresholds, extension services, warning/forecasting systems
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Plant stimulants and strengtheners
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Drift-reducing application
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Field and machine hygiene (e.g., manure free from weed seed or removal of crop residues from fields)
Application frequency	Each application

Application date	Each application and after harvest
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Trichogramma
Application frequency	Varies
Application date	Depending on the European corn borer
Stage of development of the crop	No influence
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly Pest

Tool	Site-specific crop rotation (legally required to have at least one year break after wheat)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Mostly diseases and pests

Tool	Use recommended doses
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Reduced application frequency
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Physical measures (Flaming, steaming, freezing or flooding of fields)
Application frequency	Depends on measure
Application date	Depends on measure
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on measure
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control

Tool	Mechanical weeding with plough
Application frequency	Once to prepare seed bed
Application date	September/October
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Bacillus-thuringiensis
------	-------------------------------

Application frequency	Varies
Application date	Depending on the European corn borer
Stage of development of the crop	No influence
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly Pest

Tool	Field and machine hygiene
Application frequency	as required
Application date	entire cultivation process
Stage of development of the crop	as soon as the wheat sprout from the soil
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Weed competitive/pest resistant cultivars
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Mid April to the end of May
Stage of development of the crop	Not there
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed&Pest

Tool	Pesticide selection
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Promotion of ecological habitats in maize production systems (e.g. flowering strips, hedges or wildflower fallow.)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	April/May
Stage of development of the crop	Sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Site specific application (application of pesticides only on those areas of the field where they are needed (precision agriculture))
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Mulching
Application frequency	1x/season
Application date	after sowing
Stage of development of the crop	Well established
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Shredding of maize stubble and maize straw
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	After harvesting
Stage of development of the crop	Harvested
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weeds and diseases control

Tool	Heterorhabditis bacteriophora
Application frequency	1x/season
Application date	Specific X
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest

IPM improved scenario

Number of growers	14 000
Acreage (ha)	46636ha (Silo- und Grünmais)
% of total acreage	100%
Production (tonnes/year)	993000 t/year
% of the total production	33.8 %

Cultivar	Most of the cultivars are resistant varieties
Cropping density	8 – 11 seeds/m ² (source: https://www.strickhof.ch/publikationen/merkblatt-mais/)
Cropping cycle	Mid April to the end of May (sowing) – Silage maize: Sept to Oct Grain maize: Oct to Nov (harvest) (source: https://www.strickhof.ch/publikationen/merkblatt-mais/)
Estimated annual yield	Silomais: 185 dt/ha Körnermais: 100 dt/ha (source: https://www.strickhof.ch/publikationen/merkblatt-mais/)
Price per kg product	Silo 4.75 CHF/dt; Körner 39.50 CHF/dt (source: https://redaktion.strickhof.ch/server/api/dokument/GetDokument?id=10295)
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Production without pesticide use: 400CHF/ha - Production without herbicides: 250 CHF/ha - Flowering strips: 3300CHF/ha - Covering of soil: 200 CHF/ha - Min-till: 250CHF/ha
Storage loss	X kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: Insecticides: Herbicides:
% drift reduction	75-99 % (source: Agridea, Reduktion der Drift und Abschwemmung von PSM im Acker- und Gemüsebau)

Minimum buffer zone to surface water	6 m (source: Agridea, Reduktion der Drift und Abschwemmung von PSM im Acker- und Gemüsebau)
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1 year break) (source: https://www.ipsuisse.ch/wp-content/plugins/pdfjs-viewer-shortcode/pdfjs/web/viewer.php?file=https://www.ipsuisse.ch/wp-content/uploads/Richtlinien_Pflanzenbau_A4_DE_RZ.pdf&attachment_id=53962&dButton=true&pButton=true&oButton=false&sButton=true#zoom=auto&pagemode=none&wponce=134ba3ed23) With which crops? Cereal crops such as wheat
Intercropping	Yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Site-specific crop rotation (legally required to have at least one year break after maize)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Mostly diseases and pests

Tool	Site specific application (application of pesticides only on those areas of the field where they are needed (precision agriculture))
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Sowing time in maize (adaption of the sowing time and seed density to support early germination and fast sprouting of maize)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Not there
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Base crop protection decision on observed pest infestation level, official thresholds, extension services, warning/forecasting systems
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Mulching
Application frequency	1x/season
Application date	after sowing
Stage of development of the crop	Well established
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Close monitoring and regular observation
Application frequency	as often as possible
Application date	entire growth until harvest
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Stale seedbed
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	April/Mai
Stage of development of the crop	Not there
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed

Tool	Beneficials and microbes
Application frequency	as often as need
Application date	entire growth until harvest
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest

Tool	Trichogramma
Application frequency	Varies
Application date	Depending on the European corn borer
Stage of development of the crop	No influence
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly Pest

Tool	Bacillus-thuringiensis
Application frequency	Varies
Application date	Depending on the European corn borer
Stage of development of the crop	No influence
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly Pest

Tool	Heterorhabditis bacteriophora
Application frequency	1x/season
Application date	Specific X
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest

Tool	Base crop protection decision on observed pest infestation level, official thresholds, extension services, warning/forecasting systems
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Plant stimulants and strengtheners
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Drift-reducing application
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Field and machine hygiene (e.g., manure free from weed seed or removal of crop residues from fields)
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application and after harvest
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Use recommended doses
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Reduced application frequency
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific

Tool	Physical measures (Flaming, steaming, freezing or flooding of fields)
Application frequency	Depends on measure

Application date	Depends on measure
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on measure
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control

Tool	Mechanical weeding with plough
Application frequency	Once to prepare seed bed
Application date	September/October
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Field and machine hygiene
Application frequency	as required
Application date	entire cultivation process
Stage of development of the crop	as soon as the wheat sprout from the soil
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weed control

Tool	Weed competitive/pest resistant cultivars
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	Mid April to the end of May
Stage of development of the crop	Not there
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed&Pest

Tool	Pesticide selection
Application frequency	Depends on product
Application date	Depends on product
Stage of development of the crop	Depends on product
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Promotion of ecological habitats in maize production systems (e.g. flowering strips, hedges or wildflower fallow.)
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	April/May
Stage of development of the crop	Sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly pest control

Tool	Shredding of maize stubble and maize straw
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	After harvesting
Stage of development of the crop	Harvested
Target pest/disease/weed	Mainly weeds and diseases control
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

6.7 Potato

6.7.1 Belgium

Contact person: Clara Sciffer (clara.sciffer@ilvo.vlaanderen.be)

Kaat Peeters (kaat.peeters@ilvo.vlaanderen.be)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: storage potatoes

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: storage potatoes

Strategy 2 – state of the art scenario: early potatoes

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario: early potatoes

Strategy 3 – state of the art scenario: seed potatoes

Strategy 3 – IPM improved scenario: seed potatoes

IPM strategies for potato cultivation in Flanders

Strategy selection

In 2021 51026 ha, which is 7.5% of the total agricultural land in Flanders, was used for potato cultivation. In total, 2144615 tonnes potatoes were produced in 2021. A distinction can be made between the cultivation of early potatoes for consumption that cannot be stored (harvest before 1/9) (6093 ha), potatoes for consumption that can be stored (harvest after 1/9) (43540 ha) and seed potatoes (1393 ha). Because of some differences in the timing and the cultivation technique, 3 separate IPM strategies will be constructed for these different cultivation systems of potato. As Flanders is a small region, there are no relevant regional differences in cultivation method to take into account.

- 1) Cultivation of storage potatoes for consumption: This includes the cultivation of mid season and late season potatoes. These potatoes can be stored during the winter/a longer period of time. Due to data availability, the data presented for this strategy will be covering the potatoes that are harvested after 1/9.
- 2) Cultivation of early potatoes for consumption: These potatoes are harvested early and cannot be stored for longer periods of time without quality loss. Due to data availability, the data presented for this strategy will be covering the potatoes that are harvested before 1/9.
- 3) Cultivation of seed potatoes: This includes the cultivation of starting material, used for the cultivation of consumption potatoes.

Description reference year:

Many potato farmers had a very hard time harvesting their potatoes in 2023, because of extreme weather conditions in the fall of 2023 (floods), resulting in yield losses. In 2022, lower yields were also noted because of dry and hot weather conditions. Because of this, the year before that (2021) will be chosen as the reference year for the following strategies. 2021 was an average year for potato production regarding yield, pest/disease pressure and weather and market conditions.

Strategy 1: potato cultivation in open field for consumption (storage potatoes)

Description

Number of growers	7482
Acreage (ha)	43540 ha
% of total acreage	85.3%
Production (tonnes/year)	1867240 tonnes/year (Statbel)(lichte onderschatting)
% of the total production	87.1% (Statbel)(lichte onderschatting)

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	35 000-40 000 plants/ha

Cropping cycle	April-October (exact cropping cycle depending on used cultivar; mid-season/late season potatoes)
Estimated annual yield	44.1 t/ha (Statbel); mean: 45-55t/ha
Price per kg product	175-185€/t VAT excl.
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	No additional subsidies connected to the specific IPM tools in this scenario.
Storage loss	6%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 7-12 Insecticides: 0-2 Herbicides: 5-7
% drift reduction	75%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1 m
Crop rotation	Yes/no (1:3) With which crops? Maize, cereals, beets, catch crops
Intercropping	Yes/ no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) during planting. Use seed potatoes that have been certified (following the EU and Belgian requirements) and checked before use.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Various diseases like <i>Phytophthora</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia</i> , various types of scabies,...

Tool	Choose a cultivar resistant to nematodes and possibly also against other various viruses and scabies. The exact choice of cultivar will also depend on the requirements in place from the buyer of the potatoes.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes and possibly also other various viruses and scabies.

Tool	Crop rotation of 1:3 years is obligatory by law; no consecutive potato cultivation allowed on the same field. There must be at least 2 years in between. However, most farmers apply an
------	---

	even broader crop rotation of 1:4 for storage potatoes.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Very effective against all soil-bound problems (wireworms, nematodes, rhizoctonia, weeds).

Tool	Field hygiene: avoid, monitor and intervene in case of 'recurring potato plants' ('aardappelopslag', which is an infection source of <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf and nematodes); yellow nutsedge; jimsonweed.
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf, nematodes, yellow nutsedge, jimsonweed

Tool	Buffer zone: a minimal 1-3m 'crop protection free' buffer zone from water courses is mandatory. This buffer zone can be larger depending on the crop protection product.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Drift reduction: use drift reducing spraying nozzles with a 75% drift reduction (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Alternate pesticides with different modes of action to avoid resistance (respect FRAC, IRAC and HRAC principles) (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/

Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of pesticide resistance.
--------------------------	------------------------------------

Tool	Close and frequent visual monitoring of the crop and other host plants to avoid contamination of other potato fields and intervene early.
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General pests, diseases and weeds

Tool	Soil treatment before planting (pesticide)
Application frequency	x0-1
Application date	Before planting the seed potatoes (April)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Wireworms, nematodes, <i>Rhizoctonia</i>

Tool	Treatment of the tubers before planting: fungicide
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Before planting (April)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Rhizoctonia</i>

Tool	Crop protection decisions are based on advice of extension services/experts
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General

Tool	General weed treatment (herbicide)(mix of 4-5 active substances) against weeds that occurred in the previous year(s) on the field.
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Half April- half May
Stage of development of the crop	Before emergence of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	General weeds like goosefoot, redshank, black nightshade, black bindweed, knotweed, cockspur grass, jimsonweed

Tool	<i>Phytophthora</i> treatment (fungicide)
Application frequency	x10-15
Application date	Half May-harvest (depending on the cultivar used: harvest between half August-October)

Stage of development of the crop	Intervention needed from the infection period of the fungus until the harvest of the crop (i.e. until the leaves are active).
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Insecticide treatment against Colorado bug
Application frequency	x0-1
Application date	July
Stage of development of the crop	The Colorado bug damages the leaves of the potato plants
Target pest/disease/weed	Colorado bug

Tool	<i>Alternaria</i> treatment (fungicide). This can be combined with a <i>Phytophthora</i> fungicide treatment.
Application frequency	x3-4
Application date	Half July-half September
Stage of development of the crop	Intervention needed from the infection period of the fungus until 2 weeks before the first chemical haulm killing .
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Alternaria</i>

Tool	Sprout inhibition on the field (chemical treatment with maleïnehydrazide)
Application frequency	x1
Application date	July-half September
Stage of development of the crop	3 weeks before the haulm killing starts
Target pest/disease/weed	Against recurring potato plants ('aardappelopslag'), which is an infection source of <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf and nematodes.

Tool	Chemical haulm killing (herbicide) for artificial induction of tuber periderm maturation, controlling tuber size and reducing vine volume to increase harvest efficiency. This also ensure that the tubers keep their quality. As diquat is not allowed anymore, the 2 most important alternative active substances are carfentrazone-ethyl and pyraflufen-ethyl.
Application frequency	x2
Application date	14 days before harvest (August-October)
Stage of development of the crop	14 days before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Important for the potato quality

Tool	Sprout inhibition during storage (post harvest) using herbicides. As chloorprofam is not allowed in the EU anymore, these 4 alternative active substances are now used (and allowed) during the storage of potatoes: 1,4 dimethyl naphthalene, mint oil, orange oil, ethylene).
Application frequency	From December/January on: every 6-8 weeks, depending on the sprouting characteristics of the potatoes.
Application date	December/January-end of the storage
Stage of development of the crop	After the harvest during the storage
Target pest/disease/weed	Important for the potato quality

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	35 000-40 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	April-October (exact cropping cycle depending on used cultivar; mid season/late season potatoes)
Estimated annual yield	44.1 t/ha (Statbel); mean: 45-55t/ha
Price per kg product	175-185€/kg VAT excl.
Amount of direct payments	No additional subsidies connected to the specific IPM tools in this scenario.
Storage loss	6%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 7-11 Insecticides: 0-1 Herbicides: 5-7
% drift reduction	75%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1 m
Crop rotation	Yes/no
	With which crops? Maize, cereals, beets, catch crops
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) during planting. Use seed potatoes that have been certified (following the EU and Belgian requirements) and checked before use.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Various diseases like <i>Phytophthora</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia</i> , various types of scabies,...

Tool	Choose a cultivar resistant to nematodes based on the nematode identification in the lab. The cultivar can possibly also have resistance for other various viruses and scabies. The exact choice of cultivar will also depend on the requirements in place from the buyer of the potatoes.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes and possibly also other various viruses and scabies.

Tool	Nematode identification in the lab, based on a soil sample. By identifying the exact type of nematodes present in the soil, the choice of a resistant cultivar against nematodes is more effective.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes

Tool	Crop rotation of 1:5 years; no consecutive potato cultivation allowed on the same field. Legally, there must be at least 2 years in between, but preferably there are 3-4 years in between 2 potato crops on the same field.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Very effective against all soil-bound problems (wireworms, nematodes, rhizoctonia, weeds).

Tool	<p>Field hygiene: avoid, monitor and intervene in case of 'recurring potato plants' ('aardappelopslag', which is an infection source of <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf and nematodes); yellow nutsedge; jimsonweed.</p> <p>Field choice: choose the fields that are best fit for growing potatoes. E.g. if certain fields on your farm have persistent weeds/diseases/pests that are problematic in the cultivation of potatoes, choose another field.</p>
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle

Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf, nematodes, yellow nutsedge, jimsonweed

Tool	Buffer zone: a minimal 1-3m 'crop protection free' buffer zone from water courses is mandatory. This buffer zone can be larger depending on the crop protection product.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Drift reduction: use drift reducing spraying nozzles with a 75% drift reduction (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Alternate pesticides with different modes of action to avoid resistance (respect FRAC, IRAC and HRAC principles) (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of pesticide resistance.

Tool	Close and frequent visual monitoring of the crop and other host plants to avoid contamination of other potato fields and intervene early.
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General pests, diseases and weeds

Tool	Use warning systems (weather models) of research stations (for potato blight, <i>Alternaria</i> , aphids, Colorado beetle,...).
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle

Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i> , <i>Alternaria</i> , Colorado bug, aphids,...

Tool	Treatment of the tubers before planting: fungicide
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Before planting (April)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Rhizoctonia</i>

Tool	Crop protection decisions are based on advice of extension services/experts
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General

Tool	General weed treatment (herbicide)(mix of 4-5 active substances) against weeds that occurred in the previous year(s) on the field.
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Half April- half May
Stage of development of the crop	Before emergence of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	General weeds like goosefoot, redshank, black nightshade, black bindweed, knotweed, cockspur grass, jimsonweed

Tool	<i>Phytophthora</i> treatment (fungicide)
Application frequency	x10-15
Application date	Half May-harvest (depending on the cultivar used: harvest between half August-October)
Stage of development of the crop	Intervention needed from the infection period of the fungus until the harvest of the crop (i.e. until the leaves are active).
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Insecticide treatment against Colorado bug
Application frequency	x0-1
Application date	July
Stage of development of the crop	The Colorado bug damages the leaves of the potato plants
Target pest/disease/weed	Colorado bug

Tool	<i>Alternaria</i> treatment (fungicide). This can be combined with a <i>Phytophthora</i> fungicide treatment.
Application frequency	x3-4
Application date	Half July-half September
Stage of development of the crop	Intervention needed from the infection period of the fungus until 2 weeks before the first chemical haulm killing .
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Alternaria</i>

Tool	Sprout inhibition on the field (chemical treatment with maleïnehydrazide)
Application frequency	x1
Application date	July-half September
Stage of development of the crop	3 weeks before the haulm killing starts
Target pest/disease/weed	Against recurring potato plants ('aardappelopslag'), which is an infection source of <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf and nematodes.

Tool	Chemical haulm killing (herbicide) for artificial induction of tuber periderm maturation, controlling tuber size and reducing vine volume to increase harvest efficiency. This also ensure that the tubers keep their quality. As diquat is not allowed anymore, the 2 most important alternative active substances are carfentrazone-ethyl and pyraflufen-ethyl.
Application frequency	x2
Application date	14 days before harvest (August-October)
Stage of development of the crop	14 days before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Important for the potato quality

Tool	Sprout inhibition during storage (post harvest) using herbicides. As chloorprofam is not allowed in the EU anymore, these 4 alternative active substances are now used (and allowed) during the storage of potatoes: 1,4 dimethyl naphthalene, mint oil, orange oil, ethylene).
Application frequency	From December/January on: every 6-8 weeks, depending on the sprouting characteristics of the potatoes.
Application date	December/January-end of the storage
Stage of development of the crop	After the harvest during the storage
Target pest/disease/weed	Important for the potato quality

Strategy 2: potato cultivation in open field for consumption (early potatoes)

Description

Number of growers	1603
Acreage (ha)	6093 ha
% of total acreage	11.9%
Production (tonnes/year)	239353 tonnes/year (Statbel)
% of the total production	11.2% (Statbel)

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	50 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	March - August
Estimated annual yield	40.3 t/ha (Statbel); mean: 40-45 t/ha
Price per kg product	100-140€/kg
Amount of direct payments	No additional subsidies connected to the specific IPM tools in this scenario.
Storage loss	Early potatoes are generally not stored
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 6-10 Insecticides: 0-1 Herbicides: 3-5
% drift reduction	75%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1 m
Crop rotation	Yes/no
	With which crops? Maize, cereals, beets, catch crops
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) during planting. Use seed potatoes that have been certified (following the EU and Belgian requirements) and checked before use.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	March
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Various diseases like <i>Phytophthora</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia</i> , various types of scabies,...

Tool	Choose a cultivar resistant to nematodes and possibly also against other various viruses and scabies. The exact choice of cultivar will also
------	--

	depend on the requirements in place from the buyer of the potatoes.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	March
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes and possibly also other various viruses and scabies.

Tool	Crop rotation of 1:3 years; no consecutive potato cultivation allowed on the same field. There must be at least 2 years in between.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Very effective against all soil-bound problems (wireworms, nematodes, rhizoctonia, weeds).

Tool	Field hygiene: avoid, monitor and intervene in case of 'recurring potato plants' ('aardappelopslag', which is an infection source of <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf and nematodes); yellow nutsedge; jimsonweed.
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf, nematodes, yellow nutsedge, jimsonweed

Tool	Buffer zone: a minimal 1-3m 'crop protection free' buffer zone from water courses is mandatory. This buffer zone can be larger depending on the crop protection product.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Drift reduction: use drift reducing spraying nozzles with a 75% drift reduction (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/

Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.
--------------------------	--

Tool	Alternate pesticides with different modes of action to avoid resistance (respect FRAC, IRAC and HRAC principles) (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of pesticide resistance.

Tool	Close and frequent visual monitoring of the crop and other host plants to avoid contamination of other potato fields and intervene early.
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General pests, diseases and weeds

Tool	Soil treatment before planting (pesticide)
Application frequency	x0-1
Application date	Before planting the seed potatoes (March)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Wireworms, nematodes, <i>Rhizoctonia</i>

Tool	Treatment of the tubers before planting: fungicide
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Before planting (March)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Rhizoctonia</i>

Tool	Crop protection decisions are based on advice of extension services/experts
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General

Tool	General weed treatment (herbicide)(mix of 4-5 active substances) against weeds that occurred in the previous year(s) on the field.
Application frequency	x1

Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Before emergence of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	General weeds like goosefoot, redshank, black nightshade, black bindweed, knotweed, cockspur grass, jimsonweed

Tool	<i>Phytophthora</i> treatment (fungicide)
Application frequency	X8-10
Application date	Half May-harvest (July-August)
Stage of development of the crop	Intervention needed from the infection period of the fungus until the harvest of the crop (i.e. until the leaves are active).
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Chemical haulm killing (herbicide) for artificial induction of tuber periderm maturation, controlling tuber size and reducing vine volume to increase harvest efficiency. This also ensures that the tubers keep their quality. As diquat is not allowed anymore, the 2 most important alternative active substances are carfentrazone-ethyl and pyraflufen-ethyl.
Application frequency	x2
Application date	14 days before harvest (half June-half August)
Stage of development of the crop	14 days before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Important for the potato quality

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	50000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	March - August
Estimated annual yield	40.3 t/ha (Statbel); mean: 40-45 t/ha
Price per kg product	100-140€/kg
Amount of direct payments	No additional subsidies connected to the specific IPM tools in this scenario.
Storage loss	Early potatoes are generally not stored
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 6-10 Insecticides: 4-6 Herbicides: 3-5
% drift reduction	75%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1 m
Crop rotation	Yes/no

	With which crops? Maize, cereals, beets, catch crops
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) during planting. Use seed potatoes that have been certified (following the EU and Belgian requirements) and checked before use.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	March
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Various diseases like <i>Phytophthora</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia</i> , various types of scabies,...

Tool	Choose a cultivar resistant to nematodes based on the nematode identification in the lab. The cultivar can possibly also have resistance for other various viruses and scabies. The exact choice of cultivar will also depend on the requirements in place from the buyer of the potatoes.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	March
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes and possibly also other various viruses and scabies.

Tool	Nematode identification in the lab, based on a soil sample. By identifying the exact type of nematodes present in the soil, the choice of a resistant cultivar against nematodes is more effective.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes

Tool	Crop rotation of 1:4-5 years; no consecutive potato cultivation allowed on the same field. Legally, there must be at least 2 years in between, but preferably there are 3-4 years in between 2 potato crops on the same field.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always

Target pest/disease/weed	Very effective against all soil-bound problems (wireworms, nematodes, rhizoctonia, weeds).
--------------------------	--

Tool	Field hygiene: avoid, monitor and intervene in case of 'recurring potato plants' ('aardappelopslag', which is an infection source of <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf and nematodes); yellow nutsedge; jimsonweed. Field choice: choose the fields that are best fit for growing potatoes. E.g. if certain fields on your farm have persistent weeds/diseases/pests that are problematic in the cultivation of potatoes, choose another field.
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf, nematodes, yellow nutsedge, jimsonweed

Tool	Buffer zone: a minimal 1-3m 'crop protection free' buffer zone from water courses is mandatory. This buffer zone can be larger depending on the crop protection product.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Drift reduction: use drift reducing spraying nozzles with a 75% drift reduction (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Alternate pesticides with different modes of action to avoid resistance (respect FRAC, IRAC and HRAC principles) (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/

Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of pesticide resistance.
--------------------------	------------------------------------

Tool	Close and frequent visual monitoring of the crop and other host plants to avoid contamination of other potato fields and intervene early.
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General pests, diseases and weeds

Tool	Use warning systems (weather models) of research stations (for potato blight, <i>Alternaria</i> , aphids, Colorado beetle,...).
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i> , <i>Alternaria</i> , Colorado bug, aphids,...

Tool	Treatment of the tubers before planting: fungicide
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Before planting (March)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Rhizoctonia</i>

Tool	Crop protection decisions are based on advice of extension services/experts
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General

Tool	General weed treatment (herbicide)(mix of 4-5 active substances) against weeds that occurred in the previous year(s) on the field.
Application frequency	x1
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Before emergence of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	General weeds like goosefoot, redshank, black nightshade, black bindweed, knotweed, cockspur grass, jimsonweed

Tool	<i>Phytophthora</i> treatment (fungicide)
Application frequency	x8-10
Application date	Half May-harvest (July-August)
Stage of development of the crop	Intervention needed from the infection period of the fungus until the harvest of the crop (i.e. until the leaves are active).
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Chemical haulm killing (herbicide) for artificial induction of tuber periderm maturation, controlling tuber size and reducing vine volume to increase harvest efficiency. This also ensures that the tubers keep their quality. As diquat is not allowed anymore, the 2 most important alternative active substances are carfentrazone-ethyl and pyraflufen-ethyl.
Application frequency	x2
Application date	14 days before harvest (half June-half August)
Stage of development of the crop	14 days before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Important for the potato quality

Strategy 3: seed potato cultivation in open field (starting material)

Description

Number of growers	291
Acreage (ha)	1393
% of total acreage	2.7%
Production (tonnes/year)	38022 tonnes/year (Statbel)
% of the total production	1.8% (Statbel)

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	50 000-86 0000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	March/April – August
Estimated annual yield	27.4 t/ha (Statbel)
Price per kg product	€/kg
Amount of direct payments	No additional subsidies connected to the specific IPM tools in this scenario.
Storage loss	6%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 6-10 Insecticides: 4-6 Herbicides: 3-5
% drift reduction	75%

Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1 m
Crop rotation	Yes/no
	With which crops? Maize, cereals, beets, catch crops
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use healthy planting material (seed potatoes). Use seed potatoes that have been certified (following the EU and Belgian requirements) and checked before use.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Various diseases like <i>Phytophthora</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia</i> , various types of scabies,...

Tool	Choose a cultivar resistant to nematodes and possibly also against other various viruses and scabies. The exact choice of cultivar will also depend on the requirements in place from the buyer of the potatoes.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes and possibly also other various viruses and scabies.

Tool	Crop rotation of 1:4 years; no consecutive seed potato cultivation allowed on the same field. Legally, there must be at least 3 years in between.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Very effective against all soil-bound problems (wireworms, nematodes, rhizoctonia, weeds).

Tool	Field hygiene: avoid, monitor and intervene in case of 'recurring potato plants' ('aardappelopslag', which is an infection source of <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf and nematodes); yellow nutsedge; jimsonweed. Field choice: choose the fields that are best fit for growing potatoes. E.g. if certain fields on
------	---

	your farm have persistent weeds/diseases/pests (like aphids) that are problematic in the cultivation of potatoes, choose another field.
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf, nematodes, yellow nutsedge, jimsonweed, aphids

Tool	Soil sample + analysis to make sure the field is free from quarantine organisms (nematodes) like <i>Globodera</i> spp. and <i>Meloidogyne</i> spp.
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Before planting the seed potatoes (March)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes (<i>Globodera</i> spp., <i>Meloidogyne</i> spp.)

Tool	Buffer zone: a minimal 1-3m 'crop protection free' buffer zone from water courses is mandatory. This buffer zone can be larger depending on the crop protection product.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Drift reduction: use drift reducing spraying nozzles with a 75% drift reduction (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Alternate pesticides with different modes of action to avoid resistance (respect FRAC, IRAC and HRAC principles) (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of pesticide resistance.

Tool	Close and frequent visual monitoring of the crop and other host plants to avoid contamination of other potato fields and intervene early.
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General pests, diseases and weeds

Tool	Soil treatment before planting (pesticide)
Application frequency	x0-1
Application date	Before planting the seed potatoes (March/April)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Wireworms, nematodes, <i>Rhizoctonia</i>

Tool	Treatment of the tubers before planting: fungicide
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Before planting (March/April)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Rhizoctonia</i>

Tool	Crop protection decisions are based on advice of extension services/experts
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General

Tool	General weed treatment (herbicide)(mix of 4-5 active substances) against weeds that occurred in the previous year(s) on the field.
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Half April- half May
Stage of development of the crop	Before emergence of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	General weeds like goosefoot, redshank, black nightshade, black bindweed, knotweed, cockspur grass, jimsonweed

Tool	<i>Phytophthora</i> treatment (fungicide)
Application frequency	x-8-10
Application date	Half May-harvest (end of July-beginning of August)

Stage of development of the crop	Intervention needed from the infection period of the fungus until the harvest of the crop (i.e. until the leaves are active).
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Insecticide treatment against Colorado bug
Application frequency	x0-1
Application date	July
Stage of development of the crop	The Colorado bug damages the leaves of the potato plants
Target pest/disease/weed	Colorado bug

Tool	Treatment against aphids (insecticide), as they can damage the potato plants (which results in a lower production and quality) and are carriers of viruses like the Y-virus, which can lower the quality of the seed potatoes.
Application frequency	x8-10
Application date	June-harvest
Stage of development of the crop	From 80% emergence until the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Aphids

Tool	Chemical haulm killing (herbicide) for artificial induction of tuber periderm maturation, controlling tuber size (very important in seed potatoes) and reducing vine volume to increase harvest efficiency. This also ensure that the tubers keep their quality. As diquat is not allowed anymore, the 2 most important alternative active substances are carfentrazone-ethyl and pyraflufen-ethyl.
Application frequency	x3
Application date	14 days before harvest (July- beginning of August)
Stage of development of the crop	14 days before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Important for the potato quality

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	50 000-86 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	March/April – August
Estimated annual yield	27.4 t/ha
Price per kg product	€/kg

Amount of direct payments	No additional subsidies connected to the specific IPM tools in this scenario.
Storage loss	6%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 5-8 Insecticides: 5 Herbicides: 3-9
% drift reduction	75 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1 m
Crop rotation	Yes/no
	With which crops? Maize, cereals, beets, catch crops
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use healthy planting material (seed potatoes). Use seed potatoes that have been certified (following the EU and Belgian requirements) and checked before use.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Various diseases like <i>Phytophthora</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia</i> , various types of scabies,...

Tool	Choose a cultivar resistant to nematodes and possibly also against other various viruses and scabies. The exact choice of cultivar will also depend on the requirements in place from the buyer of the potatoes.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes and possibly also other various viruses and scabies.

Tool	Crop rotation of 1:4-5 years; no consecutive seed potato cultivation allowed on the same field. Legally, there must be at least 3 years in between, but preferably more.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Very effective against all soil-bound problems (wireworms, nematodes, rhizoctonia, weeds).

Tool	Field hygiene: avoid, monitor and intervene in case of 'recurring potato plants' ('aardappelopslag', which is an infection source of <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf and nematodes); yellow nutsedge; jimsonweed. Field choice: choose the fields that are best fit for growing potatoes. E.g. if certain fields on your farm have persistent weeds/diseases/pests (like aphids) that are problematic in the cultivation of potatoes, choose another field.
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf, nematodes, yellow nutsedge, jimsonweed, aphids

Tool	Soil sample + analysis to make sure the field is free from quarantine organisms (nematodes) like <i>Globodera</i> spp. and <i>Meloidogyne</i> spp.
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Before planting the seed potatoes (March)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes (<i>Globodera</i> spp., <i>Meloidogyne</i> spp.)

Tool	Buffer zone: a minimal 1-3m 'crop protection free' buffer zone from water courses is mandatory. This buffer zone can be larger depending on the crop protection product.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Drift reduction: use drift reducing spraying nozzles with a 75% drift reduction (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Alternate pesticides with different modes of action to avoid resistance (respect FRAC, IRAC and HRAC principles) (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	/
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of pesticide resistance.

Tool	Close and frequent visual monitoring of the crop and other host plants to avoid contamination of other potato fields and intervene early.
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General pests, diseases and weeds

Tool	Use warning systems (weather models) of research stations (for potato blight, <i>Alternaria</i> , aphids, Colorado beetle,...).
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i> , <i>Alternaria</i> , Colorado bug, aphids,...

Tool	Soil treatment before planting (pesticide)
Application frequency	x0-1
Application date	Before planting the seed potatoes (March/April)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Wireworms, nematodes, <i>Rhizoctonia</i>

Tool	Treatment of the tubers before planting: fungicide
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Before planting (March/April)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Rhizoctonia</i>

Tool	Crop protection decisions are based on advice of extension services/experts
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle

Target pest/disease/weed	General
--------------------------	---------

Tool	General weed treatment (herbicide)(mix of 4-5 active substances) against weeds that occurred in the previous year(s) on the field.
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Half April- half May
Stage of development of the crop	Before emergence of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	General weeds like goosefoot, redshank, black nightshade, black bindweed, knotweed, cockspur grass, jimsonweed

Tool	<i>Phytophthora</i> treatment (fungicide)
Application frequency	x-8-10
Application date	Half May-harvest (end of July-beginning of August)
Stage of development of the crop	Intervention needed from the infection period of the fungus until the harvest of the crop (i.e. until the leaves are active).
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Insecticide treatment against Colorado bug
Application frequency	x0-1
Application date	July
Stage of development of the crop	The Colorado bug damages the leaves of the potato plants
Target pest/disease/weed	Colorado bug

Tool	Treatment against aphids (insecticide), as they can damage the potato plants (which results in a lower production and quality) and are carriers of viruses like the Y-virus, which can lower the quality of the seed potatoes.
Application frequency	x8-10
Application date	June-harvest
Stage of development of the crop	From 80% emergence until the harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Aphids

Tool	A combination of mechanical (1x) and chemical (2x) haulm killing (herbicide) for artificial induction of tuber periderm maturation, controlling tuber size (very important in seed potatoes) and reducing vine volume to increase harvest efficiency. This also ensure that the tubers keep their quality. As diquat is not allowed anymore, the 2 most important
------	---

	alternative active substances for chemical haulm killing are carfentrazone-ethyl and pyraflufen-ethyl.
Application frequency	x3 (1x mechanical + 2x chemical)
Application date	14 days before harvest (July- beginning of August)
Stage of development of the crop	14 days before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Important for the potato seed quality

References

Personal communication with potato advisors

Statbel, 2021, Landbouwgegevens van 2021, [Land- en tuinbouwbedrijven | Statbel \(fgov.be\)](#)

Agentschap landbouw & zeevisserij, 2024, Analyse recentste perceelsaangifte, [Analyse recentste perceelsaangifte | Landbouw & Visserij \(vlaanderen.be\)](#)

6.7.2 Germany

Contact person: Lars Ole Hingst (Lars-Ole.Hingst@julius-kuehn.de)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: early potatoes, under foil

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: early potatoes, under foil

Strategy 2 – state of the art scenario: storage potatoes, for consumption

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario: storage potatoes, for consumption

Strategy 3 – state of the art scenario: starch potatoes, industry

Strategy 3 – IPM improved scenario: starch potatoes, industry

IPM strategies for early and late consumption potatoes, starch potatoes

Strategy selection

Three strategies are discussed below, which differ fundamentally in the production goal of potatoes. A distinction is made between early table potatoes, late table potatoes that are also suitable for storage and starch potatoes.

The biggest and most influential differences are the varieties and how long the growing phase of the potatoes is. The longer it is, the greater the pressure from harmful organisms and therefore the treatment index with plant protection products. With potatoes, however, the main focus is on the desired varietal characteristics. Therefore, popular varieties that are in high demand usually don't have good tolerance to harmful organisms.

Early table potatoes have the advantage that they are not so strongly exposed to harmful organisms within a short growing period. A harvest that starts in mid-May/at the beginning of June is usually already ripe when *Phytophthora* treatments have to be carried out regularly. However, there is also an increased labour requirement due to the application of a film. The soil must also be passable for sowing in March. However, the yield is also lower and therefore the costs tend to be higher.

Late table potatoes are harvested from July to September, i.e. they must be regularly treated against *Phytophthora*. Depending on the weather, the interval between treatments may be longer or shorter.

Starch potatoes and potatoes for processing are harvested from September to October. Due to the longer vegetation period, the plant must be kept healthy for longer. The ingredients (starch) are also of particular importance here.

Description reference year:

2021

Description, as no more precise information is available, these figures apply to total potato production in Germany (<https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Branchen-Unternehmen/Landwirtschaft-Forstwirtschaft-Fischerei/Feldfruechte-Gruenland/Tabellen/liste-feldfruechte-zeitreihe.html#123344>)

Number of growers	X
Acreage (ha)	258 300 ha
% of total acreage	X %
t/ha	43,79 t/ha
Production (tonnes/year)	11 312 100 tonnes/year
% of the total production	X %

Strategy 1: early potatoes, for consumption

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	3-4 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	End march-june
Estimated annual yield	15 t/ha
Price per kg product	60-80€/dt
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	-
Storage loss	Not for storage
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products):

	Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X
% drift reduction	Depends of the used PPP, often min 50%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Depends of the used PPP, often min 5m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3) With which crops? Wheat, barley, rapeseed
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Chemical Phytophthora treatment, based on a warning system, after removing the foil, sometimes a treatment against late infection with <i>Phytophthora</i> is necessary
Application frequency	1-2x
Application date	half May – until haulm killing is completed (at the latest half October)
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Herbicide treatment after emerging can be used but is not necessary
Application frequency	1
Application date	After emerging
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Halum killing, to obtain a good potato quality
Application frequency	1 (can be split)
Application date	Before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	Crop rotation. Potatoes in particular are susceptible to diseases, which is why a wide crop rotation should be ensured
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	all

Tool	High yield/quality varieties, often a trade-off between yield quality and resistance characteristics, especially in the case of potatoes, consumers and the industry are fixed on certain varieties
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Healthy plant material, is a basis for a healthy emergence and a good development of the plant, previously infected seeds can lead to a total failure
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Pesticides with different MoA (especially fungicide), as otherwise resistance will occur quickly and render existing PPPs ineffective
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Monitoring diseases, Monitoring diseases is also very important for potatoes, as fungal pathogens can spread quickly and cause considerable losses. However, due to the short vegetation period for early potatoes, most diseases are only of great relevance when harvesting begins. But care must also be taken with Phytophthora
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating?
Cropping density	3-4 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	End march-june
Estimated annual yield	15 t/ha
Price per kg product	60-80€/dt
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	-
Storage loss	Not for storage
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X
% drift reduction	Depends of the used PPP, often min 50%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Depends of the used PPP, often min 5m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:5) With which crops? Wheat, barley, rapeseed, maize, sugar beet, rye, triticale
Intercropping	yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Chemical <i>Phytophthora</i> treatment, based on a warning system.
Application frequency	1-2x
Application date	half May – until haulm killing is completed (at the latest half October)
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Crop rotation 1:5
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	all

Tool	Nematode identification, can be important to select the right variety resistance and to have a general overview of the pests present
Application frequency	X
Application date	
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes, pest

Tool	Resistant and tolerant cultivars, some varieties have good resistance properties
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest and disease

Tool	Field and machine hygiene, are the prerequisites for a healthy and strong plant. however, due to time constraints, these are also measures that cannot always be implemented
Application frequency	X
Application date	Everytime a machine is used
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease/weed

Tool	Healthy plant material, is a basis for a healthy emergence and a good development of the plant, previously infected seeds can lead to a total failure
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Pesticides with different MoA (especially fungicide), as otherwise resistance will occur quickly and render existing PPPs ineffective
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Monitoring diseases, Monitoring diseases is also very important for potatoes, as fungal pathogens can spread quickly and cause considerable losses. However, due to the short vegetation period for early potatoes, most diseases are only of great relevance when harvesting begins. But care must also be taken with <i>Phytophthora</i>
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Warning system, for <i>Phytophthora</i> and <i>Alternaria</i> , very useful as they predict the spraying start and spraying distances for an area, but are not a substitute for on-site monitoring, they are weather dynamic tools that are very helpful
------	--

Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Herbicide treatment after emerging can be done, but is not necessary
Application frequency	1
Application date	After emerging
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Haulm killing + mechanical weed removal; to obtain a good potato quality. The combination of chemical and mechanical can provide a good combination. Sometimes mechanical can be sufficient
Application frequency	1 (can be split)
Application date	Before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	Tuber treatment; a very effective measure, especially for diseases that can be transmitted by seedlings. Also so that good and strong plants emerge
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Mechanical weeding, a method to keep weeds out of the crop until the plants are large enough
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	CP decisions based on advice of extension service/experts, can help with spray decisions to choose the right product at the right time to achieve an optimal result
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Strategy 2: storage potatoes, for consumption

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	4 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	End march/mid april-july/end september
Estimated annual yield	25-50 t/ha
Price per kg product	35-50 €/dt
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	X kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X
% drift reduction	Depends of the used PPP, often min 50%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Depends of the used PPP, often min 5m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3) With which crops? Wheat, rapeseed
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Chemical <i>Phytophthora</i> treatment, based on a warning system, after removing the foil, sometimes a treatment against late infection with <i>Phytophthora</i> is necessary
Application frequency	8-12x
Application date	half May – until haulm killing is completed (at the latest half October)
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Herbicide treatment after emerging can be used but is not necessary
Application frequency	1
Application date	After emerging
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Haulm killing, to obtain a good potato quality
Application frequency	1 (can be split)
Application date	Before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	Crop rotation. Potatoes in particular are susceptible to diseases, which is why a wide crop rotation should be ensured
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	all

Tool	High yield/quality varieties, often a trade-off between yield quality and resistance characteristics, especially in the case of
------	---

	potatoes, consumers and the industry are fixed on certain varieties
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Healthy plant material, is a basis for a healthy emergence and a good development of the plant, previously infected seeds can lead to a total failure
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Pesticides with different MoA (especially fungicide), as otherwise resistance will occur quickly and render existing PPPs ineffective
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Monitoring diseases. Monitoring diseases is also very important for potatoes, as fungal pathogens can spread quickly and cause considerable losses. However, due to the short vegetation period for early potatoes, most diseases are only of great relevance when harvesting begins. But care must also be taken with <i>Phytophthora</i>
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Insecticide, especially against potato bugs and aphids
Application frequency	2-3x
Application date	depending on the infestation
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	4 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	End march/mid april-july/end september
Estimated annual yield	25-50 t/ha
Price per kg product	35-50 €/dt
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	X kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X
% drift reduction	Depends of the used PPP, often min 50%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Depends of the used PPP, often min 5m

Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:5) With which crops? Wheat, rapeseed, maize, rey, barley, sugar beet, pees
Intercropping	yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Chemical <i>Phytophthora</i> treatment, based on a warning system.
Application frequency	8-12 x
Application date	half May – until haulm killing is completed (at the latest half October)
Target pest/disease/weed	Phytophthora infestans

Tool	Crop rotation 1:5
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	all

Tool	Nematode identification, can be important to select the right variety resistance and to have a general overview of the pests present
Application frequency	X
Application date	
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes, pest

Tool	Resistant and tolerant cultivars, some varieties have good resistance properties
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest and disease

Tool	Field and machine hygiene, are the prerequisites for a healthy and strong plant. however, due to time constraints, these are also measures that cannot always be implemented
Application frequency	X
Application date	Every time a machine is used
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease/weed

Tool	Healthy plant material is a basis for a healthy emergence and a good development of the plant, previously infected seeds can lead to a total failure
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Pesticides with different MoA (especially fungicide), as otherwise resistance will occur quickly and render existing PPPs ineffective
Application frequency	X
Application date	X

Target pest/disease/weed	X
--------------------------	---

Tool	Monitoring diseases. Monitoring diseases is also very important for potatoes, as fungal pathogens can spread quickly and cause considerable losses. However, due to the short vegetation period for early potatoes, most diseases are only of great relevance when harvesting begins. But care must also be taken with <i>Phytophthora</i>
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Warning system, for <i>Phytophthora</i> and <i>Alternaria</i> , very useful as they predict the spraying start and spraying distances for an area, but are not a substitute for on-site monitoring, they are weather dynamic tools that are very helpful
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Herbicide treatment after emerging can be done, but is not necessary
Application frequency	1
Application date	After emerging
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Haulm killing + mechanical weed removal; to obtain a good potato quality. The combination of chemical and mechanical can provide a good combination. Sometimes mechanical can be sufficient
Application frequency	1 (can be split)
Application date	Before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	Tuber treatment. A very effective measure, especially for diseases that can be transmitted by seedlings. Also so that good and strong plants emerge
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Mechanical weeding; a method to keep weeds out of the crop until the plants are large enough
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	CP decisions based on advice of extension service/experts, can help with spray decisions to choose the right product at the right time to achieve an optimal result
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

Strategy 3: starch potatoes, industry

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	4 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	Mid april- September-mid october
Estimated annual yield	>50 t/ha
Price per kg product	Ca. 70 €/t
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	X kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X
% drift reduction	Depends of the used PPP, often min 50%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Depends of the used PPP, often min 5m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3)
	With which crops? Wheat, rapeseed
Intercropping	no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Chemical <i>Phytophthora</i> treatment, based on a warning system, after removing the foil, sometimes a treatment against late infection with <i>Phytophthora</i> is necessary
Application frequency	8-12x
Application date	half May – until haulm killing is completed (at the latest half October)
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Herbicide treatment after emerging can be used but is not necessary
Application frequency	1
Application date	After emerging
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Halum killing, to obtain a good potato quality
Application frequency	1 (can be split)
Application date	Before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	Crop rotation. Potatoes in particular are susceptible to diseases, which is why a wide crop rotation should be ensured
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	all

Tool	High yield/quality varieties, often a trade-off between yield quality and resistance characteristics, especially in the case of potatoes, consumers and the industry are fixed on certain varieties
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Healthy plant material, is a basis for a healthy emergence and a good development of the plant, previously infected seeds can lead to a total failure
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Pesticides with different MoA (especially fungicide), as otherwise resistance will occur quickly and render existing PPPs ineffective
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Monitoring diseases. Monitoring diseases is also very important for potatoes, as fungal pathogens can spread quickly and cause considerable losses. However, due to the short vegetation period for early potatoes, most diseases are only of great relevance when harvesting begins. But care must also be taken with <i>Phytophthora</i>
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Insecticide, especially against potato bugs and aphids
Application frequency	2-3x
Application date	depending on the infestation
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	4 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	mid april-july/mid September - end october
Estimated annual yield	> 50 t/ha

Price per kg product	70 €/t
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	X kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X
% drift reduction	Depends of the used PPP, often min 50%
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Depends of the used PPP, often min 5m
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:5)
	With which crops? Wheat, rapeseed, maize, rye, barley, sugar beet, pees
Intercropping	yes

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Chemical <i>Phytophthora</i> treatment, based on a warning system.
Application frequency	8-12 x
Application date	half May – until haulm killing is completed (at the latest half October)
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Crop rotation 1:5
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	all

Tool	Nematode identification can be important to select the right variety resistance and to have a general overview of the pests present
Application frequency	X
Application date	
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes, pest

Tool	Resistant and tolerant cultivars, some varieties have good resistance properties
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest and disease

Tool	Field and machine hygiene, are the prerequisites for a healthy and strong plant. however, due to time constraints, these are also measures that cannot always be implemented
Application frequency	X
Application date	Every time a machine is used
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease/weed

Tool	Healthy plant material, is a basis for a healthy emergence and a good development of the
------	--

	plant, previously infected seeds can lead to a total failure
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Pesticides with different MoA (especially fungicide), as otherwise resistance will occur quickly and render existing PPPs ineffective
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Monitoring diseases. Monitoring diseases is also very important for potatoes, as fungal pathogens can spread quickly and cause considerable losses. However, due to the short vegetation period for early potatoes, most diseases are only of great relevance when harvesting begins. But care must also be taken with <i>Phytophthora</i>
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	Warning system for <i>Phytophthora</i> and <i>Alternaria</i> , very useful as they predict the spraying start and spraying distances for an area, but are not a substitute for on-site monitoring, they are weather dynamic tools that are very helpful
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	pest

Tool	Herbicide treatment after emerging can be done, but is not necessary
Application frequency	1
Application date	After emerging
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool	Haulm killing + mechanical weed removal; to obtain a good potato quality. The combination of chemical and mechanical can provide a good combination. Sometimes mechanical can be sufficient
Application frequency	1 (can be split)
Application date	Before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	Tuber treatment; a very effective measure, especially for diseases that can be transmitted by seedlings. Also so that good and strong plants emerge
Application frequency	X

Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	disease

Tool	Mechanical weeding; a method to keep weeds out of the crop until the plants are large enough
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	weed

Tool	CP decisions based on advice of extension service/experts, can help with spray decisions to choose the right product at the right time to achieve an optimal result
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	pest/disease/weed

6.7.3 Denmark

Contact person: Jens Erik Jensen (jinj@seges.dk)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: starch potatoes in Denmark

Strategy 1 – improved IPM scenario: starch potatoes in Denmark

IPM strategies for [Starch potatoes in Denmark]

Strategy selection

The strategy below is based on the NCC meeting for potato held on 6 June 2023. All the strategies mentioned below were suggested by participating farmers and advisers as being common in practice. When discussing about improved IPM scenarios, it was much more difficult to come up with concrete suggestions. Farmers have high expectations to plant breeding resulting in cultivars with much better late blight resistance in the future, but this is not something that can be implemented in practice today. Several more experimental tools were discussed, but as they are not commonly used in practice, they are not mentioned here.

The strategy below shows how potatoes for starch are grown in a “normal year” in Denmark from 2023 and onwards. In 2023, big changes happened to particularly potato late blight management, because in the previous year extensive resistance was found to the active ingredient mandipropamid, and in the beginning of 2023, the active ingredient cyazofamid was banned with very short notice in Denmark due to fear of leaching of metabolites to ground water. This led to a change in strategies in order to save the very few remaining active ingredients for potato late blight management. As a consequence, the inputs of fungicides have almost doubled, because now one of the principles in the strategy is to use always two different products with different modes of action in one treatment.

Starch potatoes 2024

Potato production in general and production of starch potatoes in particular in Denmark is heavily concentrated in certain parts of Denmark, see figure. These are areas with sandy soils or peat soils that have proven suitable for potato production, and concentration of farms is highest around the starch processing facilities. This also means that there is a very strong competition among farmers for land for growing potatoes, and that crop rotations are challenged.

Description reference year:

We have chosen an “average year” for the inputs, whereas 2023 was used as reference year for the figures on acreage, growers, yields, prices, etc.

Strategy 1: [Current IPM for starch potatoes in Denmark]

Description

Number of growers	Approx. 700
Acreage (ha)	41.300 ha
% of total acreage	70 % of area with potatoes, 2 % of area with rotational crops
Production (tonnes/year)	2,0 million tonnes/year corresponding to approx. 400.000 tonnes of starch
% of the total production	75-80 % of total potato production

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no – Both, several types of resistance are involved, no cultivar is resistant to all pests and diseases, but all cultivars have resistance to some pests and diseases.
	Seed coating? Yes, against <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>
Cropping density	Approx. 40.000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	April – October
Estimated annual yield	48,2 t/ha
Price per kg product	5,75 DKK per kg starch, corresponding to 1,15 DKK per kg potato, or 0,154 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	None
Storage loss	0-10 % - very variable depending on storage conditions and whether potatoes are delivered for processing directly from the field or from storage at the farm
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 12-13 applications, each with 2 products with different modes of action Insecticides: 2, each with one product Herbicides: 2 applications, 1-2 products in each application,
% drift reduction	Minimum 50 %, but in many cases 75 or 90% reduction is practiced

Minimum buffer zone to surface water	2-3 m, buffers are 2 to 20 meters, depending on pesticide product and drift reduction measures used.
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:X) Frequency max 1:3, minimum 2 potato free years between starch potatoes (not in the Danish law, but required in the contract by the processing industry), but preferably 3 or 4 free years.
	With which crops? Typically cereals to enable control of volunteer potatoes and troublesome perennial weeds
Intercropping	No

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) during planting. Use seed potatoes that have been certified (following the EU and Danish requirements) and checked before use. On 40-50% of the acreage certified seed potatoes are used, while on the remaining 50-60% farm saved seed potatoes are used for starch production.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the seed potatoes
Target pest/disease/weed	Various diseases like <i>Phytophthora</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia</i> , various types of scabies,...

Tool	Choose a cultivar resistant to nematodes and possibly also against other various viruses and scabies. The exact choice of cultivar will also depend on the requirements in place from the buyer of the potatoes.
Application frequency	1x
Application date	April
Stage of development of the crop	Planting of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematodes and possibly also other various viruses and scabies.

Tool	Crop rotation of 1:3 years is required by the starch processing industry; no consecutive potato cultivation allowed on the same field. There must be at least 2 years in between. However, most farmers apply an even broader crop rotation of 1:4 for storage potatoes for human consumption.
Application frequency	Always

Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Very effective against all soil-bound problems (wireworms, nematodes, rhizoctonia, weeds).

Tool	Testing of soil for cyst nematodes.
Application frequency	1 X, but currently only on 5-10 % of fields
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Cyst forming nematodes

Tool	Field hygiene: avoid, monitor and intervene in case of 'volunteer potato plants' which is an infection source of <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato late blight), black scurf and nematodes); <i>Datura stramonium</i> (jimsonweed), and <i>Nicandra physalodes</i>
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf, nematodes, <i>Datura stramonium</i> (jimsonweed), and <i>Nicandra physalodes</i>

Tool	Hand weeding of several unwanted plant species, including volunteer potato plants, <i>Datura stramonium</i> (jimsonweed), and <i>Nicandra physalodes</i>
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i> (potato blight), black scurf, nematodes, <i>Datura stramonium</i> (jimsonweed), and <i>Nicandra physalodes</i>

Tool	Buffer zone: a minimal 3 m 'crop protection free' buffer zone from water courses is mandatory in Denmark. This buffer zone can be larger depending on the crop protection product and the drift reduction equipment used.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Drift reduction: use drift reducing spraying nozzles with a 50-90% drift reduction, voluntary, but required if labelled buffer zones are reduced.
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	Full growth cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of water pollution due to drift of pesticides.

Tool	Alternate pesticides with different modes of action to avoid resistance (respect FRAC, IRAC and HRAC principles) (mandatory).
Application frequency	During pesticide application
Application date	During pesticide application
Stage of development of the crop	Full growth cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Avoidance of pesticide resistance.

Tool	Treatment of the tubers before planting: fungicide
Application frequency	x1
Application date	Before planting (April)
Stage of development of the crop	Before planting
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Rhizoctonia</i>

Tool	Weed mapping (records from previous years) or direct monitoring in the field – may be outsourced to advisers.
Application frequency	1-2X
Application date	April-May
Stage of development of the crop	Early crop growth
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds, dicot weeds

Tool	Crop protection decisions are based on advice of extension services/experts
Application frequency	Throughout the cropping cycle
Application date	Throughout the cropping cycle
Stage of development of the crop	Throughout the cropping cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	General

Tool	Dicot and grass weed treatment (herbicide) (mix of 3-4 active substances) against weeds that occurred in the previous year(s) on the field.
------	---

Application frequency	X2
Application date	Mid April- Mid May
Stage of development of the crop	Before and after emergence of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds and dicot weeds

Tool	Mechanical weed management with interrow equipment
Application frequency	X0-2, currently only 10% of fields
Application date	Mid April- Mid May
Stage of development of the crop	Before and after emergence of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds and dicot weeds

Tool	BlightManager – decision support for potato late blight, important tool to decide about dosages and products – particularly during high-risk periods. Also applicable to find the first high-risk period, where the spray programme will be initiated. This info is to a large extent communicated by advisers and the starch industry
Application frequency	Used throughout the growing period
Application date	May – September
Stage of development of the crop	22-91
Target pest/disease/weed	Phytophthora infestans

Tool	<i>Phytophthora</i> treatment (fungicide)
Application frequency	x12-14
Application date	May-September (depending on the cultivar used: harvest between September-November)
Stage of development of the crop	Intervention needed from the infection period of the fungus until the harvest of the crop (i.e. until the leaves are active).
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Monitoring for cicades using yellow sticky traps in the fields
Application frequency	x1
Application date	May-August
Stage of development of the crop	Before and around canopy closure
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	Control of cicades and their nymphs with the insecticide acetamiprid
Application frequency	X2, 100% of growers
Application date	May-August

Stage of development of the crop	Before and around canopy closure
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	<i>Alternaria</i> treatment (fungicide). This can be combined with a <i>Phytophthora</i> fungicide treatment.
Application frequency	x3-4
Application date	Mid July-beginning September
Stage of development of the crop	Intervention needed from the infection period of the fungus until 2 weeks before beginning yellowing of the crop (BBCH 91)
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Alternaria</i>

Tool	Chemical haulm killing (herbicide) for artificial induction of tuber periderm maturation, controlling tuber size and reducing vine volume to increase harvest efficiency. This also ensure that the tubers keep their quality. As diquat is not allowed anymore, the only alternative active substance allowed and used in practice is pyraflufen-ethyl.
Application frequency	X1 (10% of fields)
Application date	14 days before harvest (August-October)
Stage of development of the crop	14 days before harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Important for the potato quality

IPM improved scenario

As mentioned, it was hard for the farmers and advisers to suggest improved IPM scenarios that could be used today. However, some suggestions came up like:

Longer rotations – better control of volunteer potatoes and soil borne pests/diseases.

Sharing of land with other farmers to enable longer rotations

Use mechanical weed management consequently and more efficiently, perhaps combined with emerging technologies for mapping weeds. Robots may also be part of the future.

Keep inoculum pressures low – coverage of potato dumps

Desiccation of foci of potato late blight rather than spraying on active infections, some suggested a ban of organic potatoes, as they are considered by conventional farmers as a major source of potato late blight inoculum. But this is far from realistic in a Danish context.

Variety mixtures – have been a big success in cereal production – but unfortunately no documentation that it works in potatoes

Better cultivar resistance against particularly *Phytophthora infestans*. Conventional breeding as well as novel NGT-techniques are promising and should deliver in the future. There is already some minor tolerance in some cultivars, but for various reasons this is not used optimally in practice.

We have a very limited number of fungicide modes of action in Denmark because of recent ban of cyazofamid and fungicide resistance, therefore we have had to increase fungicide use in the form of mixtures and sequences to keep the few remaining actives effective.

Updated decision support – current systems are 20-25 years old and could be improved with current IT technology, but no funding available at the moment.

Below, I have only included a couple of improvements that are available and realistic today.

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no – Both, several types of resistance are involved, no cultivar is resistant to all pests and diseases, but all cultivars have resistance to some pests and diseases. Use cultivars with best resistance to potato late blight
	Seed coating? Yes, against <i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>
Cropping density	Approx. 40.000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	April – October
Estimated annual yield	48,2 t/ha
Price per kg product	5,75 DKK per kg starch, corresponding to 1,15 DKK per kg potato, or 0,154 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	None
Storage loss	0-10 % - very variable depending on storage conditions and whether potatoes are delivered for processing directly from the field or from storage at the farm
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 12-13 applications, each with 2 products with different modes of action Insecticides: 2, each with one product Herbicides: 2 applications, 1-2 products in each application,
% drift reduction	Minimum 50 %, but in many cases 75 or 90% reduction is practiced
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	2-3 m, buffers are 2 to 20 meters, depending on pesticide product and drift reduction measures used.
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:X) Frequency max 1:4 or 1:5, minimum 3-4 potato free years between starch potatoes in the rotation
	With which crops? Better rotations enabled by farmers specializing in different types of production working together and sharing their land.
Intercropping	No

Additional IPM tools as compared with the current scenario:

Tool	Better crop rotations, requirements of potatoes max 1:4 or 1:5 in the rotation. This will be a big challenge to farmers and require better collaboration among farmers to share land and enable longer rotations.
Application frequency	Always
Application date	Always
Stage of development of the crop	Always
Target pest/disease/weed	Very effective against all soil-bound problems (wireworms, nematodes, rhizoctonia, weeds).

Tool	Better and more consequent use of mechanical weed management with interrow equipment. This may substitute in total for herbicide treatments or substitute for one of the chemical herbicide treatments.
Application frequency	X2
Application date	Mid April- Mid May
Stage of development of the crop	Before and after emergence of the crop
Target pest/disease/weed	Grass weeds and dicot weeds

6.7.4 Netherlands

Contact person: Carolina Gattorno (carolina.gattorno@zlto.nl)

Yaite Cuesta Arenas (yaite.cuesta.arenas@zlto.nl)

Strategy 1 – Open field: state of the art scenario:

Strategy 1 – Open field: IPM improved Scenario

IPM strategies for potato: the Netherlands

Strategy selection

In the Netherlands, potatoes are cultivated in open fields, typically planted in ridges. There's a clear distinction between ware potatoes, starch potatoes and seed potatoes. Growers have already implemented several Integrated Pest Management (IPM) measures, and many are open to enhancing these strategies further. This need arises from the decreasing availability of chemical crop protection agents and stricter environmental standards.

Potatoes are the second most grown arable crop in the Netherlands, which highlights their importance for the income of arable farmers. Potato cultivation is expensive and quickly costs around 10,000 euros per hectare. To have some security, most farmers have contractual agreements with buyers, allowing them to deliver a large portion of their potatoes at a pre-agreed price. Although most growers have a large portion under contract, many keep a portion of their crop uncontracted. These uncontracted potatoes can then be sold at prevailing market prices, which is a risk and can sometimes be below the contract prices. In years of scarcity, however, these potatoes become more expensive than the contract potatoes.

Therefore, farmers are committed to continuing potato cultivation and are willing to adopt new IPM methods to ensure potato cultivation in the future. However, the rate at which chemicals are disappearing doesn't align with the development of reliable alternative IPM methods. This is a huge challenge in the development of IPM tools for potato production.

The usage of chemicals varies among potato types, with seed potatoes recording the highest usage. These seed potatoes are predominantly produced for global export, where strict quality standards should be met. Seed potato growers can take minimal risks when it comes to the contamination of their crops.

Source: Interview with farmers and advisors; [CBS](#); [Nieuwe Oogst](#)

Description reference year: 2022

With regards to the weather conditions, 2018-2021 were extreme years for potato cultivation. 2022, however still being a challenging year for potato growers, was moderate in comparison, therefore it was chosen as the reference year. The year started promisingly, with high demand in the industry resulting in higher-than-average contract prices. During the planting period in April and May, the weather was mild, allowing farmers to plant potatoes on time. However, an unusually warm and dry summer period followed, causing heat stress and poor plant growth. These conditions led to decreased production and lower yields, preventing some farmers from fulfilling their contracts. In some regions, this scarcity drove prices even higher. Due to the scarcity, the high prices compensated for the lower yield, providing some relief. Farmers who were optimally equipped for irrigation managed to achieve higher yields than average. Overall, despite the challenges, the high prices due to scarcity helped offset the impact of the lower yields.

Source: Interviews with farmers and advisors; [KNMI](#); [Agrimatie](#)

Strategy 1: Open-field Cultivation

Description

Number of growers	6698 farms with ware potatoes 2291 farms with seed potatoes 1531 farms with starch potatoes
Acreage (ha)	In 2022: 163,058 ha of which: - 76,595 ha ware potatoes - 43,157 ha seed potatoes - 43,306 ha starch potatoes
% of total acreage	Total arable acreage = 534.708ha potatoes are 30.5% of arable production
Production (tonnes/year)	In 2022, potatoes in total yielded 6,915,875 tonnes This is an average of 42,6 tonnes per hectare.
% of the total production	100 %

Source: [CBS](#); [Agrimatie](#);

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? No
	Seed coating? No
Cropping density	Crop density depends on the size of the tuber. When tubers are smaller, planting distance can be lower. Cropping density is usually not reported in plants per ha but kg/ha. This ranges between 1800 – 2800kg/ha
Cropping cycle	Start/end date: potatoes are usually planted in April/May and yielded during September/October
Estimated annual yield	42 ton/ha
Price per kg product	Prices fluctuate yearly and even between seasons. Price also depends on whether potatoes are delivered from farm or from the field. In 2022, on average: Ware potatoes yielded: 0.25 €/kg Seed potatoes: 0,36 €/kg Starch potatoes: 0.09 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	Eco-Scheme payments: depends on points given. Average is between €160-200/ha.
Storage loss	3-8%.

PPP-use In the Netherlands, more than 250 plant protection products, based on 80 different active substances, are authorised for use 70 in potato cultivation (Ctgb, 2020e)	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): in 2022, on average 14 products. Fungicide: 5-8 Herbicide: 4-5 Insecticide: 1-3 *See table 1 for more detail
% drift reduction	Technologies with a minimum of 75% are required since 2019. New technologies available with reduction of 98%.
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	0,5m – 3m
Crop rotation	Yes/no (frequency: 1:4) Rotated with wheat (barley), maize, beetroots, onion.
Intercropping	No

Table 1 Average PPP usage in potatoes

Average of applied products in 2022 of all varieties	Fungicide	Herbicide	Insecticide	Total
Ware potatoes on clay	8	5	1	14
Seed potatoes on clay	8	4	3	15
Starch potatoes on sand	5	4	3	12

Source:

[Kwin 2022](#); [Kennisakker](#); [nieuwe oogst](#); [NAK teeltvoorschriften](#); [Akkerbouwbedrijf](#);

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Chemical intervention

Disclaimer: The following list of chemicals is sourced from the 2022 edition of KWIN-AGV - Boek beheer, together with advisors and labels of the products. Please note that some of these products may no longer be permitted for use.

Consumption potatoes 2022				
Tool	Category	Target	Application Stage	Frequency
Metribuzin (600)	Herbicide	Annual broadleaf weeds, grasses	Pre-Emergence and early post emergence	3. once pre emergence, 2 post emergence
Prosulfocarb (800)	Herbicide	Broadleaf weeds, grasses	Pre emergence or Early post emergence	1
Mandipropamid (250)	Fungicide	Oömyceten (e.g., Phytophthora)	Post emergence	6
Fluopicolide (62,5), Propamocarb (625)	Fungicide	Phytophthora	Pre and post emergence	5
Cyazofamid (160)	Fungicide	Phytophthora	Pre and post emergence	6

Pyraflufen-ethyl (26,5)	Herbicide	Broadleaf weeds	Post-emergence	2
Carfentrazone-ethyl (60)	Herbicide	Potato leaves	Post-emergence	1
Sinasappelolie (99,91%)	Other	Sprout inhibitor	In storage	9
Clomazone (360)	Herbicide	Broadleaf weeds	Pre-emergence	1
Lambda-cyhalothrin (100)	Insecticide	Various pests	Various stages	2
Difenoconazool (250)	Fungicide	Alternaria and Rhizoctonia	Post emergence	4. namely 3x for alternaria and once for rhizoctonia
Sulfoxaflor (120)	Insecticide	Aphids	post emergence	1
Olie Mineraal	Insecticide	Aphids	post emergence	12

Starch potatoes 2022				
Tool	Category	Target	Application Stage	Frequency
Oxamyl (10%)	Insecticide	Aphids, mites, nematodes	Pre emergence	1
Metribuzin (600)	Herbicide	Annual broadleaf weeds, grasses	Pre-Emergence and early post emergence	3. namely 1x when applied pre emergence and 2x after emergence
Rimsulfuron (25%)	Herbicide	Broadleaf and grassy weeds	post-emergence	2
Mandipropamid (250)	Fungicide	Oömyceten (e.g., Phytophthora)	Post emergence	6
Benthiavalicarb-isopropyl (70), Oxathiapiproline (30)	Fungicide	Downy mildew, late blight	Post emergence	4
Difenoconazool (250), Mandipropamid (250)	Fungicide	Late blight, downy mildew	Post emergence	3
Cyazofamid (160)	Fungicide	Phytophthora	Pre and post emergence	6
Pyraflufen-ethyl (26.5)	Herbicide	Broadleaf weeds		
Metribuzin (80), Prosulfocarb (800)	Herbicide	Broadleaf weeds and grasses	Pre-emergence and post-emergence	1
Chlorantraniliprole (200)	Insecticide	Beetles and flies	post emergence	1
Acetamiprid (20%)	Insecticide	Aphids, whiteflies, sucking insects	post emergence	3
Olie Mineraal	Insecticide	Aphids	post emergence	12

Seed potatoes 2022				
Tool	Category	Target	Application Stage	Frequency
Oxamyl (10%)	Insecticide/Nematicide	Aphids, mites, nematodes	Pre emergence	1

Metribuzin (600)	Herbicide	Annual broadleaf weeds, grasses	Pre-Emergence and early post emergence	3. Namely 1x when applied pre emergence and 2x after emergence
Mandipropamid (250)	Fungicide	Oömyceten (e.g., Phytophthora)	Post emergence	6
Cyazofamid (160)	Fungicide	Phytophthora	Pre and post emergence	6
Pyraflufen-ethyl (26.5)	Herbicide	Broadleaf weeds	Post emergence	3
Carfentrazon-ethyl (60)	Herbicide	Potato leafhoppers	Post-emergence	1
carvon (93%)	grow regulation	antisprouting	after harvest	154
Clomazone (360)	Herbicide	Broadleaf weeds	Pre-emergence	1
Lambda-cyhalothrin (100)	Insecticide	Various pests	Various stages	2
Sulfoxaflor (120)	Insecticide	Aphids	post emergence	1
Olie Mineraal	Insecticide	Aphids	post emergence	12

Prevention/Monitoring/Non-chemical Intervention

Tool	Crop rotation
Application frequency	Before and after growing season
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	The crops before and after potatoes matter in terms of pest, disease or weed incidence. A carefully selected crop rotation can minimize this.

Tool	Soil health
Application frequency	Before and during the growing season
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Managing soil health before potatoes are grown can lower the incidence of soil born weeds and diseases. It also provides a good starting point for growing potatoes. Improving soil health during the growing season can improve soil (functional) biodiversity. Healthy soils make the crop more resilient against pest and diseases.

Tool	Fertilization
Application frequency	Before and during the growing season
Application date	X

Target pest/disease/weed	Ensure the soil has optimal amounts and proportion of macronutrients. This gives stronger plants that grow faster, which makes them less vulnerable for pests and diseases.
--------------------------	---

Tool	Choice of potato variety
Application frequency	Before the growing season
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Potato variety can be selected based on field or area specific pests/diseases.

Tool	Monitoring pests
Application frequency	Before, during and after growing season
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Can be for pest, diseases, and weeds

Tool	Cultivars with late blight resistance
Application frequency	Before the growing season
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Late blight resistant cultivars are selected to decrease the infection of the harmful fungus <i>Phytophthora</i> .

Tool	Anti-resistance of PPP
Application frequency	
Application date	During the growing season
Target pest/disease/weed	This tool can be used for pest, diseases and weeds. The aim of this tool is to alternate pesticides of the same chemical group or products with a similar mechanism to lower the chances of resistance.

Tool	Sanitation of seed potatoes
Application frequency	Before planting
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Starting with healthy, clean plants helps against pests and diseases.

Tool	Click beetle traps
Application frequency	May- August
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	These traps catch the adults of click beetles. Their larvae (wireworms) are harmful pests in potatoes.

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes
	Seed coating? No
Cropping density	Crop density depends on the size of the tuber. When tubers are smaller, planting distance can be lower. Cropping density is usually not reported in plants per ha but kg/ha. This ranges between 1800 – 2800kg/ha
Cropping cycle	Start/end date: potatoes are usually planted in April/May and yielded during September/October
Estimated annual yield	42 ton/ha
Price per kg product	Prices fluctuate yearly and even between seasons. Price also depends on whether potatoes are delivered from farm or from the field. In 2022, on average: Ware potatoes yielded: 0.25 €/kg Seed potatoes: 0,36 €/kg Starch potatoes: 0.09 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	Eco-Scheme payments: Depends on points given. Average is between €160-200/ha.
Storage loss	3-8%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): in 2022, on average 14 products. Fungicide: 5-8 Herbicide: 4-5 Insecticide: 1-3 *See table 1 for more detail
% drift reduction	>90 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	1-3m
Crop rotation	Yes/no (frequency: 1:6)
	Wheat, Beetroot, Maize, Onion, Grassland
Intercropping	No

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Nematodes support tool
Application frequency	Before planting
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests

Tool	Mechanical weeding on potato ridges
Application frequency	After the moment of planting until the plant canopies reaches each other.
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Volunteer potato management
Application frequency	After harvest
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest and diseases.

Tool	Spot spraying
Application frequency	During the growing season
Application date	X
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests, weeds and diseases

Appendix

Product used in starch, seed and/or consumption potatoes	Source
Acetamiprid (20%)	Certis.belchicm.nl
Benthiavalicarb-isopropyl (70), Oxathiapiproline (30)	Agrobayer.nl
Carfentrazone-ethyl (60)	Spotlightplus
carvon (93%)	Adama.nl
Chlorantraniliprole (200)	Syngenta
Clomazone (360)	Fytostat.nl
Cyazofamid (160)	royalbrinkman
Difenoconazool (250), Mandipropamid (250)	Syngenta
Fluopicolide (62,5), Propamocarb (625)	Bayer
Lambda-cyhalothrin (100)	Agro4all
Mandipropamid (250)	Syngenta
Metribuzin (600)	Bayeragro
Metribuzin (80), Prosulfocarb (800)	Syngenta
Olie Mineraal	Van Iperen
Prosulfocarb (800)	Syngenta
Pyraflufen-ethyl (26.5)	certis
Rimsulfuron (25%)	Corteva
Sinasappelolie (99,91%)	Argos

6.7.5 Poland

Contact person: Dominika Boguszewska-mankowska (d.boguszewska-mankowska@ihar.edu.pl)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario (1): Consumption Potato for Storage

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario (1): Consumption Potato for Storage

Strategy 3 – IPM improved scenario (2): Consumption Potato for Storage

IPM strategies for [Potato POLAND]

Strategy selection

[Consumption Potato for Storage is the most important cropping system in Poland]

Description reference year:

[2023]

Strategy 1: state of the art scenario:[Consumption potato for storage]

Description

Number of growers	16 500
Acreage (ha)	50 000 ha
% of total acreage	25 %
Production (tonnes/year)	2 000 000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	33%

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/ no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/ NA
Cropping density	40 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	15.04/15.09
Estimated annual yield	40 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,4 €/kg
Storage loss	Not relevant
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 5-7 Insecticides: 2-3 Herbicides: 2
Crop rotation	Yes/ no (frequency: 1:2)
	wheat
Intercropping	Yes/ no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool_1	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) when growing for seed potatoes, this is required by law
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	During planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	To obtain healthy plant material

Tool_2	Crop rotation (1:2) it is impossible to grow seed potatoes in monoculture
Application frequency	Every year

Application date	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining soil health and preventing the accumulation of pests

Tool_3	Tuber treatment before planting
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Seed tuber
Target pest/disease/weed	protection of plants against fungal diseases

Tool_4	<i>Alternaria</i> treatment 2-3x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants (Half of June -half August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Alternaria</i>

Tool_5	<i>Phytophthora</i> treatment 3-4x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants – beginning of the maturity (end of June -end of August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool_6	Pesticides with different modes of action
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Whole vegetation season
Target pest/disease/weed	prevents pests from becoming resistant to pesticides

Tool_7	General weed treatment
Application frequency	2 times per season
Application date	Before and after emergence
Stage of development of the crop	emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control

Tool_8	Colorado bug
Application frequency	2-3x
Application date	June, July

Stage of development of the crop	Full development
Target pest/disease/weed	Colorado bug control

Tool_9	Field hygiene
Application frequency	Whole season
Application date	Whole season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining phytosanitary of the field

Tool_10	Monitoring of the field
Application frequency	Whole season
Application date	Whole season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	adapting the use of pesticides to the severity of diseases and pests

Strategy 2: Improved IPM Strategy: [Consumption potato for storage] (2)

Description

Number of growers	16 500
Acreage (ha)	50 000 ha
% of total acreage	25 %
Production (tonnes/year)	20 000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	33%

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/ no
	Seed coating? Yes /no/ NA
Cropping density	40 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	15.04/15.09
Estimated annual yield	40 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,4 €/kg
Storage loss	Not relevant
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 5-7 Insecticides: 2-3 Herbicides: 2
Crop rotation	Yes/ no (frequency: 1:3)
	Wheat, rape
Intercropping	Yes/ no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool_1	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) when growing for seed potatoes, this is required by law
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	During planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	To obtain healthy plant material

Tool_2	Crop rotation (1:3) it is impossible to grow seed potatoes in monoculture
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining soil health and preventing the accumulation of pests

Tool_3	Resistant cultivars
Application frequency	Not relevant
Application date	Not relevant
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	greater resistance of varieties and reduced use of chemicals

Tool_4	Alternaria treatment 2-3x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants (Half of June -half August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fight the fungus <i>Alternaria</i>

Tool_5	Phytophthora treatment 3-4x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants – beginning of the maturity (end of June -end of August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fight the fungus <i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool_6	Combining preparations and reducing doses
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants -- beginning of the maturity

Target pest/disease/weed	protection of plants against fungal diseases
--------------------------	--

Tool_7	Pesticides with different modes of action
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Whole vegetation season
Target pest/disease/weed	prevents pests from becoming resistant to pesticides

Tool_8	General weed treatment
Application frequency	2 times per season
Application date	Before and after emergence
Stage of development of the crop	emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control

Tool_9	Colorado bug
Application frequency	2-3x
Application date	June, July
Stage of development of the crop	Full development
Target pest/disease/weed	Colorado bug control

Tool_10	Field hygiene
Application frequency	Whole season
Application date	Whole season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining phytosanitary of the field

Strategy 3: Improved IPM Strategy: [Consumption potato for storage] (3)

Description

Number of growers	16 500
Acreage (ha)	50 000 ha
% of total acreage	25 %
Production (tonnes/year)	20 000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	33%

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/ no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	40 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	15.04/15.09
Estimated annual yield	40 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,4 €/kg

Storage loss	Not relevant
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 5-7 Insecticides: 2-3 Herbicides: 2
Crop rotation	Yes/ no (frequency: 1:4) with intercrop Wheat, rape, triticales
Intercropping	Yes/ no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool_1	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) when growing for seed potatoes, this is required by law
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	During planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	To obtain healthy plant material

Tool_2	Crop rotation (1:4) with intercrop it is impossible to grow seed potatoes in monoculture
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining soil health and preventing the accumulation of pests

Tool_3	Resistant cultivars
Application frequency	Not relevant
Application date	Not relevant
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	greater resistance of varieties and reduced use of chemicals

Tool_4	Alternaria treatment 2-3x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants (Half of June -half August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fight the fungus <i>Alternaria</i>

Tool_5	Phytophthora treatment 3-4x
--------	------------------------------------

Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants – beginning of the maturity (end of June -end of August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool_6	Combining preparations and reducing doses
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants - – beginning of the maturity
Target pest/disease/weed	protection of plants against fungal diseases

Tool_7	Pesticides with different modes of action
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Whole vegetation season
Target pest/disease/weed	prevents pests from becoming resistant to pesticides

Tool_8	General weed treatment
Application frequency	3 times per season: 2x mechanical, 1x chemical
Application date	Before and after emergence
Stage of development of the crop	emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control and reducing chemicals

Tool_9	Colorado bug
Application frequency	2-3x
Application date	June, July
Stage of development of the crop	Full development
Target pest/disease/weed	Colorado bug control

Tool_10	Field hygiene
Application frequency	Whole season
Application date	Whole season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining phytosanitary of the field

Tool_11	Mechanical haulm killing
Application frequency	Once per season
Application date	End of August
Stage of development of the crop	Before senescence

Target pest/disease/weed

improving tuber maturity and reducing chemicals during storage

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario (2): Early potato for consumption

Strategy 3 – IPM improved scenario (3): Early potato for consumption

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario (1): Early potato for consumption

IPM strategies for [Potato POLAND]

Strategy selection

[Early potato for consumption is one of the important cropping system in Poland

Description reference year:

[2023]

Strategy 1: [Early potato for consumption]

Description

Number of growers	7000
Acreage (ha)	15000 ha
% of total acreage	7,5 %
Production (tonnes/year)	375 000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	6,3%

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/ no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/ NA
Cropping density	40 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	10.04/15.07
Estimated annual yield	25 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,8 €/kg
Storage loss	Not relevant
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 4-6 Insecticides: 2-3 Herbicides: 2

Crop rotation	Yes/ no (frequency: 1:2)
	wheat
Intercropping	Yes/ no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool_1	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) when growing for seed potatoes, this is required by law
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	During planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	To obtain healthy plant material

Tool_2	Crop rotation (1:2) it is impossible to grow seed potatoes in monoculture
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining soil health and preventing the accumulation of pests

Tool_3	Seed presprouting
Application frequency	Once per vegetation season
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Seed tuber
Target pest/disease/weed	accelerates the plant's development and strengthens the plant's resistance to aphids

Tool_4	Tuber treatment before planting
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Seed tuber
Target pest/disease/weed	protection of plants against fungal diseases

Tool_5	Alternaria treatment 2-3x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants (Half of June -half August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Alternaria</i>

Tool_6	Phytophthora treatment 2-3x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants – beginning of the maturity (end of June -end of August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool_7	Pesticides with different modes of action
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Whole vegetation season
Target pest/disease/weed	prevents pests from becoming resistant to pesticides

Tool_8	General weed treatment
Application frequency	2 times per season
Application date	Before and after emergence
Stage of development of the crop	emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control

Tool_9	Colorado bug
Application frequency	2-3x
Application date	June, July
Stage of development of the crop	Full development
Target pest/disease/weed	Colorado bug control

Tool_10	Field hygiene
Application frequency	Whole season
Application date	Whole season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining phytosanitary of the field

Strategy 2: Improved IPM scenario: [Early potato for consumption] (2)

Description

Number of growers	7000
Acreage (ha)	15000 ha
% of total acreage	7,5 %
Production (tonnes/year)	375 000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	6,3%

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/ no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	40 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	10.04/15.07
Estimated annual yield	25 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,8 €/kg
Storage loss	Not relevant
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 4-6 Insecticides: 2-3 Herbicides: 1
Crop rotation	Yes/ no (frequency: 1:3) with intercrop
	Wheat, rape
Intercropping	Yes/ no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool_1	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) when growing for seed potatoes, this is required by law
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	During planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	To obtain healthy plant material

Tool_2	Crop rotation (1:3) with intercrop it is impossible to grow seed potatoes in monoculture
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining soil health and preventing the accumulation of pests

Tool_3	Seed presprouting
Application frequency	Once per vegetation season
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Seed tuber
Target pest/disease/weed	accelerates the plant's development and strengthens the plant's resistance to aphids

Tool_4	Alternaria treatment 2-3x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants (Half of June -half August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Alternaria</i>

Tool_5	Phytophthora treatment 2-3x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants – beginning of the maturity (end of June -end of August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool_6	Pesticides with different modes of action
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Whole vegetation season
Target pest/disease/weed	prevents pests from becoming resistant to pesticides
Tool_7	Combining preparation and reducing doses
Application frequency	Each treatment
Application date	June-July
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants – beginning of the maturity
Target pest/disease/weed	reducing chemicals to obtain healthier tubers

Tool_8	General weed treatment
Application frequency	2 times per season
Application date	Before and after emergence
Stage of development of the crop	emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control

Tool_9	Colorado bug
Application frequency	2-3x
Application date	June, July
Stage of development of the crop	Full development
Target pest/disease/weed	Colorado bug control

Tool_10	Fild hygiene
Application frequency	Whole season
Application date	Whole season

Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining phytosanitary of the field

Tool_11	Without seed treatment
Application frequency	Not relevant
Application date	Not relevant
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	limiting chemicals in production for early harvest

Strategy 3: Improved IPM scenario: [Early potato for consumption] (3)

Description

Number of growers	7000
Acreage (ha)	15000 ha
% of total acreage	7,5 %
Production (tonnes/year)	375 000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	6,3%

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/ no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	25 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	10.04/15.07
Estimated annual yield	40 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,8 €/kg
Storage loss	Not relevant
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 4-6 Insecticides: 2-3 Herbicides: 1
Crop rotation	Yes/ no (frequency: 1:4) with intercrop
	Wheat, rape triticale
Intercropping	Yes/ no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool_1	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) when growing for seed potatoes, this is required by law
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	During planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	To obtain healthy plant material

Tool_2	Crop rotation (1:4) with intercrop it is impossible to grow seed potatoes in monoculture
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining soil health and preventing the accumulation of pests

Tool_3	Seed presprouting
Application frequency	Once per vegetation season
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Seed tuber
Target pest/disease/weed	accelerates the plant's development and strengthens the plant's resistance to aphids

Tool_4	Alternaria treatment 2-3x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants (Half of June -half August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Alternaria</i>

Tool_5	Phytophthora treatment 2-3x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants – beginning of the maturity (end of June -end of August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool_6	Pesticides with different modes of action
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Whole vegetation season
Target pest/disease/weed	prevents pests from becoming resistant to pesticides

Tool_7	Combining preparation and reducing doses
Application frequency	Each treatment
Application date	June-July
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants – beginning of the maturity
Target pest/disease/weed	reducing chemicals to obtain healthier tubers

Tool_8	General weed treatment
Application frequency	3 times per season: 2x mechanical treatment, 1x chemical treatment
Application date	Before and after emergence
Stage of development of the crop	emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control and limiting chemicals

Tool_9	Biological insecticide Colorado bug
Application frequency	1-2x
Application date	June, July
Stage of development of the crop	Full development
Target pest/disease/weed	Colorado bug control and chemicals limiting

Tool_10	Fild hygiene
Application frequency	Whole season
Application date	Whole season
Stage of development of the crop	All stages
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining phytosanitary of the field

Strategy 1 – state of art. scenario(1): Seed Potato Production

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario(1): Seed Potato Production

Strategy 3 – IPM improved scenario(2): Seed Potato Production

IPM strategies for [Potato POLAND]

Strategy selection

[Seed Potato Production is important for Potato Global Production especially in case of qualified seed shortage]

Description reference year:
[2023]

Strategy 1: [Potato Seed Production]

Description

Number of growers	2000
Acreage (ha)	6000 ha
% of total acreage	3 %
Production (tonnes/year)	170 000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	3 %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/∅
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	60 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	20.04/10.10
Estimated annual yield	28 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,7 €/kg
Storage loss	10%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (products): Fungicides: 5-7 Insecticides: 5-7 Herbicides: 2
Crop rotation	Yes/∅ (frequency: 1:3)
	wheat, rape
Intercropping	Yes/∅

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool_1	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) when growing for seed potatoes, this is required by law
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	During planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	To obtain healthy plant material

Tool_2	Crop rotation (1:3) it is impossible to grow seed potatoes in monoculture
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining soil health and preventing the accumulation of pests

Tool_3	Seed presprouting
Application frequency	Once per vegetation season
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Seed tuber
Target pest/disease/weed	accelerates the plant's development and strengthens the plant's resistance to aphids

Tool_4	canopy architecture forming
Application frequency	Once per vegetation season
Application date	During planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	obtaining the appropriate size of tuber calibration

Tool_5	Tuber treatment before planting
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Seed tuber
Target pest/disease/weed	protection of plants against fungal diseases

Tool_6	Alternaria treatment 3-4x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants (Half of June -half August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Alternaria</i>

Tool_7	Phytophthora treatment 3-4x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants – beginning of the maturity (end of June -end of August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool_8	Aphids treatment 3-4x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants (Half of June -half July)
Target pest/disease/weed	eliminates aphids that transmit viruses, which determines the health of the plantation

Tool_9	Pesticides with different modes of action
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Whole vegetation season
Target pest/disease/weed	prevents pests from becoming resistant to pesticides

Tool_10	Haulm killing 2x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Beginning of the maturity
Target pest/disease/weed	inhibit plant growth, increase tuber resistance, accelerate tuber maturity, maintain proper calibration

Strategy 2: [Potato Seed Production] **IMPROVED SCENARIO (2)**

Description

Number of growers	2000
Acreage (ha)	6000 ha
% of total acreage	3 %
Production (tonnes/year)	170 000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	3 %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	60 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	20.04/10.10
Estimated annual yield	28 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,7 €/kg
Storage loss	10%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 5-7 Insecticides: 4-6 Herbicides: 2
Crop rotation	Yes/ no (frequency: 1:4)
	wheat, rape, triticale
Intercropping	Yes/ no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool_1	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) when growing for seed potatoes, this is required by law
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	During planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	To obtain healthy plant material

Tool_2	Crop rotation (1:4) it is impossible to grow seed potatoes in monoculture
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining soil health and preventing the accumulation of pests

Tool_3	Seed presprouting
Application frequency	Once per vegetation season

Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Seed tuber
Target pest/disease/weed	accelerates the plant's development and strengthens the plant's resistance to aphids

Tool_4	canopy architecture forming
Application frequency	Once per vegetation season
Application date	During planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	obtaining the appropriate size of tuber calibration

Tool_5	Tuber treatment before planting
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Seed tuber
Target pest/disease/weed	protection of plants against fungal diseases

Tool_6	Alternaria treatment 2-3x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants (Half of June -half August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Alternaria</i>
Tool_7	Combining preparations and reducing doses
Application frequency	Each possible application
Application date	Each possible application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants – beginning of the maturity (end of June -end of August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Alternaria</i> , <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> , <i>Aphids</i> and <i>Colorado bugs</i>

Tool_8	General weed treatment x1
Application frequency	before emergence
Application date	before emergence
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control

Tool_9	Pesticides with different modes of action
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Whole vegetation season
Target pest/disease/weed	prevents pests from becoming resistant to pesticides

Tool_10	Haulm killing 2x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Beginning of the maturity

Target pest/disease/weed	inhibit plant growth, increase tuber resistance, accelerate tuber maturity, maintain proper calibration
--------------------------	---

Strategy 3: [Potato Seed Production] IMPROVED SCENARIO (3)

Description

Number of growers	2000
Acreage (ha)	6000 ha
% of total acreage	3 %
Production (tonnes/year)	170 000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	3 %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	60 000 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	20.04/10.10
Estimated annual yield	28 t/ha
Price per kg product	0,7 €/kg
Storage loss	10%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 4-6 Insecticides: 4-6 Herbicides: 1
Crop rotation	Yes/∅ (frequency: 1:3)
	wheat, rape
Intercropping	Yes/∅

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool_1	Use healthy plant material (seed potatoes) when growing for seed potatoes, this is required by law
Application frequency	Each year
Application date	During planting
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	To obtain healthy plant material

Tool_2	Crop rotation (1:3) it is impossible to grow seed potatoes in monoculture
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	maintaining soil health and preventing the accumulation of pests

Tool_3	Seed presprouting
Application frequency	Once per vegetation season
Application date	Before planting

Stage of development of the crop	Seed tuber
Target pest/disease/weed	accelerates the plant's development and strengthens the plant's resistance to aphids

Tool_4	Buffer zone
Application frequency	Once per vegetation season
Application date	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	Greater phytosanitary safety

Tool_5	Tuber treatment before planting
Application frequency	Every year
Application date	Before planting
Stage of development of the crop	Seed tuber
Target pest/disease/weed	protection of plants against fungal diseases

Tool_6	Combining preparations and reducing doses
Application frequency	Each possible application
Application date	Each possible application
Stage of development of the crop	Full development of plants – beginning of the maturity (end of June -end of August)
Target pest/disease/weed	fightes the fungus <i>Alternaria</i> , <i>Phytophthora infestans</i> , <i>Aphids</i> and <i>Colorado bugs</i>

Tool_7	General weed treatment (before emergence (x1) with mechanical weed treatment after emergence
Application frequency	Chemical weed control 1x, mechanical weed control 2x
Application date	Chemical before emergence, mechanical after plant emergence
Stage of development of the crop	emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed control

Tool_8	Monitoring on the field especially Aphids
Application frequency	Whole vegetation period
Application date	Whole vegetation period
Stage of development of the crop	Whole vegetation period
Target pest/disease/weed	Aphids control

Tool_9	Pesticides with different modes of action
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Whole vegetation season
Target pest/disease/weed	prevents pests from becoming resistant to pesticides

Tool_10	Mechanical haulm killing 1x
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application

Stage of development of the crop	Beginning of the maturity
Target pest/disease/weed	inhibit plant growth, increase tuber resistance, accelerate tuber maturity, maintain proper calibration

6.8 Onion

6.8.1 Italy

Contact person: Maria Grazia Tommasini (mgtommasini@rinova.eu)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: [Short day onion]

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: [Short day onion]

Strategy 2 – state of the art scenario: **Long day onion**

Strategy 2 – IPM improved scenario: **Long day onion**

IPM strategies for ONION cultivation in Italy

Strategy selection

In 2023 approximately 12,511 ha was cultivated in Italy on (ISTAT, 23th May 2024) with a production of 388,342 tonnes. Italy is one of the main producers of onion in Europe, together with the Netherlands and Poland and after Spain, which is the European leading producer with approximately 1 M tonnes. The competition from these countries and the lack of product uniformity has significantly reduced Italian exports which now stand at around 40,000 tonnes, particularly towards Germany and France.

Production in Italy is mainly located in Emilia Romagna (20% of national production), Puglia (14%), Sicily (12%), Campania (9%), Veneto (7%) and Piedmont (4%) (ISTAT, 23th May 2024).

A distinction can be done between cultivars and the period of cultivation. According to this, there are two categories of varieties (and productions):

- Short day varieties are Autumn-Winter crop with harvest and use during following Spring-Summer. They cannot be stored for long time and their consume is mostly fresh.
- Long day varieties are Spring-Summer crops with harvest late Summer-Autumn. These are consumed during Autumn-Winter and can be stored for long time.

Onion is cultivated along all Italy with pedoclimatic differences among the areas of cultivation. However, apart from very particular productions in very delimited areas, there are no relevant regional differences in the cultivation methods for both kinds of varieties. The cultivation system of Emilia Romagna, which is the region where mostly onion is cultivated (especially in the province of BO), is considered as representative.

Onion seed production is also important in Emilia Romagna: of the approximately 1,000 total hectares cultivated in Italy, over 1/3 are concentrated in Emilia Romagna (source: Assosementi). However, seed production is a smaller percentage (around 5%) of the total acreage of onion cultivation.

Description reference year:

Last season (2023) was characterized by a very dry Spring and Summer, but on the average of the last years. The acreage of onion cultivation was slightly minor in respect to 2022 (- 122 Ha) and the production was 15,049 tonnes lower (ISTAT, May 2024).

Due to climatic changes that make the above-mentioned conditions common today, the year 2023 in Emilia Romagna will be considered as a reference for onion production with regard to yield, pest/disease pressure, climate and market conditions.

List of the varieties recommended in Emilia Romagna Region

Yellow Bulb (Long day)	White Bulb (Long day)	Red Bulb (Long day)	Short day Onion
Ambrador f1	Biancaneve	Fiamma	Albatros
Attika F1 (CRX 2506)	BrideWhite	Focus	Blanca de fuentes
Bonus	Candor	Monastrell	Cal 214 imperial F1
Caoba	Cometa	Primula Rossa	Divina
Crockett	Gladstone	Ramata di Milano	Divina Star
Darco	Honey moon	Red Bull	Element
Darkstone F1	Ice pearl	Red label	Fabula
Derek	Nevada	Red Lady F1	Fachira
Election	Primo Blanco	Red Mech M.	Galatea
Elenka	Quarzo	Red rum	Hjdras
Fundador f1	Rhea	Red sea F1	Naranco
Hamilton	Salieri	Red Wing	Nevix
Jatoba	Solstice	Rossa d'inverno Sel.	Olympic
Lamika	Southport White Globe	Granata	Oneida f1,
Lumika	Venus	Rossa di Firenze (Rossa d'inverno)	Panter
Magika	Virgin	Tannat	Red Spring
Moondance f1	White opera		Reflex F1
Medusa	White wing		Skiner F1
Meranto			Sedesta
Musa f1			Sonic
Nogal			Top Spring
Olympic			Top star
Oneida F1			Telesto
Pantano			
Ramona			
Utrero f1			
Sonoma f1			
Valero			

Plant design and density for group of varieties (suggested in Emilia Romagna Region):

Group of variety	Distance on the row (cm)	Distance between the rows (cm)	Density (n. plants/mq)	Sowing period	Depth of sowing (cm)
Very early	4 - 5	16 - 18	140	Middle August-early September	2 - 3
Early	4 - 5	16 - 18	120	Middle February	2 - 3
Middle (big bulb)	4 - 5	20	90 - 110	Middle February	2 - 3
Late (big bulb)	5 - 6	20	80 - 100	Middle February	2 - 3
Middle-late (middle bulb)	3 - 4	16 - 18	160 - 180	Middle February	2 - 3
Small industry onion	2 - 3	8 - 9	500 - 600	End February – Early March	2 - 3

Legend: in blue the short-day varieties; in grey the long-day varieties

Strategy 1: Short day varieties

Description

Number of growers	About 75 farms
Acreage (ha)	620 ha
% of total acreage	25 %
Production (tonnes/year)	2.465 tonnes/year
% of the total production	25 %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	No resistant varieties that can guarantee a good yield
	Seed coating? Yes (with fungicides or biostimulants)
Cropping density	120-140 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	August-Sept/May
Estimated annual yield	35-55 t/ha
Price per kg product	NA
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	NA
Storage loss	NA
PPP-use	<p>Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>Fungicides</u>: 10-12 against downy mildew (e.g. with a mix of 2-3 products including copper, metiram, zoxamide, cymoxanil, metalaxyl, dimethomorph, cyazofamid); 2-3 against grey mould (e.g. with fludioxinil+cyprodinil, boscalid+pyraclostrobin, pyrimethanil) - <u>Insecticides</u>: 1 against wireworms (e.g. with soil disinfectant based on lambda cyhalothrin or cypermethrin); ca. 2 against thrips (e.g. with spirotetramat, pyrethroids, spinosad); 1-2 against flies (e.g. with pyrethroids); 1 against cutworms (e.g. with pyrethroids) - <u>Herbicides</u>: 4-5 treatments (e.g. with pendimethalin, cicloxydim, fluroxipir, aclonifen).
% drift reduction	Depends on the types of nozzles used
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Specific for each PPP (if not specified, 3 m from any superficial water)
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3)
	In general: wheat-onion-potato or beet-wheat-onion
Intercropping	No

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool 1	Crop Rotation: onion cannot be sown in the same field consecutively; avoid other <i>Alliaceae</i> family crops before onion.
Application frequency	3 years on average
Common crop in rotation	Before onion: wheat or barley
Target pest/disease/weed	Prevention of soilborne diseases and pests

Tool 2	Variety selection: select varieties with a short emergence period and a fast growth rate.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool 3	Sowing time: avoid too early sowing.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Autumn sowing (i.e., September)
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target	Prevention of drought (however postponing sowing even more will most likely result in the sowing being affected by autumn rains)

Tool 4	Sowing location: short day varieties cannot be sowed closely to long day varieties; fresh soils are preferred to guarantee and facilitate soil moisture.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target diseases	Prevention risk of downy mildew infection (<i>Peronospora destructor</i>)

Tool 5	Removal of plant residues: to reduce inoculants of pests or diseases.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest & diseases

Tool 6	Field preparation: summer ploughing to improve drainage and weed control.
Application frequency	At least every 2-3 years
Application date	Summer-early Autumn

Tillage deep	25-35 cm
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Drainage & weed control

Tool 7	Soil preparation: must be done carefully to have a smooth surface.
Application frequency	High
Application date	Before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Prevention of water stagnations and allow homogeneous emergency

Tool 8	Appropriate use of irrigation: crucial for crop emergence and root development; a carefully managed irrigation system is also helping the control of thrips infestation, reducing PPP use.
Application frequency	Depending on season
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Thrips and crop emergence

Tool 9	Monitoring of the field
Application frequency	Regular visual monitoring in the field. Generally traps are not applied because they are not available or not efficient; lack of useful thresholds of intervention.
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After crop emergence up to harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest, diseases & weeds

Tool 10	Use of forecasting models for diseases (i.e., against downy mildew a forecast model is not available but other tools are used to simulate a model in Emilia Romagna).
Forecast frequency	Weekly through IPM Bulletin
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After crop emergence up to harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool 11	Weed control: before emergence and post-emergence.
Application frequency	On average 4 herbicides per crop cycle are applied with alternative active ingredients.
Type of herbicides	E.g. pendimetalin, cicloxydim, fluroxipir, aclonifen

Dose (L/ha/year)	2.5-3 L/ha (pendimetalin); 2-2.5 L/ha (cycloxydim); 0.5 L/ha (fluroxipir); 1-1.25 L/ha (aclonifen)
Stage of development of the crop	On average from post-sowing up to about 3 true leaves
Application date	Pre-emergence (pendimetalin); Post emergence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - against <i>Graminaceae</i> species (e.g. cycloxydim) - after winter: 2 applications of fluroxipir at half dose each and 1 application with aclonifen
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool 12	Use of split dose of herbicides: post-emergence application can be done using partial doses to reduce phytotoxicity in the onion plant at an early stage of development.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Risk	High risk to increase weeds resistance
Stage of development of the crop	Post-emergence: before 6 true leaves
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool 13	IPM Guidelines for pesticide application against <i>Peronospora</i> , <i>Botrytis</i> , fly, thrips, wireworm, etc.
Application frequency	Updated yearly
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases
See attachment	https://agricoltura.regione.emilia-romagna.it/produzioni-agroalimentari/temi/bio-agro-climambiente/agricoltura-integrata/disciplinari-produzione-integrata-vegetale/Collezione-dpi/dpi_2024/orticole

Tool 14	Crop protection decisions are based on advice of extension services/experts: according to the IPM Guidelines regional support for extension services is provided weekly with IPM Bulletin that advises and suggests on PPP applications
Application frequency	Weekly
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest, diseases, weeds

Tool 15	Number of <u>fungicide</u> treatments: 10-12 (downy mildew); 2-3 (grey mould)
Application frequency	In general, weekly applications against downy mildew; for other diseases the frequency depends on the conditions and the susceptible stage of the crop.
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Sensitivity against downy mildew starts from 4-5 true leaf stage
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease

Tool 16	Number of <u>insecticide</u> treatments: 1 (wireworms); 2-4 (thrips); 1-2 (flies); 1 (cutworms)
Application frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wireworms: 1 application with soil-disinfectants (e.g. with pyrethroids) - Thrips: 1 application at presence (e.g. with spirotetramat) and/or 1-2 applications in case of reinfestations (with pyrethroids) - fly (<i>Delia antiqua</i>): 1-2 treatments with pyrethroids (e.g. deltamethrin, etofenprox)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	From sowing to full vegetative stage
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests

Tool 17	Rotation of active ingredients (PPP): alternate PPP's with different modes of action to reduce the risk of resistance of pests, diseases and weeds against certain active ingredients.
Application frequency	Commonly applied
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest, diseases, weeds

Tool 18	Sprayer calibration: it is mandatory in Italy since 2016.
Application frequency	Every 3 years (normally) or every 2 years for subcontracting
Application date	NA
Use of anti-drift nozzles	Used only by farmers with modern equipment/machineries (e.g., wide sleeve bars)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests, diseases, weeds

Tool 19	Appropriate timing for harvest: a two stages harvest is commonly used. The first stage is to dig up the onion and leave them on the field to
---------	--

	dry. The second stage is to collect onion in boxes and bring to warehouse or market to further dry (a minor part could be targeted to commercialization (for fresh consumption))
Application frequency	NA
How long to leave onion on the ground after 1 st harvest stage	Max 7-10 days
Stage of development of the crop	Harvest when 70-80% of plant have broken leaves (or before for fresh consumption)
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Research for new varieties resistant or tolerant to major pests or diseases
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	120-140 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	August-Sept/May
Estimated annual yield	35-55 t/ha
Price per kg product	NA
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	NA
Storage loss	NA
PPP-use	Optimization of the number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied and substitution of chemicals with low-impact products: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>Fungicides</u>: <10-12 against downy mildew; <2-3 against grey mould - <u>Insecticides</u>: 1 against wireworms; 1-2 against thrips; 1-2 against flies; 1 against cutworms - <u>Herbicides</u>: <4 treatments
% drift reduction	Depends on the types of nozzles used
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Specific for each PPP (if no specified, 3 m from watercourse)
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:4-5)
	E.g. wheat-onion-beet-potato
Intercropping	No

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool 1	Crop Rotation: onion cannot be sown in the same field consecutively; avoid other <i>Alliaceae</i> family crops before onion.
Application frequency	4-5 years
Common crop in rotation	Before onion: wheat or barley
Target pest/disease/weed	Prevention of soilborne diseases and pests

Tool 2	Variety selection: Alternate long day and short day varieties, use tolerant cultivars if possible.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool 3	Sowing time: avoid too early sowing.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Autumn sowing (i.e., September)
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target	Prevention of drought (however postponing sowing even more will most likely result in the sowing being affected by autumn rains)

Tool 4	Sowing location: short day varieties cannot be sowed closely to long day varieties; fresh soils are more suitable to guarantee soil moisture.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target diseases	Prevention the risk of downy mildew infection (<i>Peronospora destructor</i>)

Tool 5	Removal of plant residues: to reduce inoculants of pests or diseases.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest & diseases

Tool 6	Field preparation: summer tillage (reduction of the tillage depth) to improve drainage and weed control but preserving soil organic matter.
Application frequency	Every 3-4 years
Application date	Summer-early Autumn
Tillage deep	15-30 cm
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Drainage & weed control

Tool 7	Weed control before sowing. Stale seedbed: is a preventive method of weed control (following the preparation of the seedbed, the germination of the weeds is allowed, followed
--------	--

	by a chemical treatment or tillage to eliminate them).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Before sowing
Tillage	e.g. harrowing (5-10 cm deep)
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool 8	Soil preparation: use of modern machinery to better prepare the seed bed.
Application frequency	High
Application date	Before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Prevention of water stagnations and allow homogeneous emergency

Tool 9	Appropriate use of irrigation: crucial for crop emergence and root development; a carefully managed irrigation system is also helping the control of thrips infestation, reducing PPP use.
Application frequency	Depending on season
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Thrips and crop emergence

Tool 10	Advanced monitoring of the field
Application frequency	Regular visual monitoring in the field; use of more efficient traps; development of new or updated thresholds of intervention
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After crop emergence up to harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest & weeds

Tool 11	Development of forecasting models for diseases (i.e., for downy mildew and grey mould) + use of nematode support tool (Best4Soil)
Forecast frequency	Weekly through IPM Bulletin, Best4Soil
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After crop emergence up to harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases, pests

Tool 12	Weed control: before emergence and post-emergence
---------	---

Application frequency	<4 herbicides for crop cycle applying different classes of PPP's
Type of herbicides	Research for alternative techniques to herbicides (e.g. mechanical weeding, cover crops, mulching)
Dose (L/ha/year)	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Entire crop cycle
Application date	From pre sowing to post emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool 13	Improve soil organic matter content: use of green manure or high quality compost free from weed seeds and contaminants.
Application frequency	Spring-summer green manure (e.g. with barley or <i>Sorghum</i>): with sowing in June and burning in September
Application date	Before onion in rotation
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool 14	IPM Guidelines for pesticide application against <i>Peronospora</i> , <i>Botrytis</i> , fly, thrips, wireworm, etc.
Application frequency	Updated yearly
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases
See attachment	https://agricoltura.regione.emilia-romagna.it/produzioni-agroalimentari/temi/bio-agro-climambiente/agricoltura-integrata/disciplinari-produzione-integrata-vegetale/Collezione-dpi/dpi_2024/orticole

Tool 15	Crop Protection decision are based on advices of extension service/experts: according to IPM Guidelines a regional support for extension service is provided weekly with Bulletin that advise and suggest on PPP applications
Application frequency	weekly
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest, diseases, weeds

Tool 16	Reduction of pesticide application or use of alternatives or less toxic PPP's (e.g. BCA, natural based products....)
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest, diseases, weeds

Tool 17	Rotation of active ingredients (PPP): alternate PPP's with different modes of action to reduce the risk of resistance of pests, diseases and weeds against certain active ingredients.
Application frequency	Commonly applied
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest, diseases, weeds

Tool 18	Sprayer calibration: it is mandatory in Italy since 2016.
Application frequency	Every 3 years (normally) or every 2 years for subcontracting
Application date	NA
Use of anti-drift nozzles	Used only by farmers with modern equipment/machineries (e.g., wide sleeve bars)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests, diseases, weeds

Tool 19	Appropriate timing for harvest: a two stages harvest is commonly used. The first stage is to dig up the onion and leave them on the field to dry. The second stage is to collect onion in boxes and bring to warehouse or market to further dry (a minor part could be targeted to commercialization (for fresh consumption))
Application frequency	NA
How long to leave onion on the ground after 1 st harvest stage	Max 7-10 days
Stage of development of the crop	Harvest when 70-80% of plant have broken leaves (or before for fresh consumption)
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool 20	Use of split dose of herbicides: post-emergence application can be done using partial doses to reduce phytotoxicity in the onion plant at an early stage of development.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA

Risk	High risk to increase weeds resistance
Stage of development of the crop	Post-emergence: before 6 true leaves
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Strategy 2: [Long day varieties]

Description

Number of growers	About 225 farms
Acreage (ha)	1860 ha
% of total acreage	75 %
Production (tonnes/year)	7.394 tonnes/year
% of the total production	75 %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	No resistant varieties that can guarantee a good yield
	Seed coating? Yes (with fungicides or biostimulants)
Cropping density	80-180 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	January-Feb./June-August
Estimated annual yield	40-60 t/ha
Price per kg product	0.30-0.35 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	NA
Storage loss	NA
PPP-use	<p>Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>Fungicides</u>: 10-12 against downy mildew (e.g. with a mix of 2-3 products including copper, metiram, zoxamide, cymoxanil, metalaxyl, dimethomorph, cyazofamid); 2-3 against grey mould (e.g. with fludioxinil+cyprodinil, boscalid+pyraclostrobin, pyrimethanil) - <u>Insecticides</u>: 1 against wireworms (e.g. with soil disinfectant based on lambdacyhalothrin or cypermethrin); 2-4 against thrips (e.g. with spirotetramat, pyrethroids, spinosad); 1-2 against flies (e.g. with pyrethroids); 1 against cutworms (e.g. with pyrethroids) - <u>Herbicides</u>: 4-7 treatments (e.g. with glyphosate, pendimethalin, fluroxipir, aclonifen).
% drift reduction	Depends on the types of nozzles used
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Specific for each PPP (if no specified, 3 m from watercourse)

Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:3)
	In general: wheat-onion-potato or beet-wheat-onion
Intercropping	No

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool 1	Variety selection: according to market demand it is preferred to use varieties with intermediate cycle; alternate varieties with different sowing period.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Late winter sowing (i.e., Jan-February)
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool 2	Sowing time: commonly sowing is anticipated as much as possible to have good soil condition.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Winter sowing (i.e., January-February)
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target	Higher guarantee of success but higher risk of weed proliferation

Tool 3	Crop Rotation: onion cannot be sown in the same field consecutively; avoid other I family crops before onion.
Application frequency	3 years on average
Common crop in rotation	Before onion: in general wheat or barley
Target pest/disease/weed	Prevention of soilborne diseases and pests

Tool 4	Sowing location: long day varieties have not to be sowed closely to short day varieties.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target diseases	Prevention the risk of downy mildew infection (<i>Peronospora destructor</i>)

Tool 5	Removal of plant residues: to reduce inoculants of pests or diseases.
Application frequency	Not commonly done
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest & diseases

Tool 6	Field preparation: winter ploughing to improve drainage and weed control.
Application frequency	At least every 2-3 years
Application date	Autumn-Winter
Tillage deep	25-35 cm
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Drainage & weed control

Tool 7	Soil preparation: must be done carefully to have a smooth surface (commonly done with mini tiller/harrows).
Application frequency	High
Application date	Before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Prevention of water stagnations, allow homogeneous emergency and weed control

Tool 8	Appropriate use of irrigation: useful for crop emergence and root development; during summer a carefully irrigation system is helping also the control of thrips infestation reducing PPP use.
Application frequency	Depending on the season
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After sowing and/or during spring-summer
Target pest/disease/weed	Thrips and crop emergence/development

Tool 9	Monitoring of the field.
Application frequency	Visual and regular in the field; generally traps are not applied because not available or not efficient; lack of useful thresholds of intervention.
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After crop emergence up to harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest & weeds

Tool 10	Use of forecasting models for diseases (i.e., against downy mildew a forecast model is not available but other tools are used to simulate a model in Emilia Romagna).
Forecast frequency	Weekly through IPM Bulletin
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After crop emergence up to harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases

Tool 11	Weed control: before emergence and post-emergence.
Application frequency	On average 4-7 herbicides per crop cycle are applied with alternative PPP
Type of herbicides	E.g. glyphosate, pendimetalin, fluroxipir, aclonifen
Dose (L/ha/year)	1-4 L/ha (glyphosate); 2.5-3 L/ha (pendimetalin); 0.5 L/ha (fluroxipir); 1-1.25 L/ha (aclonifen)
Stage of development of the crop	On average from post-sowing up to about 3 true leaf stage
Application date	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - after sowing (glyphosate) - pre-emergence (pendimethalin) - post emergence (up to April-May) 2-3 applications of microdoses (0.1-0.2L/ha) of fluroxipir and 2 application of aclonifen (from 3 leaves up to mid-May)
Target pest/disease/weed	Weed

Tool 12	Use of split dose of herbicides: post-emergence application can be done with portioned interventions of the full dosage to reduce phytotoxicity on the onion plant in an early stage of development.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Risk	High risk to increase weeds resistance
Stage of development of the crop	Post-emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool 13	IPM Guidelines for pesticides application against <i>Peronospora</i> , <i>Botrytis</i> , fly, thrips, wireworm, etc.
Application frequency	Updated yearly
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases
See attachment	https://agricoltura.regione.emilia-romagna.it/produzioni-agroalimentari/temi/bio-agro-climambiente/agricoltura-integrata/disciplinari-produzione-integrata-vegetale/Collezione-dpi/dpi_2024/orticole

Tool 14	Crop protection decisions are based on advice of extension service/experts: according to IPM Guidelines a regional support for extension
---------	--

	service is provided weekly with Bulletin that advises and suggests on PPP applications.
Application frequency	Weekly
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest, diseases, weeds

Tool 15	Number of <u>fungicide</u> treatments: 10-12 (downy mildew); 2-3 (grey mould).
Application frequency	In general, weekly applications against downy mildew; for other diseases the frequency depends on the conditions and the susceptible stage of the crop.
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Sensitivity against downy mildew starts from 4-5 true leaf stage
Target pest/disease/weed	Disease

Tool 16	Number of <u>insecticide</u> treatments: 1 (wireworms); 2-4 (thrips); 1-2 (flies); 1 (cutworms).
Application frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wireworms: 1 application with soil-disinfectants (e.g. with pyrethroids) - thrips: 1 application at presence (e.g. with spirotetramat) and/or 1-2 applications in case of reinfestations (with pyrethroids) - fly (<i>Delia antiqua</i>): 1-2 treatments with pyrethroids (e.g. deltamethrin, etofenprox)
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	From sowing to full vegetative stage
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests

Tool 17	Rotation of active ingredients (PPP): alternate PPP with different mode of action reduce the risk of resistance insurgence by pests, diseases and weeds.
Application frequency	Commonly applied
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest, diseases, weeds

Tool 18	Sprayer calibration: it is mandatory in Italy since 2016.
Application frequency	Every 3 years (normally) or every 2 years for subcontracting

Application date	NA
Use of anti-drift nozzles	Used only by farmers with modern equipment/machineries (e.g., wide sleeve bars)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests, diseases, weeds

Tool 19	Appropriate timing for harvest: a two stages harvest is commonly used. The first stage is to dig up the onion and leave them on the field to dry. The second stage is to collect onion in boxes and bring to warehouse for further drying and/or storage.
Application frequency	NA
How long to leave onion on the ground after 1 st harvest stage	Max 7-10 days
Stage of development of the crop	Harvest when 70-80% of plant have broken leaves
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Research for new varieties resistant or tolerant to major pests or diseases.
	Seed coating? Yes
Cropping density	80-180 plants/m ²
Cropping cycle	January-Feb./June-August
Estimated annual yield	40-60 t/ha
Price per kg product	0.30-0.35 €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	NA
Storage loss	NA
PPP-use	Optimization of the number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied and substitution of chemicals with low-impact products: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <u>Fungicides</u>: <10-12 against downy mildew; <2-3 against grey mould - <u>Insecticides</u>: 1 against wireworms; 1-2 against thrips; 1-2 against flies; 1 against cutworms - <u>Herbicides</u>: <4 treatments
% drift reduction	Depends on the types of nozzles used
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Specific for each PPP (if no specified, 3 m from watercourse)
Crop rotation	Yes (frequency: 1:4-5)
	E.g. wheat-onion-beet-potato
Intercropping	No

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool 1	Crop rotation: onion cannot be sown in the same field consecutively; avoid other <i>Alliaceae</i> family crops before onion.
Application frequency	4-5 years
Common crop in rotation	Before onion: wheat or barley
Target pest/disease/weed	Prevention of soilborne diseases and pests

Tool 2	Variety selection: according to market demand it is preferred to use varieties with intermediate cycle; alternate varieties with different sowing period; a mix of gold, white and red varieties could be sowed. Alternate long day and short day varieties, use tolerant cultivars if possible.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool 3	Sowing time: to be optimized to have good soil condition and lower risk of weed proliferation.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Winter sowing (e.g., January-February?)
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target	Weed

Tool 4	Sowing location: long day varieties have not to be sowed closely to short day varieties.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Seed
Target diseases	Prevention the risk of downy mildew infection (<i>Peronospora destructor</i>)

Tool 5	Removal of plant residues: to reduce inoculants of pests or diseases
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest & diseases

Tool 6	Field preparation: autumn-winter tillage (reduction of the tillage depth) to improve
--------	--

	drainage and weed control but preserving soil organic matter.
Application frequency	Every 3-4 years
Application date	Autumn-winter
Tillage deep	15-30 cm
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Drainage & weed control

Tool 7	Weed control before sowing. Stale seedbed: is a preventive method of weed control (following the preparation of the seedbed, the germination of the weeds is allowed, followed by a chemical treatment or a tillage to eliminate them).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Before sowing
Tillage	e.g. harrowing (5-10 cm deep)
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool 8	Soil preparation: use of modern machinery to better prepare the seed bed.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	Before sowing
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	Prevention of water stagnations and allow homogeneous emergency

Tool 9	Appropriate use of irrigation: crucial for crop emergence and root development; a carefully managed irrigation system is helping also the control of thrips infestation reducing PPP use.
Application frequency	Depending on season
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	Thrips and crop emergence

Tool 10	Advanced monitoring on the field.
Application frequency	Regular visual monitoring in the field; use of more efficient traps; development of new or updated thresholds of intervention.
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After crop emergence up to harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest & weeds

Tool 11	Development of forecasting models for diseases (i.e., for downy mildew and grey mould) + use of nematode support tool (Best4Soil)
Forecast frequency	Weekly through IPM Bulletin
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	After crop emergence up to harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	Diseases + pests

Tool 12	Weed control: before emergence and post-emergence.
Application frequency	≤4 herbicides for crop cycle applying different classes of PPP
Type of herbicides	Research for alternative techniques to herbicides (e.g. mechanical weeding, cover crops, mulching)
Dose (L/ha/year)	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Entire crop cycle
Application date	From sowing to post emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool 13	Balanced fertilization: use of green manure is suggested; no compost application to avoid weed seeds presence and contaminants.
Application frequency	Autumn-winter green manure (mix of different plant species belonging to Graminaceae, Leguminosae and Brassicaceae families): with sowing in Autumn burning in Spring
Application date	Before onion in rotation
Stage of development of the crop	NA
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool 14	IPM Guidelines for pesticide application against Peronospora, botrytis, fly, thrips, wireworm, etc.
Application frequency	Updated yearly
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests and diseases
See attachment	https://agricoltura.regione.emilia-romagna.it/produzioni-agroalimentari/temi/bio-agro-climambiente/agricoltura-integrata/disciplinari-produzione-integrata-vegetale/Collezione-dpi/dpi_2024/orticole

Tool 15	Crop protection decisions are based on advices of extension service/experts: according to IPM Guidelines a regional support for extension services is provided weekly with IPM Bulletin that advises and suggests on PPP applications.
Application frequency	Weekly
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest, diseases, weeds

Tool 16	Reduction of pesticides application or use of alternatives or less toxic PPP (e.g. BCA, natural based products....).
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest, diseases, weeds

Tool 17	Rotation of active ingredients (PPP): alternate PPP with different modes of action to reduce the risk of resistance of pests, diseases and weeds against certain active ingredients.
Application frequency	Commonly applied
Application date	NA
Stage of development of the crop	Along crop cycle
Target pest/disease/weed	Pest, diseases, weeds

Tool 18	Sprayer calibration: it is mandatory in Italy since 2016.
Application frequency	Every 3 years or every 2 years for subcontracting
Application date	NA
Use of anti-drift nozzles	Used only by farmers with modern equipment/machineries (e.g., wide sleeve bars)
Target pest/disease/weed	Pests, diseases, weeds

Tool 19	Appropriate timing for harvest: a two stages harvest is commonly used. The first stage is to dig up the onion and leave them on the field to dry. The second stage is to collect onion in boxes and bring to warehouse for further drying and/or storage.
Application frequency	NA
How long to leave onion on the ground after 1 st harvest stage	Max 7-10 days

Stage of development of the crop	Harvest when 70-80% of plant have broken stems
Target pest/disease/weed	NA

Tool 20	Use of split dose of herbicides: post-emergence application can be done with portioned interventions of the full dosage to reduce phytotoxicity on the onion plant in an early stage of development.
Application frequency	NA
Application date	NA
Risk	High risk to increase weeds resistance
Stage of development of the crop	Post-emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

6.8.2 Poland

Contact person: Joanna Golian (joanna.golian@inhort.pl)

Joanna Pulawska (joanna.pulawska@inhort.pl)

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: [Onion (spring sowing)]

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: [Onion (spring sowing)]

IPM strategies for NCC Poland/onion

Strategy selection

[Description strategy selection]

Field onion.

Description reference year: 2023

[Description reference year]

Onion sowing in 2023 was delayed on many farms as a result of low temperatures and excessive soil moisture. The significant drop in temperatures in early May was a strong stress factor for the plants. In the second half of May, weather conditions improved, allowing an improvement in plant conditions and intensive plant mass growth. This process slowed down in June and July, influenced by high temperatures with a persistent rainfall deficit. In the second half of July and August, there was an increase in rainfall, and the intensity and extent of rainfall varied. Consequently, in some areas of the country, the water balance improved, but in areas where there were heavy rains and hailstorms, crop damage and yield losses occurred. A major problem during the growing season was strong pressure from fungal diseases and numerous plant pests. Due to unfavourable weather conditions, protection measures were of limited effectiveness. At the same time, due to a significant increase in the price of plant protection products, some producers reduced their use. The relatively high temperatures in September and October favoured the increase in vegetable weight of summer-sown onions, and conditions at harvest time in the main production areas were good. Due to the considerable variation in weather conditions during the season, the quality of the harvest obtained is generally worse than in previous years. The harvested vegetables are characterized by a lower weight and, due to physiological changes, their long-term storage capacity may be worse.

The total production of ground vegetables (early and late) is estimated at more than 3.8 million tonnes, less than 3% lower than last year. The production result was significantly influenced by favourable weather conditions in the last weeks of the growing season. Onion production was estimated at around 636,000 tonnes, which is approximately 2% less than the previous year.

Strategy 1: Onion (spring sowing)

Description

Number of growers	9992 growers/farms
Acreage (ha)	21 541 ha 21 456,60 ha
% of total acreage	10-11,5 % of total ground vegetable area
Production (tonnes/year)	636 000 tonnes/year
% of the total production	16,5 %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? <u>No</u>
	Seed coating? <u>Yes</u>
Cropping density	700-800 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	Start/end date III/IV – VIII/IX
Estimated annual yield	30-40 t/ha

Price per kg product	1,60-2,00 PLN/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	1300 – 2100 PLN/ha
Storage loss	2-5%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 10-12 Insecticides: 10-12 Herbicides: 4-5-6
% drift reduction	10-20 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	Minimum 3 m (individually selected for the plant protection product used)
Crop rotation	<u>Yes</u> (frequency: $\geq 1:3$) With which crops? mainly wheat, barley, maize, cauliflower, parsley
Intercropping	<u>Yes</u>

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Crop rotation
Application frequency	$\geq 1:3$ (cultivation in the same field every 3 years)
Application date	-
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Tool	Sprayer calibration
Application frequency	1x
Application date	III-IV
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target

Tool	Mechanical soil cultivation before sowing
Application frequency	1x
Application date	III-IV
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool – before sowing
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Tool	Rotation of active substances
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Tool	The application of chemical plant protection products in accordance with the label (instructions for use)
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Tool	Prevention of seed production by weeds
Application frequency	As needed - during weed flowering
Application date	III-XII
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Monitoring on the field
Application frequency	Once a week
Application date	IV- VIII
Stage of development of the crop	From the stage when the first leaf (> 3 cm) clearly visible (BBCH – 11) until the Leaves dead, bulb top dry (BBCH 48)
Target pest/disease/weed	1. IV-VIII: weeds 2. V-VIII (1/two weeks): <i>Peronospora destructor</i> (Downy mildew), <i>Stemphyllium spp.</i> , <i>Alternaria spp.</i> , <i>Botrytis spp.</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Pyrenochaeta terrestris</i> 3. IV-VIII: <i>Delia antiqua</i> , <i>Agrotis spp.</i> , 4. VI-VII: <i>Thrips tabaci</i> , 5. IV-VI: <i>Acrolepiopsis assectella</i> .

Tool	Downy mildew treatment
Application frequency	8x
Application date	VI-VIII
Stage of development of the crop	BBCH 18-48
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Peronospora destructor</i>

Tool	<i>Stemphyllium</i> , <i>Alternaria</i> and <i>Botrytis</i> treatment
Application frequency	4x
Application date	VI-VIII
Stage of development of the crop	BBCH 18-48
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Stemphyllium spp.</i> , <i>Alternaria spp.</i> , <i>Botrytis spp.</i>

Tool	The use of herbicide before onion emergence
Application frequency	1-2x
Application date	III-IV
Stage of development of the crop	Before onion emergence

Target pest/disease/weed	All weeds
Tool	The use herbicides after onion emergence
Application frequency	2-4x
Application date	III-VI
Stage of development of the crop	After onion emergence up to the 3 leaf stage of onion
Target pest/disease/weed	All weeds

Tool	Application of graminicide
Application frequency	1x
Application date	IV-VII
Stage of development of the crop	From the stage of 1 onion leaf, in the appropriate stage of monocotyledonous weed growth
Target pest/disease/weed	Monocotyledonous weed

Tool	<i>Delia antiqua</i> treatment
Application frequency	2 treatments
Application date	IV-V
Stage of development of the crop	Apply from the stage when the cotyledons come to the surface of the soil (BBCH 09) until 2-3 leaves have developed (BBCH 12-13).
Target pest/disease/weed	onion fly (<i>Delia antiqua</i>)

Tool	<i>Thrips tabaci</i> treatment
Application frequency	4-5 treatments every 7-10 days
Application date	Apply upon noticing an adult or the first symptoms of feeding.
Stage of development of the crop	BBCH 13-45
Target pest/disease/weed	<u>onion thrips (<i>Thrips tabaci</i>)</u>

Tool	<i>Acrolepiopsis assectella</i> treatment
Application frequency	2 treatments every 10-14 days
Application date	VI -VII (At the moment of caterpillars appearance)
Stage of development of the crop	BBCH from 14-15 to 45
Target pest/disease/weed	leek moth (<i>Acrolepiopsis assectella</i>)

Tool	<i>Agrotis spp.</i> treatment
Application frequency	VI – 2-3 treatments
Application date	At the moment of caterpillars appearance. The treatment must be performed between 15 days (in warm weather) and 25 days (in colder weather) after the butterfly peak was noticed

Stage of development of the crop	After onion emergence up to the 3 leaf stage of onion (BBCH – 13) until the Leaf bases begin to thicken or extend bulb top dry (BBCH 41)
Target pest/disease/weed	cutworms (<i>Agrotis</i> spp)

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? <u>Yes</u>
	Seed coating? <u>Yes</u>
Cropping density	800-900 plants/ha
Cropping cycle	Start/end date III/IV – VIII/IX
Estimated annual yield	40 - 60 t/ha
Price per kg product	1,60-2,50 PLN/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	6500 up to 7000 PLN/ha
Storage loss	1-2%
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: 8-10 Insecticides: 10-14 Herbicides: 4-5-6
% drift reduction	50-60 %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	min. 3 m (individually selected for the plant protection product used)
Crop rotation	<u>Yes/no</u> (frequency: 1:4)
	With which crops? mainly wheat, barley, maize, beetroot, carrot, cauliflower, parsley
Intercropping	<u>Yes</u>

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Tool	Crop rotation
Application frequency	1:4 (cultivation in the same field every 4 years)
Application date	-
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Tool	Sprayer calibration
Application frequency	1x
Application date	III-IV
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target

Tool	Mechanical soil cultivation before sowing
Application frequency	1x
Application date	III-IV
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool – before sowing

Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed
--------------------------	--------------------------------------

Tool	Rotation of active substances
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Tool	The application of chemical plant protection products in accordance with the label (instructions for use)
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Tool	Prevention of seed production by weeds
Application frequency	as needed - during weed flowering
Application date	III-XII
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	Weeds

Tool	Soil sampling to determine of degree nematodes infestation
Application frequency	I
Application date	III-IV
Stage of development of the crop	Before sowing onions
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematoda (<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>)

Tool	Nematode treatment
Application frequency	1x
Application date	Before sowing onions
Stage of development of the crop	Not applicable
Target pest/disease/weed	Nematode (<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>)

Tool	Monitoring on the field
Application frequency	Once a week
Application date	IV- VIII
Stage of development of the crop	From the stage when the First leaf (> 3 cm) clearly visible (BBCH – 11) until the Leaves dead, bulb top dry (BBCH 48)
Target pest/disease/weed	1. IV-VIII: weeds 2. V-VIII (1/two weeks): <i>Peronospora destructor</i> (Downy mildew), <i>Stemphyllium spp.</i> , <i>Alternaria</i>

	<i>spp.</i> , <i>Botrytis spp.</i> , <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Pyrenochaeta terrestris</i> , 3. IV-VIII: <i>Delia antiqua</i> , <i>Agrotis spp.</i> , 4. VI-VII: <i>Thrips tabaci</i> , 5. IV-VI: <i>Acrolepiopsis assectella</i> .
--	--

Tool	<i>Delia antiqua</i> chemical (2x) or biological (1x) treatment
Application frequency	2 chemical treatment or 1 biological treatment
Application date	IV-V (after determination of the risk threshold)
Stage of development of the crop	Apply from the stage when the cotyledons come to the surface of the soil (BBCH 09) until 2-3 leaves have developed (BBCH 12-13).
Target pest/disease/weed	onion fly (<i>Delia antiqua</i>)

Tool	<i>Thrips tabaci</i> chemical (4x) or biological (5x) treatment
Application frequency	1. Chemical treatment: 4 treatments every 7 days, 2. Biological protection: 5 treatments every 5 days
Application date	Apply after determination of the risk threshold.
Stage of development of the crop	BBCH 13-45
Target pest/disease/weed	onion thrips (<i>Thrips tabaci</i>)

Tool	<i>Acrolepiopsis assectella</i> chemical (2x) or biological (3x) treatment
Application frequency	Chemical treatment: 2 treatments every 10-14 days, Biological protection: 3 treatments every 6 days
Application date	VI -VII
Stage of development of the crop	BBCH from 14-15 to 45
Target pest/disease/weed	leek moth (<i>Acrolepiopsis assectella</i>)

Tool	<i>Agrotis spp.</i> chemical (2x) or biological (2-4x) treatment
Application frequency	Chemical treatment: 2 treatments Biological protection: 2-4 treatments every 7 days
Application date	At the moment of caterpillars appearance. The treatment must be performed between 15 days (in warm weather) and 25 days (in colder weather) after the butterfly peak was noticed
Stage of development of the crop	After onion emergence up to the 3 leaf stage of onion (BBCH – 13) until the Leaf bases begin to thicken or extend bulb top dry (BBCH 41)

Target pest/disease/weed	cutworms (<i>Agrotis</i> spp.)
--------------------------	---------------------------------

Tool	Downy mildew treatment
Application frequency	6-8x (Depends on wheather conditions)
Application date	VI-VIII
Stage of development of the crop	BBCH18-48
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Peronospora destructor</i>

Tool	<i>Stemphylium</i> , <i>Alternaria</i> and <i>Botrytis</i> treatment
Application frequency	4x
Application date	VI- VIII
Stage of development of the crop	BBCH18-48
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Stemphyllium</i> spp., <i>Alternaria</i> spp., <i>Botrytis</i> spp.

Tool	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> : Biological protection
Application frequency	1x (before sowing) and 2x (during onion vegetation every 14-21 days)
Application date	III-V
Stage of development of the crop	BBCH 00 and BBCH 13-14
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>

Tool	Weed treatment before onion emergence (use of herbicide or weed flaming)
Application frequency	1-2x
Application date	III-IV
Stage of development of the crop	Before onion emergence
Target pest/disease/weed	All weeds

Tool	The use herbicides after onion emergence
Application frequency	2-4x
Application date	III-VI
Stage of development of the crop	After onion emergence up to the 3 leaf stage of onion
Target pest/disease/weed	All weeds

Tool	Application of graminicide
Application frequency	1x
Application date	IV-VII
Stage of development of the crop	From the stage of 1 onion leaf, in the appropriate stage of monocotyledonous weed growth
Target pest/disease/weed	Monocotyledonous weed

Tool	Mechanical weeding
------	--------------------

Application frequency	1-2x
Application date	V-VIII
Stage of development of the crop	After crop and weeds emergence until harvest
Target pest/disease/weed	All weeds

6.9 Template reports

Strategy 1 – state of the art scenario: [strategy title]

Strategy 1 – IPM improved scenario: [strategy title]

IPM strategies for [NCC]

Strategy selection

[Description strategy selection]

Description reference year:

[Reference year]

Strategy 1: [strategy title]

Description

Number of growers	X
Acreage (ha)	X ha
% of total acreage	X %
Production (tonnes/year)	% tonnes/year
% of the total production	X %

State-of-the-art scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	X plants/ha
Cropping cycle	Start/end date
Estimated annual yield	X t/ha
Price per kg product	X €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	X kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X
% drift reduction	X %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	X m
Crop rotation	Yes/no (frequency: 1:X)
	With which crops?
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Example 1:

Tool	Drift reduction of 75%, which is the legally required percentage of drift reduction in Flanders.
------	--

Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Example 2:

Tool	Chemical <i>Phytophthora</i> treatment, based on a warning system.
Application frequency	10-15 x
Application date	half May – until haulm killing is completed (at the latest half October)
Stage of development of the crop	From crop emergence until last leaves
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X

Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X

Target pest/disease/weed	X
--------------------------	---

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

IPM improved scenario

Cultivar	Resistant? Yes/no
	Seed coating? Yes/no/NA
Cropping density	X plants/ha
Cropping cycle	Start/end date
Estimated annual yield	X t/ha
Price per kg product	X €/kg
Amount of direct payments for the specific tools in the scenario	
Storage loss	X kg/ha or X %
PPP-use	Number of fungicides/insecticides/herbicides applied (<u>products</u>): Fungicides: X Insecticides: X Herbicides: X
% drift reduction	X %
Minimum buffer zone to surface water	X m
Crop rotation	Yes/no (frequency: 1:X)
	With which crops?
Intercropping	Yes/no

10-20 most used and combined IPM tools:

Example 1:

Tool	Drift reduction of 75%, which is the legally required percentage of drift reduction in Flanders.
Application frequency	Each application
Application date	Each application
Stage of development of the crop	Not relevant for this IPM tool
Target pest/disease/weed	No specific target pest/disease/weed

Example 2:

Tool	Chemical <i>Phytophthora</i> treatment, based on a warning system.
Application frequency	10-15 x
Application date	half May – until haulm killing is completed (at the latest half October)
Stage of development of the crop	From crop emergence until last leaves
Target pest/disease/weed	<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
------	---

Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X

Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X

Tool	[description of the tool: e.g. general info, is it (supra)legal, application intensity,...]
Application frequency	X
Application date	X
Stage of development of the crop	X
Target pest/disease/weed	X